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JOY IN HOPE
FROM *FRATELLI TUTTI*

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Joy in Hope
from *Fratelli Tutti*

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Editorial

Joy in Hope from *Fratelli Tutti*

As Christians, we celebrate the resurrection of Christ, to be joyful in His triumph. Yet, we find ourselves today in midst of a serious pandemic, and in the largest human created ecological crisis in history. As Pope Francis writes in *Laudato Si'*, 'The earth, our home, is beginning to look more and more like an immense pile of filth.' (LS 21). The Pope's message agrees, albeit in more relatable terms, with the widely accepted scientific findings on climate today. 'Never have we so hurt and mistreated our common home as we have in the last two hundred years' (LS 53). How can we as Christians celebrate in a time when things in the world seem so dire?

As an answer – and this is what separates Pope Francis from all doomsday prophets – the Pope knows about the immeasurable power of hope.

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So the Pope is emphatic: “Hope would have us recognise that there is always a way out, that we can always redirect our steps, that we can always do something to solve our problems” (LS 61).

Hope is also why we as church, together with all people of good will, root ourselves in a trust for a better world. We believe we can, and want to, leave this world a better place after our we’re gone. Despite all the negative, disturbing and harrowing reports about the state of our beautiful, blue and very threatened planet, we find ourselves before a potentially valuable experience. We rest in a promise of which Pope Francis writes: ‘We were conceived in the heart of God, and for this reason: ‘each of us is the result of a thought of God. Each of us is willed, each of us is loved, each of us is necessary.’ (LS 65) Here and in many other places the Pope lives the hope of an alternative to the negative zeitgeist that dominates so many of our sources of information. In the two letters *Laudato Si’* and *Fratelli Tutti* he sketches a wonderful utopia, even more: something like a model of a more just, egalitarian and compassionate world.

Our future rests on two pillars: Justice and Love. On the one hand, this stands in line with our tradition, in the good space of Catholic Social Teaching, together with all people of good will who share in our mission to build a world which is more just, more humane, and more future-proof. We do this with an attitude of confidence based on faith, an attitude that can and must make us sensitive to the needs of others, and of our planet. As in the story of the Good Samaritan, the message is clear: ‘go and do likewise.’ Confidence that this world, this One Creation, is in God’s hands. We don’t have to redeem the world, that is already done, and the Lord walks with us whatever comes, whatever happens. But it is up to us, to make this event of God’s love tangible, to make it credible; to translate this single event of redemption, which has happened once and for all, into time and space, here and now, writes Michael Landau (2021), President, Caritas, Europe.

On the other hand, this message is also highly topical, and relevant to the current debate in society as a whole: if you consider the Sustainable Development Goals, the SDGs, then I think it is exciting and important that we, as church, are involved in the discourse around them, and in their implementation. We have an important voice here as Caritas, as Church: We introduce an image of the human being that reminds us that we are more than a consumer and a producer, an image of the human being that testifies to the equal dignity of every person – from the child with disabilities, to the dying old man.

It is worth recalling that the justice of a society is measured by how it treats the weakest, the most vulnerable within it: the people at the margins of society and life. I think we should also be encouraged from the experience of daily our work: We cannot change everything, but we can change a surprising amount if we want to. This change often begins in small ways, with individual people. It depends on each and every one of us (Landau 2021).

The Pope always combines the ecological with the social question. ‘A more responsible overall approach is needed to deal with both problems: the reduction of pollution and the development of poorer countries and regions.’ (LS 175) Just he writes about the ‘mystical meaning to be found in a leaf, in a mountain trail, in a dewdrop, in a poor person’s face,’ he acknowledges that the world can only be saved ‘with a sense of solidarity which is at the same time aware that we live in a common home which God has entrusted to us’ (LS 232). He expresses an awareness of the beauty of nature, and the need to act socially to save it. A Church that, like the Pope, dreams of a less populist, less capital-driven world, but instead, of a world in which all people have their fair share of a good life, where everyone has fair opportunities and where no one is left behind, is at the same time always a Church that must do everything possible to turn these wishes, dreams and visions into a reality. The Pope writes, “No one can face life in isolation... We need a community that supports and helps us, in which we can help one another to keep looking ahead. How important it is to dream together... as a single human family, as fellow travellers sharing the same flesh, as children of the same

earth which is our common home (..) , each of us with his or her own voice, brothers and sisters all” (FT 8).

We are contributing to this, fraternity and friendship. We can truly learn from *Laudato Si'* and *Fratelli Tutti* – not least in the basic attitude of joy that is expressed in the previous papal letter *Evangelii Gaudium* that already resonates this dimension of joy in the title. God does not want us small and bent up inside, but upright and straight, with a joyful and wide heart! (Landau 2021).

As committed Christians living for one another, we can also see how people are there for others, love is lived, people see a need and act. People stand in solidarity, but also look ahead in confidence.

We are convinced that we will master the path, even if it gets steeper. But for that it is necessary that we stand together and do not forget about the weakest. We stand on a horizon of hope, especially now, in a demanding time. It is the hope based on the experience that many people are ready to be there for others and to get involved and that positive changes are possible and will happen.

But deeper still, it is the horizon of great hope, a horizon which is ultimately God Himself (Landau 2021). Our path is in His hands. Of course, we are challenged: this is not a call to do nothing. But we are convinced that with what little we have in our hands, He can accomplish more than we can imagine. He counts on us: here and today.

Scientists today warn of the arrival of Sixth Mass Extinction, which may wipe out about 70-90% of life! Unlike the earlier mass extinctions, this is caused by human activity, like climate change and species annihilation (Gray 2019). On the other hand, we are also encountering the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which would radically alter the way human beings look at ourselves (Schwab 2016).

Faced with these mind-boggling possibilities, including our own self-annihilation, the essays in this volume of *Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies* traces signs of hope and draws wisdom from *Fratelli Tutti*, the third encyclical of Pope Francis. Without reducing the hope to a day dream or pipe dream, the authors trace signs of joy and hope in the daily events of our life, based on friendship, fraternity, forgiveness, compassion and care. They believe that hope is intrinsic to human beings, including atheists (Bloch 1985). As Pope Francis reminds us in *Laudato Si'* (2015), the authors believe joyfully in the collective hope of humanity:

“Yet all is not lost. Human beings, while capable of the worst, are also capable of rising above themselves, choosing again what is good, and making a new start, despite their mental and social conditioning. We are able to take an honest look at ourselves, to acknowledge our deep dissatisfaction, and to embark on new paths to authentic freedom.”

The Editor

References

- Bloch, E. 1985. *Das Prinzip Hoffnung*: 3. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp.
- Landau, Michael. 2021. ‘From Fear to Hope’. www.caritas.eu. Retrieved 22 November 2021 (<https://www.caritas.eu/from-fear-to-hope/>).
- Gray, Richard. 2019. ‘Sixth Mass Extinction Could Destroy Life as We Know It—Biodiversity Expert’. *Horizon: The EU Research & Innovation Magazine*. Retrieved 18 October 2019 (<https://horizon-magazine.eu/article/sixth-mass-extinction-could-destroy-life-we-know-it-biodiversity-expert.html>).
- Schwab, Klaus. 2016. ‘The Fourth Industrial Revolution: What It Means and How to Respond’. *World Economic Forum*. Retrieved 23 November 2021 (<https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2016/01/the-fourth-industrial-revolution-what-it-means-and-how-to-respond/>).

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Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti: **A Call to Live Our Faith** **with Hope and Joy**

Virginia Saldanha

Secretary, Indian Women Theologians Forum

Abstract: *Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti* appeals to all people of good will. The values of love and care are embedded in every human person. Catholics caught up in an individualistic faith practice and secure in their parish Church, have been called by Pope Francis to Synodality through communion, participation and mission. He calls us to look beyond ourselves, beyond the walls of our home, our parish, to the larger world, the reality of the poor, the violence done to women, to the abuse of human rights, peoples of other faiths, etc. to create a culture of encounter, towards fraternity and communion as one human family. We need a new culture to bring about change, where feminist perspectives are included

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to address the problems of society, business, politics and the environment. It is essential to get the youth on board in the process of working towards synodality as they would resonate with *Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti*.

Keywords: Love, Communion, Fraternity, Human Family, Human Rights, Encounter, Justice.

1. Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti Is Universal

Fratelli/Sorelle Tutti is based on the fundamental concept that all humans are created equal by God, and therefore is a sister or brother who needs to be acknowledged and treated as such. It appeals to all people of good will who seek justice and peace. Love and care are values deeply embedded in each and every human that need to be affirmed and nurtured.

Having been part of the women's movement in India for the past 30 years, I have been heartened to see how women of all faiths or no faith, have dedicated their lives to work for justice not only for women but also for people of the lower castes who suffer discrimination. I have observed that 'fraternity' and 'social relations' that this document is dedicated to, is integral to the women's movement in India.

For example, in 1992 when Bhanwari Devi, a grassroots social worker in Rajasthan was gang raped by upper caste men to take revenge for her efforts to prevent a child marriage in their family, women's organizations in Rajasthan immediately were on the alert and followed the shoddy way the case was handled by the local police and lower courts. When the accused were acquitted in 1995, they put pressure on the Rajasthan government to appeal against the judgement in the case. The government dragged their feet but finally did so in 2007 when 2 of the accused had died. From that case the women activists were able to draft a law on Sexual harassment of women in the workplace that helps numerous women who suffer this indignity and violence in their workplaces.

Medha Patkar (Wikipedia contributors 2021) is another woman who has incarnated herself into the lives of those displaced by the Narmada dam project in Madhya Pradesh and Gujarat. Since the mid-1980s to this day she has dedicated her life to work for their rehabilitation and right to livelihood. Born into a family of socially conscious parents, she grew up to be sensitive to the sufferings and needs of the voiceless in Indian society. She gave the displaced people hope and courage to continue their struggle against an insensitive government.

Flavia Agnes, as a young wife and mother experienced very serious domestic violence. She found solace and hope in the women's movement. As a Catholic she did not find much support in the Church, except for some priests who gave her a listening ear but directed her to the movement. She was finally able to leave her violent husband when she was given shelter in the home of a Hindu activist, the late Sonal Shukla. Sonal not only opened her home and hearth to Flavia and her children, she even gave her clothes to wear, and helped her pick up the threads of her life again. Today Flavia is a noted Advocate, thanks to the encouragement of Sonal. Flavia fights for women's rights and takes up cases of violence against women. Sonal, a Hindu woman lived "*Sorelle Tutti*", she was Eucharist to Flavia and her children at a low point in their life.

The movement consists of women who are lawyers, activists, social workers, etc., who are willing to walk that extra mile to go to the aid of any woman or child that has suffered violence. They put their lives out for the sake of another. The sisterhood is amazing. This is how we should be living the Eucharist moved by the Spirit of God.

While we also have several religious and even some lay women and men who have "walked alongside the poor, the abandoned, the infirm and the outcast, the least of their

brothers and sisters” (FT 2) the majority of Catholics are content with being ‘consumers of church services’, completely absorbed in following the commandments of the Church; satisfied with membership in some pious association, feeling satisfied that we are ‘practising’ Catholics. Even though Jesus has clearly said “Not everyone who says to me “Lord, Lord” will enter the kingdom of heaven, but the one who does the will of God (Matt.7:21), we still tend to assure our place in heaven by the number of masses we attend, the number of rosaries we say, novenas, etc. We even have people being proclaimed as a “good Catholic” for being seen around the Church a lot, being involved in parish activities which are mainly inward looking.

When I was a very young widow with three infant children, I struggled to go through each day. Another widow who had been through a similar experience came a month later and told me that I could leave my children at her home if I needed to go out on work. Most other people’s concern was more intrusive than helpful.

2. Are We Truly Living Our Faith?

Pope Francis in calling on all the People of God to Synodality through Communion, Participation and Mission is trying to reform the way we practice our faith. There is no doubt that the way we have been practising our faith has left us all in a rut of individualism because we have grown up on doctrines and not on the practice of how to “spread the love of God”. We are aware that “God is love and those who abide in love abide in God” (1 Jn 4:16) (FT 4). But the application of it in our life is absent.

In India we are constantly in contact with the poor. We see them in the streets, in the market places, when we travel and most of all we employ them in our homes as domestic workers, cleaners, garbage collectors, guards, drivers, etc. We meet them in our places of work, in our aided schools, and often they are part of our parish community. Do we see them as our brothers and sisters, “as a single human family, as fellow travellers sharing the same

flesh, as children of the same earth which is our common home”? (FT 8)

“The majority of Christians seem content to live secure within the parish community which provides spiritual nourishment, education and social interaction. The Catholic Church provides a secure setup for its people. The harsh reality of millions of India’s poor and marginalized do not seem to concern us. Some may indulge in armchair debates about the government and how it does nothing to eradicate poverty, about the perceived laziness of the poor to find work, etc. But we never discuss how we ourselves should get involved to change the situation” (Saldanha 2005).

“In general, the application of the Gospel message is limited to our private life and practice of faith. We leave the concerns of public life in society, politics and economics to the powers of selfishness and greed. Jesus has been reduced to a personal savior and a name to be praised—without discipleship. We have come to believe that Jesus died on the cross so that we can be comfortable in our faith. Jesus has been made irrelevant to the concerns of the world. It explains the throngs of people attending novenas, visiting shrines, going on pilgrimages etc. for personal favours” (Saldanha 2005).

In the early 1990s part-time domestic workers in my community were not aware of their rights as workers. I realised that most were Dalits, whose husbands were laid-off mill workers who sat at home drinking their wife’s earnings, while she worked part-time jobs in about four houses to make ends meet. I felt the need to reach out to them and make them aware of their rights as workers to get a living wage, a day off each week and a month’s paid leave. My work with them was largely successful, but I suffered a big back lash from my own parish community. A woman actually stopped me on the road and said to me “People of Santa Cruz want your blood.” Another said, “what do you think you are doing

upsetting the harmony of our homes by making our workers fight with us?” A third said “Why do we have to give them holidays? They are not like us!”

“It frequently becomes clear that, in practice, human rights are not equal for all.” Respect for those rights “is the preliminary condition for a country’s social and economic development. When the dignity of the human person is respected, and his or her rights recognized and guaranteed, creativity and interdependence thrive, and the creativity of the human personality is released through actions that further the common good”. (FT 22) Pope Francis brings to our attention the need for us to recognize the universality of human rights, because our workers are like us, they are all our brothers and sisters.

During the lockdown, it was widely known that most domestic workers had to depend on handouts because employers did not pay salaries to their workers. Workers languished with their families, many of them joining the exodus to their villages because they could not afford to continue to live in cities, because we failed to see them as sharing in the same anxiety, the same fears and insecurity that we were faced with. In FT 7 Pope Francis reminds us “the Covid-19 pandemic unexpectedly erupted, exposing our false securities”; “by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity” (FT 8).

Many homes have engaged live-in domestic workers. These workers are kept like slaves. The International Labour Organization calls domestic work as ‘modern day slavery’. “Equality and human dignity are the basic values underlying all human rights. There is perhaps, no greater denial of these universally shared values than treating human beings as mere chattels that can be owned, controlled, exploited and enslaved.

Yet, human beings across the world still suffer this fate.”¹ Live-in workers are at the beck and call of the family 24 x 7 with no free time, no friends, no one to talk to. They are separated from their families, taking up jobs in cities whose spaces are alien to them, some of them are young teenagers. But we only see them as ‘servants’, not as humans. “We should also recognize that “even though the international community has adopted numerous agreements aimed at ending slavery in all its forms, and has launched various strategies to combat this phenomenon, millions of people today – children, women and men of all ages – are deprived of freedom and forced to live in conditions akin to slavery...” (FT 24).

3. Women’s Rights

This encyclical reminds us “the organization of societies worldwide is still far from reflecting clearly that women possess the same dignity and identical rights as men. We say one thing with words, but our decisions and reality tell another story. Indeed, “doubly poor are those women who endure situations of exclusion, mistreatment and violence, since they are frequently less able to defend their rights” (FT 23).

Sadly, I have to point out that the Catholic Church is an institution where women do not have rights identical to men.

¹ UN Special Rapporteur Gulnara Shahinian, on Contemporary Forms of Slavery, highlights modern day domestic servitude as a global human rights concern, in her Report to the Human Rights Council in October 2010, “From domestic work to modern day slavery”, https://www.ilo.org/global/about-the-ilo/newsroom/news/WCMS_146485/lang-en/index.htm accessed 13 Oct. 2021.

Pope Francis often refers to the Church as a pyramid. Women are at the bottom of this pyramid because they have no power to participate in any decisions taken in the Church even when it concerns their own lives. The exclusion of women from leadership and decision making has made them vulnerable to exploitation and even violence.

Violence done to women in the family is hardly ever condemned in the Church. Wife beating is never named as a sin, and the practice continues with impunity even into the 21st century. Violence comes in ways other than physical beating. Women suffer from emotional, mental and economic violence as well. This violence reflects on the children who also suffer trauma with their mother, bringing instability in the home. Most women are unable to take any action because they lack social or family support. As pointed out earlier Catholic women hardly receive help from the Church. When the Commission for Women was established in the diocese and parish level, women working at these levels were encouraged to be proactive on the issue of domestic violence, but today it is not so. Thankfully we have the feminist movement active in the country with dedicated women who are always ready to help. The Church falls dismally far behind secular society.

Church agencies have projects to empower women economically through income generating skills training. But if women are not empowered to question their subordination to men which often results in violence, these projects are counter-productive in preventing violence, as women will be compelled to hand over their earnings to their drunken husbands.

4. Building Walls to Keep out the ‘Other’

FT further says: “the unknown, unfamiliar, not part of the village. It is the territory of the “barbarian”, from whom we must defend ourselves at all costs. As a result, new walls are erected for self-preservation, the outside world ceases to exist and leaves only “my” world, to the point that others, no longer considered human

beings possessed of an inalienable dignity, become only “them”. Once more, we encounter “the temptation to build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in the heart, walls on the land, in order to prevent this encounter with other cultures, with other people. And those who raise walls will end up as slaves within the very walls they have built. They are left without horizons, for they lack this interchange with others” (FT 27).

We build these walls in our parishes, in our families, communities, when we feel superior to the other. We do not join community events or parish activities, because we do not want to rub shoulders with those we feel are not the same as us because they come from a different economic class, or different caste, or different region. We even look down on people of other faith.

Can our catechesis tackle the divisions humans carry within them based on skin colour, economic status, profession, etc.? For when we are baptized all divisions are wiped away because we are all baptized into the one body of Christ (Gal 3:28). If we have to help bring about the reign of God amongst us, then we have to develop a mindset that does not erect walls. The forthcoming Synod on Synodality is just about that “Walking together in communion, participation and mission” with all people, even those of other faith.

When Jesus was seen speaking to the Samaritan woman (Jn 4: 4-42) his disciples were shocked because they had the same superior attitude as all Jews, who felt the Samaritans were inferior people, yet Jesus only saw her as a woman who felt troubled because of her personal life, she felt marginalized and isolated, he wanted to reach out to her bringing her God’s love. In return she was touched so deeply by her encounter with Jesus that she brought her whole village to meet Jesus. Jesus not only broke the barrier between the Jew and the Samaritan, he also helped break the

barriers in her own life she had built between herself and her community because of her troubled past.

While Pope Francis points out that “the sense of belonging to a single human family is fading, and the dream of working together for justice and peace seems an outdated utopia” (FT 30) he calls us to encounter the love of God first to enable ourselves to reach out to others to break down social, cultural and other barriers humans create between one another. This is the true mission of our Christian faith.

Today our addiction to our communication devices can also build walls around ourselves and keep us from real communication even in the family. “The ability to sit down and listen to others, typical of interpersonal encounters, is paradigmatic of the welcoming attitude shown by those who transcend narcissism and accept others, caring for them and welcoming them into their lives. The frantic pace of the modern world prevents us from listening attentively to what another person is saying. Halfway through, we interrupt him and want to contradict what he has not even finished saying. We must not lose our ability to listen” (FT 48). This applies very much to people in the family, communication between parents and young children, or between grown children and their elderly parents.

Many elderly parents are shut out of the lives of their children because they have no time, the frantic pace of their lives is an excuse to shut out elderly parents. “By isolating the elderly and leaving them in the care of others without the closeness and concern of family members, we disfigure and impoverish the family itself. We also end up depriving young people of a necessary connection to their roots and a wisdom that the young cannot achieve on their own” (FT 19).

While on the other hand, communication devices help many of us to bridge divides of space, especially during these Covid times when we were all self-isolated, we have to use them with balance. For many of us who live alone, or have families separated because of work in different cities and countries, modern communication

has been a blessing. It has helped us keep in touch, helped us build virtual communities that have sustained many who are isolated. These have been life sustaining and for many even spiritually fulfilling. I have missed this being acknowledged in the document.

5. Divisions and Walls Created by Religion, Politics and Economics

The divisions that are built in human minds and not addressed either in education or catechesis, end up being expressed by adults in their professional life, especially by political leaders and state leaders. Religion has become one of the most divisive forces in the world today when it is mixed with politics and economics, the mixture becomes potent enough to destroy human life. Politics uses religion to brainwash people into believing that those who are not one of us are against us. Walls are designed to shut out ‘the enemy other’ through indoctrination and the misuse of mass communication. “In many countries, hyperbole, extremism and polarization have become political tools” (FT 15). Tools to divide people, as there are a few who benefit from the resultant divisions and consequent oppression of sections of human persons.

Pope Francis strikes a chord of hopelessness when he states “Amid the fray of conflicting interests, where victory consists in eliminating one’s opponents, how is it possible to raise our sights to recognize our neighbours or to help those who have fallen along the way? A plan that would set great goals for the development of our entire human family nowadays sounds like madness. We are growing ever more distant from one another, while the slow and demanding march towards an increasingly united and just world is suffering a new and dramatic setback” (FT 16).

The numerous activists around the world, many of them young people who do not profess to belong to any faith are at the forefront of the Black Lives Matter Movement, the Climate Change Movement, or the Democracy movement. I see the spirit of God present and active in all these people, who, at great risk to themselves are standing up for values they believe in. Values of justice and peace. The activists in India have become the conscience of a nation whose leaders seem to have none. They rightly reject religion as a divisive force in society.

Western Christian majority countries who were former colonisers are now the largest manufacturers of arms, whose industry is thriving on the conflagration of so many low intensity conflicts around the world that has displaced millions of people. These people live in inhumane conditions in refugee camps around the world. Many try to move on by themselves becoming migrants and refugees trying to enter the richer countries in the North often illegally further becoming victims.

Pope Francis expresses deep sensitivity to the issue of migrants and refugees in our world today. He points out, “Many migrants have fled from war, persecution and natural catastrophes. Others, rightly, “are seeking opportunities for themselves and their families. They dream of a better future and they want to create the conditions for achieving it” (FT 37). “Unscrupulous traffickers, frequently linked to drug cartels or arms cartels, exploit the weakness of migrants, who too often experience violence, trafficking, psychological and physical abuse and untold sufferings on their journey”. Those who emigrate “experience separation from their place of origin, and often a cultural and religious uprooting as well. Fragmentation is also felt by the communities they leave behind, which lose their most vigorous and enterprising elements, and by families, especially when one or both of the parents migrates, leaving the children in the country of origin”. (FT 38)

While Pope Francis asserts “there is also a need to reaffirm the right not to emigrate, that is, to remain in one’s homeland” (FT

38), this can happen only when leaders have the welfare of their people at the centre of all policy. “Migrations, more than ever before, will play a pivotal role in the future of our world”.[42] At present, however, migration is affected by the “loss of that sense of responsibility for our brothers and sisters on which every civil society is based” (FT 40). We have to think about this problem seriously so that we are able to accomplish our mission of making God’s reign of justice, peace and love a reality. To relegate its solution to political leaders will never work. We have to strengthen civil society from the grassroots so that every person finds hope and acceptance in their own home country. Politicians who emerge from our communities, our families, should make conscientious leaders. This is one way we can tackle this problem decisively.

On the other hand, we should become vigilant promoters of truth and justice when leaders neglect people at the margins.

6. Cultural Diversity

“Certain economically prosperous countries tend to be proposed as cultural models for less developed countries; instead, each of those countries should be helped to grow in its own distinct way and to develop its capacity for innovation while respecting the values of its proper culture. A shallow and pathetic desire to imitate others leads to copying and consuming in place of creating, and fosters low national self-esteem. In the affluent sectors of many poor countries, and at times in those who have recently emerged from poverty, there is a resistance to native ways of thinking and acting, and a tendency to look down on one’s own cultural identity, as if it were the sole cause of every ill” (FT 51).

One negative fallout of global communication is the growth of a monoculture where the prosperous countries are seen as

role models. It has drawn in the young people who tend to look down on their indigenous culture and way of living to blindly aspire to the western models of being without appreciating the values in their own indigenous cultures. “A land will be fruitful, and its people bear fruit and give birth to the future, only to the extent that it can foster a sense of belonging among its members, create bonds of integration between generations and different communities, and avoid all that makes us insensitive to others and leads to further alienation” (FT 52).

7. Creating Bonds of Communion and Fraternity

Pope Francis uses the example of our experience with the Covid-19 pandemic to show us how adversity can bring human beings together and tap into the goodness that is found in every person. “God continues to sow abundant seeds of goodness in our human family. The recent pandemic enabled us to recognize and appreciate once more all those around us who, in the midst of fear, responded by putting their lives on the line. We began to realize that our lives are interwoven with and sustained by ordinary people valiantly shaping the decisive events of our shared history: doctors, nurses, pharmacists, storekeepers and supermarket workers, cleaning personnel, caretakers, transport workers, men and women working to provide essential services and public safety, volunteers, priests and religious... They understood that no one is saved alone” (FT 54).

Pope Francis devotes a whole chapter in the encyclical to an in depth reflection on the parable of the Good Samaritan (Lk10:25-37) in order to emphasise the importance of human relationships. He points to the beginning of Scripture where in Gen 4: 9, God asks Cain, “where is your brother?” God calls Cain to give an account because God was aware of his crime. God goes on to tell Cain how his sin creates a great disturbance within him, but God did not wish that Cain pay for his crime with his life (Gen 4:13-15).

“In everything, do to others as you would have them do to you; for this is the law and the prophets” (Mt 7:12). This command is universal in scope, embracing everyone on the basis of our shared humanity. (FT 60). The call to fraternal love echoes throughout the New Testament: “For the whole law is summed up in a single commandment, ‘You shall love your neighbour as yourself’” (Gal 5:14). “We know that we have passed from death to life because we love one another. Whoever does not love abides in death” (1 Jn 3:14). “Those who do not love a brother or sister whom they have seen, cannot love God whom they have not seen” (1 Jn 4:20, FT 61).

Like the Levite in the parable of the Good Samaritan, we often try to ignore the problems of people, passing it off as someone else’s responsibility, or because we are busy, “caught up as we are with our own needs, the sight of a person who is suffering disturbs us. It makes us uneasy, since we have no time to waste on other people’s problems. These are symptoms of an unhealthy society. A society that seeks prosperity but turns its back on suffering” (FT 65). “The parable shows us how a community can be rebuilt by men and women who identify with the vulnerability of others, who reject the creation of a society of exclusion, and act instead as neighbours, lifting up and rehabilitating the fallen for the sake of the common good. At the same time, it warns us about the attitude of those who think only of themselves and fail to shoulder the inevitable responsibilities of life as it is” (FT 67).

We are also called upon to “direct society to the pursuit of the common good and, with this purpose in mind, to persevere in consolidating its political and social order, its fabric of relations, its human goals, “the existence of each and every individual is deeply tied to that of others: life is not

simply time that passes; life is a time for interactions” (FT 66).

Francis continues to stress the importance of relationships in the life of a Christian “Life exists where there is bonding, communion, fraternity; and life is stronger than death when it is built on true relationships and bonds of fidelity.” (FT 87) It is a known fact that good relationships are good for our health. “People involved in loving, philia-based relationships have fewer doctor visits, shorter hospital visits, have less pain, and have more positive emotions,” said Kirtly Parker Jones, MD, of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at University of Utah Healthcare.² “The spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love, which in the end remains “the criterion for the definitive decision about a human life’s worth or lack thereof” (FT 92) If humans grow up in an environment of love and caring, we are likely to have a future generation of people in leadership who bring these virtues and values to impact their work in politics, economics, science, medicine, teaching, etc. Imagine the world being impacted by people who love instead hate. We can witness a world envisioned by Isaiah 2:4 where nation will not take up sword against nation and will not train for war anymore. Where all the money spent on arms can be spent on the development of people in a world of peace. This can be the fruit of love.

8. Creating a World of Equality

A long standing inequality that has existed down the ages is gender inequality. Women denied rights that are given to men. People born as LGBTQI+ persons treated as sinners, not accepted even in their families much less in parish communities. They are condemned to live in the closet all their lives, not who God created them to be. They cannot live their truth, even though we are aware that Jesus came to give us all life, life in abundance (John 10:10).

² See <https://healthcare.utah.edu/healthfeed/postings/2017/02/relationships.php> “Seven reasons why loving relationships are good for you” accessed on 20th Oct 2021.

Handicapped persons also have been ignored, kept hidden in homes because people stare or pass unkind remarks. Wheelchair users have to be given easy access to Churches and public spaces.

In India, the poor are deprived of housing, medical care, employment, and several rights. They are condemned to live on handouts and charity. This violates their human dignity and value of self.

“Every human being has the right to live with dignity and to develop integrally; this fundamental right cannot be denied by any country. People have this right even if they are unproductive, or were born with or developed limitations. This does not detract from their great dignity as human persons, a dignity based not on circumstances but on the intrinsic worth of their being. Unless this basic principle is upheld, there will be no future either for fraternity or for the survival of humanity” (FT 97).

“As a community, we have an obligation to ensure that every person lives with dignity and has sufficient opportunities for his or her integral development.” (FT 118). In the context of mass migrations taking place today because of conflict, climate change or economic pressures, Pope Francis speaks about ‘rights without borders’. “No one, then, can remain excluded because of his or her place of birth, much less because of privileges enjoyed by others who were born in lands of greater opportunity. The limits and borders of individual states cannot stand in the way of this. As it is unacceptable that some have fewer rights by virtue of being women, it is likewise unacceptable that the mere place of one’s birth or residence should result in his or her possessing fewer opportunities for a developed and dignified life.” (FT 121) He also advises for limits to capitalism. “The right of some to free enterprise or market freedom cannot supersede the rights of peoples and the dignity of the poor, or, for that

matter, respect for the natural environment, for “if we make something our own, it is only to administer it for the good of all” (FT 122).

Employment is another important dimension of equality and dignity. In India where inequalities are so great, the majority are unskilled workers and unorganized. Many are employed in homes, housing societies, small businesses, and at the drop of a hat they are fired. “As a community, we have an obligation to ensure that every person lives with dignity and has sufficient opportunities for his or her integral development” (FT 118). “Not to share our wealth with the poor is to rob them and take away their livelihood. The riches we possess are not our own, but theirs as well”. In the words of Saint Gregory the Great, “When we provide the needy with their basic needs, we are giving them what belongs to them, not to us” (FT 119).

Getting involved in our country’s political and social activities is very much part of our Christian vocation. Pope Francis describes it as “social and political charity”. “It is an equally indispensable act of love to strive to organize and structure society so that one’s neighbour will not find himself in poverty”. It is an act of charity to assist someone suffering, but it is also an act of charity, to work to change the social conditions that caused his or her suffering” (FT 186).

9. A New Culture for a Changing World

For various reasons people move out of their home territory either voluntarily or involuntarily. Pope Francis recommends a ‘new culture, a culture of encounter’ that is “capable of transcending our differences and divisions” (FT 215 & 216). A “culture of encounter” means that we, as a people, should be passionate about meeting others, seeking points of contact, building bridges, planning a project that includes everyone. This becomes an aspiration and a style of life.” This helps people integrate into the new city or country they move into. “Ignoring the existence and rights of others will erupt in some form of violence, often when

least expected. Liberty, equality and fraternity can remain lofty ideals unless they apply to everyone” (FT 219).

A culture of ‘encounter’ helps with integration of people who are different in their faith, skin colour, caste or nationality. Today we are increasingly becoming aware of members of the LGBTQI+ community who are different and so often ignored, treated like they do not exist. “Subtle ways can be found to make others insignificant, irrelevant, of no value to society.” “A realistic and inclusive social covenant must also be a “cultural covenant”, one that respects and acknowledges the different worldviews, cultures and lifestyles that coexist in society” (FT 218).

Today when we are increasingly becoming aware of the need to care for our environment, Pope Francis recommends an ‘encounter’ with indigenous people. “Indigenous peoples, for example, are not opposed to progress, yet theirs is a different notion of progress, often more humanistic than the modern culture of developed peoples. Theirs is not a culture meant to benefit the powerful, those driven to create for themselves a kind of earthly paradise. Intolerance and lack of respect for indigenous popular cultures is a form of violence grounded in a cold and judgmental way of viewing them. No authentic, profound and enduring change is possible unless it starts from the different cultures, particularly those of the poor” (FT 220). Further, “inequality and lack of integral human development make peace impossible” (FT 235).

Pope Francis introduces the people of God to a new perspective of other faiths. Men of other faiths are quoted in the document. In FT 281 he points out that God’s love is the same for everyone regardless of their religious faith or even being atheist. He recommends that we come together on common ground to work for the common good and the poor. “Sincere and humble worship of God “bears fruit not in discrimination, hatred and violence, but in respect for the

sacredness of life, respect for the dignity and freedom of others, and loving commitment to the welfare of all” (FT 283).

Conclusion

The values of love, care and respect for every human person are embedded in every person created by God. That is the image of God we carry within ourselves. This image is distorted and even erased by greed and selfishness. Love and care are seen as virtues attributed to women only. In fact, men displaying these virtues are made fun of and ridiculed. As a result, we have developed an image of man that is affirmed as strong, macho, in control, loud and assertive. These characteristics are alien to the image of God, who sadly is depicted as ‘male’. This image has created the social structure of patriarchy which has been legitimized as a structure on which all social enterprises are constructed like the family, religious authority, politics, economics even several streams of medicine. By relegating love and care only to the realm of women, we have a world where politics, economics, religion and culture is increasingly individualistic. Businesses work for their own profit, countries spend enormous amount of their budgets on arms to protect themselves from the “enemy other”. The earth is exploited for profit, people are exploited for profit, the value of the country is based on its gross domestic product not on the welfare of its people. Religions have male heads who have forgotten and neglected the “feminist” perspectives of their faith leading our world to the mess it is in today.

The Christian faith is based on the values of the Gospel which *Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti* reflects through its pages. Jesus gave us only one commandment “Love one another.” We need to get back to the basics of our faith based on the gospel message of justice, peace and love, to make God’s reign of love a reality in our midst.

Christianity is a religion of hope. “Hope speaks to us of something deeply rooted in every human heart, independently of our circumstances and historical conditioning. Hope speaks to us of a thirst, an aspiration, a longing for a life of fulfilment, a desire

to achieve great things, things that fill our heart and lift our spirit to lofty realities like truth, goodness and beauty, justice and love... Hope is bold; it can look beyond personal convenience, the petty securities and compensations which limit our horizon, and it can open us up to grand ideals that make life more beautiful and worthwhile”. Let us continue, then, to advance along the paths of hope.” (FT 55)

Young people today are disenchanted with Christianity because of the way it is being understood and practised, they feel it does not address the issues with which they are concerned. For them human rights is the moral compass. They want to see gender equality with regard to women and LGBTQI+ persons, equality between persons of different class, caste and creed. They tap into a variety of scientific and social disciplines to endorse their sense of values, while the Church is lost in the tradition of a bygone era.

In the course of the “listening” sessions that Pope Francis has encouraged as part of the Synodal process hopefully dioceses will engage with the young to understand where they are at. *Fratelli-Sorelle Tutti* can be introduced to them and I am sure they will resonate with it. The future of the world lies in the hands of these young people!

References

- Francis, Pope. 2020. *Fratelli Tutti: On Fraternity and Social Friendship*. Maryknoll, New York: Orbis Books.
- Saldanha, Virginia. 2005. “Understanding Discipleship – A woman’s Perspective”, published in “The Church in India in the Emerging Third Millenium”, p. 454, Thomas D’Sa, (Ed). NBCLC, Bangalore.
- Wikipedia Contributors. (2021, November 14). Medha Patkar. In *Wikipedia, The Free Encyclopedia*. Retrieved 19:22, November 16, 2021, from <https://en.wikipedia>.

org/w/index.php?title=Medha_Patkar&oldid=1055201225

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Fratelli Tutti: **A Call for Inclusive Love**

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Abstract: Inclusive love transcends all barriers, as implied in the teaching of *Fratelli Tutti*. It shatters the chains that keep us separate; it builds bridges. Love creates one great family, where all of us can feel at home. The spiritual stature of a person's life is measured by love. Love for others moves us to seek the best for their lives. Love impels us towards universal communion. It calls for growth in openness. At a time when various forms of fundamentalist intolerance are damaging relationships between individuals, groups and

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peoples, we have to be committed to a love capable of welcoming differences. Our hearts expand as we step out of ourselves and embrace others. A love capable of transcending borders is the basis of social friendship, to be extended to all, especially to migrants. Many migrants are seeking opportunities for themselves and their families. Like the Samaritan who cared for the wounded man, even spending his own money and time, Jesus asks us to be available to those in need of our help, a sign of real solidarity, which means thinking and acting in terms of the needs of the global community. Forgiveness and reconciliation are central to inclusive love, which can overcome the challenges of racism and fragmentation, aggressive nationalism, uncaring globalism, local narcissism, limitless consumption, empty individualism, and cultural colonization.

Keywords: Crusades, Communion, Fanaticism, Ecstasis, Fundamentalism, Compassion, Integration

Introduction

Fraternity and social friendship are the ways Pope Francis indicates to build a better, more just and peaceful world, with the contribution of all: people and institutions. What are the tangible ways to advance for those who wish to build a more just and fraternal world in their ordinary relationships, in social life, politics and institutions? This is mainly the question that “*Fratelli Tutti*” (Abbreviated as FT) is intended to answer: the Pope describes it as a “Social Encyclical,” which borrows the title of the “Admonitions” of Saint Francis of Assisi, who used these words to address his brothers and sisters and proposed to them a way of life marked by the teachings of the Gospel. The Encyclical aims to promote a universal aspiration toward fraternity and social friendship. In the background of the Encyclical is the Covid-19 pandemic which, Francis reveals, unexpectedly erupted as he was writing this letter. But the global health emergency has demonstrated that no one can face life in isolation and that the

time has truly come to dream, then, as a single human family in which we are ‘brothers and sisters all.’

The present article tries to explain the Social Encyclical as a call to inclusive love. The article is mainly divided into two parts: (1) Positive Traits of Inclusive Love and (2) Challenges to Inclusive Love.

1. Positive Traits of Inclusive Love

a. Inclusive Love Promotes Fraternity and Social Friendship

St Francis of Assisi, the saint of fraternal love, simplicity and joy, prompted Pope Francis to devote this new Encyclical to fraternity and social friendship. Francis of Assisi sowed seeds of peace and walked alongside the poor, the abandoned, the infirm and the outcast, the least of his brothers and sisters.

This saint of fraternal love, simplicity and joy, who inspired me to write the Encyclical *Laudato Si'*, prompts me once more to devote this new Encyclical to fraternity and social friendship. Francis felt himself a brother to the sun, the sea and the wind, yet he knew that he was even closer to those of his own flesh. Wherever he went, he sowed seeds of peace and walked alongside the poor, the abandoned, the infirm and the outcast, the least of his brothers and sisters. (FT 2)

Inclusive Love Transcends Barriers: *Fratelli Tutti* calls for a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance, and declares blessed all those who love their brother “as much when he is far away from him as when he is with him.”

Fratelli Tutti, With these words, Saint Francis of Assisi addressed his brothers and sisters and proposed to them a way of life marked by the flavour of the Gospel. Of the counsels Francis offered, I would like to select the one in which he calls for a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance, and declares blessed all those

who love their brother “as much when he is far away from him as when he is with him”. In his simple and direct way, Saint Francis expressed the essence of a fraternal openness that allows us to acknowledge, appreciate and love each person, regardless of physical proximity, regardless of where he or she was born or lives. (FT 1)

Inclusive Love Builds Bridges: Love does not care if a brother or sister in need comes from one place or another. For love shatters the chains that keep us separate; in their place, it builds bridges. Love creates one great family, where all of us can feel at home... Love exudes compassion and dignity.

Yet this call to love could be misunderstood. Saint Paul, recognizing the temptation of the earliest Christian communities to form closed and isolated groups, urged his disciples to abound in love “for one another and for all” (1 Thess 3:12). In the Johannine community, fellow Christians were to be welcomed, “even though they are strangers to you” (3 Jn 5). In this context, we can better understand the significance of the parable of the Good Samaritan: love does not care if a brother or sister in need comes from one place or another. For “love shatters the chains that keep us isolated and separate; in their place, it builds bridges. Love enables us to create one great family, where all of us can feel at home... Love exudes compassion and dignity. (FT 62)

The parable clearly speaks to us of an essential and often forgotten aspect of our common humanity: fulfilment in love. We cannot allow anyone to go through life as an outcast. Instead, we should feel indignant and challenged to emerge from our comfortable isolation. (FT 68)

Inclusive Love Embraces All: There is an episode in the life of Saint Francis that shows his openness of heart, which went beyond boundaries. It was his visit to Sultan Malik-el-Kamil, in Egypt, which entailed considerable hardship for St Francis. That journey demonstrated the breadth and grandeur of his love, which sought to embrace everyone. Some eight hundred years ago Saint

Francis urged that all forms of hostility be avoided and that a humble and fraternal “subjection” be shown to those who did not share his faith.

There is an episode in the life of Saint Francis that shows his openness of heart, which knew no bounds and transcended differences of origin, nationality, colour or religion. It was his visit to Sultan Malik-el-Kamil, in Egypt, which entailed considerable hardship, given Francis’ poverty, his scarce resources, the great distances to be travelled and their differences of language, culture and religion. That journey, undertaken at the time of the Crusades, further demonstrated the breadth and grandeur of his love, which sought to embrace everyone. Francis’ fidelity to his Lord was commensurate with his love for his brothers and sisters. Unconcerned for the hardships and dangers involved, Francis went to meet the Sultan with the same attitude that he instilled in his disciples: if they found themselves “among the Saracens and other nonbelievers”, without renouncing their own identity they were not to “engage in arguments or disputes, but to be subject to every human creature for God’s sake”. In the context of the times, this was an extraordinary recommendation. We are impressed that some eight hundred years ago Saint Francis urged that all forms of hostility or conflict be avoided and that a humble and fraternal “subjection” be shown to those who did not share his faith. (FT 3)

Inclusive Love Fosters Harmony and Peace: St Francis of Assisi simply spread the love of God. In this way, he became a father to all and inspired the vision of a fraternal society. In the world of that time, cities were a theatre of brutal wars between powerful families, even as poverty was spreading through the countryside. Yet there Francis was able to

welcome true peace into his heart and sought to live in harmony with all. (FT 4)

Inclusive Love as Divine: Issues of human fraternity have always been a concern of mine. In this case, I have felt particularly encouraged by the Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb, with whom I met in Abu Dhabi, where we declared that “God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters”. This was a reflection born of dialogue and common commitment. (FT 5)

Inclusive Love as Fraternal: The following pages consider the universal scope of fraternal love, its openness to every human. In the face of present-day attempts to eliminate or ignore others, we may prove capable of responding with a new vision of fraternity and social friendship. The encyclical is an invitation to dialogue among all people of good will. (FT 6)

Inclusive Love as the Measurement of Spiritual Stature: The spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love. All of us need to recognize that love takes first place: love must never be put at risk, and the greatest danger lies in failing to love. (FT 92)

Inclusive Love Seeks the Best for Others: Love, then, is more than just a series of benevolent actions. Our love for others moves us to seek the best for their lives. (FT 94)

Inclusive Love Calls for Universal Openness: Love impels us towards universal communion. It calls for growth in openness and the ability to accept others as part of a continuing adventure that makes every periphery converge in a greater sense of mutual belonging. “Love also impels us towards universal communion. No one can mature or find fulfilment by withdrawing from others. By its very nature, love calls for growth in openness and the ability to accept others as part of a continuing adventure that makes every periphery converge in a greater sense of mutual belonging. As Jesus told us: “You are all brothers” (Mt 23:8).” (FT 95)

Inclusive Love as Foundation of Virtues: Without charity, we may perhaps possess only apparent virtues, incapable of sustaining life in common. The other virtues, without charity, do

not fulfil the commandments the way God wants them to be fulfilled. (FT 91)

Inclusive Love as Expression of Political Charity: Political charity is expressed in a spirit of openness. Government leaders should be the first to make sacrifices that foster encounter and to seek convergence on some issues. They should be ready to listen to other points of view. Through sacrifice and patience, they can help to create a beautiful polyhedral reality in which everyone has a place. It may seem utopian, yet we cannot renounce this lofty aim. (FT 190)

Inclusive Love as Welcoming Differences: At a time when various forms of fundamentalist intolerance are damaging relationships between individuals, groups and peoples, let us be committed to living and teaching the value of respect for others, a love capable of welcoming differences. Even as forms of fanaticism, closedmindedness and social and cultural fragmentation proliferate, a good politician will insist that different voices be heard. Disagreements may well give rise to conflicts, but uniformity leads to cultural decay. (FT 191)

Inclusive Love as Embracing Foreigner: In the parable of the Good Samaritan, we find a reason why our hearts should expand to embrace the foreigner. It derives from the enduring memory of the Jewish people in Egypt: “You shall not wrong or oppress a stranger, for you were strangers in the land of Egypt” (Ex 22:21). The call to fraternal love echoes throughout the New Testament: “For the whole law is summed up in a single commandment, ‘You shall love your neighbour as yourself’” (Gal 5:14). (FT 61)

b. Inclusive Love as Welcoming Migrants

Move to Stop Influx of Migrants: Certain populist political regimes maintain that an influx of migrants is to be prevented at all costs. Arguments are also made for the propriety of limiting aid to poor countries, so that they can hit rock bottom

and find themselves forced to take austerity measures. One fails to realize that behind such statements, great numbers of lives are at stake. Many migrants have fled from war. Others “are seeking opportunities for themselves and their families. They dream of a better future. (FT 37)

Response to Migrants: Unnecessary migration ought to be avoided; this entails creating in countries of origin the conditions needed for a dignified life. Yet until substantial progress is made in achieving this goal, we are obliged to respect the right of all individuals to find a place that meets their basic needs. Our response to the arrival of migrants can be summarized by four words: welcome, protect, promote and integrate. (FT 129)

Dignity of the Migrants: Migrants possess the same intrinsic dignity as any person. The inalienable dignity of each human person regardless of origin, race or religion, and the supreme law of fraternal love. (FT 39)

Protect Citizens and Help Migrants: Migrations will play a pivotal role in the future of our world. Europe has to find the right balance between its twofold moral responsibility to protect the rights of its citizens and to assure assistance and acceptance to migrants.

Migrations, more than ever before, will play a pivotal role in the future of our world”. At present, however, migration is affected by the “loss of that sense of responsibility for our brothers and sisters on which every civil society is based”. [43] Europe, for example, seriously risks taking this path. Nonetheless, “aided by its great cultural and religious heritage, it has the means to defend the centrality of the human person and to find the right balance between its twofold moral responsibility to protect the rights of its citizens and to assure assistance and acceptance to migrants”. (FT 40)

Fear of Migrants: Some people are fearful with regard to migrants. We need to move beyond those primal reactions because “there is a problem when doubts and fears condition our way of thinking and acting to the point of making us intolerant,

racist. Fear deprives us of the desire and the ability to encounter the other.” (FT 41)

c. Inclusive Love as Helping the Needy

Samaritan Helped with Money and Time: The Samaritan stopped, approached the man and cared for him personally, even spending his own money to provide for his needs. He also gave him his time. Certainly, he had his own plans for that day. Yet he was able to put all that aside in order to care for someone in need. He saw him as deserving of his time and attention. (FT 63)

Ignoring the Needy: Let us admit that, for all the progress we have made, we are still “illiterate” when it comes to caring for and supporting the most frail and vulnerable members of our societies. We have become accustomed to looking the other way, ignoring situations until they affect us directly. (FT 64)

Imitate the Good Samaritan: The parable presents the basic decision we need to make in order to rebuild our wounded world, to imitate the Good Samaritan. Any other decision would make us either one of the robbers or one of those who walked by without showing compassion for the sufferings of the man on the roadside.

The parable eloquently presents the basic decision we need to make in order to rebuild our wounded world. In the face of so much pain and suffering, our only course is to imitate the Good Samaritan. Any other decision would make us either one of the robbers or one of those who walked by without showing compassion for the sufferings of the man on the roadside. The parable shows us how a community can be rebuilt by men and women who identify with the vulnerability of others, who reject the creation of a society of exclusion, and act instead as neighbours, lifting up and rehabilitating the fallen for the sake of the common good. At the same time, it warns us

about the attitude of those who think only of themselves and fail to shoulder the inevitable responsibilities of life as it is. (FT 67)

Becoming Neighbours to All: Jesus told the parable of the Good Samaritan in answer to the question: Who is my neighbour? The word “neighbour”, in the society of Jesus’ time, usually meant those nearest us. For some Jews of that time, Samaritans were looked down upon, considered impure and were not among those to be helped. Jesus, himself a Jew, completely transforms this approach. He asks us not to decide who is close enough to be our neighbour, but rather that we ourselves become neighbours to all. (FT 80)

Help the Needy: Jesus asks us to be present to those in need of help, regardless of whether or not they belong to our social group. (FT 81)

Gift of Self to Others: Human beings cannot live, develop and find fulfilment except in the sincere gift of self to others. They also fully know themselves only in an encounter with other persons. Life exists where there is bonding, communion, and fraternity. (FT 87)

d. Inclusive Love as Moving Beyond Ourselves

In the depths of every heart, love creates bonds and expands existence. Lover ‘goes outside’ the self to find a fuller existence in another. For this reason, human always has to take up the challenge of moving beyond oneself.

In the depths of every heart, love creates bonds and expands existence, for it draws people out of themselves and towards others.[65] Since we were made for love, in each one of us “a law of *ekstasis*” seems to operate: “the lover ‘goes outside’ the self to find a fuller existence in another”.[66] For this reason, “man always has to take up the challenge of moving beyond himself”. (FT 88)

Closed Groups as Selfish: We find that our hearts expand as we step out of ourselves and embrace others. Closed groups that

define themselves in opposition to others tend to be expressions of selfishness. (FT 89)

Unity and Common Destiny of All: This need to transcend our own limitations also applies to different regions and countries. The ever-increasing number of communications in today's world makes us powerfully aware of the unity and common destiny of all. (FT 96)

Universal Aspiration to Fraternity: In this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity. (FT 8)

e. Inclusive Love Moves Towards Integration

For decades, it seemed that the world had learned a lesson from its many wars and disasters, and was slowly moving towards various forms of integration. For example, there was the dream of a united Europe, capable of acknowledging its shared roots and rejoicing in its rich diversity.

For decades, it seemed that the world had learned a lesson from its many wars and disasters, and was slowly moving towards various forms of integration. For example, there was the dream of a united Europe, capable of acknowledging its shared roots and rejoicing in its rich diversity. We think of “the firm conviction of the founders of the European Union, who envisioned a future based on the capacity to work together in bridging divisions and in fostering peace and fellowship between all the peoples of this continent”.[7] There was also a growing desire for integration in Latin America, and several steps were taken in this direction. In some countries and regions, attempts at reconciliation and rapprochement proved fruitful, while others showed great promise. (FT 10)

f. Inclusive Love Transcends Borders

A love capable of transcending borders is the basis of “social friendship”, which makes true universal openness possible. Those who look down on their own people tend to create within society categories of first and second class people.

A love capable of transcending borders is the basis of what in every city and country can be called “social friendship”. Genuine social friendship within a society makes true universal openness possible. This is a far cry from the false universalism of those who constantly travel abroad because they cannot tolerate or love their own people. Those who look down on their own people tend to create within society categories of first and second class, people of greater or lesser dignity, people enjoying greater or fewer rights. In this way, they deny that there is room for everybody. (FT 99)

Good Samaritan as a Foreigner: The parable of the Good Samaritan has still much to say to us. He was simply a foreigner without a place in society. He was able to interrupt his journey, change his plans, and unexpectedly come to the aid of an injured person who needed his help. (FT 101)

g. Inclusive Love as Solidarity

Solidarity Calls for Commitment: Solidarity calls for commitment on the part of those responsible for education and formation. (FT 114)

Solidarity Expressed in Service: Solidarity finds concrete expression in service, which means caring for vulnerability, for the vulnerable members of our families, our society, our people. (FT 115)

Meaning of Solidarity: Solidarity means thinking and acting in terms of community. It means that the lives of all are prior to the appropriation of goods by a few, combatting the structural causes of poverty, inequality, and unemployment.

The needy generally “practise the special solidarity that exists among those who are poor and suffering, and which

our civilization seems to have forgotten or would prefer in fact to forget. Solidarity is a word that is not always well received; in certain situations, it has become a dirty word, a word that dare not be said. Solidarity means much more than engaging in sporadic acts of generosity. It means thinking and acting in terms of community. It means that the lives of all are prior to the appropriation of goods by a few. It also means combatting the structural causes of poverty, inequality, the lack of work, land and housing, the denial of social and labour rights. It means confronting the destructive effects of the empire of money... Solidarity, understood in its most profound meaning, is a way of making history, and this is what popular movements are doing". (FT 116)

h. Inclusive Love as Local and Universal

Glocalization: An innate tension exists between globalization and localization. We need to pay attention to the global so as to avoid narrowness. Yet we also need to look to the local, which keeps our feet on the ground. Together, the two prevent us from falling into one of two extremes.

It should be kept in mind that “an innate tension exists between globalization and localization. We need to pay attention to the global so as to avoid narrowness and banality. Yet we also need to look to the local, which keeps our feet on the ground. Together, the two prevent us from falling into one of two extremes. In the first, people get caught up in an abstract, globalized universe... In the other, they turn into a museum of local folklore, a world apart, doomed to doing the same things over and over, incapable of being challenged by novelty or appreciating the beauty which God bestows beyond their borders”.[124] We need to have a global

outlook to save ourselves from petty provincialism. When our house stops being a home and starts to become an enclosure, a cell, then the global comes to our rescue, like a “final cause” that draws us towards our fulfilment. At the same time, though, the local has to be eagerly embraced, for it possesses something that the global does not: it is capable of being a leaven, of bringing enrichment, of sparking mechanisms of subsidiarity. Universal fraternity and social friendship are thus two inseparable and equally vital poles in every society. To separate them would be to disfigure each and to create a dangerous polarization. (FT 142)

i. Inclusive Love Promotes Healthy Openness

A healthy openness never threatens one’s own identity. A living culture does not import a mere carbon copy of those new elements, but integrates them in its own unique way. The result is a new synthesis that is ultimately beneficial to all. (FT 148)

Global Society as Universal Communion: Global society is not the sum total of different countries, but rather the communion that exists among them. The mutual sense of belonging is prior to the emergence of individual groups, which are part of the fabric of universal communion. All individuals know that they are part of the greater human family, without which they will not be able to understand themselves fully. (FT 149)

Self-fulfilment Requires Others: No one people, culture or individual can achieve everything on its own: to attain fulfilment in life we need others. An awareness of our own limitations and incompleteness becomes the key to envisaging and pursuing a common project. (FT 150)

j. Inclusive Love Integrates and Unites

We have to work strenuously to spread the culture of tolerance and of living together in peace. When a specific policy sows hatred towards other nations in the name of its own country’s

welfare, there is need to react in time and immediately to correct the course.

In this regard, Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb and I have called upon “the architects of international policy and world economy to work strenuously to spread the culture of tolerance and of living together in peace; to intervene at the earliest opportunity to stop the shedding of innocent blood”.[189] When a specific policy sows hatred and fear towards other nations in the name of its own country’s welfare, there is need to be concerned, to react in time and immediately to correct the course. (FT 192)

k. Inclusive Love Promotes Forgiveness and Reconciliation

There are those who prefer not to talk of reconciliation, for they think that conflict, violence and breakdown are part of the normal functioning of a society. Others think that promoting forgiveness means yielding ground and influence to others. For this reason, they feel it is better to keep things as they are. Still others believe that reconciliation is a sign of weakness.

There are those who prefer not to talk of reconciliation, for they think that conflict, violence and breakdown are part of the normal functioning of a society. In any human group there are always going to be more or less subtle power struggles between different parties. Others think that promoting forgiveness means yielding ground and influence to others. For this reason, they feel it is better to keep things as they are, maintaining a balance of power between differing groups. Still others believe that reconciliation is a sign of weakness; incapable of truly serious dialogue, they choose to avoid problems by ignoring injustices. Unable to deal with problems, they opt for an apparent peace. (FT 236)

Forgiveness and Reconciliation as Inter-religious Themes: Forgiveness and reconciliation are central themes in Christianity and in other religions. Yet there is a risk that an inadequate understanding of these profound convictions can lead to fatalism, apathy and injustice, or even intolerance and violence. (FT 237)

2. Some Challenges to Inclusive Love

a. Racism and Fragmentation

There is an aspect of universal openness in love that is existential. Every brother or sister in need, when abandoned or ignored by the society in which I live, becomes an existential foreigner, even though born in the same country. Racism is a virus that quickly mutates and goes into hiding, and lurks in waiting. (FT 97)

b. Pandemic Fragmentation

The Covid-19 pandemic has unexpectedly erupted, exposing our false securities. Aside from the different ways that various countries responded to the crisis, we witnessed a fragmentation that made it more difficult to resolve problems that affect us all. (FT 7)

c. Aggressive Nationalism

However, our own days, show signs of a certain regression. Past conflicts are breaking out anew, while instances of an extremist, resentful and aggressive nationalism are on the rise. In some countries, a concept of national unity influenced by various ideologies is creating new forms of selfishness and a loss of the social sense. These things remind us that it is not possible to settle for what was achieved in the past and complacently enjoy it, disregarding the fact that many of our brothers and sisters still endure situations that cry out for our attention.

Our own days, however, seem to be showing signs of a certain regression. Ancient conflicts thought long buried are breaking out anew, while instances of a myopic, extremist, resentful and aggressive nationalism are on the

rise. In some countries, a concept of popular and national unity influenced by various ideologies is creating new forms of selfishness and a loss of the social sense under the guise of defending national interests. Once more we are being reminded that “each new generation must take up the struggles and attainments of past generations, while setting its sights even higher. This is the path. Goodness, together with love, justice and solidarity, are not achieved once and for all; they have to be realized each day. It is not possible to settle for what was achieved in the past and complacently enjoy it, as if we could somehow disregard the fact that many of our brothers and sisters still endure situations that cry out for our attention”. (FT 11)

d. Uncaring Globalism

“Opening up to the world” is an expression co-opted by the economic and financial sector and is now used exclusively of openness to foreign interests or to the freedom of economic powers to invest without obstacles. We are in a world that promotes individual interests and weakens the communitarian dimension of life. The advance of this kind of globalism strengthens the identity of the more powerful, who can protect themselves, but it tends to diminish the identity of the weaker and poorer regions, making them more vulnerable and dependent. (FT 12)

e. Local Narcissism

Local narcissism is born of a certain insecurity and fear of the other that leads to rejection and the desire to erect walls for self-defence. Yet it is impossible to be “local” in a healthy way without being sincerely open to the universal.

There is a kind of “local” narcissism unrelated to a healthy love of one’s own people and culture. It is born of a certain insecurity and fear of the other that leads to rejection and the desire to erect walls for self-

defence. Yet it is impossible to be “local” in a healthy way without being sincerely open to the universal, without feeling challenged by what is happening in other places, without openness to enrichment by other cultures, and without solidarity and concern for the tragedies affecting other peoples. A “local narcissism” instead frets over a limited number of ideas, customs and forms of security; incapable of admiring the vast potential and beauty offered by the larger world, it lacks an authentic and generous spirit of solidarity. Life on the local level thus becomes less and less welcoming, people less open to complementarity. Its possibilities for development narrow; it grows weary and infirm. A healthy culture, on the other hand, is open and welcoming by its very nature; indeed, “a culture without universal values is not truly a culture”. (FT 146)

f. Limitless Consumption and Empty Individualism

As the document notes, there is a growing loss of the sense of history, a kind of “deconstructionism,” which is making headway in today’s culture. The one thing it leaves in its wake is the drive to limitless consumption and empty individualism. (FT 13)

g. Cultural Colonization

These are the new forms of cultural colonization. The peoples that abandon their tradition allow others to rob their very soul, end up losing not only their spiritual identity but also their moral consistency and, in the end, their intellectual, economic and political independence.

These are the new forms of cultural colonization. Let us not forget that “peoples that abandon their tradition and, either from a craze to mimic others or to foment violence, or from unpardonable negligence or apathy, allow others to rob their very soul, end up losing not only their spiritual identity but also their moral consistency and, in the end, their intellectual, economic

and political independence”.[11] One effective way to weaken historical consciousness, critical thinking, the struggle for justice and the processes of integration is to empty great words of their meaning or to manipulate them. Nowadays, what do certain words like democracy, freedom, justice or unity really mean? They have been bent and shaped to serve as tools for domination, as meaningless tags that can be used to justify any action. (FT 14)

Conclusion

Fratelli Tutti calls for a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance. Love shatters the chains that keep us separate; it builds bridges. Love creates one great family, where all of us can feel at home. God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters. In the face of present-day attempts to eliminate others, we may prove capable of responding with a new vision of fraternity and social friendship. The spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love. The greatest danger lies in failing to love. Love for others moves us to seek the best for their lives. Love impels us towards universal communion. It calls for growth in openness. Without charity, we may perhaps possess only apparent virtues, incapable of sustaining life in common.

At a time when various forms of fundamentalist intolerance are damaging relationships between individuals, groups and peoples, we have to be committed to living and teaching the value of respect for others, a love capable of welcoming differences. Disagreements may well give rise to conflicts, but uniformity leads to cultural decay. We find that our hearts expand as we step out of ourselves and embrace others. A love capable of transcending borders is the basis of “social friendship”, which makes true universal openness possible.

Many migrants have fled from war. Others “are seeking opportunities for themselves and their families. The Samaritan stopped, approached the man and cared for him personally, even spending his own money and time. Jesus asks us to be present to those in need of our help, a sign of real solidarity. Solidarity means thinking and acting in terms of the global community. We need to pay attention to the global so as to avoid narrowness. Yet we also need to look to the local, which keeps our feet on the ground. Forgiveness and reconciliation are central to inclusive love. Some of the challenges to inclusive love are racism and fragmentation, aggressive nationalism, uncaring globalism, local narcissism, limitless consumption, empty individualism, and cultural colonization.

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Living in Hope: *Fratelli Tutti*, Friendship and Forgiveness for a Sustainable Humanity

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Abstract: Basing ourselves on Pope Francis' *Tratelli Tutti* and the life of Charles de Foucauld, in this article, we make an attempt to outline a life lived in hope. After exploring the prophetic image of Charles de Foucauld we look at the worth of everyone who is abandoned. Then we try to converse with the others in a friendly manner leading to the overcoming of suspicion and conflict. This helps us to live our lives based on the two principles of forgiveness and friendship, which

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alone will enable us to live in hope and foster a sustainable world community. So we are challenged to walk on the path of living and sustaining hope! Hope for a just, egalitarian and love-filled world! A world of care, concern and compassion, especially for the weak and vulnerable!

Keywords: Fratelli Tutti, Hope, Best of Politics, Best of Religion, Charles de Foucauld, Friendship and Forgiveness

Introduction

How can we find traces of hope in the world we live in? How is Pope Francis' *Fratelli Tutti* an encyclical of realistic hope? How can we go forward with hope and joy and make ourselves and the world better? These are some of the questions we post in this article, that reflects on hope in *Fratelli Tutti*.

a. A Meditation on Living Hope

In this encyclical, Pope Francis invites everyone to renewed hope, for hope “speaks to us of something deeply rooted in every human heart, independently of our circumstances and historical conditioning. Hope speaks to us of a thirst, an aspiration, a longing for a life of fulfilment, a desire to achieve great things, things that fill our heart and lift our spirit to lofty realities like truth, goodness and beauty, justice and love... Hope is bold; it can look beyond personal convenience, the petty securities and compensations which limit our horizon, and it can open us up to grand ideals that make life more beautiful and worthwhile.” Let us continue, then, to advance along the paths of hope” (FT 55).

The noteworthy affirmation here is, “Hope is bold.” What does that mean in the context of this document and our pandemic era? Hope is far less than a straightforward future expectation. It alludes to something that can be felt after a long and harrowing journey. It could be a set period. It could be a trial that places demands on the individual. However, it is not a pipe dream or a fantasy. It suggests that something “More beautiful and worthwhile” can be a part of God’s plan for us. We are not

condemned to a future bleak and in decline from what our older generations have lived and experienced (Modern 2020).

b. Frustrated by injustice?

In this encyclical, Pope Francis challenges us to seek solutions to the injustices and growing indifference occurring throughout the world (Olea, 2020). It is mainly addressed to those who are frustrated by the injustice they perceive all around them.

An activist holds that “this is the type of reading that brings me a fresh wave of hope. This work, positioned next to the divisiveness and political trauma we’ve endured, offers the world renewed sense of hope” (Olea, 2020). She adds further that those who have felt frustrated with the injustices they have experienced may receive Christ’s living hope through this encyclical.

What touched the activist was Pope Francis’ centering this encyclical on the parable of the good Samaritan. The title of this second chapter, ‘A stranger on the road’ makes those who have experienced injustice feel it deeply. The activist ruminates: “I, too, am a stranger. For my entire life, I have been neither from here nor there. I have spent years adapting, relearning, moulding, trying to fit in as the perfect immigrant” (Olea, 2020).

In this hope-filled encyclical, Pope Francis “affirmed my dignity as a daughter of Christ. No, it is not my fault that my life has been used as a political pawn, a part of the throwaway culture we have created. This is not God’s will” (Olea, 2020).

While Pope Francis, of course, did not change the prevalent injustice, he addresses, recognizes and hears it. Pope Francis

noted that so much injustice has been disguised as justice, which only deepens the wound of the inflicted.

This resonates with the social activist who cares for the poor and the migrant. Drawing hope from the letter, he affirms: “Yet, we will continue to advocate for immigrant rights because it truly works of justice. It’s holy work” (Olea, 2020).

The motivation for the work for the poor and the vulnerable have “come from my belief in dignity and justice for all — not some — not the rich — not just for privileged — for all.” She is convinced that “fighting against policies designed to further alienate poor and vulnerable immigrants is the work of Christ. What an honour to be able to do this work” (Olea, 2020).

Further, she holds that “Pope Francis’ willingness to write about our dark reality, which is uncomfortable and challenging, is why I was given a renewed sense of hope. We cannot bring light to darkness if we don’t allow ourselves to see darkness.”

Brothers and sisters, we cannot only pray for better days. We have to be willing to be the reason better days will come. Do we recognize our own role as the good Samaritan? (Olea, 2020).

It provided us with hope when the pope affirms, “Sincere and humble worship of God ‘bears fruit not in discrimination, hatred and violence, but in respect for the sacredness of life, respect for the dignity and freedom of others, and loving commitment to the welfare of all’” (No. 283). Pope Francis’ reflection in this encyclical and particularly on the Good Samaritan offers a poignant examination of our interior selves. (Briscoe, 2020). It offers rays of hope to those who are terribly frustrated by experiences of injustice around them.

c. The Outline

So in this article, basing ourselves on Pope Francis’ *Tratelli Tutti* and the life of Charles de Foucauld, we make an attempt to outline a life lived in hope. After exploring the prophetic image of Charles de Foucauld we look at the worth of everyone who is

abandoned. Then we try to converse with the others in a friendly manner leading to the overcoming of suspicion and conflict. This helps us to live our lives based on the two principles of forgiveness and friendship, which alone will enable us to live in hope and foster a sustainable world community.

1. Living in Hope: Charles de Foucauld in *Fratelli Tutti*

This new encyclical on fraternity and social friendship, inspired by St. Francis of Assisi, the saint of fraternal love for all creatures, especially our abandoned brothers and sisters, focuses on the proclamation of Christianity's essential obligations: adoration of God and service to our neighbours. It states: “We believers are challenged to return to our sources, to concentrate on what is essential: worship of God and love for our neighbour, so that some of our teachings, taken out of context, do not end up feeding forms of contempt, hatred, xenophobia or negation of others” (FT 282).

Pope Francis is not bothered by his critics, those who claim his speeches are too concerned with politics and say little about eschatology (Fares, 2020).¹ Rather, following the criteria that the Lord has given us in the parable of the Good Samaritan, he removes eschatology from the sphere of abstract affirmations about the end of time and places it in our present-day reality, on the “roadside,” where we “come to know ourselves through our relationships with our

¹ For this section I am indebted to the enlightening article by Diago Fares (2020) which was originally published *La Civiltà Cattolica*, a periodical published by the Jesuits in Rome, Italy, since 1850. For the original article please see <https://www.laciviltacattolica.it/articolo/la-figura-di-charles-de-foucauld-in-fratelli-tutti/>.

brothers and sisters,” whenever “we encounter a person who is suffering” (FT 69).

If there were any doubts about what Francis wishes to announce and witness during his pontificate, he returns in this new encyclical to point out where social issues, the economy, politics, and religious life play out, undivided and unconfused: “Today there are more and more injured people. The decision to include or exclude those lying wounded along the roadside can serve as a criterion for judging every economic, political, social and religious project” (FT 69).

2. The Prophetic Image of Charles de Foucauld: Dreaming Together

Along with the opening image of Francis of Assisi, a closing image of Charles de Foucauld encircles the entire content of the encyclical in a hopeful embrace. The pope dynamically summarizes the encyclical by emphasizing fraternity and social friendship: “It is my desire that, in this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity” (FT 8). Let us dream together, he exhorts us at the beginning. And he repeats the suggestion at the end: “May God inspire in each of us the dream that inspired Charles de Foucauld” (cf. FT 287, Fares, 2020).

The figure of the soon-to-be-canonised Charles de Foucauld² serves as a great testimonial force in *Fratelli Tutti*: He gathers and updates Francis of Assisi's legacy, synthesizes and embodies Gospel content, and challenges us concretely wherever the most pressing issues of our time arise.

The pope's final two paragraphs, which he explicitly dedicates to Blessed Charles de Foucauld, are brief but dense with evangelical

² It may be noted that Blessed Charles de Foucauld will be canonised on May 15, 2022 along with the Indian Blessed Lazarus or Devasagayam. See (Vatican News. 2021).

content. Francis describes de Foucauld's dream of total self-giving to God and his brothers and sisters, allowing him to become "brother of all" or "universal brother." de Foucauld understood that he could realise this only by "identifying himself with the least" (FT 287; cf. 2-4). The most important thing the pope points out to us is that this is not a random dream. It comes weighted with history: the dream of Blessed Charles is the same one that God inspired in Francis of Assisi. It is an ideal long dreamed, an ideal that also involves a path of transformation within us, to make us feel ourselves to be brothers, sisters and friends of all, just like these saints (Pandikattu 2005).

This dream of fraternity and social friendship has always been among the primary concerns of Pope Francis (cf. FT 5). And we note that de Foucauld's spirituality does not appear only in the final paragraphs but pervades the entire encyclical. In addition to the explicit reference to fraternity and social friendship specific to this saint, Farres highlight aspects of his spirituality that are extensively present in *Fratelli Tutti*.

3. The Worth of the Abandoned

In chapter three, the "stranger on the roadside" is called "the abandoned," an expression that the pope uses to speak of the concreteness of Francis of Assisi's universal love and Charles de Foucauld's identification "with the poor, abandoned deep in the African desert" (FT 287).

This preference for the most abandoned has an ethical as well as a deeply theological underpinning. In Charles de Foucauld's life, abandonment into the hands of the Father ("prayer of abandonment") and embracing the least in their abandonment are synonymous: "Embrace humility, poverty, abandonment, abjection, loneliness, suffering with Jesus in the manger; do not make any case for human greatness,

elevation, the esteem of men, but esteem the poor as well as the rich. As for me, I always aim to seek the last of the last places, to order my life so as to be the last, the most despised of men” (Cited in Fares, 2020).

It is worth noting that de Foucauld not only searches for the abandoned one by one, but he also captures all of the people in each of them: to be more specific, he searches for the most abandoned peoples. According to Blessed Charles: “Since no people seemed to be more abandoned than these, I urged my request and obtained permission from the Apostolic Prefect of the Sahara to settle in the Algerian Sahara and to lead you into solitude, seclusion and silence, manual labour and holy poverty, alone or with some priest or lay brother in Jesus, a life as far as possible in accordance with the life of the beloved Jesus in Nazareth” (Fares, 2020).

What is the value of a human being? In this encyclical, Francis tells us that a human being has a value not only because he is worthy of justice and mercy, because he is a brother or sister, and because he is equal in humanity, but also because he is worthy of being our friend. “As the Latin American Bishops taught, ‘only the closeness that makes us friends can enable us to appreciate deeply the values of the poor today, their legitimate desires, and their own manner of living the faith. The option for the poor should lead us to friendship with the poor’” (FT 234, Fares, 2020)

4. The Conversation with Friends

Chapter six, on dialogue and social friendship, reflects the wisdom of Charles de Foucauld’s own resolution to “increase my conversation with the humble, shorten it with the powerful.” Worthy of note is the emphasis on dialogue in his way of approaching his Muslim brothers: “Approaching them, making contact, befriending them, making their prejudices against us fall, through daily and friendly relations; changing, through

conversation and the example of our life, their ideas” (Cited in Fares, 2020).

His conversation stems from more than just his natural sociability, nor is it merely a pastoral strategy. Prayer, for him, is the most important thing in life because it allows him to communicate with God: “Prayer is any conversation of the soul with God [...], an intimate conversation, a delightful secret” (Cited in Fares, 2020). And it is precisely this most precious dimension of his that he offers to the most humble people he meets. Charles de Foucauld is one of those men of whom one can say, as the highest praise, “he speaks to everyone,” a person who makes no distinction between people, not only as regards being just and open, but also as regards the kind of conversation that we reserve only for those we consider worthy of friendship.

In the first chapter entitled, “The shadows of a closed world,” the pope goes beyond a criticism of the degradation affecting dialogue through false news, slander and denigration of neighbours, which are so damaging to the political and social life of a country and the world. Francis goes to the heart of a friendly dialogue because it is the only one capable of uniting humanity, of making us speak in the first person plural, saying “us” with the heart. He says: “They lack the physical gestures, facial expressions, moments of silence, body language and even the smells, the trembling of hands, the blushes and perspiration that speak to us and are a part of human communication. Digital relationships, which do not demand the slow and gradual cultivation of friendships, stable interaction or the building of a consensus that matures over time, have the appearance of sociability. Yet they do not really build community; instead, they tend to disguise and expand the very individualism that finds expression in xenophobia and in contempt for the vulnerable. Digital

connectivity is not enough to build bridges. It is not capable of uniting humanity” (FT 43).

There is a way of conversing that is only possible with social friendship. The pope's goal is to build consensus around the fundamental truth of every human being's absolute dignity, the pleasure of recognizing the other, and the recovery of kindness. When speaking with friends, these are the modes of communication that are fully in place. (Fares, 2020)

Such conversion or dialogue means going deeper than “feverish exchange” (FT 200) on social media and a “noisy potpourri of facts and opinions” (FT 201) we often find in the traditional media. Political leaders practising dialogue would recognize that others have something valuable to contribute and that conflicting points of view are worthy of respect.

The true encounter does not push others away because they make us uncomfortable; it is rooted in a “basic sense of belonging” to each other which is present within each human being (230). It does not mean avoiding conflicts or “making society blandly uniform” (FT 228). Political leaders practising encounters would foster reconciliation that happens through “open, honest, and patient negotiation” (FT 244, Jones, 2020)

Leaders who show solidarity would practice “thinking and acting in terms of community,” and would recognize that being born in one place or another does not make a person more or less worthy of the rights and privileges of being human (FT 116). On the contrary, “the dignity of others is to be respected in all circumstances, not because that dignity is something we have invented or imagined, but because human beings possess an intrinsic worth” that comes from God (FT 213).

This call for dialogue, encounter, and solidarity politics may appear utopian or naive. Francis admits this several times. Yet, he reminds us that change happens on the level of ordinary people, and that “each individual can act as an effective leaven by the way he or she lives each day” (FT 231). In a very practical way, we

can strive to change our lives day by day according to the model of the Good Samaritan, and we can vote for the political leaders who best exemplify this “better kind of politics.” No candidate, or society, will ever be perfect, but we must not lose hope: Francis reminds us that “God continues to sow abundant seeds of goodness in our human family” (FT 54, Jones, 2020)

5. The Overcoming of Conflicts through the Intimate and the Universal

The figure of Charles de Foucauld assumes a paradigmatic stature in the perspective of Francis, who presents him as the one who embodied in our time the Gospel truth of the yeast that ferments the dough.³

The pope returns to this intimate concern in the encyclical in a broader context of reflection (cf. FT 5), where he seeks to universalize what exists most freely and intimately, such as friendship, so that fraternity can take root deeply in humanity's social and political life. In fact, fraternity is insufficient. From Cain on, the conflicts between brothers – from inheritance disputes to civil wars – are frequently the most ferocious. It is necessary to cultivate freely offered friendship in order to have a good fraternal relationship. This adds the qualitative component of the free choice to be friends to fraternity and thus consolidates a fraternal relationship that, because it is based on an unchosen common

³ According to the German theologian, Romano *Guardini* (1885 – 1968), whom the Pope cherishes, only what is more intimate can be transformed into something truly universal; and only what is more universal can be radically internalised. This contrasts with all false universalism and all false intimacy.

origin, can lead to friendship as much as the opposite (Fares, 2020).

The pope's discernment of social exclusion as the evil of our time leads us to the conclusion that it can only be resolved by an intimate and gratuitous reality such as the desire for friendship, which involves considering the other not only as equal in dignity, despite differences of race, religion, or social condition, but also as capable of friendship. The figure of Charles de Foucauld, far removed from that of the solitary little friar dedicated to a heroic but individual and inimitable mission, before our eyes are transformed into a universal figure, who carries out a mission that is totally imitable and programmatic. It was his intuition, for example, that in order to prepare the Muslim world for the coming of the Gospel and Christ, slow work of establishing unconditional friendship and service is required, without the pretension of imposing any universal truth. He universalised the Christian service practised toward every person he met, and not simply general Christian ideas. On these, rather, he was silent. He declared: "Such is the pastor, such is the people." "The good that a soul does is in direct proportion to its inner spirit." "The sanctification of the peoples of this region is, therefore, in my hands! They will be saved if I become holy."¹

Let us examine how intense the relationship between the radicality of Blessed de Foucauld's personal holiness and the force of universal irradiation of that same holiness to all peoples is in Blessed de Foucauld. This is exemplified by the parable of the yeast in the dough. But Pope Francis also demonstrates the other side of the coin: the relationship between interiority and universality is not a one-way street in which the more interior one becomes, the more universal one becomes. Francis teaches us that there is no true universality that does not attempt to take root in the most fundamental values, which are both free and gratuitous. A politics that does not cultivate a desire for friendship among the people and instead focuses on manipulating attitudes and votes from without will never be true politics, that is, service to the

common good. And, although it appears to take longer, we can say the same about the economy: an economic system that does not reach out to the most marginalized will eventually collapse on a global scale (Fares, 2020).

And, going a step further, we can say the same thing about joy and beauty: a joy that not everyone can rejoice in, that only a few can share selfishly, is not a complete joy. It's missing something. Everything is interconnected, and the relationship between interiority and universality is about being, not theory (Pandikattu, 2019).

6. The Principles of Forgiveness and Friendship

This healthy and fundamental connection between interiority and universality also illuminates those famous principles the pope always recalls: the principle that the whole is more than the part, and even more than the mere sum of the parts (cf. FT 78; 145; 215); and the principle that “unity is superior to conflict” (FT 245). These should not be read in the line of abstract reasoning, opposing the different definitions of each concept, but in the vital sense that goes beyond any definition, because it is expressed in the asymmetrical tension that is given between what exists in the most intimate and gratuitous setting, and what can be expected to be more universal (Fares, 2020).

The pope asserts that universality is rooted in the intimacy of what is more local: “There is a false openness to the universal, which derives from the empty superficiality of those who are not able to penetrate deeply into their own homeland, or of those who carry an unresolved resentment toward their own people. In any case, ‘we constantly have to broaden our horizons and see the greater good which will benefit us all. But this has to be done without evasion or uprooting. We need to sink our roots deeper into the fertile soil and history of our native place, which is a gift of God.

We can work on a small scale, in our own neighbourhood, but with a larger perspective...The global need not stifle, nor the particular prove barren.’ Our model must be that of a polyhedron, in which the value of each individual is respected, where ‘the whole is greater than the part, but it is also greater than the sum of its parts’ (FT 145).

The image of the Good Samaritan sums up this relationship between dealing with the whole heart of a single case and building of an “us” around it. For this, “we can start from below and, case by case, act at the most concrete and local levels, and then expand to the farthest reaches of our countries and our world, with the same care and concern that the Samaritan showed for each of the wounded man’s injuries. [...] Yet let us not do this alone, as individuals. The Samaritan discovered an innkeeper who would care for the man; we too are called to unite as a family that is stronger than the sum of small individual members. For ‘the whole is greater than the part, but it is also greater than the sum of its parts’” (FT 78).

In the same way, the union capable of overcoming conflicts is the one that is rooted “in the highest dimension of ourselves.” “On numerous occasions, I have spoken of ‘a principle indispensable to the building of friendship in society, namely, that unity is greater than conflict... This is not to opt for a kind of syncretism, or for the absorption of one into the other, but rather for a resolution which takes place on a higher plane and preserves what is valid and useful on both sides.’ All of us know that ‘when we, as individuals and communities, learn to look *beyond* ourselves and our particular interests, then understanding and mutual commitment bear fruit... in a setting where conflicts, tensions and even groups once considered hostile can attain a multifaceted unity that gives rise to new life’” (FT 245, Fares, 2020).

Speaking of his desire to be a universal brother, Charles de Foucauld opines: “The natives seem to welcome us well. This reception is not sincere; they give in to necessity... How long will it take for them to have the feelings they simulate? It may be that

they will never have them. If they do, it will be the day when they will be Christians... Will they know how to distinguish between soldiers and priests; to see in us servants of God, ministers of peace and charity, universal brothers? I don't know... If I fulfil my duty, Jesus will spread abundant graces, and they will understand" (Cited in Fares, 2020).

Francis, in this context, points out two things as the highest and most intimate, because they are fully free: forgiveness and friendship. (Fares, 2020)

a. Forgiveness

After a detailed phenomenological description in which he admits all the difficulties and deviations connected with the idea of forgiveness, the pope speaks to us of "free and heartfelt forgiveness," which is "a reflection of God's own infinite ability to forgive." He writes: "If forgiveness is gratuitous, then it can be shown even to someone who resists repentance and is unable to beg pardon" (FT 250). In one of the most original passages of the encyclical, the pope states that forgiveness does not mean forgetting, and specifies his proposal: "In the face of a reality that can in no way be denied, relativised or concealed, forgiveness *is still possible*. In the face of an action that can never be tolerated, justified or excused, *we can still* forgive. In the face of something that cannot be forgotten for any reason, *we can still* forgive" (FT 250; italics ours). We see here, expressed as what is most universally able to be demanded, the condition without which a fraternal society cannot be built: forgiveness. That is, we see that it can only be given as a free and gratuitous interior act.

The pope does not say "we must" but "we can" forgive. This decision – choosing to forgive – is not idealistic or a purely religious matter. Any alliance – local, national or worldwide – always implies a decision to forgive certain things in order

to move forward. Forgiveness as a free decision is at the root of any policy that seeks the common good.

b. Friendship

Further, Francis points out: “Social friendship and universal fraternity necessarily call for an acknowledgement of the worth of every human person, always and everywhere. If each individual is of such great worth, it must be stated clearly and firmly that ‘the mere fact that some people are born in places with fewer resources or less development does not justify the fact that they are living with less dignity.’ This is a basic principle of social life that tends to be ignored in a variety of ways by those who sense that it does not fit into their worldview or serve their purposes” (FT 106).

Reflecting on friendship, Francis emphasises what he calls the “law of ecstasy,” of going out of oneself to find in the other potential for the growth of our being (Fares, 2020). “In the depths of every heart, love creates bonds and expands existence, for it draws people out of themselves and toward others. Since we were made for love, in each one of us a law of *ekstasis* seems to operate: ‘the lover *goes outside* the self to find a fuller existence in another.’ For this reason, ‘people must take up the challenge of moving beyond themselves” (FT 88).

This is why the noblest forms of friendship are found in the hearts that let themselves be completed. The bonds binding couples and friends open the heart around us, making us capable of going out of ourselves to welcome everyone (cf. FT 89). The most proper characteristic of friendship is love for others as such, and this moves us to seek the best for them. “Only by cultivating this way of relating to one another will we make possible a social friendship that excludes no one and a fraternity that is open to all” (FT 94).

7. Choosing the Best of Politics and of Religions

Thus we see how the tension between interiority and universality is the one that builds the best politics and fosters dialogue between the best aspects of each religion.

The pope's message on politics, however, speaks to this current climate in a particularly striking way. Pope Francis admits that “for many people today, politics is a distasteful word” (FT 176). Corruption, poor governance, and seemingly hopeless division have led to a high degree of cynicism toward political leaders in many countries. On the contrary, he considers politics a noble profession, but only if leaders practice it “out of a tender care for others” (FT 194). Politicians have a unique opportunity: they can help individuals, yes, but they also have the power to create the very conditions by which people can flourish, which has a much larger impact. Politics has fallen into disrepute because individualism and an unhealthy populism have corrupted it. What we need, says Francis, is “a better kind of politics, one truly at the service of the common good” (FT 154, Jones, 2020).

The pope adds: “Recognising that all people are our brothers and sisters, and seeking forms of social friendship that include everyone, is not merely utopian. It demands a decisive commitment to devising effective means to this end. Any effort along these lines becomes a noble exercise of charity. For whereas individuals can help others in need, when they join together in initiating social processes of fraternity and justice for all, they enter the ‘field of charity at its most vast, namely, political charity.’ This involves working for a social and political order whose soul is social charity. Once more, I appeal for a renewed appreciation of

politics as “a lofty vocation and one of the highest forms of charity, inasmuch as it seeks the common good” (FT 180).

As for the relationship between the various religions, Francis continues to direct the dialogue not around ideas about God, but rather to the appreciation of every human person as a creature called to be a child of God. This, to begin with, always allows each religion to “contribute significantly to building fraternity and defending justice in society. Dialogue between the followers of different religions does not take place simply for the sake of diplomacy, consideration or tolerance. In the words of the Bishops of India, ‘the goal of dialogue is to establish friendship, peace and harmony, and to share spiritual and moral values and experiences in a spirit of truth and love’” (FT 271).

The eighth chapter – “Religions at the Service of Fraternity in the World” – is particularly clear if we read what Charles de Foucauld said about his hermitage at Béni Abbès, where he welcomed the visits of nomads and people in general: “In the ‘Fraternity’ – as he called his hermitage – to always be humble, sweet and serve, just as Jesus and Mary and Joseph did in the holy house of Nazareth... Sweetness, humility, abjection, charity, serving others” (Fares, 2020).

8. The Call to Live in Hope

“I offer this social encyclical as a modest contribution to continued reflection, in the hope that in the face of present-day attempts to eliminate or ignore others, we may prove capable of responding *with a new dream of fraternity and social friendship* that will not remain at the level of words” (FT 6; italics ours). (Fares, 2020)

A reaction is necessary given the magnitude of the world crisis affecting us on all sides. The pope invites us to react not with words, but with a new dream, that dream realised by Francis of Assisi and Charles de Foucauld with small gestures of a radicality that carries within itself a seed of universal expansion. Francis

proposes the concrete example of the many ordinary people who reacted generously in the face of the unexpected pandemic of Covid-19: “The recent pandemic enabled us to recognise and appreciate once more all those around us who, in the midst of fear, responded by putting their lives on the line” (FT 54, Fares, 2020)

The pages of his encyclical, according to the pope, “do not claim to offer a complete teaching on fraternal love, but rather to consider its universal scope, its openness to every man and woman” (FT 6). This love, capable of extending beyond borders “has as its basis what we call ‘social friendship’ in every city and in every country.” “Genuine social friendship within a society makes true universal openness possible” (FT 99). This is the dynamic contained in the words of St. Francis who declares “blessed is he who loves the other ‘when he is as far from him as if he were next to him’” (FT 1), those who are distant – from a geographical, cultural, ideological, political, or religious point of view – as much as those who are closest. (Fares, 2020) (Fares, 2020)

Fratelli Tutti has the style of a conversation between friends, of those conversations from which, dealing with the vital issues that challenge us and move us, more than mere definitions, inspire our interest in the concrete hope that comes from this friendly and fraternal way of speaking (Fares, 2020). That changes the partners in conversation and their worlds!

Conclusion

The parable of the Good Samaritan, which is the basis of *Fratelli Tutti*, begs every person of good will to examine that key aspect of human life that every Christian knows is true: *in giving we receive*. The pouring forth of selfless love,

the imitation of Christ the Good Shepherd who laid down his life for his sheep, alone offers the restless heart peace. Pope Francis puts it this way: “The parable clearly does not indulge in abstract moralizing, nor is its message merely social and ethical. It speaks to us of an essential and often forgotten aspect of our common humanity: we were created for a fulfilment that can only be found in love” (Briscoe, 2020).

Whether the suffering we encounter is racial injustice, sickness, poverty or exhausted politics, only love born of compassion and sacrifice will bring aid to our afflicted sisters and brothers (Pandikattu 2002).

The parable provides a poignant examination of our interior selves through its characters and their responses to injustice, even evil. There are robbers. Are we robbers? How should robbers be dealt with? Are we merely devout passers-by? Are we the injured man? What inhibits us from being Good Samaritans?

In order to further the goods of fraternity and social friendship, Pope Francis instructs us: “All of us have a responsibility for the wounded.” It is, after all, in the stranger, the prisoner, the hungry and thirsty, and the sick, that we find ourselves meeting Christ (Mt. 25:35-36).

In the classical philosophical and theological tradition, to be a friend to another means to see another’s good as one’s own. St. Thomas Aquinas says of friendship, “a certain mutual love is requisite, since friendship is between friend and friend” (ST II-II, q. 23, a. 1). To be a Good Samaritan, to be willing to regard another as neighbour, seems to require something of the offering of the hand of friendship: to desire for another his or her true good (Briscoe, 2020).

Here we do not need to enumerate the challenges that such a project faces. What we need to embrace is the hope that such an undertaking is possible. And it is.

Far from being a utopian fantasy, sacrificial love is to be had all around us. The Good Shepherd himself pours into our worn and

wear and wary hearts the ever-new wine of charity. This wine will fill us, warm us, and vivify us.

There is always hope to be had in the Gospel. Jesus will extend his invitation to self-renunciation and compassion again, and again, and again. Pope Francis encourages us, saying: “Each day offers us a new opportunity, a new possibility. We should not expect everything from those who govern us, for that would be childish. We have the space we need for co-responsibility in creating and putting into place new processes and changes” (FT 77).

When next we find ourselves on the road, whether today, tomorrow or soon after, let us find ourselves, that is, let us discover again the things truly worth spending our lives for, by loving our neighbour (Briscoe, 2020). Charles de Foucauld will accompany us. Francis Assisi will follow us. On the path of living and sustaining hope! Hope for a just, egalitarian and love-filled world! A world of care, concern and compassion, especially for the weak and vulnerable!

References

- Bernard, Joseph. n.d. ‘How Having An Open Mind And Open Heart Can Change The World’. *Explore Life Coaching*. Retrieved 28 October 2021 (<http://www.explorelifeblog.com/blog/2012/8/29/how-having-an-open-mind-and-open-heart-can-change-the-world-1.html>).
- Borg, Joe. 2020. ‘Encyclical Special 3: Migrants: A Heart Open to the Whole World’. *Newsbook*. Retrieved 28 October 2021 (<https://newsbook.com.mt/en/encyclical-special-3-migrants-a-heart-open-to-the-whole-world/>).
- Briscoe, Patrick. 2020. ‘The Theological Heart of “Fratelli Tutti,” and Where to Find Hope’. *Aleteia — Catholic*

Spirituality, Lifestyle, World News, and Culture. Retrieved 28 October 2021 (<https://aleteia.org/2020/10/04/the-theological-heart-of-fratelli-tutti-and-where-to-find-hope/>).

Fares, Diago. 2020. 'React in Hope: The Figure of Charles de Foucauld in "Fratelli Tutti"'. *Catholic Outlook*. Retrieved 28 October 2021 (<https://catholicoutlook.org/react-in-hope-the-figure-of-charles-de-foucauld-in-fratelli-tutti/>).

Francis, Pope. (2020). *Fratelli Tutti of the Holy Father Francis: On Fraternity and Social Friendship*. Cottbus, Germany HijezGlobal Press.

Jones, Doug. 2020. 'The Politics of Pope Francis: Fratelli Tutti's Message of Hope'. *The Jesuit Post*. Retrieved 22 November 2021 (<https://thejesuitpost.org/2020/10/the-politics-of-pope-francis-fratelli-tuttis-message-of-hope/>).

Modern, Juan Diego. 2020. 'Fratelli Tutti 55: An Invitation To Hope'. *Catholic Sensibility*. Retrieved 28 October 2021 (<https://catholic-sensibility.wordpress.com/2020/12/10/fratelli-tutti-55-an-invitation-to-hope/>).

Olea, Edith Avila. 2020. 'Frustrated by Injustice? Read "Fratelli Tutti" and Have Hope'. *Catholic Philly*. Retrieved 28 October 2021 (<https://catholicphilly.com/2020/11/commentaries/frustrated-by-injustice-read-fratelli-tutti-and-have-hope/>).

Pandikattu, K. 2002. *Hopefully Yours...* Pune: Jnanam.

Pandikattu, K. 2005. *Reasons for Hope: Its Nature, Role, and Future*. Washington, D.C: Council for Research in Values and Philosophy.

Pandikattu, K. 2019. *Everything is Interrelated: Christian Trinity and Hindu Advaita as experienced by Raimundo Panikkar and Francis D'Sa SJ*. Delhi: Indian Society for

Promoting Christian Knowledge; Pune: Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth.

Vatican News. 2021. 'Charles de Foucauld to Become a Saint on 15 May - Vatican News'. Retrieved 22 November 2021 (<https://www.vaticannews.va/en/vatican-city/news/2021-11/charles-de-foucauld-blesseds-canonization-15-may.html>).

Wood. 2013. '7 Ways To Open Your Heart to The World'. *Lifhack*. Retrieved 28 October 2021 (<https://www.lifhack.org/articles/lifestyle/7-ways-open-your-heart-the-world.html>).

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Fratelli Tutti: A Feminist Biblical-Theological Appraisal

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Abstract: With immense gratitude to God for the person, vision and mission of Pope Francis who titled his Encyclical Letter *Fratelli Tutti* (FT) after the example of St. Francis of Assisi, my paper makes a modest attempt to unearth the significance of FT.

True to the title of the paper, it must be said that, in the light of today's post-Vatican thinking and women's movements, the traditional understanding of the Bible needs to be reviewed and reinterpreted. The Bible, regarded as synonymous with the Word of God, is liberative and empowering. However, it comes to us mediated by human beings, languages and thought patterns conditioned by their particular age and culture. Hence, we should

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not allow to be victimised by the androcentric and sexist elements in biblical texts. A holistic approach to biblical and theological studies ought to be developed, keeping in mind the emergence of feminist liberation hermeneutics and theology.

Keywords: *Fratelli Tutti*, Feminist Hermeneutics, Feminist Theology, Women in the Bible

Introduction

In response to the request of the editor of *Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies* to write an article on Pope Francis' *Fratelli Tutti* (FT) from women's perspective, my paper makes a modest attempt to explore the richness of Pope Francis' encyclical letter on 'Fraternity and Social Friendship' as stated in the title, and share my views as a woman committed to balanced feminist ideologies, hermeneutics and theology.

Situating the study in the lived experiences of women, who form part of the patriarchal society and church, calls us to challenge the discrepancy between the idealized concept of women and their real life situation. On the one hand, women are exalted and praised; on the other they are subjugated and side-lined. Despite the Goddess worship in our temples and shrines, Marian veneration in our churches and grottos, and the assurance of equal opportunities guaranteed by the Indian Constitution, as well as by the empowering declarations of the official documents of Vatican II (e.g., *GS/29*, 8, 9, 60; *AA/9*), women are still struggling to find their own space to redefine their identities and roles. Set within this paradoxical context, we shall reflect on FT the third encyclical letter of Pope Francis. Although used liberally, the terms 'feminist', 'feminist hermeneutics and theology' need clarification.

Feminist is a person who believes in and supports feminism, especially one who actively campaigns to achieve change. Feminism may be described as a theory and movement capable of challenging patriarchal structures which keep women subjugated, and at the same time providing alternatives for a just society. It does not mean a rejection of men or a replacing of male power with female power. On the contrary, its emphasis is on enhancing shared responsibility, partnership and trust, inclusive decision-making with an inclusionary authority structure. It connotes a genuine commitment to realizing the full equality of women with men in the possession and exercise of human dignity and rights (Gen 1:26-27). Feminists see power as empowerment of self, not control over others; power is exercised as power *with* and not power *over*. Feminism in its broadest sweep is a humanistic concern; it is about liberation (Raj 1984 & Coll 1994). Unfortunately, feminism has been projected as a ‘Western’ phenomenon by traditionalists and Leftists alike, though for different reasons (Jayawardena & Kelkar 1989). Far from denying the God-given biological differences between the sexes, feminists acknowledge, accept and celebrate them.

Feminist Hermeneutics and Theology share the concerns of feminism. For centuries theology has been the ‘privileged possession’ of clerics. Consequently, Christian theology has side-tracked the experiences of the oppressed, particularly of women. Feminist theology presents a radical critique of religious and theological thinking stuck in patriarchal moorings. It provides a clear paradigmatic shift in biblical interpretations. It makes one realize that a religion developed out of partial experience cannot respond adequately to the needs of full humanity. A theology that perceives God, humankind and the world through solely masculine experience is obviously defective and incomplete. Feminist theology envisions a new community based upon the values of mutuality, reciprocity and inclusiveness. Underlining the experience-based and struggle-centred nature of feminist hermeneutics, Pearl Drego says, ‘Women’s lives are the ‘text’ for interpretation and elucidation’ (Drego 2010: 232-252).

Aware of the fact that the Bible and its interpretations have been embedded in a patriarchal culture, religion and society, feminist scholars – women and men alike – have underlined the need for reading the biblical texts from feminist perspectives. Written from the socio-cultural perspective of male authors, the Bible – God’s Word in human language – has legitimized women’s subordination in Christian tradition. Therefore, a hermeneutics of suspicion should inform any reading of biblical texts and commentaries, and reconstruct them in terms of praxis for liberation of all. In the words of Schüssler Fiorenza, a leading New Testament feminist scholar, a hermeneutics of suspicion challenges androcentric texts and interpretations ‘as ideological articulations of men expressing, as well as maintaining patriarchal historical conditions’ (Schüssler Fiorenza 1983: 60). As all theological articulations are based on a particular understanding of the Bible, feminist scholars emphasize the need to scrutinize the androcentric and patriarchal/*kyriarchal* elements in biblical texts and retrieve the position of women and their partnership with God in the story of salvation. It is rightly said: ‘the hermeneutical principles that we choose to employ are determined by our theological stands operative in exegesis and interpretation’ (Melanchthon 1998: 281).

Divided into two main parts, **Part 1** of this paper deals with the Encyclical of the Pope and explores its God-centred and people-oriented approach. While highlighting the concerns of Pope Francis, and the values proclaimed in the encyclical and issues raised therein, we shall make a critique of the ground reality at different levels, with special reference to women.

Part 2 delves into feminist reading of relevant biblical texts, in particular the all-embracing, all-inclusive vision and praxis of Jesus of Nazareth, as well as Paul’s liberative and unitive vision of equality and oneness of all in Christ Jesus

(Gal 3:26-28). It also takes up one of the main concerns frequently voiced by the Pope, namely interreligious harmony for world peace.

1. Exploring the Wealth of Fratelli Tutti

a. Highlighting Pope Francis' Oft-Repeated Concerns

FT, the third encyclical of Pope Francis speaks volumes about his concern for 'Fraternity and Social Friendship' as highlighted on the cover of the book. Inspired by St. Francis of Assisi, it is rightly called a Franciscan encyclical letter. In the words of Pope Francis, 'St. Francis who inspired me to write the Encyclical *Laudato Si*, prompts me once more to devote this new Encyclical to fraternity and social friendship' (Francis 2020. Henceforth FT). The very choice of his name 'Francis' reveals the Pope's admiration for St. Francis of Assisi who with his words FT addressed his brothers and sisters and proposed to them a way of life marked by the flavour of the Gospel (FT 1).

In his scholarly editorial, Suresh Mathew has culled the relevance of FT. Calling it 'a ground-breaking encyclical', he has unearthed its salient features (Mathew 2020: 3). Written in eight chapters, this new encyclical becomes 'the road map for a new world'. Religious fundamentalism, majority-minority feelings, the unending violence against women contributing to their physical, sexual and emotional subjection, selfish notion of development at the expense of the other are among several crucial points underlined in the encyclical.

Along the same lines Mathew Paikada's well-researched article provides informative and educative detailed analysis of FT (Paikada 2020: 6-11). He too underscores the influence of St. Francis of Assisi on Pope Francis. According to his findings, FT 'continues programmatically the main focus of the ministry of Pope Francis'. Among his favourite themes, the following deserve our special attention:

- Earth, the common home for entire humanity

- Interreligious harmony and cooperation for world peace and progress
- Build-up of friendly, brotherly/sisterly relationship beyond boundaries, in the spirit of humility (FT 3). The parable of the Good Samaritan is an excellent example (FT 68).¹
- Problems of injustice caused by various factors such as induced poverty, racism, migration, etc. (FT 28-55)
- Pope's determination expressed in NO to just war and death penalty

It is remarkable that Pope Francis' simplicity prompted him to insert into the encyclical the common appeal made by the Pope and the Grand Imam Ahmad al-Tayyeb in 2019 (FT 285). Similarly, the Pontiff's humility to acknowledge the influence of great saints and sages on his life is admirable, despite the absence of any woman saint on the list.

Human rights and peace activist-cum-writer Cedric Prakash (2020: 12-16) calls FT a 'path-breaking' encyclical that presents Pope Francis' passionate call for a meaningful and all-embracing discipleship, an invitation addressed to 'brothers and sisters all' (FT 8). The Pope's emphasis on brotherhood and sisterhood between men and women is praiseworthy. His concern for dialogue as a means of fostering/nurturing justice, dialogue as a means of mutual encounter (FT 198), dignity of every human being and the right of every person to live with dignity and to develop integrally (FT 107) are among other relevant issues raised in the FT. The Pope condemns every desire for dominance and destruction (FT 249), rules out the ideology justifying the

¹ On Good Samaritan, see Chakkalakal 2020: 327-349. It was originally an endowment lecture delivered at Vidyajyoti, Delhi. I am grateful to Ms. Jean Saldanha for final editing of my paper and Melody for typing and technical assistance.

rational of a ‘just war’ (FT 258), and rejects the death penalty (FT 263).

Trainer and consultant to non-profit organisations and closely associated with Universal Solidarity Movement, Jacob Peenikaparambil considers FT as a means to ‘Build Fraternity’ (Peenikaparambil 2020: 17-19). In his view FT promotes respect for different religions together with religious diversity as a means for building a just society based on the values enshrined in the Preamble of the Indian Constitution and the teaching of Vatican II in *Nostra Aetate*. In his research, Peenikaparambil underscores the Pope’s emphasis on the relationship between religions and politics. It is noteworthy that the document states clearly ‘religious ministers must not engage in party politics that are the proper domain of the laity’ (FT 276). Peenikaparambil offers a practical suggestion, to exhibit the Preamble of the Indian Constitution in a prominent place in all parishes and Catholic institutions. He also proposes the dissemination of the same through all ministries of the Church. He sees the relevance of Pope Francis’ exhortation to the Catholic Church to sow seeds of peace and compassion in the context of hateful feelings and dividing factors perpetuated by those in power structures on the basis of religion. He has also highlighted Pope Francis’ anxiety ‘to offer common witness to the love of God for all people by working together in the service of humanity.’ FT 281-285 deal with the issue of religion and violence.

Prakash Louis, former Director of Indian Social Institute, New Delhi and Bengaluru, known for his multi-faceted talents (action researcher, writer, activist and animator) finds in FT a shared inheritance for all (Louis 2020: 20-21). He draws our attention to the fact that the encyclical was published at the tomb of St. Francis of Assisi on 3 October 2020. He picks up two interrelated themes running through the encyclical that are central to the Gospel and to all religions, thereby establishing the brother-sister relationship of all human beings. He emphatically states, ‘To be human is to be inter-human, to be human is to be interdependent

and to be human is to be with and for other selves and in that find oneself.’ In the same breadth he speaks about Indian Christian commitment to FT wherein he underscores the need to be intercultural, interreligious and interconnected, transcending humanly erected barriers and promoting brotherly-sisterly love.

One of the most prominent professors of Missiology Jacob Kavunkal considers FT as an encyclical that ‘unfolds the Kingdom prayer...’ (Kavunkal 2021: 6-9). Underlining the essence of brotherly-sisterly society, he acknowledges the importance of basing it on the Fatherhood and Motherhood of God. Contemplating FT from various angles, Kavunkal picks up many issues close to the Pope’s heart that find expression in FT 3 (all-inclusive love of God); FT 5 (equality in rights, duties and dignity of human beings); FT 6 (universal scope of sisterly-brotherly love, friendship through dialogue with all people of good will). He places on record the Pontiff’s ongoing discussion on the inequality experienced by different groups particularly women, guest workers, children, migrant workers (FT 37) and others.

b. Critique of the Ground Reality with Special Reference to Women

In a commentary by Marcus Mescher (2021), associate professor of Christian ethics, on *Fratelli Tutti*, the author critiques the gendered term ‘fraternity’ and reliance on exclusively male sources and examples. While the Pope encourages us to recognize social problems as spiritual problems, he fails to address its ‘inadequate approaches to the religious and moral formation that contribute to these spiritual problems’. Mescher also critiques the institutionalized churches’ mistreatment of LGBTQ persons, marginalization of women, white supremacy, hypocrisy and corruption that bear a counter witness to Jesus’ teaching and healing ministry oriented towards inclusion and mercy. He

asserts that *Fratelli Tutti* emphasizes that ‘love is social and political’. He underscores the importance of mutual respect, equality and reciprocal concern as a means to build good relationships among people within the Church and society.

Theckanath, reflecting on the Indian Christian community in the context of the pandemic points out how the Church missed the opportunity for frontline leadership and collective action. He proposes a few points relevant to the Church in India in the current socio-economic and political context: the authoritarianism exhibited by nations and governments prohibiting the rights of the people to voice their opinion, to dissent and to organize. In this regard, he exhorts the Church leadership to stand up ‘to speak truth to those in power, even if it means that the institutional power of the Church will be decimated’ (Theckanath 2020: 22-23). His observation regarding sharing of power with women is very pertinent: the title of the encyclical excludes women. He too acknowledges the absence of women saints and sages mentioned by the Pope in FT.

2. Reviewing Some Biblical Texts

a. The all-embracing, all-inclusive vision and praxis of Jesus, our Prophet-Liberator

Women in Jesus’ Movement

Jesus is presented as accepting women and their partnership in his ministry in an astonishing manner which contrasts with his Jewish contemporaries.² Against the background of first century patriarchal culture, Jesus’ behaviour towards women is so extraordinary that New Testament scholar Moule cites it as evidence of scriptural authenticity: ‘The Gospel portrait of Jesus would seem to have fairly forced its way through an atmosphere

² It is said that a pious Jew thanked God daily for not having been born a Gentile, a woman or a slave. See ET in A. L. Williams, ed., *Tractate Berakoth: Mishna and Tosephta* (London: SPCK, 1921), p.84. For Schussler Fiorenza’s comments on this, see *In Memory of Her*, p.217 f.

still... alien to it and still scarcely comprehending' (Moule 1967: 65 & Sayers 1971). His positive attitude to women disciples enhanced their leadership functions at different levels in the Jesus' movement.

Women Who Followed Jesus (Luke 8:1-3)

This pericope provides the following information (Ricci 1994: 31-32).

- More than one phrase goes with a single theme: there are two referring to Jesus' healing activity and two detailing the composition of the group and identifying the women.
- The first two, *travelling and evangelising* (8:1) have Jesus as their subject, and are linked to the group theme. The link is established 'in that they are placed in a context of shared resources and in that the circle around Jesus were the first to hear the good news' (Ricci 1994: 52).
- The *healing and freeing of those possessed* has a direct dependence on the women members of the group theme.
- Besides three whose names have been mentioned (Mary Magdalene, Joanna and Susanna), there are many unnamed women.
- The action of *providing* (v.3) indicates the relationship between the women, as subjects, and Jesus as the object.

Thus the whole passage revolves around the group theme. The group is composed of Jesus, the Twelve and the women. They are constantly with him. This is consonant with Luke 23:49, 55 and with the other Synoptics (cf. Mt 27:55; Mk 15:40) which indicate the women who had followed Jesus from Galilee. In fact, Luke 8:1-3 explicitly puts the women on the same footing as the apostles by stating that the Twelve went with him, as well as certain women who also looked after the material needs of Jesus and his team. The Greek word used here is *diakoneo*, usually rendered 'minister', and

'*diakonia* expresses leadership exercised at the common meal including the celebration of the Eucharist' (Seim 1994: 743). As Francis Pereira elucidates, in the whole work of Luke the word *diakoneo* occurs nine times (Lk 4:39; 8:3; 12:37; 17:8; 22:26,27; Acts 6:2; 19:22; Pereira 2000: 161). A similar group of women is mentioned by Mark and Matthew in their passion narrative (Mk 15:40; Mt 27:55). The word used here for 'follow' is *akolouthein*, the one regularly used in the Gospels for discipleship in the fullest sense (e.g., Mk 2:14; Mt 8:19-22).

Women in Mission

The word 'mission' so frequently used today has different connotations. In its immediate meaning of 'sending', the word reveals deep theological notions.³ It is rooted in the intimate life of the Triune God. There is the action of sending: God sends Jesus; Jesus sends the apostles (Jn 20:21) and the church sends missionaries. There is also the accomplishment of the task entrusted to the envoy. The missionary, then, is one who is *sent* to fulfil a particular function of the person who sends him/her. Thus the women disciples of Jesus are missionaries in the true sense of the word. The Gospels provide ample evidence of the missionary dynamism of women that takes them from the foot of the cross to the tomb and beyond.

Whatever be the prejudice against the women disciples, the fact is that they were the first to hear the news: 'He is risen'! Although culturally women's testimony had no legal standing, Jesus acted counter-culturally when he made women's witness as the bedrock of Christian faith (cf. 1 Cor 15:7). Not only Mary Magdalene, but also the women witnesses of the resurrection deserve the title apostles. Jesus commissioned them as a group (Mt 28:10): 'Go tell.' Indeed, the women who figure in the resurrection stories are models of true discipleship. In her meticulously researched book,

³ In its radical sense, the word 'mission' has come to be understood as a 'defining characteristic' of what it means to be a Christian. See Mattam and Kim 1995.

Virginia R Sandiyagu portrays women as eyewitnesses to the Christian *Kerygma* (Sandiyagu 2017).

b. Apostle Paul's Liberative and Unitive Vision in Gal 3:26-28

Paul's letters have had tremendous impact on Christian thinkers and reformers of all ages and cultures down the centuries. However, Paul of Tarsus continues to be a controversial figure in feminist circles. He has been labelled a male chauvinist or anti-feminist because of his alleged denigration of the role and status of women (e.g., 1Cor 11:2-16; 1Cor 14:26-40). In fact, Pauline literature in the New Testament 'has formed the battleground upon which women's issues in the Church have been contested' (Byrne 1988: xiii).

Women will no longer tolerate the indiscriminate use of Pauline writings and other biblical texts in order to perpetuate female domestication in the church and society. They have begun to challenge the dynamics of oppression in the name of God and religion. The awakening of the 'feminist' consciousness is a sign of the times that needs to be interpreted in the wider context of the people's movements. As Pope John XXIII rightly remarked, 'Since women are becoming ever more conscious of their dignity, they will not tolerate being treated as mere material instruments, but will demand rights befitting a human person both in domestic and in public life' (John XXIII 1978: 44/71).

It is beyond the scope of this article to do a detailed analysis and exegetical study of Gal 3:26-28. Paul's phrase 'no male and female' points to the quality of the 'new creation in Christ' (Gal 5:6; Col 3:10). This new creation in Christ brings about the 'oneness' of all believers in Christ Jesus (Gal 3:28d). The original equality and unity of male and female (Gen 1:27) destroyed by sin (Gen 3) is restored in Christ who is the image (εἰκών) of the invisible God, the first born of all

creation (Col 1:15). The male-female relationship which has become one of subordination and domination can no longer be maintained in Christ.

From a feminist perspective, ‘the implications of Gal 3:28 for gender roles and status are momentous’, especially considering its impact on the community, effected by ‘the abolition of the three sets of hierarchical relations’ (Briggs 1983: .219). Male privileges, whether legal-societal or cultural-religious were no longer valid for Christians. Challenging the religious male prerogatives within the Christian community on the basis of Paul’s egalitarian vision, Schussler Fiorenza has remarked: ‘In so far as this egalitarian Christian self-understanding did away with all male privileges of religion, class and caste, it allowed not only gentiles and slaves but also women to exercise leadership functions within the missionary movement’ (Schüssler Fiorenza 1983:218).

Reflecting from an Indian context, with its culture predominantly rooted in Hindu ethos, deeply entrenched in the caste system, Paul’s message sounds prophetic. Against the backdrop of a patriarchal mindset with its preference for sons, sex-gender stereotypes and atrocities against women, Paul’s egalitarian vision paves the way for the creation of a society built on the principles of human dignity, equality, liberty and partnership.

All too often Pauline texts on women have been locked out of their contexts, and applied to totally different situations, or to issues, which lie beyond their concern. It is amazing to note how Pauline authority has been invoked in favour of female domestication in the churches through the centuries. Reading Paul out of his specific context, patriarchal patterns from dominant culture obscured Paul’s view of equality and oneness of all in Christ (Gal 3:28). Consequently, ‘submission, silence and subordination became watchwords for Christian women....’ (Thomson 1986: 151). This has not only deteriorated women’s position but also contributed to the development of patriarchal

theology as exemplified in the teachings of the prominent Christian thinkers in the patristic era (See Chakkalalal 2004).

c. Inter-religious Harmony and Cooperation for World Peace and Progress

Religious pluralism being a fact of history, religious belongingness should not be an obstacle to harmonious living and interfaith partnership. For a multi-religious and pluricultural country like India/Asia, interreligious dialogue is a living reality; it is not a luxury but a necessity, particularly in the present socio-economic, religio-cultural and political context of Asian countries. Followers of different religious traditions should be encouraged to work with all people of goodwill in furthering the Reign/Kingdom of God.

Today Pope Francis, the leader of more than 1.2 billion Catholics across the globe, remains an icon of interfaith dialogue and relationship. His exhortation to the people of Bosnia during his visit in 2015 is relevant to our own context: ‘In a world unfortunately rent by conflicts, this land can become a message: attesting that it is possible to live together side by side, in diversity but rooted in common humanity’ (Cited in Peenikaparambil 2015: 19-22). Together with other world religious leaders who exhort all people ‘irrespective of gender, faith and culture’ to network for peace and justice, Pope Francis paves the way for transcending ‘the narrow identities of religion and dogma’, thereby placing the accent on ‘higher identities of the common humanity and divine presence in every human being’ (Cited in Peenikaparambil 2015: 22)

Describing religion as ‘a divine-human relationship,’ Amaladoss accentuates the need for learning from other religions: ‘...what I am suggesting is that each religion, while believing in its specificity and uniqueness, can – and does – accept the legitimacy of other religions as facilitating divine-human encounter. Each religion will explain this in

accordance with its own faith-vision' (Amaladoss 2003: 138). Critiquing the people who brand pluralistic approach as 'relativization strategy', Pathrapankal stresses: 'It is to be forcefully maintained that when we speak of pluralistic approach, it is not a relativization of one's own faith in Christ that is proposed, but rather an objective approach to the reality of religions in God's plan of salvation.'⁴

A more creative form of dialogue is expressed as united action for a common cause in society, such as the eradication of social evils. All religions should unite in the fight against poverty, illiteracy, child labour, psychological and sexual assault on women, exploitation of Dalits even to the extent of dehumanizing practices, communalism, environmental destruction and whatever. The negative role of religions as witnessed in contemporary India does not negate the positive role religions can play in building a better nation, a better world.

My interfaith journey: Examples of interfaith partnership abound in our country; dialogue initiatives at various levels have been carried out by many centres throughout India (Painadath 2007). At this juncture, it would be good to provide some useful information about my own contribution to interfaith ministry. I

⁴ Pathrapankal, 2001: 140. A word about cultural expressions of the Christian faith is in place here. A Church in dialogue with followers of other religions is called to express its faith in and through local cultures which are liberating and empowering. Although the Council documents recognise the legitimacy of plurality of cultural expression in the Church (*LG* 13; *GS* 58; *AG* 9), the Indian Church (all denominations) leaders and pastors and post-Vatican II theologians, including liturgy experts, by and large (I am aware of the few exceptions.) still cling to a Western form of Christianity as seen in the architecture of our churches, the atmosphere of worship, postures, gestures, signs, symbols, vestments of priests, music, prayer forms, etc. Consequently, a majority of the laity too follow an imported spirituality, liturgy, and style of mission, which do not appeal or cater to the needs of the oppressed and exploited section of the Church. Many have uncritically accepted the Western form of Christianity as normative and universal.

ventured into the interreligious movement after violence hit the western Indian city of Mumbai (then known as Bombay) during December 1992 and January 1993. As per reports, the riots claimed about 900 lives. The violence was Muslim retaliation against the demolition of an ancient mosque in the northern Indian city of Ayodhya by right-wing Hindu groups.

In the aftermath of the riots, together with one of our sisters, I visited people of all faiths in our immediate neighbourhood for their response to a proposed interfaith get-together. From its inception that year, the gathering has attracted people of all religions and walks of life in the area. What began as an ‘All-Religion Prayer and Get-Together’ 27 years ago with less than a 100 people, has grown to a crowd of more than 600 youth and adults over the years. A special feature of this yearly programme aimed at celebrating Unity in Diversity, is its focus on the selected theme for the year, keeping in mind its contemporary relevance. Another speciality is youth participation by way of innovative presentations based on the theme.

My experience of promoting unity in diversity and harmony among various religious communities has deepened my conviction that followers of other religions are not mere objects of our theological discourse, but partners in our common search for Truth. What is important is the quality of our involvement, the humility to work with and not merely for people. Reflecting on the ‘plurireligious Indian context’, Mangai, the editor of *VJTR* views ‘dialogue at the service of human promotion’ (Mangar 2021: 234-238).

3. The Way Forward: Challenges and Proposals

Despite Pope Francis’ earnest desire to give women their rightful space, the Church structure is not conducive to

translate the Gospel ideals declared in FT. It is evident that in the existing patriarchal framework, with its clergy-centred leadership, women and the 'laity' in general are at the bottom of the church hierarchy. Moreover, the clerical structures reinforce structures of hierarchy and domination, and simultaneously prohibit women from policy formation in the Church. The exclusion of women from positions of decision-making deprives them of their effective role in shaping the Church's mission, its theology, its doctrines, its biblical interpretations, its liturgy, its spirituality and its laws. In her well-researched article, Bincy George pinpoints the inconsistency between the words and deeds of Church leadership with regard to women (George 2021: 70-88).

The institutional church that claims to champion the cause of human rights including women's empowerment in all aspects (*GS* 29,8,9,60) would do well to retrieve the teachings and praxis of Jesus who envisaged his community as a circle of friends (*Jn* 15:12-16), a discipleship of equals (*Mt* 23:2-10; *Gal* 3:26-28) and allow women's potential to enliven and rejuvenate its existence. At this juncture, it is worth pondering the words of Pope Francis who, while acknowledging women's share in pastoral responsibilities and contributions to theological reflection, 'demands that the legitimate rights of women be respected, based on the firm conviction that men and women are equal in dignity....' (Francis 2013: 84. See also Soares-Prabhu 1985).

It is time that the entire Christian community acknowledged that the church has been impoverished because the faithful are deprived of feminine and feminist insights and perspectives at various levels. Church leaders should call into question the contradictions between the theological interpretations of ministry as service, and the practices of clerical privilege and exclusion. The church leadership is called to recapture the original vision and praxis of Jesus and move towards the realization of a community of 'discipleship of equals' (*Mt* 23:9-10; cf. *Gal* 3:26-28). The differentiation of the role of sexes in keeping with the

socio-cultural perceptions of male-centred societies has been contingent on a given historical situation; one cannot deduce from it a divine, immutable model that would apply to other different circumstances.

Women's Commitment: Women of all Christian denominations have a specific contribution to make in liberating the structures of the church from the constraints of patriarchal ideology and theology operative in ministry, liturgy and leadership. We can no longer afford to remain the silent and silenced half in the Church. Rooted in Jesus Christ and energized by the Spirit, we can overcome hurdles of every kind and become agents of individual, social and structural transformation. Like our forefathers/foremothers in the faith, today we shall function as powerful witnesses and spokespersons of God's liberative action in favour of the voiceless, faceless and marginalized, including the exploited children and mother earth.⁵ Discipleship demands a preferential option for the poor: "A religion that does not challenge us and disturb us in our dealings with the poor is not religion" (Joachim 2019).

An egalitarian society or church is possible only with the cooperation of both women and men, committed to social justice and Gospel values. Through our ministry of writing, teaching, conducting animation sessions, and interacting with women at the grassroots by organizing various community development programmes, we shall strive to ensure gender justice for women in civil as well as

5 Astrid Lobo Gajiwala, Virginia Saldanha, Kochurani Abraham, Shalini Mulackal, Julie George, Metti Amirtham, Evelyn Monteiro, Rekha Chennattu, Noella Desouza, Patricia Santos, Aruna Gnanadason, Stella Baltazar, Cyrilla Chakkalakal, Joycia Thorat, Philo Thomas, Philo Desouza, Manju Kulapuram, Marcia D'cunha, Anita Cheria are among other feminists who have frequently voiced their views.

ecclesiastical society. Moving towards a community of 'discipleship of equals' demands all church personnel to rediscover the person, vision and mission of Jesus of Nazareth portrayed in the Gospels. As a fitting tribute to Jesus' vision, let me add the following:

The New Testament presents the call of Jesus to discipleship and ministerial service as universally inclusive. They were not restricted by sex, gender roles, marital status, social class, race or nationality. Although much of women's history in the early church has been submerged, it is remarkable that not a single story or statement is transmitted in which Jesus would affirm the subjugation of women under patriarchal norms. The inclusion of women in the leadership of the early Christian community (e.g., Apostle Paul's women co-workers) was indeed a break from the Jewish tradition of the role of women.

It is imperative that the position of women in today's Church together with its misogynist theology and biblical interpretation be subjected to a thorough revision. Women's active involvement and women in leadership are essential to the Church to deepen and enrich its own identity and legitimize its mission as a community of equals, a process that cannot take place when only males are decision makers. By our ability to imbibe the spirit of Jesus, we can challenge the institutional church to liberate itself from its ideological fetters. Empowered by the Spirit of God, we shall continue to motivate pastors/leaders and all God's people to move away from the emphasis on orders and 'divine' unchanging patterns of church life towards an emphasis on an organization that seeks to be faithful to the mission of Jesus Christ in ever changing contexts. Following the example of Jesus, who brought about a Godly revolution, a complete reversal in a person's scale of values, attitudes and actions (e.g., Mt 5:1-12; Lk 6:20-26), we are impelled to resist sinful structures that restrict women's full participation in the life and mission of the Church and society.

Both women and men ought to work in partnership, co-responsibility and assume a participatory style of leadership as desired by Pope Francis. Indeed, this process demands creative criticism, openness, acceptance, inclusiveness and democracy – all urgent needs of our Church and society.

Reference

- Amaladoss, M. 2003. *Making Harmony: Living in a Pluralistic World*. Delhi: IDCR & ISPCCK.
- Briggs, Sheila. 'Galatians,' in Schüssler Fiorenza 1983.
- Byrne, Brendan. 1988. *Paul and the Christian Woman*. Homebush: St. Paul Publications.
- Chakkalalal, P. 2020. 'Who is My Neighbour?': An exegetical-hermeneutic reflection on the parable of the Good Samaritan...', originally an endowment lecture delivered at Vidyajyoti, Delhi, *VJTR* Vol. 84/5. May 2020).
- Chakkalalal, Pauline. 2004. *Discipleship: A Space for Women's Leadership? - A Feminist Theological Critique*. Mumbai: Pauline Pub.
- Coll, Regina A. 1994. *Christianity and Feminism in Conversation*. Mystic, CT: Twenty-Third Publications.
- Drego, Pearl. 2010. 'Women Theologizing: Beginnings of Feminist Theologies and Their Concerns', *Jeevadhara* XL, 237. May, 2010), pp.232-252.
- Francis, Pope. 2013. Apostolic Exhortation, *Evangelii Gaudium*. The Joy of the Gospel), Trivandrum: Carmel International Publishing House
- Francis, Pope. 2020. *Fratelli Tutti. Brothers and Sisters All*) Encyclical Letter on Fraternity and Social Friendship. Mumbai: St. Pauls.
- George, B. 2021. 'A Spirituality of Justice: Towards a Just Church and Society in the Twenty-first Century', *Jeevadhara*, Vol. LI, No. 303. May 2021).

- Jayawardena, Kumari and Govind Kelkar. 1989. 'The Left and Feminism,' *EPW*. September 23, 1989).
- Joachim, I. 2019. 'Prophetic Role of Religious in the Indian Church Today', *Jeevadhara*, Vol. XLIX, No. 292. July 2019).
- John XXIII, Pope. 1978. *Pacem in Terris*, in Vincent P. Mainelli, *Official Catholic Teachings: Social Justice*. Wilmington: A Consortium Book from McGrath Publishing Co.
- Kavunkal, J. 2020. 'Fratelli Tutti, an Encyclical that Unfolds the Kingdom Prayer, the Our Father', *Vidyajyoti Journal of Theological Reflection*, Vol. 85/3. March 2021), pp.6-19.
- Louis, P. 2020. 'Fratelli Tutti: Towards a Shared Inheritance for All', *Indian Currents*, Vol. XXXII, Issue 42. 12-18 October 2020).
- Mangai, P. 2021. 'Religious Pluralism and Dialogue for Human Promotion', *VJTR* 85. 2021).
- Mathew, Suresh. 2020. 'Letter from a Brother', *Indian Currents*, Vol. XXXII, Issue 42. 12-18 October 2020).
- Mattam, Joseph and S. Kim, eds. 1995. *Dimensions of Mission in India*. Bombay: St. Pauls.
- Melanchthon, M.J. 1998. 'Indian Women and the Bible: Some Hermeneutical Issues', in *Feminist Theology Perspectives and Praxis*, ed., P. Kumari. Chennai: Gurukul Lutheran Theological College.
- Mescher, M. 2021. 'Commentary: A year after 'Fratelli Tutti,' it's time the church move from dreaming to doing', *NCR Online via CNUA* Vol. XIV, Issue 050. October 5, 2021).
- Moule, C. F. D. 1967. *The Phenomenon of the New Testament*. Naperville, Ill: Alice R. Allenson, Co.
- Paikada, M. 2020. 'Fratelli Tutti: A Franciscan Encyclical', *Indian Currents*, Vol. XXXII, Issue 42. 12-18 October 2020).
- Painadth, Sebastian. ed). 2007. *Jeevadhara*, Vol, XXXVII, No. 221. September 2007). The whole issue deals with Dialogue Initiatives in India.

- Pathrapankal, J. 2001. 'The Significance of Jesus Christ in the Context of Religious Pluralism: A Biblical Critique,' in Errol D' Lima and Max Gonsalves, eds., *What Does Jesus Christ Mean? The Meaningfulness of Jesus Christ amid Religious Pluralism in India*. Bangalore: Dharmaram Publications.
- Peenikaparambil, J. 2020. 'Build Fraternity: Message of *Fratelli Tutti* to the Indian Church', *Indian Currents*, Vol. XXXII, Issue 42. 12-18 October 2020).
- Peenikaparambil, Jacob. 2015. 'Dialogue: A School of Humanity and a Builder of Unity,' *Indian Currents*, Vol. XXVII, Issue No. 25. 22-28 June 2015).
- Pereira, F. 2000. *Jesus the Human and Humane Face of God: A Portrait of Jesus in Luke's Gospel*. Mumbai: St. Pauls.
- Prakash, C. 2020. 'Fratelli Tutti: A Call to Discipleship!', *Indian Currents*, Vol. XXXII, Issue 42. 12-18 October 2020).
- Raj, Maithreyi Krishna. ed. 1984. *Feminist Theorists, Three Centuries of Women's Intellectual Traditions*. Bombay: The Women's Press
- Ricci, C. 1994. *Mary Magdalene and Many Others: Women Who Followed Jesus*. Kent TN: Burns & Oates.
- Sandiyagu, V. 2017. *Women as Eyewitnesses to the Christian Kerygma, The Galilean Women in the Redaction of Luke, An Exegetical Study of Luke 8:1-3*. Bengaluru: Kristu Jyoti Publications.
- Sayers, Dorothy. 1971. *Are Women Human?* Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Pub. Co.
- Schüssler Fiorenza, Elisabeth. 1983. *In Memory of Her: A Feminist Theological Reconstruction of Christian Origins*. New York: SCM Press.
- Seim, T. K. 1994. 'The Gospel of Luke,' in Schüssler Fiorenza, ed., *Searching the Scriptures, Volume Two: A Feminist Commentary*. New York: Crossroad.

- Soares-Prabhu, George M. 1985). 'Radical Beginnings: The Jesus Community as the Archetype of the Church', *Jeevadhara*, Vol. XV, No. 88. July 1985).
- Theckanath, V. 2020. 'Fratelli Tutti: Challenges and Opportunities for the Church in India', *Indian Currents*, Vol. XXXII, Issue 42. 12-18 October 2020).
- Thomson, William G. 1986. *Paul and His Message for Life's Journey*. New York: Paulist Press.
- Williams, A. L. ed. 1921. *Tractate Berakoth: Mishna and Tosephta*. London: SPCK

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***Fratelli Tutti* from Biblical Perspectives**

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Abstract: Based on the Papal Encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, the author reflects on its relevance for today and applies it to various contexts like immigrants, inter-religious dialogue, political charity and peace and reconciliation. The author bases his exploration from Biblical perspectives and indicates the relevance of this powerful encyclical for our religious, spiritual, moral and political lives.

Keywords: Peace and Reconciliation, *Fratelli Tutti*, Immigrants, Good Samaritan, Good Politics.

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Fratelli Tutti is an encyclical. An encyclical is a letter circulated by the Pope to Catholic Churches worldwide. It is often addressed to all the people of good will who may want to read the document. Pope Francis' encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* (henceforth abbreviated as FT) is addressed to 'brothers and sisters all' (FT. 8). Papal encyclicals provide analysis, in the light of the Gospel and of the Tradition of the Church on relevant issues for the faithful. The topic given to me was "A Way of life for the New Year 2021 after Fratelli Tutti." Since this article was based on my recollection talk organized by Prerana, the Ignatian Spirituality Centre from Bangalore for the selective public on-line which is available on Youtube,¹ the style of this paper is conversational rather than technical. Definitely, you might have heard very many times this encyclical explained to you. But this is going to be somewhat different as I am going to look at each chapter of the encyclical from a Biblical point of view and will set certain guidelines from there, for our way of life during these coming years.

1. Dark Clouds Over a Closed World

Let us take the first chapter which speaks about Dark Clouds over a Closed World. Here I would like to bring to your attention the Foundational God Experience in the bible.

a. Dark Cloud in the Old Testament

As we know, the bible is divided into two parts: The Old Testament and the New Testament. In the Old Testament, the foundational God experience is the Exodus experience. What do we see in the Exodus experience? It begins with the call of Moses (Ex 3:6-14). Any call narrative has four parts: Whenever there is a need God calls. Then, he commissions. Then, the Prophet objects. Finally, God responds to the objection. When we come to Moses, first, God calls. What is the need for which God calls Moses? It is because that the people of Israel were languishing in

¹ Rathinam, Selva, *Prerana Retreat Talk 03*, Prerana Ignatian Retreat Centre. January 9, 2021, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sdZ9-J3F5II&t=9s> accessed on 08/07/2021.

Egypt as slaves. This is the Dark Cloud. God wants to liberate these people and for which God calls Moses. Then God gives a commission to Moses, “you go and liberate them.” But, Moses objected: “Lord, who am I that you should send me? Suppose the people to whom you send me, ask me, who is it that has sent you, what shall I say? What is your name? God responded to him: I am who I am, i.e., Yahweh! Then, Moses said, I do not know how to speak. But God responded to him saying, what about your brother Aaron and he can speak well and he shall become your mouth. This is the Call Narrative. But after listening to everything Moses said, ‘Oh, send somebody else!’ But, God told him, ‘I will be with you’ for this mission. In order to prove that God will be with him, God gave him three signs: God asked him, ‘what is in your hand?’ Moses said, ‘a stick.’ God said, ‘throw it in front of me.’ When he did this, it became a serpent. When he saw the serpent, he started running away. God called Moses and told him, ‘do not be afraid, come back and catch hold of the serpent.’ When he caught hold of the serpent it became a stick. Then, God told Moses to take water from the Nile and pour it upon the ground. It became blood. Then God told Moses, ‘put your hand into your cloak and take it out.’ His hand became a leprous hand. Again, God told him to put his hand back into his cloak and take it out. Now it became a clean hand. What is the meaning of these signs? In those times people were afraid of three things in Israel. Israel was a desert land and it was infested with snakes. People were afraid of snakes. Secondly, people were afraid of violence and that’s what blood. When they moved from one place to another, there was no police force to protect them. The robbers can barge in at any time, kill the travellers and take away their property. Finally, people were afraid of the dreaded leprosy. Therefore, we have serpent, blood and leprosy. They symbolize evil in Israel at that time. The meaning is this: yes, there is evil in the world, but God has

got power over evil. Thus, Moses was encouraged by these three signs. So, what do we see here? The Dark Cloud here is slavery! Then, God calls Moses to liberate these people out of this dark cloud.

b. Dark Cloud in the New Testament

Let us come to the New Testament. Here the Foundational God Experience is the baptism of our Lord Jesus Christ. Jesus came from Galilee and went to Judea to be baptized by John the Baptist at the river Jordan. When Jesus came to the Jordan where John was baptizing, he saw at least five groups of the elites. They were not stepping into the water but were just watching John baptizing. Who were in those groups? They were Pharisees, Sadducees, Zealots, Essenes and Apocalyptic. For the Pharisees, the Law was everything and if you obey the law, the Lord will bring the Kingdom of God. The Kingdom of God is the intervention of God in history. Sadducees were priests. They believed that if you perform the rituals well, then God will bring the Kingdom of God. Zealots trusted in the weapons and they believed in the power of arms. Essenes believed in the power of prayer. If you pray well, then God will bring the Kingdom of God. The apocalyptic had their Worldview. For them, this world is under the power of Satan. Satan controls the world through demons and demonic persons. When the fullness of time comes, God will destroy the power of Satan and will establish the Kingdom of God. When Jesus was at the Jordan, he saw all those elite groups and he rejected all of them. There was another group which was rejected by all those elite groups. They were the poor, the marginalized, and the underside of the history, the blind, the lame, the deaf and the dumb. It is those people who were standing in the water in order to be baptized in the hands of John the Baptizer. Jesus made a deliberate option for them. He went and stood among them. When he stood among them, what happened? The heavens opened, the Spirit of God descended upon him in the form of a

dove and he heard the voice saying, 'you are my beloved Son, in whom I am well pleased' (Mk 1:9-11). When Jesus made an option for the underprivileged, God seemed to have told him that he was dear to his own heart and he had made a right decision! Jesus stood with those marginalized people and there is one word which refers to those marginalized people and it is '*anawim*.' In Hebrew the word '*anawim*' comes from the word '*anaw*' meaning 'the bent,' 'the broken,' and 'the crushed.' The '*anawim*' are of four categories: the physically handicapped like the blind, the lame, the deaf and the dumb; the mentally ill people who thought that they were possessed by demons; the economically deprived people; and finally the socially ostracized people like the tax collectors, prostitutes, soldiers etc. These were the oppressed people. This is what the dark cloud during the time of Jesus Christ. Jesus had a call to liberate them. What did Jesus do? Jesus healed the physically handicapped, drove away the demons of the mentally ill, fed the economically deprived by multiplying bread and finally he accommodated the socially ostracized people and was even called to be the friend of the sinners and the tax collectors.

c. Dark Cloud in Our Time

Let us come to our country. What is the dark cloud here in 2020? On Jan. 30, 2020 the Covid-19 pandemic was confirmed to have spread to India from China. The first case of Covid-19 was spotted in Kerala in India. Janata Curfew on March 22 and immediately after a 21-day lockdown was announced by the Prime-Minister throughout India to prevent the spread of the Covid 19 pandemic. Millions of poor and jobless migrant labourers were returning to their homes hundreds of kilometers away on foot since public and private transport has come to a standstill across India. Instead of helping distraught citizens cope with these frustrating and

hungry times, many Indian police personnel were increasingly caught harassing and assaulting them.

Ever since the Modi government passed the CAA (Citizenship Amendment Act) in December 2019, there has been fear and panic around the country. Hundreds and thousands of people were on the streets to call for the laws to be rolled back. On February 23 riots broke out in Delhi between Anti-CAA and pro-CAA protestors. The violence took a communal turn and led to the death of over 53 people. Modi and his Party have chosen to dig in their heels and have refused to acknowledge the concerns of the protesters and have instead sought to depict the protesters as violent anti-nationals, as reported in the article “Delhi Violence” in *Scroll.in*, 22/12/20.

In September 2020 during the time of the pandemic the Parliament of India passed three farm acts. Many farmer unions described the acts as “anti-farmer laws” and many opposition political parties also said it would leave farmers at the mercy of corporates. In tens of thousands of farmer unions notably from Punjab, Rajasthan and Haryana protested against the three farm acts and marched towards the nation’s capital with a movement named *Dilhi chalo* (transl, let’s go to Delhi). Although several rounds of talks have taken place between the centre and farmers no solution is sighted till date.

Such insensitivity and lovelessness towards the suffering can be called the dark clouds in 2020. Now I want to ask you two questions: What is the Cloud of Darkness that you experience at present? If God sends you out as he sent out Moses and Jesus, will you be ready to take up the mission you are called for in 2021?

2. Parable of the Good Samaritan

We have three types of characters in this parable. The first one was the wounded man, perhaps he was a Jew because he was coming from visiting the Jerusalem Temple. The second one was the Good Samaritan who approached him. The third category was the people like the priest and the Levite, who avoided the wounded man. Why did they do what they did? The priest and the Levite avoided the wounded man because they asked the wrong type of question: if I go near the wounded man what will happen to ME? This is very self-oriented and selfish question. Suppose the wounded man dies I will be polluted, made unclean and disqualified to offer sacrifices to the Lord. This is the reason why they abandoned the wounded man and walked away. But, the Samaritan asked the right type of question: if I do not go near him, what will happen to HIM? This is the other oriented question. Since he didn't want to let him die abandoned, he opted for him. The word 'neighbour' comes from the word 'neigh' which means 'near.' Jesus asked the question, who was the neighbour to the one who was wounded? It is the Good Samaritan who went near him. Jesus gives us no choice here, either you take care of the needy or you do not take care of the needy. The Good Samaritan could have given other excuses: He is a Jew and I am a Samaritan and why should I help him? Or he could have gone either after the robbers or to the higher authorities to make a complaint. But, Jesus gives only two choices: Here are the needy people and when you see them what will you do? When we pay attention to the Good Samaritan we see that he took care of the wounded man. What is it that moved him to take care of him? In the passage it is said that when he saw the wounded man, he had compassion on him (Lk 10:33).

a. Compassion

This particular word ‘compassion’ is very important. In Ex 33:18-23 Moses wanted to see God and he expressed his desire to Yahweh. But God told him that no one can see me and live and yet, since you are my friend I will make an exception to you. Come tomorrow to the mountain top and there I will walk before you and will show myself to you. The next day, Moses went up to the top of the Mountain and was standing behind the rock. God was walking in front of him. At that time, these were the words which were pronounced: “the Lord, the Lord, a God merciful and gracious, slow to anger, and abounding in steadfast love and faithfulness, keeping steadfast love for the thousandth generation, forgiving iniquity and transgression and sin, yet by no means clearing the guilty, but visiting the iniquity of the parents upon the children and the children’s children, to the third and the fourth generation” (Ex 34:6-7). There are three words which give the character of God here: merciful, gracious and steadfast love. In Hebrew the word for merciful is *rahamim* which is translated usually as compassion. But, literally *rehem* in singular means the womb of a mother. Tony de Mello used to say that if you had asked Jesus Christ, who God is like, he would have said with a wink in his eyes, do you want to know who God is? God is wombish! The word ‘wombish’ does not appear in English but this is what the literal translation of the Hebrew word ‘*rehem*.’ A mother will never hate the child which is formed within her womb. She will always forgive the child. Not that after we have been born, she scolded us and hurt us, but what I mean is that when we were within her womb she chose to love us and allowed us to survive. This is the love of the mother. We were all formed within the womb of God before we were formed within the womb of our mothers. Therefore, God will never punish us and God will always forgive us. Even before we thought of committing a sin, God had forgiven us and we only have to appropriate this forgiveness from the Lord. This is the love of God. Thus, ‘merciful’ or ‘compassion’ means forgiveness.

b. Relationships

Secondly ‘compassion’ also is an action word. There are very many levels of relationships. In fact, the whole *Fratelli Tutti*, speaks about relationships. The first level of relationship is ‘hai bye’ relationship. You meet someone and say ‘hi’ and he or she says after sometime ‘bye,’ and sometimes, with this, the relationship comes to an end. The second level of relationship is speaking about the externals: you say ‘oh, it is going to rain,’ and the other says ‘oh, yes, it is going to rain.’ The third level of relationship is discussing ideas. Now we have come to the head and it is deeper than the previous levels. Then, the fourth level is giving expression to our feelings: ‘I feel sad’ or ‘I feel bored’ etc. Finally, the deepest level of relationship which is called the ‘gut’ level relationship and this is what ‘*rahamim*,’ ‘compassion.’ This Hebrew word ‘*rahamim*’ is translated as ‘*splangnizomai*’ in the New Testament Greek. ‘*splangnon*’ means ‘bowel’ or ‘entrail.’ In Mk 6:34 it is said that when Jesus saw the crowd in the desert, he had compassion (*splangnizomai*) for them, that is, he was moved at the deeper level, at the gut level, by bowels or entrails. Then, what did he do? He multiplied bread and fed the hungry. Thus, the gut level relationship does not remain only with feelings but it does something to the other in action. Very many places in the New Testament we have instances where Jesus had compassion on the people and in all those instances Jesus did something to them. When the father saw the prodigal son, it is said that he had compassion on him (Lk 15:20). Then, we ask the question, what did he do? The father put a ring on finger and put sandals on his feet. In Lk 7:11-17 there was a widow who was walking on the street with the dead body of her son. When Jesus saw, he had compassion (Lk 7:13). Then, what did he do? He gave life to the dead man and returned the son to his mother.

3. Love Is a Value for Us

We all need to have compassion to bring the people out of this Cloud of Darkness. This is what the Good Samaritan has done. Do we have this compassion within us? For us, Christians, love is a value. Love is actually a Trinitarian Spirituality: The Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit. How to understand the Holy Trinity? Let me share with you how the Lord enlightens me with regard to this. First of all, who is the Father? Ex 3:6-14: I am the God of your father, the God of Abraham, the God of Isaac, and the God of Jacob. I have come down from heaven in order to deliver the people from their slavery and take them to the land flowing with milk and honey. The people have experienced the love of this God through the burning bush, the ten plagues, the division of the red sea, the pillar of cloud, the pillar of fire, Manna in the desert! It is Jesus who gives name to this God in the New Testament as Father (Lk 11:2). Therefore, It is the love which the people thought that has come from above is the Father. Secondly, who is the Son? Who is this Jesus Christ whom we are talking about? For this we need to go to the gospels and see his life from Bethlehem to Calvary. In Lk 7:11-17, when a widow of Naim lost her only son, Jesus goes there and weeps with her. This is Jesus. In Jn 8:1-11 when a woman caught in the very act of adultery was about to be stoned to death, Jesus goes there and protects her. This is Jesus. In Jn 11 we see Martha and Mary who have lost their only brother Lazarus. Jesus goes there to the tomb and weeps with them. This is Jesus Christ. In Lk 19, Zacchaeus, a short man wanted to have a glimpse of Jesus Christ from the tree top, Jesus came there, called him down and went to his house to dine with him. This is Jesus. Jesus is the love which the people experienced WITH them. This love was walking upon the earth and miracles took place. Who did the miracle? It is love that did the miracle. Jesus is another name for this love. Finally we come to the Holy Spirit. When I reflect upon myself I see that I am finite. Before my birth I was nothing. After my death it looks as though I am going to be

nothing. Yet, I exist. Since I am finite, I could not have come from myself. The source from where I have come I call God. Who is this God? 1 Jn 4:7 says that this God is love. A steel chair cannot come from a wood. Only a wooden chair can come from a wood. So, if I am from love, then I too should be love. Thus, the more I become aware of my source I become love-able. This love-ability within me is the Holy Spirit. Rom 8:9 says that the Holy Spirit dwells within you. That's why, the personal prayer is very important in our personal life. Once I was teaching the diploma students, mostly the junior sisters in Jnana Deepa. In that group, I saw one of the students whose way of talk and smile reminded of another student whom I met in Jnana Deepa few years back. After the class, I asked her whether she knows that particular previous student. She said, yes, she was my Novice Mistress. Then, she told me that she was trained by her Novice Mistress for two years and she liked her so much that without her knowledge she imbibed her mannerism in her way of talk and smile etc. This is exactly the Christian prayer. St. Ignatius gives us what is called the imaginative contemplation in order to enter into the mysteries (the episodes) of Jesus Christ. Take one episode everyday for your prayer, become part of it, listen to Jesus, enter into conversation with him, see him, hear him and feel his presence and finally one day without your knowledge you will become unto the image of Jesus Christ imitating him and going out to others in love. Thus, the love which the people experienced from above is the father; the love which the people experienced with them is Jesus Christ and the love which the people have experienced within them is the Holy Spirit. God is love. If God is love, then, he cannot remain within four walls. Love needs the other. Therefore, God is a community. This community consists not of things but of persons, because, we use things and love persons and we should not love things and use persons. Therefore, this divine community consists

of the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit. Since God is a community, community is a value for us. We all belong to one community or the other like family, religious community, club or guild. Do we facilitate the building up of the community or do we hinder the building up of the community? A genuine love will impel us towards universal communion (FT 95). When there is no universal openness in love, the abandoned or ignored brothers and sisters in our own community or country can become existential foreigners to us. “Racism is a virus that quickly mutates and, instead of disappearing, goes into hiding, and lurks in waiting” (FT 97). Since God is a person, person is a value for us. One may be poor or ugly or sick or old, yet, I will love him or her because he or she is a person. Today we need to recall to our minds all those persons whom we hate. Can we take a decision, now, right now to love them and forgive them, and only then, we have understood the Trinitarian God in our life. Christian virtue consists in not loving the lovable but in loving the unlovable.

Pope Francis uses the word ‘*ekstasis*’ in this particular chapter: “Since we were made for love, in each one of us “a law of *ekstasis*” seems to operate: “the lover ‘goes outside’ the self to find a fuller existence in another.” For this reason, “man always has to take up the challenge of moving beyond himself” (FT 88). What is this ‘*ekstasis*’? It has got two words: *ek* (out) + *stasis* (stand) meaning ‘to stand out.’ All of us have got the capacity to stand out of ourselves, to transcend ourselves. In love we transcend ourselves and reach out to others. Until and unless we become aware of this capacity to transcend in love we will not be able to come out of the wall we have built around ourselves. This is what the Incarnational Spirituality: Jesus, in the beginning, was the Word [in the heavens] and the Word became flesh [upon the earth]. So, Jesus transcended from one to the other, from heaven to the earth out of love for us. In the same way, we will transcend from ourselves to the other in love. This is what the capacity of ‘*ekstasy*’ in each one of us. We need to be aware of this.

So, what is this love? Love means ‘doing good.’ Pope Francis, in this chapter uses the word ‘*agathosyne*’ which is one of the fruits of the Spirit in Gal 5:22. This “Greek word expresses attachment to the good, pursuit of the good. Even more, it suggests a striving for excellence and what is best for others, their growth in maturity and health, the cultivation of values and not simply material wellbeing. A similar expression exists in Latin: *benevolentia*. This is an attitude that “wills the good” of others” (FT 112). This is the very same word, in Greek, similar to ‘*agape*.’ What does it mean? It means ‘using the determination of will to do good to others.’ Suppose there are two people in the community. One is the elder and the other younger. The younger one doesn’t like the elder one at all, perhaps, in the past the younger one was hurt by the elder. Now, both of them are watching a TV program. In between, the elder one gets up and walks out of the room trying to wipe her running nose. In the meantime, her kerchief falls down without her knowledge. The younger one noticed it and took the kerchief and gave it to the elder. Now, my question is this: has the younger one loved the elder one so much that she did something good to the elder? ‘No.’ In fact, she hates the elder one. But, by giving the kerchief to her, did she do something good to her? ‘Yes.’ This is what the New Testament agapeic love. It is using the determination of will to do good. This is nothing to do with feeling but with will. Jesus says in Jn 13:35: “By this everyone will know that you are my disciples, if you have love (*agape*) for one another.”

In the remaining chapters, Pope Francis points out to the target groups we must do good to. In the fourth chapter he speaks of the immigrants. In the fifth chapter he speaks of the political charity. In the sixth chapter he speaks of the

dialogue and social friendship. In the seventh chapter he speaks about peace and reconciliation with others. In the eighth chapter he speaks about the inter-religious dialogue.

4. Immigrants

Let us come to chapter four, the immigrants. Who are the immigrants? The immigrants are those people who do not have a conducive situation in their own place to grow and to develop and therefore they move from their place to another place. Whether they are immigrants or migrants or strangers, we need to accept them because they are human beings. In Gen 1:27 we read, “So God created humankind in his image, in the image of God he created them; male and female he created them.” In former times, only the kings were considered to be the images of God and the common people have to give dignity to them. But, in the book of Genesis, this idea of ‘image of God’ is democratized and applied to all human beings. Every human being is the image of God. God is in every human being and therefore we need to give this human dignity to everyone. Therefore, we need to give human dignity to the immigrants; the migrants and the strangers and we need to accept them. Then, Pope Francis gives the example of Gen 11:1-9 (FT 144) which deals with the tower of Babel. In this story we see ‘unity in uniformity.’ Here the people say, “let us make a name for ourselves” (Gen 11:4). It’s a kind of group or siege mentality. Very often we have such group mentality and do not allow others to get into our circle. In such group, there is no transcendence and it is unity in uniformity which is bad. In the Acts 2, quite opposite to tower of Babel takes place. Here the people seem to be diverse and they speak different languages. Yet, they all hear and understand perfectly the preaching of the Apostles on the Pentecost. Here, there is unity in diversity. In unity in diversity we are enriched and challenged. Therefore, we need not fear that we may lose our identity when we allow the strangers to join us. On the contrary, in their company we will be enriched and challenged. Then, Pope Francis uses the term

‘gratuitousness’ here (FT 139). What does it mean? Very often, when we see the strangers or the immigrants, we accept only those who are talented. But, Pope Francis says that we need to accept all of them, even the common people among them. This is what he calls ‘gratuitousness, that is, ‘gratis’ meaning freely we need to accept them. “Our response to the arrival of migrating persons can be summed up by four words: welcome, protect, promote and integrate” (FT 129).

5. Political Charity

Let us move on to Chapter five. It is on Political Charity. Charity is not only personal, intimate relationships but also macro-relationships which includes economic, political and social elements of the society having the goal of common good. Here, he speaks about the economic reality in the society. In order to have an economic strength, the nation should have two things: Capital with the business people and consumer demand. In very many countries, including our own, the government fills the hands of the business people with money exempting them from all sorts of taxes and obligations believing that they will start businesses and employ common people, so that the money will trickle down from the business people to the poor. But what happens is that money, instead of trickling down to the poor, going into the pockets of the business people. Quite opposite to this ‘trickle down economic theory,’ there is ‘trickle up economic theory.’ Here, the money is put first in the hands of the workers and it creates consumer demand. In order to meet the consumer demand, the businesses are developed. Thus, the money goes up in this ‘trickle up economic theory.’ The point of Pope Francis is that we should not be satisfied with any one ideology but need both the trickle down and the trickle up, keeping more importantly, the common good, in mind.

Majoritarianism, Populism, Concupiscence, Tenderness

He also gives examples from political life especially on majoritarianism and populism. Here is the government which is elected by the people. Once it is elected, the government should look into the needs of all the people. This is what democracy which is by the people, for the people and of the people. But, instead of taking care of all the people, what the government, most often, does is to take care of only that section of the people who voted for it. This is called majoritarianism. For example, when Fr. Stan Lourdasamy, SJ who was fighting for the rights of the oppressed Adivasis, was languishing in the prison without a bail, Goswami who was accused of crime against the nation, was released from the prison within a short time because he belonged to the ruling party. Similarly, the farmers are fighting for their rights for a long time, but the government is very insensitive towards them because it favours the corporates as it shares the trickledown theory. Pope Francis also speaks about populism which implies support for the poor and at the same time opposing the big institutions. Pope's point is that we need institutions also along with the option for the poor. Drawing the example from the Good Samaritan story, Pope Francis tells that in order to admit the wounded man, the Good Samaritan needs the Inn which is an institution. The point is that we should not be settled down to any one ideology. We must always ask the question whether it would serve the common good and accordingly we must make a decision. Pope Francis also speaks about 'concupiscence,' that is, promoting individualistic and selfish attitudes emphasizing, my community, my people, my language and my geographical area. It reminds us of the story of the Tower of Babel which lacks the dynamism of love element moving from one to the other. When Pope Francis spoke about political charity, he draws our attention to the social reality and in this context he speaks about what is called 'the tender love.' "What is tenderness? It is love that draws near and becomes real" (FT 194). He says that politics must make

room for tender love of others. For him, tender love is the love which springs from the heart touched by the smallest, the weakest and the poorest and reaches the eyes, ears and hands. For example, we live in a throw away culture where the people who are unborn are already thrown away by abortion and the elderly who are considered to be useless are thrown away by isolation. What Pope Francis is saying is that the suffering of such people should touch our hearts and sensitize us to their needs. Through social media often times we show our insensitivity towards others. Once the suffering of the people touches our hearts, the tender love will flow from our hearts to our eyes, ears and hands in order to take care of them. Therefore, Pope Francis wants us to keep alive within ourselves this sensitivity. So, what is this ‘political charity’ finally? Pope Francis advises us that we need to discuss about politics. In fact, before reading this encyclical, I used to tell myself what a waste of time that we speak about politics in our recreations and at table etc., But, what Pope Francis says here is that if we do not discuss and express our opinion on political life in smaller or larger groups, the other people who believe in certain ideologies will shape the society in their own terms. Therefore, we need to keep such conversation going in our day today life. We need to listen to the news, read the newspapers, get in touch with the signs of the times and enter into interdisciplinary conversation with others with regard to politics.

6. Dialogue and Social Friendship

In Chapter six, Pope Francis speaks about dialogue and social friendship, by which, what he means is that we need to build up the society together. In very many social networks when people are expressing their opinions entering into dialogue, in actual they are not in dialogue but in monologue, he says. Dialogue will take place only when we listen to the other.

When we hold on to our own ideas, then it is not dialogue. Reality is multi-dimensional and it cannot be looked at from different angles at the same time. If I say that the perspective from which I look at the reality is the only reality, then I make judgments out of prejudice, preconceived ideas and stereotyped views. We need to listen to others in order to build up a genuine society and this is his point. Recently, the Jesuits have emphasized what is called ‘the spiritual conversation.’ What do we do here? First of all, we pray over the matter which is given to us for reflection (that is, think about the matter in the presence of God). When we pray over the matter two things happen within us: we become interiorly free (which is technically called ‘indifference’). Here we distance ourselves from our own likes and dislikes; and we experience the movements of the heart (consolation and desolation). At the personal level what is it that gives me a prolonged peace (consolation) we consider it as the internal confirmation of the will of God. With this we come to a smaller group for spiritual conversation which consists of three stages: in the first round we share in the group what we felt in our prayer and this sharing requires ‘intentional speaking’ and ‘attentive listening’; in the second round we have a ‘reflective sharing’ of what we felt while listening to each other and in the final round we have ‘an open discussion’ to arrive at a possible consensus as the will of God. Then, if it requires, we come to a larger group for the sharing of our findings to arrive at a final consensus which is submitted to the superior for an external confirmation of the divine will. The basis of consensus is not relativism but truth and values (FT 206-208). Cultivating a new culture of acknowledging others can help us in this process of arriving at consensus. In this matter of consensus, Pope Francis draws our attention to St. Paul, who uses the Greek word *chrestotes* (kindness) in Gal 5:22 (FT 223). It describes an attitude of gentleness and not rude towards others in words and actions. “Often nowadays we find neither the time nor the energy to stop and be kind to others, to say “excuse me,” “pardon me,” “thank you”.... If we make a daily effort to do exactly this, we can create a healthy social atmosphere in which

misunderstandings can be overcome and conflict forestalled. Kindness ought to be cultivated; ... once kindness becomes a culture within society it transforms lifestyles, relationships and the ways ideas are discussed and compared. Kindness facilitates the quest for consensus” (FT 224). In the spiritual conversation I share what I feel and at the same time I remain free. Here what is important is the capacity to move from the head to the heart. Here, there is spiritual poverty, that is, I cannot know everything and I need the other. In spiritual conversation we believe that God has a mission for this world and he speaks through each one of us to draw us into this mission. Therefore, when we listen to each other, we actually listen to God and thus it becomes prayer. In the recent past, when I was the President of Jnana Deepa I made a suggestion to my Provincial that the administrative building should be turned into women’s hostel and the administrative set up can be moved into the newly built Postgraduate Block. The Provincial called for a spiritual conversation among all the Jesuit administrators on the campus. In the first round of it, only two people were convinced of the idea. Then with more information the group was asked to come back after two days with prayerful reflection for the process of spiritual conversation. During this time half of the group said that we need to turn this into the women’s hostel. Then, the Provincial asked us to come for the final round of spiritual conversation the following day. During this time, it so happened that unanimously we felt that we need to go for the women’s hostel and we concluded it. It was like a miracle for me! Therefore, when we have such spiritual conversation, it is possible to move towards the building up of the society.

7. Peace and Reconciliation

Let us come to the seventh Chapter. Here, Pope Francis speaks about Peace and Reconciliation. What is peace? For

Pope Francis peace is not the absence but it is the presence. Peace is not the absence of war. In the cemetery there is peace but this peace is born out of the absence of persons and that's not the real peace. In some of the Indian art, God is shown with *abhaya mudra* (the gesture of protection) which sums up the message of the risen Lord. Whenever the risen Lord appeared to the people, he said two things: do not be afraid; and peace be with you. Both are related. When we are walking on the road alone at night, we are afraid. But, when there is someone with us, we are not afraid and we become bold. Now, the risen Lord is within us and therefore Jesus says, "Do not be afraid" for you are not alone and I am with you. The awareness of the presence of Jesus within us brings peace into our lives and this peace the world cannot give to us. When will such peace take place in the Society? When we believe that each person has the presence of this risen Lord within him or her. Then, we will give dignity to each person. When dignity is restored, peace will be established in the society.

Then, Pope Francis speaks about reconciliation through forgiveness. Forgiveness is not forgetting, he says, but forgiveness is giving up my right to take revenge. You have hurt me and I have the right to take revenge upon you. Can we give up that right because vengeance belongs to God? When I was reading this, what came to my mind was the example of Graham Staines, the Australian Christian missionary who was burned to death in 1999 along with his two sons in the car. After his death, his wife made the statement: I forgive the killer. Then, someone asked her, what about justice in the court? She said that the law will take its own course. This is what forgiveness. Justice is there with the legal court but at the same time one gives up one's right to take revenge. We need this forgiveness to build up the society. In fact, the Greek word for forgiveness is *aphiemi* which means 'breathe out,' 'exhale,' and 'empty.' Suppose, you have hurt me, and I swallow up the hurt feeling within me. Is it forgiveness? No. The hurt feeling will become an acid within me corroding all my

interior parts creating ulcer and cancer and this is not forgiveness. Forgiveness is emptying and exhaling. Forgiveness heals us; forgiveness makes our prayer heard; forgiveness converts others.

First of all, forgiveness heals us. There is a book called, *Answers to Positive Thinking* in which the author narrates an incident. A young woman suffering from all sorts of diseases comes to the author for a cure. He prescribes the following. Take two buckets: one blue and the other red. Fill the red bucket with pebbles. Then, take the pebbles one by one and put it in the blue bucket. As you put the pebble each time relive the hurtful moment and pray for the person against whom you nurse grudge, and say, 'I forgive you, in the name of Jesus.' She did exactly the same. The result is when she emptied the bucket, she was completely cured. We are all wounded in one way or the other. When we forgive others we are healed from our wounds. In this our Master Jesus Christ is our example. The wounded Jesus even when hanging on the cross forgave the people who unjustly treated him. Can we say that his love transformed him and healed him completely that he rose from the dead like a new born child?! Secondly, forgiveness makes our prayer heard. In Mk 11:25 we read, "When you stand praying, forgive." Why does the Lord say this? It is because when we nurse grudge within our hearts, our prayer will not hit the roof and reach out to God. We need forgiveness for our prayers to be heard. Thirdly, forgiveness converts others. Once there was a woman who came to attend a charismatic renewal prayer session. There was no peace within her because she came for the prayer after burying her only young daughter who was raped and murdered by someone. The culprit was caught and was languishing in the prison. The preacher told her to forgive that man. After much struggle, she wrote a simple

letter to him saying that she forgive him completely and totally. To her surprise she received a reply from him saying, “mother, if you forgive me, I am sure that God has forgiven me”. Forgiveness converts others! There is a place in Italy where Maria Gorettri was stabbed to death, butchered like an animal by her own maternal uncle Alexander out of sexual passion. But the unyielding Maria Gorettri did not nurse grudge against her own uncle. She looked at him with love and compassion as she breathed her last in his hands. This had converted him. Alexander repented for his sins, even joined the religious order and died as a Monk! Suppose you have anger towards someone in your personal life, forgive that person from within your heart, and you will see that the forgiven person is completely transformed. Once there was a boy who was saying his family rosary. As part of the family prayer, he has to read out the list of the names of the family members for the blessing of God. While doing this, he omitted his brother’s name and his mother noticed it. His mother asked him, ‘my son, why have you left out your brother’s name?’ he said, ‘he hit me today.’ But his mother said, ‘don’t you remember that our Lord asked us to forgive our enemies,’ but he retorted saying, ‘yes, but he is not my enemy but my brother yet he hit me.’ When people who are very close to us hurt us, it hurts us very deeply. When we are hurt deeply what do we do? We avoid others. If at all we happen to meet, we either blame each other or in a denial mode replacing it with some other impersonal matter. But the Lord wants us to forgive. Once there was a father and his teen aged son. The relationship between them became so strained until one day the boy ran away from the house. The father realized his mistake, went after his son. After searching for a long time he put an Ad as a last resort in one of the local Newspapers in Madrid, Spain saying, ‘all is forgiven, come back tomorrow noon in front of the office of this News paper. We love you Paco.’ The next day when he went in front of the local office, there were 800 boys with the name of Paco waiting for their fathers to come and pick up!

In the very same chapter, Pope Francis also speaks about death penalty. Today there are ways to implement the law and therefore we do not require a death penalty. He also goes to the extent of saying that a life sentence also is a secret death penalty. When speaking about war, he says that always in the world, after the war, the situation is worse than what was before and therefore he is against the war, too. In the context of forgiveness, he brings all the above points.

8. Inter-Religious Dialogue

Finally, in Chapter eight, Pope Francis speaks about inter-religious dialogue. According to the Bishops of India, the Pope says that the goal of dialogue is to establish friendship, peace and harmony and to share spiritual and moral values and experiences in a spirit of truth and love. The interreligious dialogue can take place hierarchically or complementarily. ‘Hierarchically’ means ‘my religion is superior and yours is inferior.’ Here, dialogue cannot take place. ‘Complementarily’ means ‘yes, what I have not seen, you have seen and come, let us sit and share about this.’ In this encyclical, Pope Francis gives another idea of the interreligious dialogue. He gives an example from 1 Cor 12:13 “For in the one Spirit we were all baptized into one body – Jews or Greeks, slaves or free – and we were all made to drink of one Spirit.” What he means is that our body has got many parts, and all the parts of the body work towards the welfare of the body. In Indian Philosophy, there is a word for it: the welfare of the whole, the ‘*lokasangraha*.’ Now, there are different religions and they are like different limbs of our body. The whole body is like the society. The society has got very many issues. Each religion can offer solutions. Therefore, we, Christians, need to train ourselves in this. In Theology we try to give this methodology of theologizing on issues to our students. They go out for their weekend

ministries and during which they become aware of the issues in the society. When they come back with those issues, they were trained to look at them from the point of view of Scripture and the Christian Tradition. What does the Scripture say with regard to those issues and what do the Church documents say with regard to those issues? Thus, gradually we develop such a methodology and then share with the faithful and with the other religions. Then, the interreligious dialogue will become useful and beneficial to the society. Finally, Pope Francis ends by saying, “And in imitation of Mary, the Mother of Jesus, “we want to be a Church that serves, that leaves home and goes forth from its sacristies, in order to accompany life, to sustain hope, to be the sign of unity... to build bridges, to break down walls, to sow seeds of reconciliation” (FT 276).

Conclusion

In conclusion, I would like to add a note on combining the social commitment with our personal prayer life and it can be termed as Apostolic Mysticism. In the history of the Church, prayer life broadly went through three stages:² one in the fourth century where there were Syrian monks, called *Messalians* meaning the people who were always praying (1 Thess 5:17). They had a kind of prayer which was called ‘*theoria*,’ ‘*theo*’ means ‘God’ and ‘*horan*’ means ‘to see.’ They spent all their time in prayer elevating their mind to see the invisible God within and without. They were contemplatives. Looking at them people thought of two kinds of Christians: Martha, the people of the world, who work; Mary, the monks, whose duty was only to pray. Then, in the sixth century another type of prayer came with St. Benedict whose famous maxim ‘*Ora et labora*’ (prayer and work) was a refutation of those supercharismatics. Here, as in the Benedictine Monastery, people work for sometimes like Martha and come together to pray at other times like Mary. But, it doesn’t solve the

² Tomas Spidlik, “Ignatian Meditation and the Prayer of the Oriental Church,” in: *Ignatian Spirituality* (Roma: Centrum Ignatianum Spiritualitatis, 1979), 16-18.

problem. When I am absorbed in my daily work I simply cannot keep my mind on praying. Then, in the sixteenth century, St. Ignatius of Loyola came and introduced to us what is called, in the words of Fr. Lindworsky, the ‘School of the Will.’ What does it mean? The Ignatian prayer method supposes the unity of mind and body. This mentality seems to imply: “I know what God wants, and in the coming days or weeks or years I can do it.” Through such practice we purify our heart, and only the pure heart sees God. It is typically Ignatian to see God in my activity, to be a contemplative in action, to be Mary in Martha, not to be Mary at one moment and Martha at another moment. It is similar to what St. Paul says in 1 Thess 5:17 ‘pray always.’ How to pray always? St. Ignatius advises us to ask ourselves at any moment of our time: what is the will of God at this stage for me? Once I discover that this is the will of God, then, I put my heart and soul in doing it. When you are doing the will of God, you are praying. For example, I am teaching Scripture in the Theologate at Jnana Deepa, in Pune. What is the will of God for me at this stage? It is teaching Scripture. Once I know that this is the will of God for me now, then, I put my heart and soul into preparing and teaching the subject given to me. For others who are teachers, it may be Mathematics or History, doesn’t matter, when they are doing it well, they are praying. Tony de Mello has got two stories: once there was a little fish which asked the older fish, ‘where is the ocean?’ The older fish said that the place where you are in is the ocean. But, the little fish responded saying, ‘no, it is only water’ and it went away. Then the little fish put on the garment of a sanyasi, met the guru and spoke to him in sanyasi’s language: “Sir, where is God, I am searching for God everywhere, in the valleys and on the mountains. Guru asked him, ‘did you find God?’ He said, ‘No.’ Then, the guru told him, ‘Do not search for God, but just look and you will never miss God.’ Tony de Mello gives another story: there

was a guru giving classes to the businessmen. He told them that the fish taken out of water suffocates and dies. In order to survive the fish has to get into the water. In the same way if you are entangled in worldly affairs, you also will suffocate and die. Then, one of the businessmen asked a question: ‘does it mean that we have to abandon our businesses and join monasteries? The guru said, ‘No, hold on to your businesses but get back into your heart!’

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To Be Neighbours in Our World: Pope Francis' Vision for Humanity and Society in *Fratelli Tutti*

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Abstract: Fratelli Tutti can be considered Pope Francis' manifesto of the "social covenant" of human fraternity and social friendship for modern times. Here, he envisions a society that is open to all, includes all and values all. He invites us to dream together for a society that integrates everyone and fosters interrelatedness and interdependence.

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He visualizes a society that opens to the needs of the world and promotes healthy neighbourhood in the world. He envisages a society that overcomes the evils of intolerance, social exclusion, racism, the culture of “throwaway” and social media. He calls for a society that nurtures a culture of fraternity, dialogue, encounter, and tolerance. He foresees a society that raises human dignity, and fosters opportunity and dignity of human labour. He visualizes a society that develops global ethics of solidarity and cooperation to find solutions for common issues. Fratelli Tutti is Pope Francis’ invitation to “dream together” (FT 127) for “a single human family” (FT 8); his spiritual testament and social manifesto for a better fraternal and universal brotherhood.

Keywords: Fratelli Tutti, Human Fraternity, Interrelatedness, Interdependence, Inclusive.

Introduction

In *Fratelli Tutti*, Pope Francis envisions a global society in which individuals and nations care for one another and acknowledge each human person's dignity. It focuses on contemporary social and economic problems and proposes an ideal world of fraternity in which everyone can be part of a “larger human family” (FT 141).¹ Therefore, he treats this encyclical as a reflection on human fraternity and social friendship as the remedy for the social problems of this world. He makes this clear from the very purpose of this encyclical: “It is my desire that, in this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity: Brotherhood between all men and women” (FT 8). He encourages

¹ All citations in the text are from Pope Francis, *Fratelli Tutti, Encyclical Letter on Fraternity and Social Friendship*, published by Conference of Catholic Bishops of India (ATC Publishers, Bangalore 2020). Henceforth *Fratelli Tutti* will be abbreviated as FT.

a universal fraternity. However, he says that it demands “a decisive commitment to devising effective means to this end” (FT 180). He calls for a “heart open to the whole world” (FT 128-153), a “better kind of politics” (FT 154-197), and “paths of renewed encounter and dialogue” (FT 198-270) for universal fraternity and social friendship. This encyclical is not only an invitation extended to Christians to “dream together” (FT 127) for “a single human family” (FT 8) firmly grounded on human fraternity and social friendship but also to everyone who dreams for it. For he says, “Although I have written it from the Christian convictions that inspire and sustain me, I have sought to make this reflection an invitation to dialogue among all people of good will” (FT 6). Following is an attempt to understand Pope Francis’ vision for humanity and society in *Fratelli Tutti*.

1. An Open, Inclusive, Larger Human Family

Pope Francis’ call for a universal fraternity and dream for a universal human family can be vividly seen at the outset of the encyclical itself:

It is my desire that, in this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity. Fraternity between all men and women.[...] Let us dream, then, as a single human family, as fellow travellers sharing the same flesh, as children of the same earth which is our common home, each of us bringing the richness of his or her beliefs and convictions, each of us with his or her own voice, brothers and sisters all (FT 8).

Pope Francis notes that “an individual and a people are only fruitful and productive if they are able to develop a creative

openness to others” (FT 41) because we are meant for each other. He believes that “A truly human and fraternal society will be capable of ensuring in an efficient and stable way that each of its members is accompanied at every stage of life. Not only by providing for their basic needs but by enabling them to give the best of themselves...” (FT 110). According to him, “Solidarity means thinking and acting in terms of community. It means that the lives of all are prior to the appropriation of goods by a few. It also means combatting structural causes of poverty, inequality, lack of work, land and housing, the denial of social and labour rights” (FT 116).

Inspired by the words of St. Francis of Assisi, Pope Francis envisages “a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance” (FT1) because he firmly believes that “a love capable of transcending borders is the basis of... social friendship,” and it is the “genuine social friendship within a society makes true universal openness possible” (FT 99). It is, therefore, he condemns all those who continue to “support varieties of narrow and violent nationalism, xenophobia and contempt, and even the mistreatment of those who are different” (FT 86). Therefore, Pope Francis asks us to create a culture of encounter to get to know one another because he believes that it is not possible “to experience the true beauty of life without relating to others, without having real faces to love” (FT 87). Therefore, he encourages the individuals and nations to open up more, showing gestures of more human fraternity and solidarity (cf. FT 87-90). He believes that “individualism does not make us more free, more equal, more fraternal” (FT 105) but a “universal love” that promotes the dignity of every human being (FT 106-111). According to him, a fundamental familial unity of all humankind is love because “love... impels us towards universal communion” (FT 95). He also says that “the spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love, which in the end remains ‘the criterion for the definitive decision about a human life’s worth or lack thereof’” (FT 92).

Pope Francis sees the need for a larger human family, especially in times of crisis: “The true worth of the different countries of our world is measured by their ability to think not simply as a country but also as part of the larger human family. This is seen especially in times of crisis. Narrow forms of nationalism are an extreme expression of an inability to grasp the meaning of this gratuitousness” (FT 141). He further warns that “only a social and political culture that readily and “gratuitously” welcomes others will have a future” (FT 141).

Pope Francis says that when we fail to recognize each person as a brother or sister, even those “born in the same country” can become “an existential foreigner” (FT 97) or a “hidden exile” (FT 98). A genuinely “human and fraternal” society will work to ensure that every member can thrive at each moment in life (FT 110). This is what it means to “foster integral human development,” a development that promotes the common good and allows us to “advance together towards an authentic and integral growth” (FT 113).

According to Pope Francis, solidarity and social friendship challenge us to place the common good for the universal good. It is in this context that Pope Francis says in Catholic teaching, “the right to private property” is not absolute; it is secondary to the “principle of the universal destination of created goods” (FT 120). This has implications for policies that affect the global poor (e.g., debt relief [FT 126] and access to work opportunities [FT 123]), women (FT 121), migrants (no. 124), and the natural environment (FT 122). He asserts that the global community must place the ability of every human person to thrive over goals of wealth and conquest, “for a real and lasting peace will only be possible ‘on the basis of a global ethic of solidarity and cooperation in the service of a future shaped by interdependence and shared responsibility in the whole human family’” (FT 127).

In short, Pope Francis says that “we need to think of each other more and more as a single family dwelling in a common home” (FT 87).

According to him, the COVID-19 pandemics once again revealed humanity’s vulnerability and the need to work together globally to tackle a common issue:

True, a worldwide tragedy like the Covid-19 pandemic momentarily revived the sense that we are a global community, all in the same boat, where one person’s problems are the problems of all. Once more we realized that no one is saved alone; we can only be saved together. As I said in those days, “the storm has exposed our vulnerability and uncovered those false and superfluous certainties around which we constructed our daily schedules, our projects, our habits and priorities (FT 32).

Following the invitation to “advance along the paths of hope” (FT 55), Pope Francis offers reflections on the parable of the Good Samaritan as a starting point for our call to universal fraternity: “The parable shows us how a community can be rebuilt by men and women who identify with the vulnerability of others, who reject the creation of a society of exclusion and act instead as neighbours, lifting up and rehabilitating the fallen for the sake of the common good” (FT 67). Pope Francis invites us to take up “co-responsibility” in creating communities built upon solidarity and social friendship: “Today we have a great opportunity to express our innate sense of fraternity, to be Good Samaritans who bear the pain of other people’s troubles rather than fomenting greater hatred and resentment” (FT 77). He reminds us that change happens on the level of ordinary people, and that “each individual can act as an effective leaven by the way he or she lives each day” (FT 231).

Pope Francis reminds us that “God continues to sow abundant seeds of goodness in our human family” (FT 54). He believes that “to be part of a people is to be part of a shared identity arising from social and cultural bonds. And that is not something automatic, but rather a slow, difficult process ... of advancing towards a common project” (FT 158).

2. Society that integrates everyone

Pope Francis envisions a human and fraternal society where everyone is integrated and taken care of. For he says: “A truly human and fraternal society will be capable of ensuring in an efficient and stable way that each of its members is accompanied at every stage of life. Not only by providing for their basic needs, but by enabling them to give the best of themselves, even though their performance may be less than optimum, their pace slow or their efficiency limited” (FT 110). He also visualizes a human and fraternal society characterized by liberty and equality, for he says: “Fraternity is born not only of a climate of respect for individual liberties, or even of a certain administratively guaranteed equality. Fraternity necessarily calls for something greater, which in turn enhances freedom and equality” (FT 103). He says that equality is not achieved by an abstract proclamation that “all men and women are equal” (FT 103). Instead, it is the result of the conscious and careful cultivation of fraternity” (FT 104). He also dreams a human and fraternal society that fosters human dignity: “Social friendship and universal fraternity necessarily call for an acknowledgement of the worth of every human person, always and everywhere” (FT 106). Therefore, he warns that if the human dignity of the elderly, poor, unborn and disabled are not taken care of, then the dream of a universal fraternity will be a vague ideal (FT 18).

Pope Francis urges us to “include or exclude those lying wounded along the roadside” (FT 69) in our community. While reflecting upon the parable of the Good Samaritan, the framework upon which he built *Fratelli Tutti*, he instructs, “Each day we have to decide whether to be Good Samaritans or indifferent bystanders” (FT 69). He explains it in the following way, “Every brother or sister in need, when abandoned or ignored by the society in which I live, becomes an existential foreigner, even though born in the same country. They may be citizens with full rights, yet they are treated like foreigners in their own country” (FT 97).

Strikingly, Pope Francis calls for the creation of a “social covenant” (FT 218) between all members of society, rich and poor, which obliges everyone to give up some things for the common good (FT 219). According to the Pope, “a realistic and inclusive social covenant must also be a “cultural covenant”, one that respects and acknowledges the different worldviews, cultures and lifestyles that coexist in society” (FT 219). He further explains its nature: “Such a covenant also demands the realization that some things may have to be renounced for the common good” (FT 221). Social covenant demands authentic acknowledgement of our neighbour and the ability to “stand in the place of others” (FT 221). He says that “Words like freedom, democracy or fraternity prove meaningless, for only when our economic and social system no longer produces even a single victim, a single person cast aside, will we be able to celebrate the feast of universal fraternity” (FT 110).

Pope Francis also calls for a society that “cultivates kindness” (FT 222), an attitude to be recuperated because it “free us from the cruelty..., anxiety and ...frantic flurry of activity” (FT 224) that prevail in our contemporary age. Pope Francis says that cultivating “kindness” is necessary in order to move beyond mere civility to true social love for our neighbours (FT 224).

3. Society that Fosters Interrelatedness and Interdependence

One of the significant concerns of Pope Francis is humanity's interconnectedness. Therefore, he says that the suffering or impoverishment in part of the globe will not stay confined there: "we are either all saved together or no one is saved" (FT 137). He speaks of a "universal consciousness" that creates a mutual concern for the well-being of the earth and those most impacted by injustices occurring within it (FT 117). He reminds us of our interrelatedness, saying: "No one people, culture, or individual can achieve everything on its own: to attain fulfilment in life we need others" (FT 150). A feeling of interconnectedness must remain central in thinking to cultivate solidarity among the nations across the world: "an appropriate and authentic openness to the world presupposes the capacity to be open to one's neighbour within a family of nations" (FT 151). What is important is that we remain interconnected. He would say how our interconnectivity has made us "powerfully aware of the unity and common destiny of nations" (FT 96). He articulates the interrelatedness of humanity theologically, saying: "Human beings are so made that they cannot live, develop and find fulfilment except 'in the sincere gift of self to others'" (FT 87).

Pope Francis explains the role of interrelatedness and interdependence for the unity and common destiny of the nations in the following way: "The ever-increasing number of interconnections and communications in today's world makes us powerfully aware of the unity and common destiny of the nations. In the dynamics of history, and the diversity of ethnic groups, societies and cultures, we see the seeds of a vocation to form a community composed of brothers and sisters who accept and care for one another" (FT 96).

4. Society that Opens to the Needs of the World

Pope Francis invites us to foster a heart open to the whole world that allows us to see that our well-being is tied up to that of our neighbours near and far, that “to attain fulfilment in life we need others” (FT 150). In chapter four, titled “A Heart Open to the Whole World” he discusses some of the practical political applications of universal fraternity, particularly one of the central political challenges of our time: immigration. According to him, everyone has the right to migrate to “meet their basic needs and those of their families” (FT 129). He has reiterated his call for a more welcoming attitude toward migrants, saying that everyone has the right to “dream of a better future.” He says: “If every human being possesses an inalienable dignity, if all people are my brothers and sisters, and if the world truly belongs to everyone, then it matters little whether my neighbour was born in my country or elsewhere” (FT 125). This is because “each country also belongs to the foreigner, inasmuch as a territory’s goods must not be denied to a needy person coming from elsewhere” (FT 124).

Pope Francis supports the cause of immigrants, saying: “No one, then, can remain excluded because of his or her place of birth, much less because of privileges enjoyed by others who were born in lands of greater opportunity. The limits and borders of individual states cannot stand in the way of this” (FT 121). He is convinced that “each country also belongs to the foreigner inasmuch as a territory’s goods must not be denied to a needy person coming from elsewhere” (FT 124). He quotes Moses’ exhortation to Israelites to call his concern for the migrants: ““you shall not wrong or oppress a stranger, for you were strangers in the land of Egypt’ (Ex 22:21)” (FT 61).

Pope Francis appeals to countries to welcome, protect, promote, and integrate migrants, especially for those fleeing serious humanitarian crises. These include: “developing and simplifying the granting of visas, opening humanitarian corridors, providing

housing, security and essential services, offering work and training opportunities, promoting family reunification, protecting minors, guaranteeing religious freedom” (FT 129). He says that “ideally, unnecessary migration ought to be avoided” (FT 129). Nobody should feel forced to leave their place of origin and be uprooted from their family, religion, and culture (cf FT 38). While we must make efforts to reduce migration, Pope Francis says that we are “obliged to respect the right of all individuals to find a place that meets their basic needs and those of their families” (FT 129). Rather than considering immigrants as a threat to the country, he says, they enrich a country, and their presence is “a gift” (FT133). He criticizes that most wealthy nations see immigrants as “usurpers who have nothing to offer” (FT 141). He also emphasizes the enrichment of the cultures by mutual encounters with one another, and he specifically mentions how the immigrants have enriched the United States, as well as how Jewish immigrants blessed his home country of Argentina (FT 135).

Pope Francis argues that “The world exists for everyone because all of us were born with the same dignity” and “the Christian tradition has never recognized the right to private property as absolute or inviolable” for “the right to private property can only be considered a secondary natural right, derived from the principle of the universal destination of created goods” (FT 118, 120). He takes the principle “the world exists for everyone” further saying:

Nowadays, a firm belief in the common destination of the earth’s goods requires that this principle also be applied to nations, their territories and their resources. Seen from the standpoint not only of the legitimacy of private property and the rights of its citizens but also of the first principle of the common destination of

goods, we can then say that each country also belongs to the foreigner, inasmuch as a territory's goods must not be denied to a needy person coming from elsewhere. As the Bishops of the United States have taught, there are fundamental rights that 'precede any society because they flow from the dignity granted to each person as created by God' (FT 124).

Pope Francis urges us to resist "the temptation to build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in the heart, walls on the land, to prevent this encounter with other cultures, with other people" (FT 27). He warns that "those who raise walls will end up as slaves within the very walls they have built" (FT 27). In short, Pope Francis' vision of an "open-world" can be "summarized in four words: welcome, protect, promote and integrate. For it is not a case of implementing welfare programs from the top-down, but rather of undertaking a journey together, through these four actions" (FT 129). He cautions not to narrow our minds and hearts: "Let us realize that as our minds and hearts narrow, the less capable we become of understanding the world around us" (FT 147). He asks us "to think not simply as a country but also as part of the larger human family" (FT 141).

5. Society that Fosters Healthy Neighbourhood in the World

Pope Francis' call to be neighbours in the world is very hopes giving. He asks us "not to decide who is close enough to be our neighbour, but rather that we ourselves become neighbours to all" (FT 80). In the second chapter, titled "A Stranger on the Road," he presents the Samaritan who helped a traveller who had been left for dead as a model of human fraternity, in contrast to others who passed by (Lk 10: 25-37). According to him, this parable provides insights into the deep connections that bond all humans as brothers and sisters, and it functions as a "ray of light in the

midst of what we are experiencing” (FT 56). He considers this parable an invitation from Jesus to “rediscover our vocation as citizens of our respective nations and the entire world, builders of a new social bond” (FT 66). According to him, it “speaks to us of an essential and often forgotten aspect of our common humanity: we were created for a fulfilment that can only be found in love” (FT 68).

Pope Francis asks us to discern to be Good Samaritans in our day-to-day life: “Each day we have to decide whether to be Good Samaritans or indifferent bystanders” (FT 69). He says that our efforts for fraternity should become a “vocation,” a calling that shakes us from our sinful habits (FT 66). He says that each new day should be seen as an opportunity to “include, integrate, and lift up the fallen” rather than “an arena for [our] own power plays” (FT 77). He reiterates the teaching of the apostle of James: “Those who do not love a brother or sister whom they have seen, cannot love God whom they have not seen (1 Jn 4:20)” (FT 61). He is concerned about our indifference towards a suffering person, and he says that it is a symptom of an unhealthy society: “The sight of a person who is suffering disturbs us. It makes us uneasy since we have no time to waste on other people’s problems. These are symptoms of an unhealthy society” (FT 65). He considers it as a grave mistake not to care for the weakest and most fragile: “We need to acknowledge that we are constantly tempted to ignore others, especially the weak. Let us admit that, for all the progress we have made, we are still “illiterate” when it comes to accompanying, caring for and supporting the most frail and vulnerable members of our developed societies” (FT 64).

Pope Francis even praises those unbelievers who become true Samaritans and thus do the will of God for humanity: “Paradoxically, those who claim to be unbelievers can sometimes put God’s will into practice better than believers”

(FT 74). He urges them to follow the teaching of Jesus by not setting limits on who they regard as their neighbours. He says that love builds bridges, and we “are made for love” (FT 88), urging Christians, in particular, to recognize Christ in the face of all those who are excluded (FT 85).

He reminds us that the parable of the Good Samaritan makes us aware of our responsibility “for the fragility of others” and moves us to “set aside” our desires and goals “before the concrete gaze of those who are most vulnerable” (FT 115). He exhorts us to “go outside the self to find a fuller existence in another” (FT 88) “toward universal communion” (FT 95).

6. Society that Overcomes the Dark Clouds over a Closed World

In the first chapter, titled “Dark Clouds over a Closed World,” Pope Francis makes a frank assessment of a world in turmoil, and he tells that there are many serious issues currently preventing us from living as true brothers and sisters with common goals. He denounces the selfishness and the disinterest in the common good, the prevalence of a market logic based on profit and the culture of waste, unemployment, racism, poverty etc., which hinder universal brotherhood. He states that tendencies of isolationism, nationalism, a global economy that promotes individual interests, a loss of the sense of history, deconstructionism, limitless consumption wastefulness, the lack of concern for the environment, and a throwaway culture are blocking to achieving this goal of universal fraternity (cf. FT 13 & 18). He points out that globalization has created only an illusion of giving a sense of belonging to a common family, but it only drove toward a “globalized indifference” (FT 30).

In today’s world, the sense of belonging to a single human family is fading, and the dream of working together for justice and peace seems an outdated utopia,” ...“What reigns instead is a

cool, comfortable and globalized indifference, born of deep disillusionment concealed behind a deceptive illusion: thinking that we are all-powerful, while failing to realize that we are all in the same boat (FT30).

According to Pope Francis, the farfetched individual concerns play a vital role in the rejection of the dignity and well-being of the whole of humanity:

The gap between concern for one's personal well-being and the prosperity of the larger human family seems to be stretching to the point of complete division between individuals and human community ... It is one thing to feel forced to live together, but something entirely different to value the richness and beauty of those seeds of common life that need to be sought out and cultivated" (FT 31).

Pope Francis identifies one's fears and doubts as to the root cause for intolerance against the other, leading even to racism: "There is a problem when doubts and fears condition our way of thinking and acting to the point of making us intolerant, closed and perhaps even without realizing it racist" (FT 41). He criticizes "culture of walls" that favours the proliferation of mafias, fueled by fear and loneliness: "new walls are erected for self-preservation...we encounter "the temptation to build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in the heart, walls on the land, to prevent this encounter with other cultures, with other people "(FT 27).

Intolerance and Social Exclusion

Pope Francis considers racism as an attitude that can be compared to "a virus that quickly mutates and, instead of

disappearing, goes into hiding, and lurks in waiting” (FT 97). Quoting the U.S. bishops’ 2018 pastoral letter against racism, “Open Wide Our Hearts,” he condemns this inhuman behaviour saying there are fundamental rights that “precede any society because they flow from the dignity granted to each person as created by God (FT 124). He also alludes to the “hidden exiles,” that is people with disabilities, “who are treated as foreign bodies in society (FT 76). Many persons with disabilities “feel that they exist without belonging and without participating” (FT 98). However, he feels that we can overcome the barriers of intolerance and seek the truth through dialogue and passionate conversation: “Together, we can seek the truth in dialogue, in relaxed conversation or in passionate debate. To do so calls for perseverance; it entails moments of silence and suffering, yet it can patiently embrace the broader experience of individuals and peoples” (FT 50).

In a world where gender discrimination and exploitation exist, Pope Francis strives to ensure the dignity of women globally so that the dream of the universal fraternity will have its desired fruits. For he says, “The organization of societies worldwide is still far from reflecting clearly that women possess the same dignity and identical rights as men” (FT 23).

A Culture of “Throwaway”

While there were promising movements of unity and fraternity among nations and peoples, Pope Francis says that we are showing “signs of a certain regression” in growing in collaboration and extending friendship to the nations (FT 11). He feels that the entire world is drawn into a form of globalism that neglects authentic fraternity and instead offers “cool, comfortable, and globalized indifference” (FT 30). He attributes this mainly to the throwaway culture favouring a crude utilitarian view of the economy and humanity itself (FT 22). According to him, the “throwaway world” promotes abortion and euthanasia, neglect of the elderly, discrimination against women, slavery, etc.

In this “throwaway world”, he feels that “persons are no longer seen as a paramount value to be cared for and respected, especially when they are poor and disabled, ‘not yet useful’ – like the unborn, or ‘no longer needed’ – like the elderly” (FT 18).

Pope Francis warns against the tendencies of the throwaway culture of the modern world, and he exhorts us to consider that “loving the most insignificant of human beings as a brother as if there were no one else in the world but him, cannot be considered a waste of time” (FT 193):

The modern world, with its technical advances, tends increasingly to functionalize the satisfaction of human desires, now classified and subdivided among different services. Less and less will people be called by name, less and less will this unique being be treated as a person with his or her feelings, sufferings, problems, joys and family. Their illnesses will be known only in order to cure them, their financial needs only to provide for them, their lack of a home only to give them lodging, their desires for recreation and entertainment only to satisfy them”. Yet it must never be forgotten that “loving the most insignificant of human beings as a brother, as if there were no one else in the world but him, cannot be considered a waste of time (FT 193).

Digital “Non-Connectivity”

Despite the increase in digital communication in response to our obvious need for engagement, Pope Francis says that “Digital connectivity is not enough to build bridges. It is not capable of uniting humanity” (FT 43). He articulates how digital communication can bring havoc in society, such as

remarkable hostility, insults, abuse, defamation, verbal violence, etc. (FT 44). He argues that “Persons or situations we find unpleasant or disagreeable are simply deleted in today’s virtual networks; a virtual circle is then created, isolating us from the real world in which we are living” (FT 47). However, Pope Francis says that media can foster solidarity and a more dignified life for all:

In today’s globalized world, “the media can help us to feel closer to one another, creating a sense of the unity of the human family which in turn can inspire solidarity and serious efforts to ensure a more dignified life for all... We need constantly to ensure that present-day forms of communication are in fact guiding us to generous encounter with others, to honest pursuit of the whole truth, to service, to closeness to the underprivileged and to the promotion of the common good (FT 205).

7. Society that Fosters a Culture of Fraternity

Pope Francis suggests that universal fraternity and social friendship must be rooted in an authentic cultural encounter that resists the temptation to “build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in the heart, walls on the land” (FT 27). He sees the possibility for a beautiful integration of one’s own culture while striving for the common good of the whole of humanity. “Each particular group becomes part of the fabric of universal communion and there discovers its own beauty. All individuals, whatever their origin, know that they are part of the greater human family, without which they will not be able to understand themselves fully” (FT 149).

However, Pope Francis also stresses the need to stay grounded in one’s own cultural identity and not be driven by “a false openness to the universal, born of the shallowness of those lacking insight

into the genius of their native land” (FT 145). He argues that receptivity and mutual acceptance will come only when we get rooted in our own culture: “I can welcome others who are different, and value the unique contribution they have to make, only if I am rooted in my own people and culture. [. . .] The common good likewise requires that we protect and love our native land” (FT 143). According to him, cultural enrichment is a “healthy and enriching exchange” (FT 144), and “a healthy openness never threatens one’s own identity” (FT 148). He also says that it applies to our approach to the other faiths. Rather than “watering down” (FT 151) one’s own beliefs, each side must hold its own beliefs firmly for authentic dialogue to be possible. Only then can one culture (or religion) “be nourished” by another (FT 148).

Pope Francis also articulates that rootedness in one’s own cultural identity is fundamental for social cohesion and dialogue with other cultures.

“Just as there can be no dialogue with ‘others’ without a sense of our own identity, so there can be no openness between peoples except on the basis of love for one’s own land, one’s own people, one’s own cultural roots. I cannot truly encounter another unless I stand on firm foundations, for it is on the basis of these that I can accept the gift the other brings and in turn offer an authentic gift of my own. I can welcome others who are different, and value the unique contribution they have to make, only if I am firmly rooted in my own people and culture” (FT 143).

Pope Francis does not propose “a completely enclosed, a-historic, static ‘indigenism’ that would reject any kind of blending (mestizaje)” (FT 148). This mutual enrichment,

which he calls “mestizaje,” a word derived from mestizo, describes a true, healthy openness:

A living culture, enriched by elements from other places, does not import a mere carbon copy of those new elements, but integrates them in its own unique way. The result is a new synthesis that is ultimately beneficial to all, since the original culture itself ends up being nourished. That is why I have urged indigenous peoples to cherish their roots and their ancestral cultures ... The world grows and is filled with new beauty, thanks to the successive syntheses produced between cultures that are open and free of any form of cultural imposition” (FT 148).

He says that disdain of one’s own culture is nothing more than a kind of elitism: “This is a far cry from the false universalism of those who constantly travel abroad because they cannot tolerate or love their people. Those who look down on their people tend to create within society categories of the first and second class, people of greater or lesser dignity, people enjoying greater or fewer rights” (FT 99). He questions the cultural integrity of those who look down on their own people: “There can be a false openness to the universal, born of the shallowness of those lacking insight into the genius of their native land or harbouring unresolved resentment towards their own people” (FT 145).

According to Pope Francis, what is at stake is a kind of cross-pollination between cultures, in which they enrich one another while preserving their own cultural richness: “The path to peace does not mean making society blandly uniform, but getting people to work together, side-by-side, in pursuing goals that benefit everyone” (FT 228).

8. Society that Fosters a Culture of Dialogue

According to Pope Francis, an authentic dialogue requires an abiding presence with others, even those we disagree with or dislike, sometimes “in relaxed conversation or passionate debate” (FT 50). According to him, dialogue is a middle path between “selfish indifference” and “violent protest” (FT 198). True dialogue is much more than a monologue, debate or back-and-forth arguing. Rather it is a process involving: “Approaching, speaking, listening, looking at, coming to know and understand one another, and to find common ground: all these things are summed up in the one word “dialogue”” (FT 198). He says that monologues engage no one (FT 200). Whenever people are unafraid to get to the heart of an issue, the interests of society, consensus and the reality of objective truth can be harmonized in authentic dialogue (FT 212).

Pope Francis says that genuine dialogue has “the ability to respect the other’s point of view and to admit that it may include legitimate convictions and concerns” (FT 203). He believes that genuine dialogue does not come at the sacrifice of justice and truth: “We need to learn how to unmask the various ways that the truth is manipulated, distorted and concealed in public and private discourse” (FT 208). According to him, genuine dialogue allows us to discover those shared values we know to be true and fosters a consensus among and within societies that becomes the basis for a shared social ethic:

In a pluralistic society, dialogue is the best way to realize what ought always to be affirmed and respected apart from any ephemeral consensus. Such dialogue needs to be enriched and illumined by clear thinking, rational arguments, a variety of perspectives and the contribution of different

fields of knowledge and points of view. ... Our understanding of their meaning and scope can increase – and in that respect, consensus is a dynamic reality – but in themselves, they are held to be enduring by virtue of their inherent meaning (FT 211).

Pope Francis suggests the path of dialogue, which seeks congruence between “the interests of society, consensus and the reality of objective truth. These three realities can be harmonized whenever, through dialogue, people are unafraid to get to the heart of an issue” (FT 212). Society is built on authentic dialogue, which involves respecting the other’s viewpoint: “it must respect the truth of our human dignity and submit to that truth” (FT 207). To explain the nature of the authentic dialogue, he draws on a favourite image, that of the polyhedron, “whose different sides form a variegated unity, in which ‘the whole is greater than the part’” (FT 215).

9. Society that Fosters a Culture of Encounter

Pope Francis calls for a new culture – a “culture of encounter” rooted in bridge building and community: “Life, for all its confrontations, is the art of encounter” (FT 215). He says that everyone is indispensable and can learn from each other: “Each of us can learn something from others. No one is useless and no one is expendable” (FT 215). He suggests for a culture of encounter “capable of transcending our differences and divisions. He places “culture of encounter” as a new culture and a style of life: “a “culture of encounter” means that we, as a people, should be passionate about meeting others, seeking points of contact, building bridges, planning a project that includes everyone. This becomes an aspiration and a style of life” (FT 216).

Pope Francis says that the “culture of encounter” should take place at all levels of society: “Encounter cannot take place only between the holders of economic, political or academic power.

Genuine social encounter calls for a dialogue that engages the culture shared by the majority of the population” (FT 219). True encounter does not push others away because they make us uncomfortable. It is rooted in a “basic sense of belonging” to each other which is present within each human being (FT 230). It does not mean avoiding conflicts or “making society blandly uniform” (FT 228). Political leaders practising encounter would foster reconciliation that happens through “open, honest, and patient negotiation” (FT 244). Moreover, he calls the international community to work for a culture of tolerance: “the architects of international policy and world economy to work strenuously to spread the culture of tolerance and of living together in peace; to intervene at the earliest opportunity to stop the shedding of innocent blood” (FT 192).

10. Society that Fosters Human Dignity

According to Pope Francis, an authentic human fraternity recognizes the inherent dignity of all persons. It takes care of the person’s integral development by giving “sufficient opportunities for his or her integral development” (FT 118). He believes that if we are willing to dream together of a world firmly grounded on the dignity of all persons, “we can rise to the challenge of envisaging a new humanity. We can aspire to a world that provides land, housing and work for all” (FT 127).

Pope Francis says that our commitment to the dignity of every person and the common good must guide our relationships, civil institutions, and economic systems so that all people have the opportunity to “develop integrally” (FT 108). He is convinced that “the dignity of others is to be respected in all circumstances, not because that dignity is something we have invented or imagined, but because human beings possess an intrinsic worth” that comes from God (FT

213). According to him, peace would require “to place at the center of all political, social and economic activity the human person, who enjoys the highest dignity, and respect for the common good” (FT 232).

Pope Francis affirms that “God has created all human beings with equal rights, duties, and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters” (FT 5). He further asserts that human dignity is the basis of the common good and universal brotherhood: “When the dignity of the human person is respected, and his or her rights recognized and guaranteed, creativity and interdependence thrive, and the creativity of the human personality is released through actions that further the common good” (FT 22). He places human dignity and respect for the common good are central to end to the building of a country’s social peace:

Individually and together, we must commit and work to eradicate the oppression and selfish greed that dehumanizes others for personal or national gain. “There is no end to the building of a country’s social peace. Rather, it requires us to place at the centre of all political, social and economic activity the human person, who enjoys the highest dignity, and respect for the common good” (FT 232).

In the context of human dignity and uniqueness of human life, Pope Francis’s teaching on capital punishment becomes very significant. He states clearly that “the death penalty is inadmissible and the Catholic Church is firmly committed to calling for its abolition worldwide” (FT 263). He condemns the death penalty because it rejects the dignity of human persons. He explains it in the following way: “The firm rejection of the death penalty shows to what extent it is possible to recognize the inalienable dignity of every human being and to accept that he or she has a place in this universe” (FT 269). He exhorts to heal the

wounds of the souls rather than taking punitive measures. He says, “Do not let the atrocity of their sins feed a desire for vengeance, but desire instead to heal the wounds which those deeds have inflicted on their souls” (FT 256). He considers the death penalty as a symptom of a society that has lost awareness of its interconnectedness and disregards the dignity of the human person (FT 263). He extends this call further to improve the quality of prison conditions, which is another example of how we deny our brothers and sisters authentic encounter and social friendship (FT 268).

11. Society that Fosters Opportunity and Dignity of Human Labour

According to Pope Francis, the best politics is also one that protects the dignity of employment, an “essential dimension of social life ... personal growth, the building of healthy relationships, self-expression and the exchange of gifts” (FT 162). He considers employment as the biggest issue for a developed society: “The biggest issue is employment. The truly “popular” thing – since it promotes the good of the people – is to provide everyone with the opportunity to nurture the seeds that God has planted in each of us: our talents, our initiative and our innate resources” (FT 162). He further says that “In a genuinely developed society, work is an essential dimension of social life, for it is not only a means of earning one’s daily bread, but also of personal growth, the building of healthy relationships, self-expression and the exchange of gifts. Work gives us a sense of shared responsibility for the development of the world, and ultimately, for our life as a people” (FT 162). According to him, the best help that we can give to the poor is to provide them with employment, because it is a path to “a life of dignity”: “This is the finest help we can give to the poor, the best path to a life of dignity. Hence my insistence that

“helping the poor financially must always be a provisional solution in the face of pressing needs. The broader objective should always be to allow them a dignified life through work” (FT 162). He categorically says that “there is no poverty worse than that which takes away work and the dignity of work” (FT 162).

Pope Francis believes that jobs that pay a living wage and honour the dignity of the human person are essential. He writes, “In a genuinely developed society, work is an essential dimension of social life, for it is not only a means of earning one’s daily bread, but also of personal growth, the building of healthy relationships, self-expression and the exchange of gifts. Work gives us a sense of shared responsibility for the development of the world, and ultimately, for our life as a people” (FT 162). He says, “helping the poor financially must always be a provisional solution in the face of pressing needs. The broader objective should always be to allow them a dignified life through work” (FT 162).

12. Society that Fosters a Global Ethics of Solidarity and Cooperation

Pope Francis calls for global ethics of solidarity and cooperation for envisaging new humanity. By recalling his address on Nuclear Weapons, Nagasaki, Japan (November 24 2019), he says: “For a real and lasting peace will only be possible “on the basis of a global ethic of solidarity and cooperation in the service of a future shaped by interdependence and shared responsibility in the whole human family” (FT 127). He argues that “if we accept the great principle that there are rights born of our inalienable human dignity, we can rise to the challenge of envisaging new humanity (FT 127). According to him, every person, because of their inalienable dignity, has a right to the goods necessary for “a developed and dignified life”, and “the limits and borders of individual states cannot stand in the way of this” (FT 121).

Pope Francis criticizes selfishness and wrong policies in the economy and handling common issues. So, in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, he writes that it has shown that “not everything can be resolved by market freedom” and that human dignity must be put “back at the center” (FT 168). Therefore, he denounces “the “dogma” of neoliberalism that the market by itself can resolve any problem, a dogma which repeatedly “resort[s] to the magic theories of ‘spillover’ or ‘trickle’” to solve any societal problem” (FT 168). The proper anti-poverty strategy, he thinks that it should be from the perspective of solidarity and subsidiarity (FT 187). According to him, it is not enough to “contain” poverty. Still, it should enable the poor to shape their future, and to participate in society: “What is needed are new pathways of self-expression and participation in society. Education serves these by making it possible for each human being to shape his or her own future. Here too, we see the importance of the principle of subsidiarity, which is inseparable from the principle of solidarity” (FT 187).

Pope Francis’ invitation to embody the love of the Good Samaritan is not merely a call to a new social ethic. It is also an invitation to remember the purpose of our life: “created for a fulfilment that can only be found in love. We cannot be indifferent to suffering. . . . Instead, we should feel indignant, challenged to emerge from our comfortable isolation, and to be changed by our contact with human suffering” (FT 68). According to him, the parable the Good Samaritan challenges us to prioritize the needs of the other and begin to “restore the dignity to the suffering and to build a society” that honours the human person and the common good of all (FT 71). He argues that “no one solution, no single acceptable methodology, no economic recipe can be applied indiscriminately to all” (FT 167). Therefore, what is needed

is global solidarity and cooperation for more fraternal humanity.

Pope Francis condemns an attitude of contempt or indifference for the poor, as well as the mentality of those who feel threatened by social programs for those in need, thinking these could “edge them out” from their current social status (FT 73). He exhorts the wealthy of the world that they must “care for and cultivate something that [they] possess, in such a way that it can contribute to the good of all” (FT 143). According to him, “Neoliberalism simply reproduces itself by resorting to the magic theories of “spillover” or “trickle” – without using the name – as the only solution to societal problems” (cf. FT 168). He believes that the market cannot resolve every problem, and the theory of “spillover” does not resolve the inequalities (FT 168). He argues that poverty cannot be measured according to “criteria from the past” but “must always be understood and gauged in the context of the actual opportunities available in each concrete historical period” (FT 21).

By quoting St. John Paul II’s encyclical *Centesimus Annus* no.35, Pope Francis also addresses the question of foreign debt and the fate of the developing countries: “the fundamental right of peoples to subsistence and progress” [...] is at times severely restricted by the pressure created by foreign debt. [...] While respecting the principle that all legitimately acquired debt must be repaid, how many poor countries fulfil this obligation should not end up compromising their very existence and growth” (FT 126). By quoting his predecessor Benedict XVI, *Caritas in Veritate* no. 67, he argues that poorer countries need to be given a fair shake and “an effective voice in shared decision-making” (FT 138).

Pope Francis reminded us of the interdependence and shared responsibility of the whole human family. Therefore, he says that each country must feel responsible for people who are not born in it. Unfortunately, this Christian worldview today, according to him, is rejected by individualistic liberal approaches (cf. FT 163),

and he exhorts the Christians to reject nationalism which views society as merely the sum of coexisting interests (FT 163) and to welcome immigrants with love (FT 129-132).

Pope Francis argues that the right to live in dignity cannot be denied to anyone because rights are without borders, and no one can remain excluded according to his or her place of birth:

“No one, then, can remain excluded because of his or her place of birth, much less because of privileges enjoyed by others who were born in lands of greater opportunity. The limits and borders of individual states cannot stand in the way of this. As it is unacceptable that some have fewer rights by virtue of being women, it is likewise unacceptable that the mere place of one’s birth or residence should result in his or her possessing fewer opportunities for a developed and dignified life” (FT 121).

For the same reason, Pope Francis affirms that the “rights to free enterprise or market freedom” cannot “supersede the rights of peoples” and “respect for the natural environment”: “The right of some to free enterprise or market freedom cannot supersede the rights of peoples and the dignity of the poor, or, for that matter, respect for the natural environment, for “if we make something our own, it is only to administer it for the good of all” (FT 122; cf. LS 95).

13. Society that Fosters Inclusive Economy

The Catechism of the Catholic Church defines “common good” as “the sum total of social conditions which allow people, either as groups or as individuals, to reach their fulfilment more fully and more easily” (CCC 1906). It is in

tune with this teaching that Pope Francis spells out his vision of universal destination of created goods for a more fraternal society. His basic presumption for universal destination of created goods is that “the world exists for everyone” (FT 118), and he is very clear that the “privileges of some” over “the right of all” cannot be justified from “differences of colour, religion, talent, place of birth or residence”:

The world exists for everyone because all of us were born with the same dignity. Differences of colour, religion, talent, place of birth or residence, and so many others, cannot be used to justify the privileges of some over the rights of all. As a community, we have an obligation to ensure that every person lives with dignity and has sufficient opportunities for his or her integral development (FT 118).

Pope Francis restates the Church’s teaching of the “common destination of created goods,” which states that “if one person lacks what is necessary to live with dignity, it is because another person is detaining it” (FT 119). He believes that “if we accept the great principle that there are rights born of inalienable human dignity, we can rise to the challenge of envisaging new humanity. We can aspire to a world that provides land, housing and work for all” (FT 127). According to him, “Unless the rights of each individual are harmoniously ordered to the greater good, those rights will end up being considered limitless and consequently will become a source of conflicts and violence” (FT 111).

Pope Francis bases the Fathers of the Church to substantiate his arguments for the universal destination of created goods, and he quotes Saints John Chrysostom, Gregory the Great, Basil, Peter Chrysologus, Augustine etc.:

In the first Christian centuries, a number of thinkers developed a universal vision in their

reflections on the common destination of created goods. This led them to realize that if one person lacks what is necessary to live with dignity, it is because another person is detaining it. Saint John Chrysostom summarizes it in this way: “Not to share our wealth with the poor is to rob them and take away their livelihood. The riches we possess are not our own, but theirs as well”. In the words of Saint Gregory the Great, “When we provide the needy with their basic needs, we are giving them what belongs to them, not to us (FT 119).

Pope Francis also quotes St. John Paul II to validate his arguments on universal destination of created goods: “God gave the earth to the whole human race for the sustenance of all its members, without excluding or favouring anyone” (FT 120; cf. *Centessimus Annus* 31). He quotes St. John Paul II from his encyclical *Laborem Exercens* again: “The principle of the common use of created goods is the “first principle of the whole ethical and social order” [FT 120; cf. *Laborem exercens*, 19] and he also cites from the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Church by the Pontifical Council for Justice and Peace, “it is a natural and inherent right that takes priority over others” (FT 120). His proposal for the universal destination of goods “calls for an alternative way of thinking” (FT 127). He believes that if we are willing to dream together of a world firmly grounded on the dignity of all persons, “we can rise to the challenge of envisaging new humanity. We can aspire to a world that provides land, housing and work for all” (FT 127).

14. Society that Fosters Inclusive Property Rights

Pope Francis mentions that most of us live in unjust economies, even if we are not suffering ourselves. At the root of the disparity between the poor and rich, he says it is a “profit-based economic model” (FT 22). He reiterates John Paul II’s teaching in *Centesimus Annus*,

In fact, the purpose of a business firm is not simply to make a profit but is to be found in its very existence as a community of persons who in various ways are endeavouring to satisfy their basic needs, and who form a particular group at the service of the whole of society. Profit is a regulator of the life of a business, but it is not the only one; other human and moral factors must also be considered which, in the long term, are at least equally important for the life of a business (FT 35).

Pope Francis believes that market freedom and efficiency do not give place for disabled, the poor and the uneducated people because “If a society is governed primarily by the criteria of market freedom and efficiency, there is no place for such persons, and fraternity will remain just another vague ideal” (FT 109). He urges that the “right to private property” be accompanied by the “prior principle” of “subordination of all private property to the universal destination of the earth’s goods, and thus the right of all to their use” (FT 123). Therefore, he never disowns capitalism but asks for proper use of the wealth. He considers the right to property as a responsibility for the care for all: “All this brings out the positive meaning of the property right: I care for and cultivate something that I possess, in such a way that it can contribute to the good of all” (FT 143). Thus, private property can only be considered a secondary natural right, derived from the principle of the universal destination of created goods: “The right to private property can only be considered a secondary natural

right, derived from the principle of the universal destination of created goods (FT 120). But he complains that very often that this secondary right overrides the primary rights: “This has concrete consequences that ought to be reflected in the workings of society. Yet it often happens that secondary rights displace primary and overriding rights, in practice making them irrelevant” (FT 120).

Pope Francis also reiterates his teaching on “right to private property” from his earlier Encyclical *Laudato Si*: “the Christian tradition has never recognized the right to private property as absolute or inviolable, and has stressed the social purpose of all forms of private property” (FT 120; LS 93). He further refers to his earlier teachings to bring this point for: “The right to private property is always accompanied by the primary and prior principle of the subordination of all private property to the universal destination of the earth’s goods, and thus the right of all to their use”(FT 12; cf. LS 93; EG 189-190).

Indeed, Pope Francis considers “business activity is essentially ‘a noble vocation, directed to producing wealth and improving our world’” (FT 123). Moreover, he argues, a certain self-interest, including the taking of profit, is not repugnant to the moral purpose of economic activity: “In God’s plan, each individual is called to promote his or her own development, and this includes finding the best economic and technological means of multiplying goods and increasing wealth” (FT 123). He reminds us of our shared responsibility to care for the other and to have a more fraternal sharing with those in need.

15. Society that fosters a Politics at the Service of the Common Good

Pope Francis calls for a “better kind of politics” to find solutions for global problems. According to him, a “better kind of politics” is one that places itself at the service of the common good (FT 180). In the context of migration and refugee issues, he writes, “states are not able, on their own, to implement adequate solutions, ‘since the consequences of the decisions made by each inevitably has repercussions on the entire international community’” (FT 132). He reiterates that “politics must not be subject to the economy,” an appeal that he has made in his previous encyclical, *Laudato Si* (LS 189): “Here I would once more observe that “politics must not be subject to the economy, nor should the economy be subject to the dictates of an efficiency-driven paradigm of technocracy” (FT 177). He calls for a model of social, political and economic participation “that can include popular movements and invigorate local, national and international governing structures with that torrent of moral energy that springs from including the excluded in the building of a common destiny” (FT 169).

Pope Francis considers a “better kind of politics” as “a politics which is far-sighted and capable of a new, integral and interdisciplinary approach to handling the different aspects of the crisis.”... a “healthy politics... capable of reforming and coordinating” (FT 177). He is convinced that “we cannot expect economics to do this, nor can we allow economics to take over the real power of the state” (FT 177); a politics that “guarantees a sustainable equality” which executes “welfare projects, which meet certain urgent needs” (FT 161). According to him, “Good politics will seek ways of building communities at every level of social life, to recalibrate and reorient globalization and thus avoid its disruptive effects” (FT 182). In this context, he calls for global governance for migration that can open up long-term projects (129-132).

16. Society that Fosters “Political love” for Universal Fraternity

Pope Francis’ call to universal fraternity demands a political and social order built on charity and a shared pursuit of the common good. By using the term “political love,” Pope Francis shows us that there is another way to approach public life and that we can use politics to serve the common good without excluding anyone. According to him, political love is not unrealistic, for he says, “Recognizing that all people are our brothers and sisters, and seeking forms of social friendship that include everyone, is not merely utopian. It demands a decisive commitment to devising effective means to this end. Any effort along these lines becomes a noble exercise of charity” (FT 180). The “political love” that Pope Francis is asking is, in fact, a practical love, that is a “social love” (FT 183), a term that he borrows from John Paul II’s Encyclical *Redemptor Hominis* (RH 15). Political charity is also a spirit of openness to everyone as he articulates: “Government leaders can help to create” a beautiful polyhedral reality in which everyone has a place” (FT 190).

In contrast to populism that exploits the vulnerable and liberalism that serves the interests of the powerful (FT 155), Pope Francis says that political charity seeks the common good and help for those left behind (FT 165). According to him, we must seek “an integral human development that goes beyond ‘the idea of social policies being a policy for the poor, but never with the poor and never of the poor, much less part of a project that reunites peoples’” (FT 169). He proposes this as the norm for the international community, “where subsidiarity and solidarity work together in a complementary way” (FT 175), and therefore, he says that we must look for a political love that seeks “new ways of approaching the problems of today’s world, of profoundly renewing

structures, social organizations and legal systems from within” (FT 183).

Pope Francis explains that “political charity” is vital for a just and fair society:

There is a kind of love that is “elicited”: its acts proceed directly from the virtue of charity and are directed to individuals and peoples. There is also a “commanded” love, expressed in those acts of charity that spur people to create more sound institutions, more just regulations, more supportive structures (...). It is an act of charity to assist someone suffering, but it is also an act of charity, even if we do not know that person, to work to change the social conditions that caused his or her suffering (FT 186).

According to Pope Francis, social charity is more than just good intentions (FT 185), but a commitment to solidarity with our sisters and brothers: “It is an act of charity to assist someone suffering, but it is also an act of charity, even if we do not know that person, to work to change the social conditions that caused his or her suffering” (FT 186). Political love is practised in sacrifice for those in greatest need, and therefore, it does not become “a soulless pragmatism” (FT 187), and it looks for “fruitfulness” against “results”: “what is important is not constantly achieving great results... It is truly noble to place our hope in the hidden power of the seeds of goodness we sow, and thus to initiate processes whose fruits will be reaped by others” (194-195).

In chapter three, titled “Envisaging and Engendering an Open World”, Pope Francis presents love as “universal dimension” (FT 83) for “envisaging and engendering an open world” (FT 87). He explains it quoting St. Thomas Aquinas that “love made possible by God’s grace as a movement outwards towards another,

whereby we consider ‘the beloved as somehow united to ourselves’” (FT 93). He affirms the power of love towards universal communion, saying that true love “impels us towards universal communion... By its very nature, love calls for growth in openness and the ability to accept others as part of a continuing adventure that makes every periphery converge in a greater sense of mutual belonging” (FT 95). He says that “the spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love,” (FT 92) but “some believers think that it consists in the imposition of their own ideologies upon everyone else, or a violent defence of the truth, or impressive demonstrations of strength” (FT 92). He never forgets to remind us of our responsibility of love: “All of us, as believers, need to recognize that love takes first place: love must never be put at risk, and the greatest danger lies in failing to love” (FT 92). Therefore, what is needed is a “universal love” that promotes the dignity of every human being (FT 106), and the value of solidarity (FT 114). Pope Francis says that it is love, Gospel love, “that impels us towards universal communion” (FT 95).

17. Society that Fosters a Global Network for a Fraternal Society

Pope Francis calls for a “new network of international relations” to ensure “the fundamental rights of people to subsistence and progress” (FT 126), a theme that he already dealt with in LS 51:

We are really speaking about a new network of international relations, since there is no way to resolve the serious problems of our world if we continue to think only in terms of mutual assistance between individuals or small groups. Nor should we forget that “inequity affects not only individuals but entire countries; it compels

us to consider an ethics of international relations (FT 126; cf. LS 51).

Taking the COVID-19 pandemic situation and our failure to handle it, Pope Francis says that we need are new models that focus on promoting human dignity and solidarity: He says: “the fragility of world-systems in the face of the pandemic has demonstrated that not everything can be resolved by market freedom” (FT 168). He is convinced that the common destination of the earth’s goods calls for a new way of understanding relations between countries:

This presupposes a different way of understanding relations and exchanges between countries. If every human being possesses an inalienable dignity, if all people are my brothers and sisters, and if the world truly belongs to everyone, then it matters little whether my neighbour was born in my country or elsewhere. My own country also shares responsibility for his or her development (FT 125).

Pope Francis also calls for more robust and more efficient organized international networking. According to him, the transnational nature of economic and financial sectors brings weakness of the power of nation-states: “The twenty-first century “is witnessing a weakening of the power of nation-states, chiefly because the economic and financial sectors, being transnational, tend to prevail over the political” (FT 172). It is therefore essential to devise stronger and more efficiently organized international institutions: “Given this situation, it is essential to devise stronger and more efficiently organized international institutions, with functionaries who are appointed fairly by agreement among national governments, and empowered to impose sanctions” (FT 172). Therefore, he urges to reform both of the international financial system and multilateral institutions such as the United Nations, saying it was vital for countries “to

establish shared goals and to ensure the worldwide observance of certain essential norms” (FT 174). By quoting Benedict XVI’s Encyclical Letter *Caritas in Veritate*, 67 Pope Francis says, “In this regard, I would also note the need for a reform of “the United Nations Organization, and likewise of economic institutions and international finance, so that the concept of the family of nations can acquire real teeth” (FT 173). According to the Pope, the UN must promote the force of law over the law of force by ensuring “tireless recourse to negotiation, mediation and arbitration” (FT 173).

18. Society that fosters Peace through Penitential Memory

Pope Francis asks us to cultivate a penitential memory to accept the past, not to cloud the future (FT 226). He encourages us to foster the opportunity for true reconciliation and forgiveness that honours the memories of past suffering and injustice by quoting the Message for the 2020 World Day of Peace: “We need to ‘keep alive the flame of collective conscience, bearing witness to succeeding generations to the horror of what happened,’ because that witness ‘awakens and preserves the memory of the victims, so that the conscience of humanity may rise up in the face of every desire for dominance and destruction” (FT 249). Forgiveness by those who have been harmed is the prophetic act of “break[ing] the vicious cycle; ... [and] halt[ing] the advance of the forces of destruction” (FT 251).

Pope Francis asserts that forgiveness and reconciliation are not passive. According to him, “reconciliation is a personal act”, and human evils like the Shoah and the atomic bombings must be remembered as symbols of the depths of human evil (246-247). He firmly believes that the value and

meaning of forgiveness should not be at the expense of renouncing our own rights: “loving an oppressor does not mean allowing him to keep oppressing us, or letting him think that what he does is acceptable. On the contrary, true love for an oppressor means seeking ways to make him cease his oppression” (FT 241). He affirms that “authentic reconciliation does not flee from conflict, but is achieved in conflict, resolving it through dialogue and open, honest and patient negotiation” (FT 244). He also emphasizes the inherent relationship between truth, justice and mercy: “Truth, in fact, is an inseparable companion of justice and mercy” (FT 227).

By quoting *Caritas in Veritate* 71-72, Pope Francis says that peace is not a product that can be manufactured through skill and technological know-how (FT 231). He says that peace requires an enduring commitment: “It is a patient effort to seek truth and justice, to honour the memory of victims and to open the way, step by step, to a shared hope stronger than the desire for vengeance” (FT 226). He compares the peace process with a “craft” in which everyone must do his or her part and whose task is never finished “a never-ending task” (FT 232). He further says that peace making process is a tireless commitment to restoring the dignity of every human person, especially of those who are often overlooked or ignored:

For peace “is not merely absence of war but a tireless commitment – especially on the part of those of us charged with greater responsibility – to recognize, protect and concretely restore the dignity, so often overlooked or ignored, of our brothers and sisters, so that they can see themselves as the principal protagonists of the destiny of their nation (FT 233)

According to Pope Francis, peace is, fundamentally, a process: “There is no end to the building of a country’s social peace; rather, it is an open-ended endeavour, a never-ending task that demands the commitment of everyone and challenges us to work

tirelessly to build the unity of the nation” (FT 232). Peacemaking is also a never-ending process and an “a real and lasting peace will only be possible on the basis of a global ethic of solidarity and cooperation in the service of a future shaped by interdependence and shared responsibility in the whole human family” (FT 127).

The so-called peace, according to Pope Francis, is merely an “apparent peace” created by politicians who silence the cry of the poor with promises of money but who do nothing to end the evil of inequality (EG 218, FT 236). He reminds us that “Those who work for tranquil social coexistence should never forget that inequality and lack of integral human development make peace impossible (FT 235).

19. Society that Rejects War and Conflicts

Pope Francis not only condemns war but also considers it as a “failure of politics” (FT 261). According to him, war is a “constant threat” that represents “the negation of all rights” (FT 257), the “failure of politics and humanity,” “a shameful capitulation” before the forces of evil” (FT 261). He is convinced that total elimination of nuclear weapons is a moral and humanitarian imperative: “the ultimate goal of the total elimination of nuclear weapons becomes both a challenge and a moral and humanitarian imperative” (FT 262). He is convinced that the most dreadful casualty of war is “the human family’s innate vocation to fraternity” (FT 26).

Pope Francis proposes a counterculture against war and military expenditures by offering a global effort to eradicate hunger in the world and favour development in the most impoverished countries: “With the money spent on weapons and other military expenditures, let us establish a global fund that can finally put an end to hunger and favour development in the most impoverished countries so that their citizens will

not resort to violent or illusory solutions, or have to leave their countries to seek a more dignified life” (FT 262).

While reflecting upon the moral legitimacy of just war, Pope Francis says, “it is easy to fall into an overly broad interpretation of this potential right. In this way, some would also wrongly justify even “preventive” attacks or acts of war that can hardly avoid entailing “evils and disorders graver than the evil to be eliminated” (FT 258). He is convinced that wars can no longer be considered justifiable, as we cannot draw rational criteria: “it is very difficult nowadays to invoke the rational criteria elaborated in earlier centuries to speak of the possibility of a just war” (FT 258). In a puzzling footnote (fn. 242), he disagrees with St. Augustine regarding just war, the Church Father who developed the concept of just war, and he says that St. Augustine “forged a concept of ‘just war’ that we no longer uphold in our own day,” and thus he rejects the “rational criteria elaborated in earlier centuries” (FT 258). To substantiate his point, he quotes Pope St. John XXIII, who wrote in his encyclical *Pacem in Terris*, “It no longer makes sense to maintain that war is a fit instrument with which to repair the violation of justice.” He also strictly warns about how the traditional understanding of just war has been abused to justify every kind of war:

The Catechism of the Catholic Church speaks of the possibility of legitimate defence by means of military force, which involves demonstrating that certain ‘rigorous conditions of moral legitimacy’ have been met. Yet, it is easy to fall into an overly broad interpretation of this potential right ... In view of this, it is very difficult nowadays to invoke the rational criteria elaborated in earlier centuries to speak of the possibility of a ‘just war’. Never again war! (FT 258).

Pope Francis also criticizes war in the name of ‘preventive’ attacks saying, “some would also wrongly justify even

‘preventive’ attacks or acts of war that can hardly avoid entailing ‘evils and disorders graver than the evil to be eliminated’ (FT 258). He notes that “war can easily be chosen by invoking all sorts of allegedly humanitarian, defensive or precautionary excuses, and even resorting to the manipulation of information. In recent decades, every single war has been ostensibly ‘justified’” (FT 258) by its apologists.

Pope Francis categorically states that “violence has no basis in our fundamental religious convictions, but only in their distortion” (FT 282). He is convinced that we should not attempt to justify it “by invoking all sorts of allegedly humanitarian, defensive or precautionary excuses” (FT 258). Instead, we must understand the harsh reality that “every war leaves our world worse than it was before. War is a failure of politics and of humanity” (FT 261). Instead of getting entangled in “theoretical discussions,” he urges us to “touch the wounded flesh of the victims” (FT 261). According to him, war is an example of a broken solution to the conflict that has resulted in the “destruction in the fabric of national and global society” (FT 255). Instead of war, he asks us to foster kindness that “opens new paths where hostility and conflict would burn all bridges” (FT 224)

20. Society that Fosters Religious Harmony

Pope Francis highlights the role of religious communities in building a more fraternal world as outlined in the “Document on Human Fraternity” (FT 271). He says that our shared commitment to “witness to God” through word and action helps us to live with a “sincere heart” and “recognize one another as travelling companions, truly brothers and sisters” (FT 274). He is convinced that we have to focus on the message of peace that religions have in common, thereby recognizing that “universal communion with the entire

human family, [is] a vocation of all” (FT 277). He believes that all religions, “based on their respect for each human person as a creature called to be a child of God, contribute significantly to building human fraternity and defending justice in society” (FT 271). While religion can become a tool for violence and terrorism in the hands of unconscionable people, he invites people of all religions to return to that which are fundamental to all faith traditions: “worship of God and love for our neighbour” (FT 282).

Pope Francis calls for religious freedom in the journey towards fraternity and peace: “One fundamental human right must not be forgotten in the journey towards fraternity and peace. It is religious freedom for believers of all religions” (FT 279). Mutual respect and religious freedom challenge us to return to our sources and to work for a sustainable peace: “We believers are challenged to return to our sources, to concentrate on what is essential: worship of God and love for our neighbour, lest some of our teachings, taken out of context, end up feeding forms of contempt, hatred, xenophobia or negation of others. The truth is that violence has no basis in our fundamental religious convictions, but only in their distortion” (FT 282). He believes that the foundation of modern totalitarianism is the “denial of the transcendent dignity of the human person” and that violence “has no basis in religious convictions, but rather in their deformities” (FT 273). Pope Francis recalls that terrorism is not due to religion but to misinterpretations of religious texts and policies of hunger, poverty, injustice, and oppression (282-283).

According to Pope Francis, as believers in God, we are called to be true “people of dialogue,” to cooperate in building peace, not as intermediaries but as authentic mediators (FT 284). He believes that the Church cannot limit its influence to the private sphere and is responsible for participating in the public square to work for the common good (FT 276). According to him, being “catholic” means we are “called to take root in every place” and bring the wisdom of our tradition to the continual work for justice and integral human development (FT 278).

He cites the Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Common Coexistence, signed by him on February 4, 2019, in Abu Dhabi, with the Grand Imam of Al-Azhar, Ahmed Al-Tayyeb, to emphasize the fraternal call of different religious traditions: “In the name of God and of everything stated thus far, [we] declare the adoption of a culture of dialogue as the path; mutual cooperation as the code of conduct; reciprocal understanding as the method and standard” (FT 285).

Conclusion

As we have seen, *Fratelli Tutti* is Pope Francis’ reflection on human fraternity and universal brotherhood. He proposes universal fraternity and social friendship as antidotes for most of the social problems of contemporary society. *Fratelli Tutti* can be considered Pope Francis’ manifesto of the “social covenant” of human fraternity and social friendship for modern times. Here, he envisions a society that is open to all, includes all and values all. He dreams and invites us to dream together for a society that integrates everyone and fosters interrelatedness and interdependence. He visualizes a society that opens to the world’s needs and promotes a healthy neighbourhood in the world. He envisages a society that overcomes the evils of intolerance, social exclusion, racism, the culture of “throwaway”, and social media. He calls for a society that nurtures a culture of fraternity, dialogue, encounter, and tolerance. He foresees a society that raises human dignity and fosters the opportunity and dignity of human labour. He visualises a society that develops global ethics of solidarity and cooperation to find solutions for common issues. He dreams of a society that ensures an inclusive economy and assures property rights and the destination of the created goods for everyone in society. He calls for a better kind of politics at the service of the common

good, a politics that fosters “political love” and global network for a fraternal society. He envisages a society that realizes peace and reconciliation through penitential memory and forgiveness. He dreams a society that rejects war and conflicts; instead of a society that treasures integral growth and development of the nations and communities. Finally, he envisages a society that fosters religious harmony for building a more fraternal world. In short, *Fratelli Tutti* can be seen as a spiritual testament and social manifesto of Pope Francis for a better fraternal and universal brotherhood.

References

Francis, Pope. (2020). *Fratelli Tutti of the Holy Father Francis: On Fraternity and Social Friendship*. Cottbus, Germany HijezGlobal Press.

Pandikattu, K. 2005. *Reasons for Hope: Its Nature, Role, and Future*. Washington, D.C: Council for Research in Values and Philosophy.

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A QUICK KEY TO *Fratelli Tutti*

Shadows over the closed world (Ch. 1) are spreading everywhere, leaving injured people by the roadside, cast out and discarded. The shadows plunge humanity into confusion, loneliness, and desolation. When we come upon an injured stranger on the road (Ch. 2), we can assume one of two attitudes: we can pass by or we can stop to help. The type of person we are and the type of political, social or religious group we belong to will be defined by whether we include or exclude the injured stranger.

God is universal love, and as long as we are part of that love and share in it, we are called to universal fraternity, which is openness to all. There are no "others," no "them," there is only "us". We want, with God and in God, an **open world** (Ch. 3), a world without walls, without borders, without people rejected, without strangers. To achieve this world, we must have an **open heart** (Ch. 4). We need to experience social friendship, seek what is morally good, and practice a social ethic because we know we are part of a universal fraternity. We are called to solidarity, encounter, and gratuitousness.

To create an open world with an open heart, it is necessary to engage in politics, and a **better kind of politics** (Ch. 5) is essential. Politics for the common

and universal good. Politics that is “popular” because it is for and with the people. It is politics with social charity that seeks human dignity. The politics of men and women who practice political love by integrating the economy with the social and cultural fabric into a consistent and life-giving human project.

Knowing how to **dialogue** is the way to open the world and build social friendship (Ch. 6) which manifests an open heart and provides the basis for a better politics. Dialogue seeks and respects the truth. Dialogue gives rise to the culture of encounter, which becomes a way of life, a passionate desire. Whoever dialogues is generous, recognizing and respecting the other.

But it is not enough just to engage in encounter. We have to face the reality of the injuries of past mis-encounters, and so we have to establish and walk the **paths of re-encounter** (Ch. 7). We need to heal the wounds, which requires seeking and offering forgiveness. To forgive is not to forget. We need to be daring and start from the truth—the recognition of historical truth—which is the inseparable companion of justice and mercy. All this is indispensable for advancing towards peace. Conflict is inevitable on the road to peace, but violence is inadmissible. That is why war is a recourse that must be rejected, and the death penalty a practice that must be eliminated.

The different religions of the world recognize human beings as God's creatures. As creatures, we are in a relationship of fraternity. **The religions** are called to the **service of fraternity in the world** (Ch. 8). In dialogue and with hearts open to the world, we can establish

social friendship and fraternity. In our openness to the Father of all, we recognize our universal condition as brothers and sisters. For Christians, the wellspring of human dignity and fraternity is in the Gospel of Jesus Christ, and that is what inspires our actions and commitments. This path of fraternity also has a Mother called Mary.

Faced with those injured by the shadows of a closed world and still lying by the roadside, we are invited by Pope Francis to make our own the world's desire for fraternity, starting with the recognition that we are “*Fratelli tutti*”, **brothers and sisters all**.

<https://www.usccb.org/resources/02-%20Quick%20Key%20to%20FRATELLI%20TUTTI%20-%20EN.pdf>

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Am I Truly the Brother of All? The Challenge of Paradoxical Responsibility

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Abstract: This is a study of the need for a peaceful and fraternal resolution of the world crisis we are in. It argues against any confrontational resolution of the conflict. Literature and literary minds see the issue as fratricidal way of domination and subjugation. The clash of civilisations simply another name of colonisation. We look for a human resolution which is ethical and of mutual respect and understanding. Pope Francis as spiritual leader is presenting the only alternative of human initiative of being an initiator which is that dialogue and fraternity.

Keywords: Barbarians, Civilizations, Christianity, Islam, Conflict and Conversation, Responsibility, *Fratelli Tutti*.

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1. Waiting for the Barbarians

In *Waiting for the Barbarians* (1980), J. M. Coetzee interrogates the foundations of imperial states by highlighting the differences from the barbarians that the anonymous Empire maintains. It is simply a parable of modern nations. This is true not only nations but even groups of ethnic, religious and caste identities. Coetzee's novel helps us in participating in resistance literature and critiquing imperialism. Said interpreting the novel says: "... narrative is crucial to my argument here, my basic point being that stories are at the heart of what explorers and novelist says about strange regions of the world; they also become the method colonized people use to assert their own identity and the existence of their own history. The main battle in imperialism is over land, of course, but when it came to who owned the land, who had the right to settle and work on it, who kept it going, who won it back, and who now plans its future—these issues were reflected, contested, and even for a time decided in narrative" (Said 1994: xii-xiii). Coetzee is questioning the bases of imperial identity. Such loose labels are clear when the magistrate who is the voice of conscience shifts the label —enemy, and implicitly —barbarian. The imperial perceptive on the other who is not one of same as its own is a view of enemy – barbarian. It is Manichaeic perceptive of the right against the wrong. It boldly asserts that, to be living in a world ruled by egoism, a world in which no one could feel the human element as the human element in others, [in which] each one [could feel it] immediately only in his own self." "Through torture, the Empire therefore tries to unmake the "voice," the expression of the "I" of the person. After this, the Empire can "reconstruct" it at pleasure, rewrite it according to its wishes and ... create them as its victims, controlling them in whatever it wants.

Once the voice is deconstructed, prisoners are left with just their injured body, and in this condition they become the slaves of their physical needs. Being left with just the body—what Descartes identified with the primary Other—prisoners then lack the element that supposedly distinguishes human beings from animals, and are finally turned into what the Empire has been waiting for: Barbarians and, in many cases of racist politics, subhuman beings” (Canepari-Labib 2005) The barbarian—is one who speaks a different language. Indeed, among the most identifiable marks of everyday foreignness are an accent, a mismanaged idiom, an alterity in expression: language bears a primary relation to foreignness. The magistrate tells the colonel, “Those pitiable prisoners you brought in—are they the enemy I must fear? Is that what you say? You are the enemy, Colonel! ‘I can restrain myself no longer. I pound the desk with my fist. You are the enemy, you have made the war, and you have given them all the martyrs they need—starting not now but a year ago when you committed your first filthy barbarities here! History will bear me out!’” (Coetzee 1999: 112). He is a voice of something different. “To the objectivism of war we oppose a subjectivity born from the eschatological vision” (Levinas 1969: 25). The tasks which face the human apparatus at the turning points of history cannot be solved by optical means—that is, by contemplation alone. For Levinas, there can be no end in sight—until this moral lucidity becomes the vigilance of a revolutionary messianic consciousness that finally breaks the spell of fatality, the “truth of being” operative in the triumph of the logic of identity, the ideology of totality and the rule of a cold objectivity (Levinas 1969: 21). And yet, even when we take seriously the unusual eschatology invoked here, between the thought of “an equitable life” and the thought with which John Rawls concludes *The Theory of Justice*, there can be only—as Kafka said of the Messiah’s intervention—the slightest difference. “The perspective of eternity is not a perspective from a certain place beyond the world, nor the point of view of a transcendent being; rather it is a certain form of thought and feeling that rational

persons can adopt within the world. And having done so, they can, whatever their generation, bring together into one scheme all individual perspectives and arrive together at regulative principles that can be affirmed by everyone as he lives by them, each from his own standpoint. Purity of heart, if one could attain it, would be to see clearly and to act with grace and self-command from this point of view” (Rawls 1978: 587).

2. The Clash of Civilizations

“The fundamental source of conflict in this new world will not be primarily ideological or primarily economic. The great divisions among humankind and the dominating source of conflict will be cultural. Nation states will remain the most powerful actors in world affairs, but the principal conflicts of global politics will occur between nations and groups of different civilizations. The clash of civilizations will dominate global politics. The fault lines between civilizations will be the battle lines of the future” (Huntington 1993: 22-49). The Clash of *Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order*, Huntington stated that, “this book is not intended to be a work of social science. It is instead meant to be an interpretation of the evolution of global politics after the Cold War. It aspires to present a framework, a paradigm, for viewing global politics that will be meaningful to scholars and useful to policymakers” (Huntington 1996: 13). Huntington’s “clash of civilizations” argument for electoral gain, what, more generally, has become of Huntington’s prophesy of civilizational conflicts between blocs of culturally-defined states? Huntington discussed two civilizational conflicts which he thought would be of great importance in post-Cold War international relations: fights between “Islam” and the West, and between China and the West. Huntington’s claim was not only that the West would be in conflict with “core” states of the Muslim world, such

as, potentially, Pakistan, Egypt Saudi Arabia, and Iran, but would also be at loggerheads with China, the “Sinic” civilization “core” state. Huntington would claim that the Muslim world “lacks the core political values that gave birth to representative democracy in Western civilization: separation of religious and secular authority, rule of law and social pluralism, parliamentary institutions of representative government, and protection of individual rights and civil liberties as the buffer between citizens and the power of the state.” Islamophobia has been growing since the early 1990s, exacerbated by 9/11 specifically and fears of Islamist terrorism generally. Islamophobia can be found across society but is increasingly evident in the right wing political parties across the globe. The underlying problem for the West is not Islamic fundamentalism. It is Islam, a different civilization whose people are convinced of the superiority of their culture and are obsessed with the inferiority of their power. It is the West, a different civilization whose people are convinced of the universality of their culture and believe that their superior, if declining, power imposes on them the obligation to extend that culture throughout the world. These are the basic ingredients that fuel conflict between Islam and the West. The right figures such as Gert Wilders in The Netherlands and Marine Le Pen in France. They claim that Europe’s Muslim immigrants pose a clear and persistent threat to “European” traditions of tolerance, freedom, and democracy. Everywhere in Europe such tendencies grow. The clash of civilizations paradigm is today helpful in explaining and accounting for electoral gains of right-wing populist politicians in various Western countries, including the USA, Hungary, Poland, and Slovenia. The new European right-wing populism has thus succeeded in rhetorically reconciling Christianity and secularism as markers of a claimed “civilized” identity, while simultaneously merging Islam and specific “Oriental” ethnic features as key signs of barbarism.

3. The Myth of 'The Clash of Civilizations'

- i. The notion that civilizations are monolithic and homogeneous and it is assumed the unchanging character of the duality between us and them. Huntington defines Islamic civilization reductively, as if what most matters about it is its supposed anti-Westernism. It doesn't matter to him that Muslims have other things to do than to think about the West with hatred, how to destroy the West, bomb it and destroy the whole world really.
- ii. There is blind assumption that Islam has never modernized, that it never separated between Church and State, that it's incapable of understanding other civilization, all of them complete untruths. Of course the Arabs, Muslims have travelled well before the Europeans in the East, in Africa, and in Europe and were great discoverers of other civilizations well before Marco Polo and Columbus. For him Islam, Confucianism, and the other five or six civilizations, Hindu, Japanese, Slavic, Orthodox, Latin American and African that still exist, are separate from each other and consequently potentially in a conflict, which he wants to manage, not resolve. He writes therefore as a crisis manager.
- iii. Is it wise to produce a simplified map of the world and then hand it to generals and civilian lawmakers as a prescription for first comprehending and then acting in the world? Doesn't it mobilize nationalist passions and therefore nationalist murderousness? Shouldn't we be asking the question, to mitigate or to aggravate the likelihood of conflict?
- iv. There is colonising mentality. Perhaps the most famous of such devices is French notion of the civilizing mission a notion underlying which is the idea that some races and cultures have a higher aim in

life than others. This gives the more powerful, the more developed, the more civilized, the higher, the right to colonize others, not in the name of brute force, or plunder.

- v. The conquest of the Earth mentality which mostly means the taking it away from those who have a different complexion, a slightly flatter noses than ourselves is not a pretty thing, when you look into it too much. What redeems it, is the idea. An idea at the back of it, not a sentimental pretence but an idea, and an unselfish belief in the idea, something you can bow down before and sacrifice to. Where is our ethical or spiritual calibre?

- vi. The Clash of Civilization argument completely forgets the counter-culture in the mainstream or official cultures. There are dissenting or alternative, unorthodox, heterodox, strands that contain many anti-authoritarian themes in them that are in competition with the official culture. No culture is understandable without some sense of this ever-present source of creative provocation from the unofficial to the official. To disregard the sense of restlessness in the West, in Islam, in Confucianism within each culture and to assume that there's complete homogeneity between culture and identity, is to miss what is vital and fertile in culture. To emphasize the differences between cultures is completely to ignore the literally unending debate about defining the culture or civilization within those civilizations including western ones. These debates completely undermine any idea of a fixed identity and hence the relationships between identities. What culture today, whether Japanese, Arab, European, Korean, Chinese, Indian, has not had long intimate and extraordinarily rich contacts with other cultures?

- vii. The work of man is only just beginning and it remains to conquer all the violence entrenched in the recesses of our passion and no race possess the monopoly of beauty, of intelligence, of force, and there's a place for all at the rendezvous of victory and what they imply. There are kinds of benign globalism already to be found for instance in the environmental movement, in scientific cooperation, in the women's movement, and the universal concern for human rights, in concepts of global thought that stress community and sharing over racial, gender or class dominance. It would seem that there are efforts to return the community of civilizations and incitements to wasteful conflicts and un-edifying chauvinisms and that seems to be exactly what we don't need.

4. The Measure of Our Responsibility

As humans, we come into the world as “*initium*, newcomers and beginners”; we are beginners accomplishing newness. This state of being-beginners is essential to the human condition, and by means of it we “take initiative, are prompted into action” (Arendt 1958: 177). “Unexpectedness” and “natality” and the call for newness and the expansion of meanings is to resist the pressure of fatality of politics and to envision creative ways of engaging with new generations in the concrete and crucial practice of coming into the world. This is what Pope Francis does in his encyclical *Tutti Fratelli*. He is entering history to change history of civilizational hatred to a call to a civilisation of cooperation, dialogue and fraternity.

It is a dreadful evil when a man measures his behaviour to his fellow humans. It is as if he were always manipulating weights and measures. Plato told us that God is man's measure. “For the little humanity that adorns the earth, a relaxation [relâchement] of essence . . . is needed: in the just

war waged against war to tremble or shudder at every instant because of this very justice. This weakness is needed. This relaxation of virility without cowardice is needed for the little cruelty our hands repudiate” (Levinas 1981: 185). Moreover, the “presence” of the other is “infinite”, and constitutes for me an “infinite” obligation. As “infinite”, this “presence” is also a certain “absence”, and consequently it exceeds all measure—not only my own, but all conceivable, all possible measures. Ethical life can only be a question, for Levinas, of “measuring oneself against the perfection of the infinite” (Levinas 1987: 58). “We must be human. We need eternity, for it alone provides our gestures room; and yet we know ourselves in cramped finality. We must, then, create an infinity within these barriers, since we no longer believe in boundlessness” (Rilke 1977: 37).

The measure Pope Francis presents is not a doctrine but a story. The story of the Good Samaritan is constantly being repeated with ever new interpretations. “All of us have in ourselves something of the wounded man, something of the robber, something of the passers-by, and something of the Good Samaritan” (FT69). It is through the story the future is foreseen as an insight. It is fundamental metaphor. “Metaphor remains, in all its essential characteristics, a classical philosopheme” wrote Derrida (1982: 219). It is his 'White Mythology'. A natural explanation of this is that metaphor is uniquely paradoxical, and uniquely disturbing to philosophy. “We can see this clearly as social and political inertia is turning many parts of our world into a desolate byway, even as domestic and international disputes and the robbing of opportunities are leaving great numbers of the marginalized stranded on the roadside.” (FT 71)

What we imagine we become, is our world facing a great concern of the “clash of civilizations”? If we imagine we become, are we people of different cultures which hate, insult, and slaughter each other, and struggle to protect our own interests (think of the Rwanda genocide). Surely, this is the reason why Samuel Huntington said in his article *The Clash of Civilizations and the*

Remaking of World Order: “Nation states are and will remain the most important actors in world affairs, but their interests, associations, and conflicts are increasingly shaped by cultural and civilizational factors.” But can we imagine the world differently? The totally new that the Pope initiates is that the essential thing was that our way of life was the most true, good, beautiful, and efficient, and that the beliefs, values, and practices of others, insofar as they are different from ours are not false, shameful, unpleasant and irrational. This is bias and myth from which we have to free ourselves. We need a story that seeks to see the affairs of the global world “with the eyes of others” uniting historians from various parts of the world.

The pope is joining the world religions which is positive step to address the world problems. There is positive thinking which is not an attitude ruled by egoism, a world in which “no one could feel the human element as the human element in others, in which each one [could feel it] immediately only in his own self” (Rosenzweig 1971: 82). “The tasks which face the human apparatus at the turning points of history cannot be solved by optical means—that is, by contemplation alone. They are acquired gradually by habit, under the tutelage of tactile reception” (Benjamin 1969: 240). The moral lucidity becomes the vigilance of a “revolutionary messianic consciousness that finally breaks the spell of fatality, the “truth of being” operative in the triumph of the logic of identity, the ideology of totality and the rule of a cold objectivity” (Levinas 1969: 21).

The Pope proposes an understanding which is a dimension of our “spiritual nature”. In this sense, human history is a spiritual work (Levinas 1990: 91). History as a relationship among human beings ignores a position of the I before the other [*l'autre*] in which the other remains transcendent with respect to me. I am not exterior to history, I do find in the

Other a point that is absolute with regard to history. History is worked over by the ruptures of history, in which a judgement is borne upon it. When man truly approaches the Other he is uprooted from history. But the “first question in the inter-human” is “the question of justice.” “The ethical order,” deriving its measure from the realm of messianic prophecy, “does not merely prepare us for the Divinity; it is the very accession to the Divinity. All the rest is dream” (Levinas 1990: 102). There is an anarchic responsibility which summons me from nowhere into a present time! And what if it is “the measure . . . of an immemorial freedom that is older than being, or decisions, or deeds?” “There is a paradox in responsibility, in that I am obliged without this obligation having begun in me, as though an order slipped into my consciousness like a thief But this is impossible in a consciousness, and clearly indicates that we are no longer in the element of consciousness” (Levinas 1981: 13).

Pope Francis is entering history not like Bernard of Clairvoix but like Francis of Assisi taking not the route of Crusade but a call to dialogue of communication in spirit and communion of human brotherhood. Bernard was the preacher of crusade while Francis was dialoguing even in the time of crusade. Extremist thinkers and terrorist activities are no more fictions they are among us. But there are also a lot of sensible men and women among us who want to live peacefully with all. Even within the Catholic Church Islamphobia is growing. Even though Catholics in Kerala had a quality of being cultured and fare minded even some laity and even clerics are coming out and start preaching hatred. The Pope’s ways are abandoned with dangerous communal hate speech. Providing insights on contemporary realities such as the COVID-19 pandemic and social media, the encyclical is still a very traditional document. Pope Francis makes reference to the Scriptures, Church Fathers, and thinkers as diverse as Aristotle, Thomas Aquinas, and Paul Ricoeur. He notes that while he writes from Christian convictions, he intends “to dialogue among all people of good will” (FT 6). In light of this, it’s not surprising that he manifests esteem for the wisdom of Rabbi Hillel (FT 59)

and Mahatma Gandhi (FT 286) and that he highlights the 2019 Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together that he signed with the Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb of Al-Azhar (FT 192 and 285). “History is worked over by the ruptures of history, in which a judgement is borne upon it. When man truly approaches the Other, he is uprooted from history” (Levinas 1969: 52). The perception oriented toward revelation and sacred language because God is at work in religions. The Last Judgement of God is decisive, but the judgement is of all the instants in time, when the living is judged. Whenever divine power enters into the secular world it breathes destruction, the breach of the totality. Each instant of historical time in which action commences is a birth and breaks the continuous time of history of violence and subjugation.

References

- Arendt, H. 1958. *The Human Condition*, Chicago, IL and London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Benjamin, Walter. “The Artwork in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction,” *Illuminations*, New York: Schocken.
- Canepari-Labib, Michela. 2005. *Old Myths—Modern Empires: Power, Language and Identity in J. M. Coetzee’s Work*, Peter Lang Publishing.
- Coetzee, J. M. 1999. *Waiting for the Barbarians*, New York: Penguin.
- Derrida, J. 1982. 'White Mythology', in his *Margins of Philosophy*, trans. A. Bass, Brighton: Harvester.
- Huntington, Samuel. 1993. “The Clash of Civilizations?” *Foreign Affairs*, Summer.
- Huntington, Samuel. 1996. *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order*. Simon and Schuster.

- Levinas, E. 1969. *Totality and Infinity. An Essay on Exteriority*, trans. by Alphonso Lingis, Pittsburgh: Duquesne University Press.
- Levinas, E. 1981. *Otherwise than Being or Beyond Essence*, trans. by Alphonso Lingis, The Hague/Boston/London: Martinus Nijhoff Publishers.
- Levinas, E. 1987. "Philosophy and the Idea of Infinity," *Collected Philosophical Papers*, 1 Martinus Nijhoff Publishers Dordrecht, Boston, Lancaste.
- Levinas, E. 1990. "Messianic Texts", *Difficult Freedom: Essays on Judaism*, translated by Sean Hand. Baltimore: John Hopkins University Press.
- Rawls, John. 1978. *The Theory of Justice*, Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Rilke, Rainer Maria. 1977. *Diaries of a Young Poet* (New York: W. W. Norton.
- Rosenzweig, Franz. 1971. *The Star of Redemption*, Notre Dame: The University of Notre Dame Press, 1971, Part I, Book 3.

Said, E. 1994. *Culture and Imperialism*. New York: Vintage.

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Being-with the Other: Critical Reflections in the Light of *Fratelli Tutti*

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Abstract: All relationships are castrated by abiding self-interest. Face to face relationships being mediated by teletechnologies, we have entered what Gilles Deleuze has described as societies of control. Capitalist leaven is unfortunately embedded in what we called friendship. Given this condition of humanity, the encyclical letter, *Fratelli Tutti* of Pope Francis is a welcome light in the dark atmosphere marked by hate and fear of the other. In the light of the encyclical, we consider the challenge to build borderless

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friendship through our answerability to the other. Jesus being the model of answerability to the Other, we consider the challenge to measure up to the measureless standard of His love.

Keywords: *Fratelli Tutti*, Answerable, Friendship, Good Samaritan, Other, Jesus Christ, Measureless.

All relationships are castrated by abiding self-interest. Face to face relationships being mediated by teletechnologies, we have entered what Gilles Deleuze has described as societies of control (Deleuze 2021). Capitalist leaven is unfortunately embedded in what we call friendship. Given this condition of humanity, the encyclical letter, *Fratelli Tutti* of Pope Francis is a welcome light in the dark atmosphere marked by hate and fear of the other. Heeding to the clarion call in the encyclical, this study attempts to study the politics of friendship in the light of the world of French thinker, Jacques Derrida and try do understand why Pope Francis is trying to reclaim the nobility of friendship. The first part of the study examines the call for a borderless friendship and explores new modes of belonging in the light imperative to be answerable to the Other. The next section tries to critically consider the complexities of the imperative of answerability to the other from the point of view of ‘answerability to’ and ‘answerability before’ and propose Jesus as our Model to the imperative of answerability to the Other. The final section examines the imperative of our faith to measure up to the measureless standard of the love of Jesus.

1. Borderless Friendship and Answerability to the Other

For a long time, human relations are under siege. Religious people have often concentrated more on the vertical, human-God relations while neglecting the inter-human as well human-cosmos relations. After Modernity, self-interest has become central in both politics and economics in our society (Conju. 2015). This has corrupted all human relations. We can notice how we give concessions to the ideals of inter-human sympathy, fairness and

love. Even Philosopher Immanuel Kant dismissed friendship in favour of abstract rational impartial rules of justice (Van Impe 2021). This is completely different from the manner in which Aristotle treated friendship as an ethical bond that holds together a city while its decay becomes the harbinger of civil war or tyranny.¹ Unfortunately, modern philosophy privatized friendship and ethical life in general and left room only for self-interest to dictate the public domain. Fortunately, thinkers like Jacques Derrida (2005) and Maurice Blanchot (1997) tried to bring the discussion on friendship back into the mainstream. We can also notice how Pope Francis also tried to bring friendship to the centre stage with his encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* (Francis 2020) and called us to reclaim the nobility of friendship and political acts.²

In the encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, while challenging us to open ourselves to the stranger (FT 56), we are faced with the curvature of the social space that is marked by walls of egoism, suspicion, indifference and hate (dark clouds) (FT 9-55). The Pope invites us to embrace borderless friendship amidst walls of separation that close us and our world (FT 3-8). The call to new forms of social friendship echoed in *Fratelli Tutti* indicates that friendship is never given in the present. It always remains in the promise. Its discourse is one of prayer and commitment that makes us open to new modes of belonging together. Friendship, therefore, enters the performativity of prayer³ where the modern self for itself turns into the Levinasian self that is answerable to the Other

¹ Aristotle teaches about friendship in *Nicomachean Ethics*. See Mulgan 2021.

² Hope completely abandon the conflictual model of politics that construes the political around friend and enemy. Mehring 2020.

³ Following Derrida John D. Caputo thinks that Friendship has a structure of prayer. See Caputo 2021.

(Murray 2021). This answerability to the Other is the ethical basis of friendship. The principle of answerability is universal as well as singular. As universal, it is 'answerability before' a law, nation, tradition, political community, faith community or tradition etc. This means we are answerable before the tribunal that represents or stands for the Other who is a singular Other. As singular, on the other hand, it stands for the imperative of the singular Other whom we face in a face to face mode. This imperative triggers a singular encounter that enables us 'to be answerable to' the singular Other. This is a characteristic of double affirmation or yes of Derrida (Sant 2017).

The Other is unnamed and unnameable both in Levinas and Derrida.⁴ Levinas teaches that this answerability occurs in the singular encounter with the other (Veling 2021). It asserts the absolute singularity and irreducibility of the other. Derrida teaches that this 'singular answerability to' the other easily dissolves in 'the answerability before' the one that represents the Other, the law or the political community (nation) that becomes the ultimate tribunal and therefore, our moral response then gets reduced to justice alone where justice is interpreted as being in accordance to the law (Dallymar 2005). The story of the good Samaritan, introduced by Pope Francis for our reflection in his encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* embodies the passage of the singular answerability dissolving into an 'answerability before' a law or tradition in the response of the Jewish priest and the Levite who ignore the ailing stranger and move to keep the law while we can also see how Jesus transgresses it through the good Samaritan who is the chief character in the parable. The good Samaritan remains submerged into the singularity of the encounter. He stays with the imperative that calls him to answerability to the wounded stranger and does not jump to the universal deduction that enables us to jump from the mode of being 'answerable to' to the mode of being 'answerable before'. This jump from 'being answerable to' through a singular encounter that stays in the moral realm

⁴ The other is irreducible. See Willians 2021.

moves to the mode of 'being answerable before' the law or tribunal (Dallymar 2005). This also means that the singular moral response of love dies into justice that remains only in the realm of law and tradition. We need justice seasoned with love and mercy which is lived in the warmth of friendship/being-with. It requires a new affirmative politics that takes not the only the responsibility of the human family but also of each human person.

We can see how Jesus in public ministry transgresses the imperative of 'being answerable before' the law, and tradition and clearly chooses 'being answerable to' the person who is sick, afflicted by the devil, considered a sinner by society etc. He clearly transgresses the imperative that calls us to 'be answerable before' and embraces 'being answerable to' the singular call of the suffering Other. This is why Pope Francis challenges us to give up our excesses of individualism, consumerism, nationalism etc. His message is very important at this time of covid-19 as we can all be only safe by making each human being singularly safe. Only by converting ourselves to the culture of care that lives in friendly bonds, we can save ourselves and the world. In fact, paradoxically we have no choice but to get out of the traps of modernity and choose 'to be answerable to' and not 'answerable before'. In fact, we become 'answerable before' by 'being answerable to'.

It is by reaching out to the stranger that the Good Samaritan truly became just. It is by giving a singular response of love to the call of the other through the singular encounter that we can truly become just. This face to face bonding of friendship is the true way of being with the other. It is the way of being-with. Therefore, being answerable to the Other remains at the heart of friendship. This does not mean that we are thrown between the binary of 'being answerable to' and 'being answerable before' or we have to choose between love

(friendship) or justice. In fact, we become just through love. In the same way, we become 'answerable before' God, law, tradition, nation etc., only by being answerable to the suffering Other. We live the generality of law only by living it in a singular encounter. This means love/friendship and justice belong together. Being-with, therefore, challenges us to be answerable to the Other of our being-with. It is only through 'being answerable to' the Other of our being-with that we can become truly 'answerable before' God, law, tradition, nation etc.

2. Between 'Answering to and Answering Before'

Friendship lives in the coming. It mainly has its life breathe in the future. This makes way for growth in friendship. Pope Francis also does not look at friendship as simply given. It is both a gift and a task. We have to grow in friendship. He invites us to grow in forms of social friendships. The Holy Father opens the horizon of the growth of friendship. Here we do not just have to look at friendship as closeness, reciprocity, and commitment. Such a way of thinking friendship will put friendship on trial before the tribunal and castrate all friendship as it will find it wanting in terms of its already universally established forms. This puncturing of friendship introduces what Jacques Lacan calls lack or 'object a' (Kirshner 2021) which will then let the friendship grow. But lack produces a desire to satisfy oneself. Therefore, such a friendship is self-seeking and not self-giving. Christian friendship finds itself by giving itself. This means friendship that calls us to be faithful before the already set moulds of the ideality of friendship is a hidden egology in the Levinasian sense. Hence, following Derrida, we have the challenge to embrace the friendship in the becoming in its dynamically lived sense. Hence we may have to recognize the boundaries of separateness, distance, caution and vulnerabilities associated with the becoming or the making of friendship. This takes us to think of friendship not from the point of answerability before the universal ideal of friendship but from the point of the flesh and blood friendship living in the singular encounter. This means friendship

opens several ways of belonging to the friend (s) and does not simply close on to a set point which itself becomes a haunting ideal that calls the lived friendship to its criterion of justice.

This is why Derrida's thinking of friendship is impossible (Fernandez 2021). It opens us to the absolute horizons where we do not have any expectations from friends nor any closures or fixed destinies for friends to move. This means the promise of friendship in the Derridian sense is that there is no promise. Derrida takes us beyond our familiar either-or structure of thought and opens the playground for friendship to flower. This means he brings friendship to be answerable to the singular encounter with the Other. This, therefore, indicates that friendship to him is not answerable before the tribunal of the already set essence of friendship. He enables us to remain open to the coming of friendship by dynamically responding to the imperative of the singular Other. Therefore, friendship to Derrida (if we can say this) is brought under the tribunal of answerability to the call of the Other. This call of the Other is a moral call in the Levinasian sense. Therefore, this openness cannot mean that anything goes as friendship. The friendship that we are thinking of here is a moral bonding that awaits the coming of the good, true, love and just in the very becoming of friendship.

In the spirit of opening all closures, Derrida interrogates friendship as a fraternity. Friendship to him has no model. Fraternity genders friendship (Devere 2005). Hence, Derrida tries to dissociate all traces of gender, race, caste etc., from understanding friendship. To him, friendship lives and breathes in the becoming of friendship and hence cannot become closed. It opens itself to all its becoming possibilities in as much it responds to the ethical imperative of the Other in the Levinasian sense. Thus friendship stays beyond understanding, beyond comparison and beyond definition but

not beyond love. The measure of real love is to love without measure. Hence there is no one model of being friends. There are several models of being friends and each is unique, singular and incomparable. Each human person has a unique capacity for friendship. This means friendship to him is democratic. There are no boundaries to be friends.

We can trace a similar democratic spirit of social friendship in Pope Francis' encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, although it remains closed within our Christic horizon. Christic horizon is not a closed horizon. To some of us, it being catholic remains open to profoundly loving and emancipative forms of friendship. The word *Fratelli* could be said to be androcentric but it is not patriarchal and does not fraternize in a sense of male privilege but remains sufficiently open to include women into its embrace. Derrida does accept this openness as he points out that brotherhood comes from common parenthood. He thus underlines that there is a mother in the brother that open the notion to include women. Like always, he does not close its meaning to only inclusive semantics but stays open to those who may still find traces of male privilege in our male-dominated world. We too have to remain open to this possibility. Otherwise, we run the risk of invisibilizing women in our society running contrary to our Christian call. Therefore it is important that we become sensitive that although fraternization is inclusive of women, it can still neutralize the difference and uniqueness of women. Besides, fraternization of friendship may still exclude friendship between women and women and man and women. Thus, like the measure of love which is to love without measure, we may have to agree that we may have to live friendship measured up against its measurelessness.

We can find God in Jesus Christ the benchmark of this outpouring of love that stays beyond measure. We therefore as Christians are challenged to become the love that is measured up against its own measurelessness. Maybe we may have to grant that it is immeasurable divine silence that becomes the measure of our

love and friendship. We can trace that divine silence has become both audible, visible and palpable in Jesus Christ. We do find the sound, sense and vision of this measureless measure in the self-emptying kenosis in the mystery of incarnation, mission, passion, death and resurrection of Jesus. This is why 'being answerable to' is an invitation to love without measure while 'being answerable before' is love that is truncated and cannot live up to the measure of Jesus Christ that certainly measures up to its own measurelessness. Hence, the paradox is that we have the challenge that calls us 'to be answerable to' by 'becoming answerable before' the measure of Jesus Christ that is sacramentally present in the mystery of the Church.

3. Measuring up to Measurelessness of Love

How can we measure the immeasurable? The fact that we can love, we can receive and give love without measure point out that we live a love that is immeasurable. True love is to love without measure. This means love exceeds and transgresses all our measures. Love cannot be calculated, measured and be plain careful. Love is excess and beyond all measures. Love cannot follow the calculus of exchange. It does not belong to the market. It belongs to the absolute horizon where we do the impossible. The horizon of the possible is measurable and is closed. Such a closed horizon closes us. Therefore, the language of love cannot reflect the language of business and economics. Love cannot be an investment. True love loves without attaching any strings. Love calls us to be 'answerable to'. It is not so much 'answerable before' any given ideal of love. But this does not mean that anything can go as love. Love cannot harm the loved one. If it does, it cannot be love.

Love transgresses the economic model of exchange. Love follows an excessive model. It is the element of excess that gives power to the initial act of loving regardless of the

consequences. It belongs to the order that makes us ‘answerable to’ and not ‘answerable before’. Love that belongs to order that makes us ‘answerable to’ is an original and abundant gift and can be both extravagant and reciprocal. Our love is only ‘answerable before’ the excessive love of God. Perhaps it is in this meeting or comingling of being ‘answerable to and answerable before’ that there is a meeting point of the model of excess and the model of exchange.

One may raise the question that asks: can excess be exchanged? Excess cannot be exchanged. It produces excess. God gives us so that we give what we receive to others. God, therefore, gives through our giving. Our giving continues God’s giving. God’s giving produces its own economy of giving. Love being excessive is also one that produces its own economy of love where there is mutuality as well as simply loving without receiving. This means love does not have to be only reciprocal but carries its own impossibility. It carries its own reverse engineering when love fails to be love. This occurs when love fails to keep its promise and becomes unacceptable. Love is so precious that it carries its own impossibility within it. This is why love remains always in the coming, always in the promise. We are always in danger of transgressing as well as exceeding the algorithm of love (if there is any such a thing). Therefore, love embeds its own deconstruction within it. There is thus, dynamism and indeterminacy in love and stands beyond what Derrida calls the metaphysics of presence.

Love is an ethic of excess. Like love, friendship belongs to the ethic of excess. It calls us to be excessively responsible. We may find similar echoes of excessive responsibility in the encyclical letter of Pope Francis, *Fratelli Tutti*. There is an unconditional come or future anterior affirmation in friendship since there are only Christic openings or overflows. This is the excessive responsibility that calls us to continuously transform the becoming of friendship so that it always remains saturated into Christic modes of being human in the world. The Christic

dynamism in our friendship offers us room to continuously grow and exceed our previous levels of friendships. Christic modes of friendship can only exceed and have to exceed as we are called 'be answerable before' an inexhaustible measure of an unmeasurable model of Christ's Love lived on a daily basis by being 'answerable to' the call of Christ in the Other (creation and human).

This indicates that there is a double responsibility. The first is the one that calls us to be 'answerable to' Christ in the Other while the other is the one that calls to be 'to be answerable before' our Lord Jesus Christ. Our 'answerability to' overflows simultaneously into our 'answerability before' but we have the challenge to remain in what Levinas calls ethical saying and not merely the ethical said. The ethical said summons our ethical saying challenging us to live up to measure Christ's Love. To us, the ethical saying is imbued in the ethical said We do tilt towards the an-archy of the dynamism of 'answerability to' but we do not turn away from arche of our 'answerability before' Christ and His Church. We have the challenge to let the singularity of our ethical 'answerability' to Christ in the Other be soaked into our collective/ universal 'answerability before' Jesus Christ and His Church. The imperative of 'answerability to' the Other in Jesus Christ and the 'answerability before' Jesus and the Church has to be based on what the Pope calls the principle of capacity to love. It is through this principle of capacity to love that we can envisage an open world which leads us to go outside of ourselves with a heart open to the whole and find fuller existence in the Other. This means we need a better politics that renders no one useless and expendable. To build a world built on the spirit of friendship, the Holy Father exhorts us to eliminate war and nuclear arms and calls for the establishment of a global fund for the elimination of hunger with the money invested in the weapons (FT 225-286).

Conclusion

Our study examined the challenge to the politics of friendship in today's world. We have discovered that we all are drawn by the imperative of our answerability to the Other. We have to combine our 'answerability to' and 'answerability before' as we responds to this call of the other. Jesus being our model of our 'answerability to' the Other, we have the challenge to measure up to the measureless standard of his love.

Reference

- Blanchot, Maurice. 1997. *Friendship*, Trans., Elizabeth Rottenberg. Stanford: Stanford University Press, (1997).
- Caputo, John D. 2021. ' Good Will and Hermeneutics of Friendship', <https://www.artsrn.ualberta.ca/symposium/files/original/f5241bbd09634eec51b65d6aedb24c08.pdf>, accessed on 18/09/2021.
- Conju, Valentino. 2015. ' Self-interest and Modernity of Homo-economus', *International Journal of Social Economics*, <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IJSE-07-2015-0192/full/html>, accessed on 18/09/2021.
- Dallymar, Fred. 2021. 'Derrida and Friendship' <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/citedby/10.1080/13698239908403293?scroll=top&needAccess=true>, accessed on 24/09/2021.
- Deleuze, Gilles. 2012. 'Post-script on Societies of Control', https://cidadeinseguranca.files.wordpress.com/2012/02/deleuze_control.pdf accessed on 28/09/2021.
- Derrida, Jacques. 2005. *The Politics of Friendship*, Trans. George Collins (New York: Verso, 2005).
- Devere, Heather. 2005. *ACCESS Critical Perspectives on Communication, Cultural & Policy Studies* Vol. 24 (1 &

- 2) 75- 82https://pesaagora.com/access-archive-files/ACCESSAV24N12_075.pdf accessed on 24/09/2021.
- Fernandez, Michael Roland Flor. 2021. ‘Derrida’s Impossible Justice and Political possibilities of deconstruction’, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333671381_Derridas_Impossible_Justice_and_the_Political_Possibilities_of_Deconstruction, accessed on 24/09/2021.
- Francis, Pope. 2020. Encyclical letter , Fratelli Tutti, https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/encyclicals/documents/papa-francesco_20201003_enciclica-fratelli-tutti.html, accessed on 18/09/2021. Abbreviated as FT.
- Kirshner, Lewis. 2021. ‘Rethinking Desire : Object A in Lacanian Theory’. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/7915207_Rethinking_Desire_The_Objeto_Petit_A_in_Lacanian_Theor accessed on 24/09/2021.
- Mehring, Reinhard. 2020. ‘Carl Schmitt, friend-enemy distinction today’, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318075693_Carl_Schmitt's_friend-enemy_distinction_to accessed on 28/09/2021
- Mulgan, Richard. 2021. ‘The role of friendship in Aristotle’s Political theory’, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/13698239908403289?journalCode=fcrl>, accessed on 18/09/2021.
- Murray, Jeffrey W. 2021. ‘Bakhtinian Answerability and Levinasian Responsibility: Forging a Fuller Dialogical Communicative Ethics’, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/10417940009373163?journalCode=rsjc20>, accessed on 18/09/2021.

Sant, Janice. 2017. ‘ Ethics of Poetic Force: Jacques Derrida, Helene Cixous, Pau; Celan’, <https://orca.cardiff.ac.uk/107652/1/2017SantJPhD.pdf> accessed on 18/09/2021.

Van Impe, Stijn. 2021. ‘ Kant on Friendship’, [tps://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi= 10.1. 1.301.2403 &rep= rep1&type = pdf](https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.301.2403&rep=rep1&type=pdf), accessed on 18/09/2021.

Veling, Terry A. 2021. ‘For You Alone: Immanuel Levinas and Answerable Life’, [https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10. 1177 /1 030 570 X16 682527](https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1030570X16682527), accessed on 24/09/2021.

Willians, Raymond. 2021. *Otherwise than Being of J. M. Coetzee and Emanuel Levinas*, [ace.library.uq.edu.au/data/UQ_138912 /n33156343_ mphil_t oththesis.pdf?Expires = 1632459434& Key-Pair-Id=AP KAJK NBJ4MJ BJNC6NLQ & Signature= LDM4r HIDm~A 8KTW8uE](https://ace.library.uq.edu.au/data/UQ_138912/n33156343_mphil_t_oththesis.pdf?Expires=1632459434&Key-Pair-Id=APKAJKNBJ4MJBJNC6NLQ&Signature=LDM4rHIDm~A8KTW8uE) accessed on 24/09/2021.

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QUOTES FROM FRATELLI TUTTI

“Let us dream, then, as a single human family, as fellow travellers sharing the same flesh, as children of the same earth which is our common home, each of us bringing the richness of his or her beliefs and convictions, each of us with his or her own voice, brothers and sisters all” (FT 8)

“Instances of racism continue to shame us, for they show that our supposed social progress is not as real or definitive as we think” (FT 20).

“True, a worldwide tragedy like the Covid-19 pandemic momentarily revived the sense that we are a global community, all in the same boat, where one person’s problems are the problems of all. Once more we realized that no one is saved alone; we can only be saved together” (FT 32)

“We have the space we need for co-responsibility in creating and putting into place new processes and changes. Let us take an active part in renewing and supporting our troubled societies. Today we have a great opportunity to express our innate sense of fraternity, to be Good Samaritans who bear the pain of other people’s troubles rather than fomenting greater hatred and resentment” (FT 77)

“Solidarity finds concrete expression in service, which can take a variety of forms in an effort to care for others” (FT 115)

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Called to “Witness:” The Invitation of *Fratelli Tutti*

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Abstract: On October 3, 2020, Pope Francis issued the encyclical named *Fratelli Tutti* (*We Are All Brothers*) to urge the humanity to promote a universal aspiration toward fraternity and social friendship. In the final chapter of the encyclical, Pope Francis repeatedly appeals us to bear witness to God (Cf. FT § 274 § 276 § 280) and thereby to contribute to the formation of the universal friendship and solidarity. After one year, from 25 to 28 April 2021, Indian theological Association (ITA) discussed the theme “Credibility and Witness” in their 43rd annual conference. Earlier in the mission documents we oft found the repeated presence of the term ‘witness’. Therefore, the present article “Witness in *Fratelli Tutti*”

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tries to explore the role of witness in the encyclical FT while initiating a universal home of peace and love. Does witnessing life (of Christian) play a significant role to initiate a common home?

Keywords: Witness, Fraternity, Creation Theology, Evangelization, *Fratelli Tutti*.

Introduction

The latest encyclical of Pope Francis, namely *Fratelli Tutti* (*We Are All Brothers*), aims to promote fraternity and universal friendship. FT borrows the title of the “Admonitions 6” of Saint Francis of Assisi to address the brothers and sisters in our world to propose “a way of life marked by the flavor of the Gospel” (FT § 1, Assisi 2021). After analyzing this encyclical, we understand the role of ‘witness’ in bringing fraternity in this world. The term “witness” explicitly appears in many places in this documents (Cf. FT § 274 § 276 § 280).¹ The usage of ‘a way of life marked by the flavour of the Gospel’ points out that the encyclical demands a witnessing attitude from the People of God. In this sense, the encyclical is an urge to the People of God to bear witness to the love of God and thereby hold on to the universal friendship without any discrimination.

This article is an attempt to analyse the role of witness in forming universal friendship. The first part of the article describes the notion of “witness” and its characteristics.

¹ “[O]ur *witness* to God benefits our societies” (FT, § 274); “[A] family among families, this is the Church, open to bearing *witness* in today’s world, open to faith hope and love for the Lord” (FT, § 276); “It is also urgent to continue to bear *witness* to the journey of encounter between the different Christian confessions” (FT, § 280). The emphases are not part of the original text.

Afterwards, we come across a theology behind both fraternity and witness. Then, we will analyse the role of witness in forming a fraternal society on the basis of the encyclical FT. Different kinds of witness will be introduced here with the references from the encyclical FT. How does ‘witnessing life’ help in forming a universal brotherhood or “common home”? is the question that we address in this article.

1. What Is Witness?

Witness is ‘the first means of evangelization’ (Cf. EN § 41, RM §§ 42-43). It is one among many other methods of evangelization such as proclamation, inter-religious dialogue, inculturation, etc. The earliest mission documents used the term “witness” from a religious point of view where it means ‘an evidence of a person’s strong religious beliefs that they show by what they say and do in public’ (Witness 2021). Though we have a number of methods for proclaiming the Good News, ‘witness’ is a much appreciated method for initiating the process of evangelization. Indian Theological Association (ITA) recently had discussed the theme “Credibility and Witness” in its 43rd annual conference. This is an indication that witness has still the priority among different methods of evangelization along with the proclamation. In the final chapter of FT, namely “Religions at the Service of Fraternity in Our World”, one could find out explicit references of ‘witness’ and its practical role in building a common home. This section will reveal the features of the method of witness in evangelization on the basis of the Church documents.

a. Witness: First Means of Evangelization

The apostolic exhortation of Pope Paul VI, *Evangelii Nuntiandi* (EN), explains the importance of the witness of life. Pope Paul VI writes:

It is often said nowadays that the present century thirsts for authenticity. Especially in regard to young people it is said that they have a horror of the artificial or false and that they

are searching above all for truth and honesty. These “signs of the times” should find us vigilant. Either tacitly or aloud- but always forcefully- we are being asked: Do you really believe what you are proclaiming? Do you live what you believe? Do you really preach what you live? *The witness of life* has become more than ever an essential condition for real effectiveness in preaching (EN § 76, Emphasis added).

The Pope invite all of us to reflect on the authenticity of the lives that we live. By realizing ‘the signs of his time’, he asked the faithful to lead a witnessing life² because it has an important role in the mission of the Church.³ It is the primary means of evangelization. It is an essential condition for effective proclamation.

² The Greek verb used for witnessing is *martureo*, which means ‘to bear witness’ or ‘to be witness for something’. The verb *martureo* is found in 76 times in the Bible- 43 times in the Gospel of John and his Epistles, 4 times in the book of Revelation, 2 times in Synoptic Gospels, 11 times in the Acts of the Apostles and the rest in the Old Testament. In the Old Testament, witness is often used for legal testimony (Cf. Num 35:30; Deut 19:15, 18) or for something one has experienced or entrusted to one to testify. Cf. Namitha 2000: 109.

³ Christian witness is a witness to Christ who is the witness par excellence (Cf. Rev 1: 5, 3: 4). Christ is the model of all Christian witnesses. While living among people a radical Christian challenges other people with fundamental questions of the heart. Through the charity extended to all strata of people without discrimination, a Christian witness becomes more concrete and effective. Cf. Jerman 2008: 98-120.

Pope Paul VI writes again, “[F]or the Church, *the first means of evangelization* is the witness of an authentically Christian life, given over to God in a communion that nothing should destroy and at the same time given to one’s neighbour with limitless zeal” (EN § 41, Emphasis added. RM § 42). Here explicitly Pope mentions that witness of life is “the first means of evangelization” (RM § 42). This witnessing life makes possible communion with God and neighbour. Paul VI also mentions in his address to the Members of the *Consilium de Laicis*, “Modern man listens more willingly to bear witness than to teachers, and if he does listen to teachers, it is because they are witnesses” (Paul VI 1974). This statement also conveys the same emphasis as the other statements in EN. The new generation does not listen to a person if s/he does not live morally. In that sense, if the evangelizer do not witness Christ, her/his proclamation will become fruitless.⁴ Along with these documents, the decree of Vatican Council II, *Ad Gentes* (AG), mentions that life witnessing is “an obligation” (Cf. AG §11) for all Christians and is presented as the first means of evangelization. All these statements give importance to life-witnessing.

In FT, Pope Francis quotes, “if the music of the Gospel ceases to sound in our homes, our public squares, our workplaces, our political and financial life, then we will no longer hear the strains that challenge us to defend the dignity of every man and woman” (FT § 277).⁵ If the Gospel values do not live in us or in our own

⁴ “*The witness of life* is the only solid foundation of all whatever we do to proclaim the Kingdom of God. Through our celebration of Eucharist, we participate in the empowering memorial of Jesus’ death and resurrection. This mystery constantly calls us to die to ourselves and enables to live for others in truth, love and justice.” Cf. CBCI Consultation on Mission 1997: 274-304. The emphasis in the text is not part of the original text.

⁵ Quoted from *Ecumenical Prayer Service*, Riga, Latvia (24 September 2018): *L’Osservatore Romano*, (24-25 September 2018), 8; available from <https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2018/september/documents/papa->

circles, we do not have any credibility to demand it from others. Our indifference to the ills and evils is a hindrance for forming a common home of peace and solidarity. Our witnessing lives, on the other hand, motivate others to follow the acts of solidarity and love. Gradually, justice, peace and love will appear in the society. So, witness is primary means of spreading Christian values.

b. Witness: A Silent Proclamation

In *Apostolicam Actuositatem* (AA), a decree on the apostolate of the laity promulgated on 1965, Pope Paul VI writes, “The *witness of a Christian* life and good works done in a supernatural spirit have great power to draw men to the faith and to God” (AA § 6, Emphasis added). This text reminds us the “great power” of witness. Without any help of the modern communication media, a Christian can proclaim the Gospel of God silently. It is just through his/her life. Every single moment is a moment of evangelization in one’s life, if one bear witness to Christ through one’s life. No need of a fixed audience here. No need of formalities here. Simply one lives the Christian values through one’s own life.⁶

Life-witnessing is an economic and practical evangelization method. It does not cost financially anything to live Christian values. Even in different lands, where evangelization is publicly prohibited, this method can be adapted for bearing witness to Christ. In that sense, it is very much practical.

francesco_20180924_incontroecumenico-riga-lettonia.html; accessed on 6th November 2021; internet.

⁶ Here I do not neglect the role of the proclamation in the act of evangelization. But in a situation where people already knew Christ and have experienced the presence of His community (the Church), more than the proclamation the life-witnessing is necessary. This will bring more result in the evangelization.

How does it work as a method of evangelization? “Through this *wordless witness* [life-witnessing] these Christians stir up irresistible questions in the hearts of those who see how they live: why are they like this? Why do they live in this way? What is it that inspires them? Why are they in our midst?” (EN § 21, Emphasis added). These irresistible question help people to realize the worth of the Christian values and thereby the source of it, i.e., Christ. The encyclical FT is a social encyclical with lots of practical suggestions for forming a universal brotherhood. Pope Francis motivates the People of God to share the love of Christ to the poor and the afflicted through different ways understanding their struggles in the society. Dialogues (FT § 203 § 271), political pressurization for peace (FT § 258-260), social reformation (FT § 233-234), charitable works (FT §116), etc. are some ways. Here we bear witness to the Christian values. Such witness is a silent proclamation of the Good News and a very powerful and effective method of evangelization. So, it is primarily by her life and conduct that the Church evangelizes the world and form a common home.

c. Witness: A Pre-Requisite for Other Methods

In the *Catechism of the Catholic Church* (CCC), there are passages which speak about the importance of witness of life. In CCC § 2044, we read, “The fidelity of the baptized is a primordial condition for the proclamation of the Gospel and for the Church’s mission in the world. In order that the message of salvation can show the power of its truth and radiance before men, it must be authenticated by *the witness of the life* of Christians” (CCC § 2044, Emphasis added). Here in this section, the witness of life is considered as “the primordial condition”. In another document, *Redemptoris Missio* (RM), we read, “The witness of a Christian life is the first and irreplaceable form of mission” (RM § 42). Without pointing out some witnessing lives, how can one speak about “the Kingdom” values? Even before the proclamation of Jesus, He bore witness to God. At least we know more clearly from the scriptures that throughout His life, Jesus practised the

values which He preached. Because of this accompaniment of witnessing life, His proclamation was acceptable to the people. Like this each Christian has to live the values while proclaiming it.

If we take other different methods of evangelization, the witness of life has a primary role. For example, inter-religious dialogue is one of the methods of evangelization. But without any witnessing of Christian lives, how could we go for such a method? It is said that “Dialogue is not merely an exchange of ideas and views, but a specific mode of being and a way of life” (CBCI Consultation on Mission 1997: 296). Each dialogue has to be an exchange of witnessing lives. In FT, Pope Francis urges to involve in dialogue with the people who have different perspective of worldviews. Here he also demands us to bear witness to the love of the Father of all, before we engage in a dialogue with them (Cf. FT §169).⁷ An inter-religious dialogue becomes unsuccessful without a witnessing life. Inculturation is another method. Will it fulfil its aim without the witness of life? Will proclamation be a successful without witness of life? All these methods depend on the witness of life. So, we call life-witnessing a primordial condition for all other mission methods.

d. Witness: The Imitation of the Divine Master

Each Christian is a missionary in this world. He/she bears witness to Jesus Christ through life. Pope John Paul II, in one of his apostolic exhortations, motivates the people in Asia to lead a witnessing life. He writes, “Every situation is an opportunity for Christians to show forth the power which the truth of Christ has become in their lives. Therefore,

⁷ Pope writes here “we must move beyond the idea of social policies as being for the poor but which are never with the poor” (FT, § 169).

inspired by the many missionaries who bore heroic witness to God's love among the peoples of the continent in the past, the Church in Asia tries now to witness with no less zeal to Jesus Christ and his Gospel" (*Ecclesia in Asia*, henceforth abridged as EA § 24). Each single moment in one's (Christian's) life is an occasion to witness Christ. With much enthusiasm, each Christian has to bear witness to Christ in their different situations. Here one has to follow the example of missionaries who lived before us and Jesus, the source of life-witnessing. In this sense, life-witnessing is an imitation of the divine master, Jesus.

How do Christians bear witness to Christ? In *the Catechism of the Catholic Church* § 2046 one reads, "By living with the mind of Christ, Christians *hasten the coming of the Reign of God*, a kingdom of justice, love, and peace. They do not, for all that, abandon their earthly tasks; faithful to their master, they fulfil them with uprightness, patience, and love" (CCC § 2046). This text illustrates that by imitating Christ in words and deeds, one can bear witness to Him. In their living situation, they have to be like "another Christ." The qualities of Jesus become qualities of each Christian here. The "Kingdom" values such as uprightness, patience, love, *etc.*, becomes values of each person who bear witness. Through one's life witness, each Christian makes the presence of "Kingdom" nearer. One has to follow the laws of Christ. The law of Christ is nothing but the law of love. Each Christian has to love his neighbors and God. This would be the ultimate principle even to witness Christ.

Another passage of *the Catechism of the Catholic Church* § 2471, explains the witnessing model of Jesus as a perfect model before us and it also motivates us to bear witness courageously. The text states, "Before Pilate, Christ proclaims that he "has come into the world, to bear witness to the truth." The Christian is not to "be ashamed then of testifying to our Lord." In situations that require witness to the faith, the Christian must profess it without equivocation, after the example of St. Paul before his judges. We must keep "a clear conscience toward God and toward men""

(*Ibid.* § 2471). St. Paul and all other martyrs⁸ of the Church bore witness to God through their courageous life-witnessing in difficult situations. All these models are centered on the life-witnessing model of Christ on the Cross at Calvary. Here in Jesus’s crucifixion, one sees the culmination and source of life-witnessing. All other life-witnessing models participate in this model of Christ. By quoting three New Testament texts, namely, Jn 18: 37; 2 Tim 1:8 and Acts 24:16, the CCC explain that the mission of Christ and that of each Christian is the same, namely, to bear witness. In FT, Pope Francis urges us to follow the model of Christ to forgive others (Mt. 18: 22-35, FT § 238), to help the needy (FT § 81), to practice gratuitous love (FT § 139, Mt 5: 45; 6: 34; Mt 10:8), etc. Christ bore witness to God and the Christians bear witness to God through Christ, the Son of God. Each Christian has to imitate his/her Divine Master.

e. Witness: A Language of Evangelization

Language is the medium of communication. If we are not competent enough in the language with which we communicate, our conversation may fail to achieve its goal. Like this, in the field of evangelization a Christian uses a language of life. It is through one’s life, which is the medium for evangelization, that one communicates Christian values to others. In *Ad Gentes* (AG) one reads, “All Christians by the example of their lives have an obligation to manifest the new man which they put on in baptism” (AG § 11). Through

⁸ Pope Francis on 21st June 2017 at the time of General Audience preached that “a great cloud of witnesses” (Heb 12:1) strengthen us to bear witness. Here he speaks of the lives of saints and their companionship with us. Cf. *General Audience*; available from https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/audiences/2017/documents/papa-francesco_20170621_udienza-generale.html; accessed on 5th November 2021; internet.

our lives, we bear witness to Christ whom we put on in baptism. That means, the medium of life has an important role in fulfilling our obligation which we received through our baptism.

If we have a good language competence we can communicate well; if not, our communication may bring the opposite effect. Similarly if the life of a Christian, the medium of evangelization, is not of a good model, the witnessing that the person brings in his community is something opposite to what Jesus wants. “The presence of Christians among other religious groups should be one that is animated by that love with which we are loved by God” (AG § 12). This “competent” language of evangelization, i.e. witness of life, communicates the loving and self-giving nature of God to others. In *Catechism of the Catholic Church* § 2472, one reads,

The duty of Christians to take part in the life of the Church impels them to act as witnesses of the Gospel and of the obligations that flow from it. This witness is a transmission of the faith in words and deeds. Witness is an act of justice that establishes the truth or makes it known. All Christians by the example of their lives and the witness of their word, wherever they live, have an obligation to manifest the new man which they have put on in Baptism and to reveal the power of the Holy Spirit by whom they were strengthened at Confirmation (CCC § 2472, Witness 2018).

As the text explains, the faith is transmitted through our words and deeds. Through our good deeds and words, we are supposed to convey the message of Jesus to all people. This is the mission of each Christian which s/he receives by the sacrament of baptism. In FT, Pope writes, “We want to be a Church that serves, that leaves home and goes forth from its places of worship, goes forth from its sacristies, in order to accompany life, to sustain hope, to be the sign of unity [...] to build bridges, to break down

walls, to sow seeds of reconciliation” (FT § 276).⁹ Pope here emphasizes that the language of evangelization is love and charity. Doing charity to the poor and the needy is an act of witness which spreads the message of the Good News.

f. Witness: The Method of Methods

When we say that one bears witness to God through one’s life, all the activities that s/he does are included by that expression. For example, one’s proclamation, his/her activities connected with inter-religious dialogue, inculturation, other social activities, *etc.*, are included by the expression of life-witnessing. That means, life-witnessing is a wide concept which includes all other methods of evangelization. A man, who bears witness, cannot avoid other methods. The other methods of evangelization become parts of life-witnessing. Could we think witness of life as a separate method excluding all other methods of evangelization? It is not possible because of the interconnectedness of the witness of life with other methods. Our proclamation and our interaction with different religious and social groups are part of our lives. So, we cannot avoid such elements in our method of life-witnessing.

The emphasis in the previous sections is the essential role of the life-witnessing in the process of evangelization. Though some of the texts from documents mention “the permanent priority” (RM § 44) of the proclamation, the life-witnessing is also described as “the first means of evangelization” (EN § 41) and “the first and irreplaceable form of mission” (RM § 42) in some other texts in the documents. This shows that

⁹ Quoted from *Homily*, Santiago de Cuba (22 September 2015); available from https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/homilies/2015/documents/papa-francesco_20150922_cuba-omelia-santiago.html; accessed on 5th November 2021; internet.

the church documents find it difficult to give a status to the life-witnessing lesser than the proclamation. Both EN and RM described the life-witnessing before they describe about the proclamation.¹⁰ This shows the priority of life-witnessing in evangelization. Without negating the role of the proclamation, the present discussion tries to find out the importance of the life-witnessing.

2. Theology Behind Fraternity and Witness

In the encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, Pope Francis reveals the theology behind the call for fraternity that he demands. He considers the whole world as a ‘common home’. He writes, “Let us dream, then, as a single human family, as fellow travelers sharing the same flesh, as children of the same earth which is our *common home*, each of us bringing the richness of his or her beliefs and convictions, each of us with his or her own voice, brothers and sisters all” (FT § 8, Emphasis added). The whole world is considered as a single community where the members of it shares everything together. This was the same experience the first Christian communities lived. They had concern for their fellow beings and lived as a family. The other encyclical of Pope Francis, namely *Laudato Si’*, also reminds us that we are part of a ‘common home’ (Cf. LS §13). Here Pope Francis urges us to

¹⁰ “[I]t is appropriate first of all to emphasize the following point: for the Church, *the first means of evangelization* is the witness of an authentically Christian life, given over to God in a communion that nothing should destroy and at the same time given to one's neighbour with limitless zeal” (EN, § 41). “People today put more trust in witnesses than in teachers, in experience than in teaching, and in life and action than in theories. The witness of a Christian life is *the first and irreplaceable form of mission*: Christ, whose mission we continue, is the “witness” *par excellence* (Rv 1:5; 3:14) and the model of all Christian witness. The Holy Spirit accompanies the Church along her way and associates her with the witness he gives to Christ (cf. Jn 15:26-27)” (RM, § 42). The emphases added.

protect the creation of God from all kinds of misuse and pollution. A theology of creation is noticeable here. The conviction that God has created everything (Cf. Col 1: 16) from nothingness and we the human beings were created in the image likeness of God to be the crown of His creation (Cf. Gen 1:26) helps Pope Francis to hold such a view on the protection of creation. Without considering religion, culture, language, etc., one has to treat others as their brothers and sisters.

The creation theology is based on the revelation that all creatures of the world are created by the heavenly father. Pope Francis in FT points out the loving care of the heavenly father. God is love and those who abide in this love abide in him. Those who live a life in fellowship and love and concern for others live in God (Cf. FT § 4).¹¹ The realization that we are the children of a loving God (Cf. Mt 11:25), motivates the people in the world to live in fraternity. The single fatherhood of all creation brings unity and solidarity in the world (Cf. FT §§ 272-274). Basing on this creation theology and theology of love, one realizes his/her proper role in the salvation history. As children of God we are not only the beneficiaries; but are caretakers of the creation. Pope Francis writes in LS, “All of us can cooperate as instruments of God for the care of creation, each according to his or her own culture, experience, involvements and

¹¹ With the Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb Pope Francis declares, “God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters.” *Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Living Together*, Abu Dhabi (4 February 2019); *L'Osservatore Romano*, (4-5 February 2019), 6; available from https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/travel/2019/outside/documents/papa-francesco_20190204_documento-fratellanza-umana.html; accessed on 5th November 2021; internet.

talents” (LS §14). The father of the common home instructs us, His children, to take care of His creations (Cf. Gen 1: 28). The creation theology motivates us to protect this universe where we live.

In the encyclical FT, Pope Francis narrates the example of St. Francis of Assisi who lived the fraternal love. At the time of Crusades, St. Francis took the pain to visit Sultan Malik-el-Kamil, in Egypt, travelling a long distance and neglecting the differences of language, culture and religion. This event demonstrates the grandeur of his love towards his fellow beings without considering the differences they had. Following the model of St. Francis of Assisi, Pope Francis also visited some of the religious leaders and together with these leaders he declared his will to join for universal brotherhood. In this encyclical, he dreams a world which would be led by the cooperative commitment of the members of it.

What Pope Francis describes as the theological basis for his teaching on fraternity, is also the basis of evangelization and witness. What would be the role of witness in bringing fraternity that Pope Francis urges to do? I assume that the witnessing life of the people of God would make the vision of Pope Francis closer. The Trinitarian love inspires the people of God to lead a fraternal and witnessing life. In the mission documents of Catholic Church, we realize that God, the Father, is the foundation of mission (Cf. AG § 2). The ‘*abba* experience’ of Jesus (Cf. Mt 11: 27) motivates him to bear witness to the heavenly Father. Kavunkal writes, “The basis of Jesus’ mission is his experience of God as his *abba*” (Kavunkal 1986: 8-15). Jesus says, “For this I was born, and for this I came into the world, *to bear witness to the truth*” (Jn. 18:37). The mission of Jesus is continued with the help of the Holy Spirit (Cf. Jn. 20:21-23). So the intimate relation with the Trinity is much needed for living a witnessing life. The realization of the ‘paternal relation with God’ motivate people to bear witness. Lack of such conviction causes the counter-witnessing responses from their part. So the

Trinitarian and creation theology promote both fraternity and witnessing attitudes in the people.

3. Different Kinds of Witness in FT

In the encyclical FT, Pope Francis uses the word “witness” in different sense. In some places it gets a secular meaning and rest of the places it gets a religious connotation as in the mission documents like *Evangelii Nuntiandi* (EN), *Redemptoris Missio* (RM), etc. Some texts from FT are taken here for much analysis. Witness is classified into different varieties according to the way it is done. For example, we call it ‘individual type’ or ‘communal type’ based on the number of witness. Here we analyse the encyclical FT and find out the role of different witness-types in bringing fraternity in the world.

a. Individual Witness

There are individuals in our Church who witness Christ through their own life. There are many examples. The disciples of Jesus after the Pentecost experience gave witness to Christ courageously. Afterwards there were many missionaries and the saints of the Church who spread the Good News around the world. Eminent personalities like St. Teresa of Calcutta,¹² St. Oscar Romero¹³ the Archbishop of El Salvador, *etc.*, are some of the saints of our times who bore witness to Christ. Like them, many missionaries went to

¹² Mother Theresa incarnated God’s love and could see God’s presence in all the poor and the afflicted. She started a new community as ‘Missionaries of Charity’, which is an embodiment of God’s love. She received Noble Peace Prize in 1979. Her witnessing life has influenced many people. Cf. Schroeder 2008: 86.

¹³ Oscar Roero was the fourth Archbishop of San Salvador who was assassinated while offering Mass.

different corners of the world and preached and lived the Word of God.

In the encyclical FT, Pope Francis motivates the people of God to follow the attitude of the Samaritan man who saved the man assaulted by thieves on the wayside. He was not legally bound to do such an act of love. Though he had his own plan for that day, he stood back with the injured man and cared him. The chapter second of this encyclical gives an account of this parable and different practical suggestions (FT §§ 56- 86). The witness of the Samaritan can be included in the individual type of witness. Though he was a pagan, he bore witness to love of God through his timely deeds. The priest and the Levite who passed-by the injured man showed a kind of indifference. Their attitudes show that “belief in God and the worship of God are not enough to ensure that we are actually living in a way pleasing to God” (FT §73). To act like the Samaritan one has to experience the love of God and then one has to be ready to share this love of God to the fellow being. More than polished words or being at the safe distance, the abandoned and the poor around us expect our compassionate involvement for helping them. This approach will make us authentic children of God. When we open our hearts to our brothers and sisters, we will have authentic openness to God (Cf. FT § 74). Nothing creates a barrier to this individual type of witness. Even the people who belong to other religions can bear witness to their common Father. Pope Francis dreams such an attitudes of concern and love from all people on the earth.

Roger P. Schroeder writes, “The most witnessing is done by ordinary baptized Christians in their daily life at home, in their neighbourhood, at work and in social situation” (Schroeder 2008: 113). In this sense, everyone in the Church is called to live the Christian values and by that way bear witness to Christ. The new law of love is very important in this respect. Many forms of injustice exists in our world. Some live in opulence and others live in poor conditions. Their fundamental rights are even discarded (FT § 22). In some places women, children, people in

different caste system, etc., are going through lot of difficulties. They were considered as slaves and useless part of the society. Human trafficking, sexual abuse, kidnapping for the sake of selling their organs, etc. are common in some places (FT § 24). In such situation, individual witness can bring lots of changes. If we consider the poor and the needy of the society and if we respect them, we actually witness to God's love and also give a model to the people live among them. In this sense, the witnessing life is not that which is only bounded to priests or missionaries; rather it is demanded from each members of the community. No one is excluded from such kind of witness. Women and children also share the missionary role of the Church through their witnessing-life.

The encyclical FT inspires us to practice certain values in our life. Gratuitous¹⁴ love (FT §§ 92-94 § 139), charity (FT §§164-166), kindness (FT §§ 222-224), peace (FT §§ 228-230), forgiveness (FT §§ 240-243) etc. are values which are supposed to be practiced by a person who seeks universal friendship. These are the values which Jesus, the son of God, practiced in his life. The one who bears witness to a common Father also practices such values and through his/her life motivates others to practice them. For this, dialogue between persons is needed (FT §§ 203-205). The interaction between them will help each one of them to practice such virtues.

b. Communal Witness

Through the authentic life activities, many people bear witness to Christ at a parish or diocesan or state or country level. In the early Christian community such kinds of communal witness were very visible. Roger P. Schroeder

¹⁴ “The ability to do some things simply because they are good in themselves, without concern for personal gain or recompense” (FT, § 139)

writes, “Early Christian communities, in cities around the Mediterranean, reached out to help the sick and those in need.”¹⁵ Along with their personal life-witnessing, together with other members, they bore witness to Christ. In the present situation, the parish communities, pious associations, and other organizations within the Church organize certain community activities to witness Christ. The Eucharistic celebration and the fellowship within the Church is very important in this respect. Catholic *Ashramas* also witness Christ through their communitarian life.¹⁶ These religious communities come forward with some social programmes to teach Christian values and to bring social changes.

Pope Francis writes, “A kind of “deconstructionism”, whereby human freedom claims to create everything starting from zero, is making headway in today’s culture” (FT §13). This kind of deconstructionism end up in the spiritual identity and moral consistency of an individual and groups (Cf. FT § 14). If we are not aware of our history we do not realize the worth of the Church. Pope writes, We need to “keep alive the flame of collective conscience, bearing witness to succeeding generations to the horror of what happened”, because that witness “awakens and preserves the memory of the victims, so that the conscience of humanity may rise up in the face of every desire for dominance and destruction” (FT § 249).¹⁷ Each society has their own history

¹⁵ Schroeder 2008: 114. So, some theologians call the local congregation as “hermeneutic of the gospel.” Cf. Bevans and Schroeder 1994: 354.

¹⁶ *Ashram* life as a movement started in Indian Church only since 1921 with the foundation of the Christukula Ashram in Tirupathur, South India by Dr. Jesudasan and Dr. Paton. *Ashrams* are engaged in social uplift programmes, personal services, contemplation, etc. Cf. Karokaran 1978: 187-194.

¹⁷ *Message for the 2020 World Day of Peace* (8 December 2019), 2: *L'Osservatore Romano*, 13 December 2019, 8; available from https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/messages/peace/documents/papa-francesco_20191208_

which has to be communicated to the future generation to realize the uniqueness of that community. Common witness is the result of such realization. The historical consciousness of a Christian country enables it to stand with the poor and the migrants because they know their past that they suffered a lot and exiled in Egypt. The church community can stand together to pressurize the government to take steps against racial or religious persecution and other social issues.

The Catholic community should live authentically. It is their authentic presentation of Christ through their lives that make them a separate community. Hans Raun Iversen writes, “We are in serious need of a new appreciation of “Christ in us” as a basic concept in missiology, for sociological as well as theological reasons. [...] Churches and congregational life are beginning to look much more like a process where Christ is being presented and re-presented to people in all sort of ways rather than a static situation in which specific people “are in Christ” good as his very Church” (Iversen 2010: 193-194). Iversen preferred “Christ in us” rather than “we in Christ”. “Christ in us” expression implies the authenticity that is required from the members of the Church. It also reveals the importance of bearing witness to Christ through life-witnessing. Through the authentic way of living, the communities can bring the message of Christ to the world.

c. Universal Witness

There are many institutions in the Church to bear witness to Christ in this world. Roger P. Schroeder writes, “The Church-sponsored institutions like hospitals, schools, orphanages, and social service centers with authentic leaders witness Christian values” (Schroeder 2008: 114). These institutions bear witness to Christ’s saving action, concern

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and love towards the poor and the marginalized. These institutions though they are not directly involved with religious matters, through their service to humanity make the values of Christ visible to the secular world too. Hospitals, schools, orphanages, *etc.*, are such institutions where one can witness Christ among people from other religions. Pope Francis writes, “The believers of the different religions know that our witness to God benefits our societies” (FT § 274). At the Covid-19 pandemic time, we realized that “no one is saved alone; we can only be saved together” (FT § 32). During this period, our institutions could serve all kinds of people. At the beginning of the pandemic, doctors and nurses were serving the Covid-19 patients at the risk of their own lives.¹⁸ In this way they could bear witness to the love of the universal Father.

Pope Francis in FT warns us about “the destructive forms of fanaticism” (FT §46), “hostility, insults, abuse, defamation and verbal violence” (FT § 44), “concupiscence” (FT § 166), *etc.* Most of these issues are related with people’s perverted view on other people and religions. If these people can experience the love of God through the institutions of another religion that may change their attitudes towards these religions. For example, the people from other religion experience Christian values when they come into our institutions and interact with the members of these institutions. People who work in these institutions also belongs to different religions. By inspiring them to stand for values, the Christian directors of this institutions bring a new message to them. In this way, the other religious members also cooperate with the mission of Church. The members of these institutions and the directors through their authentic and loving activities bear

¹⁸ Cf. [*Extraordinary Moment of Prayer in Time of Epidemic*](#) (27 March 2020): *L’Osservatore Romano*, (29 March 2020), 10; available from https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/homilies/2020/documents/papa-francesco_20200327_omelia-epidemia.html; accessed on 5th Nov 2021; internet.

witness to the kingdom values. The Church works for the advancement of humanity and of universal fraternity. She is “open to bear witness in today’s world, open to faith, hope and love for the Lord [...]. A home with open doors” (FT § 276).

d. Common Witness

There are many Christian churches and denominations in this world. These denominations and small churches have different distinctive natures. Still they come together to witness Christ.¹⁹ There would be areas where these different denominations can work together and bring changes to the society. For example, a movement named ‘Common Witness’ in the United States works for justice and service-oriented projects. Churches witness together when they pray together, work together for justice, offer common counter cultural witness, participate in theological education, *etc.* This kind of common witness has some ecumenical tones. Instead of quarrelling with each other, these denominations can bear witness to Christ if they are ready to work together for some social purposes, for some ecumenical prayers, and dialogues.

For bearing witness to the common Father, there should be unity among different confessions. Pope Francis prays to God for strengthening unity among different denominations by the grace of the Holy Spirit (Cf. 1 Cor 12:13) (Cf. FT § 280). Pope Francis writes, “Courage and generosity are needed in order freely to establish shared goals” (FT §174).

¹⁹ Now the most serious obstacle to the evangelization is the scandalous separation of Christian communities. Their unity in mission will be an eloquent witness to the gospel’s power to unite and reconcile salve and free, male and female rich and the poor. Cf. Stephen B. Bevans and Roger P. Schroeder, *Constants in Context: A Theology of Mission for Today*, 356.

We should be ready to cooperate with these denomination for the wellbeing of the afflicted and downtrodden. Pope Francis writes, “we already have the duty to offer common witness to the love of God for all people by working together in the service of humanity” (*Ibid*). The usage of “common witness” occurs in this text very explicitly.

Conclusion

The article “Witness in *Fratelle Tutti*, reveals the role of ‘witness’ in bringing fraternity in the world. The theology behind the urge for universal fraternity and witness is theology of love and creation. The realization of people as the creation of a common Father motivates them to work together for the common good. A peaceful and just world is possible through this cooperative work of people of all kinds. The cooperative work of people of all kinds have to be promoted through the active participation of Christians. It is not for the conversion of other people into Christianity that they participate in it. A Christian participates in this project of fraternity gratuitously. The way he/she lives or bears witness to God makes lots of changes in the attitudes of other people. Different kinds of witness are the ways helpful to bring the Christian values in the different life circles. In this way, witnessing life of a Christian gradually forms a common home of peace and solidarity.

References

- Assisi, St. Francis of. 2021. “Admonition”, available from https://oll.libertyfund.org/title/assisi-the-writings-of-saint-francis-of-assisi#lf0535_label_121, accessed on 8th November 2021; internet.
- Bevans, Stephen B. and Roger P. Schroeder. 1994. *Constants in Context: A Theology of Mission for Today*. New York: Orbis Books.
- CBCI Consultation on Mission. 1997. “The Paths of Mission in India Today”, in *The Paths of Mission in India Today*, ed.

- Augustine Kanjamala. Mumbai: St. Paul's Publication, 1997
- Francis, Pope. 2017/ *General Audience*; available from https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/audiences/2017/documents/papa-Francesco_20170621_udienza-generale.html; accessed on 5th November 2021; internet.
- Francis, Pope. 2018. *Ecumenical Prayer Service*, Riga, Latvia (24 September 2018): *L'Osservatore Romano*. 24-25 September 2018), 8; available from https://www.vatican.va/content/francesco/en/speeches/2018/september/documents/papa-francesco_20180924_incontro-ecumenico-riga-lettonia.html; accessed on 6th November 2021; internet.
- Iversen, Hans Raun. 2010. *Pro me in the Age of Authenticity: The Missiological Significance of "Christ in us" and "We in Christ"*, in *Walk Humbly with Lord: Church and Mission Engaging Plurality*, eds. Viggo Mortensen and Andreas Österlund Nielsen. Cambridge: William B. Eerdmans Publication Company.
- Jerman, Shaji. 2008. "Church of Mission to a Missionary Church," in *Mission and Conversion- Towards a New Ecclesiology*, eds. Selvister Ponnunmuthan and Shaji Jerman. Bangalore: Asian Trading Corporation.
- John Paul II, Pope. 1999. *Redemptoris Missio*. Boston : Pauline Books & Media (Abbreviated as RM).
- Karokaran, Anto. 1978. *Evangelization and Diakonia*. Bangalore: Dharmaram.
- Kavunkal, Jacob. 1986. "The Abba- Experience, the Model and Motive for Mission Today", in *FABC Paper* 43. Hong Kong, 1986) 8-15.
- Namitha. 2000. *A New Paradigm for Evangelization in the Third Millennium*. Trivandrum: St. Peter's Pontifical Institute Publications.

Paul VI, Pope. 1999. Apostolic Exhortation, *Evangelii Nuntiandi*. Washington, D.C. : United States Catholic Conference(Abbreviated as EN).

Paul VI, Pope. 1974. Address to the Members of the Consilium de Laicis (2 October 1974); available from https://www.vatican.va/content/paul-vi/fr/audiences/1974/documents/hf_p-vi_aud_19741002.html; accessed on 05th November 2021; internet.

Schroeder, Roger P. 2008. *What is Mission of the Church*. New York: Orbis Book.

Shaji Jerman, “Church of Mission to a Missionary Church,” in *Mission and Conversion- Towards a New Ecclesiology*, eds. Selvester Ponnuthan and Shaji Jerman (Bangalore: Asian Trading Corporation, 2008), 101- 103 (98-120).

Witness. 2021. *Oxford Dictionary*, available from https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/american_english/witness_1; accessed on 7th November 2021; internet.

Witnesses. 2018. *Catechism of the Catholic Church*; available from <http://www.vatican.va/archive/ENG0015/_P8J.HTM>; accessed on 17th Nov 2018; internet.

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St Francis of Assisi and *Fratelli Tutti*: A Historical Purview

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Abstract: As humans we are always faced with problems. In this world of problems there have always been persons, who lead the world to reach the other shore. It is in this context of present world that Pope Francis brings out his Encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, with the theme fraternal love and social relationship, a way to live in this world as brothers and sisters. He tells us that in these pages of the Encyclical of reflection on universal fraternity, he is inspired particularly persons of the past like by Saint Francis of Assisi, but also others who are not Catholics, like Martin Luther King,

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Desmond Tutu, Mahatma Gandhi and many others. These persons are people who bring hope to the world. The Pope says that he would like to conclude by mentioning another person of great faith. He is blessed Charles de Foucauld. He was a man of intense experience of God, who made a journey of transformation towards feeling a brother to all. It is from this background that this research paper is being brought out titled, “St Francis of Assisi and Fratelli Tutti: A Historical Purview.”

Keywords: Pope Francis, Fratelli Tutti, St Francis of Assisi, Fraternity, Social Relationship.

Introduction

Fraternity and social relationship are the ways, the Holy Father Pope Francis indicates to build a better world by the cooperation and understanding of all peoples and institutions of the world. The Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, deals with the ideals and the tangible ways for all people of good will to build a more just and fraternal world in our ordinary relationships, in social life, politics and institutions. This is what this encyclical tries to convey to us. The holy Father describes it as a universal social encyclical, which borrows the admonitions of Saint Francis of Assisi who used these words to address his brothers and sisters and put forward to them a way of life flavored by the Gospel. The encyclical invites everyone to aspiration towards fraternity and social relationship. It is brought out in the background of the Covid-19 pandemic, which Pope Francis says, unexpectedly erupted as he was writing this letter. It is from this context that this paper is being brought titled, *St Francis Assisi and Fratelli Tutti: A Historical Purview*, for a future world of cooperation, understanding and way of living as individuals and as a society. The Bible is used for reference is *The New Jerusalem Bible*, New York: Doubleday, 1985, referred as NJB.

1. St Francis of Assisi, a Historical Perspective

In this Encyclical seeing St Francis of Assisi as a historical person makes the Christian life plausible and attractive even in the

circumstance of today and at all time. He is the saint of God, humans and the environment. For example, Pope Francis says that St Francis of Assisi was great in the thirteenth century but he has become even more important today (Murphy, 2014). St Francis was considered a saint at the time of his death, October 3, 1226, Francis was canonized only two years later in 1228 by Pope Gregory IX, who said of him on that occasion that Francis shone in his days as a morning star in the midst of clouds (Murphy, 2014). Among those who followed includes St Elizabeth, the young widow of the king of Hungary, who become a secular Franciscan and was renowned for her love of the poor before her early death in 1231- only five years after the death of St Francis himself (Murphy, 2014). It is one of the examples of how greatly was the widespread the spiritual renewal he inspired (Murphy, 2014).

St Francis of Assisi had great influence on the Church of his time. He lived when a time the Church was in a new situation, which needed a renewal. The twelfth century Europe saw the revival of arts and learning. The election of the thirty-seven-year-old noble and learned Innocent III saw the initial establishment of the papal states and an immense enlargement of the papal prestige; Innocent was the first call himself “vicar of Christ” (Murphy, 2014). Innocent III is known for many important reforms in the Church, which has come down to this day although his sponsorship of the Fourth Crusade to liberate the Holy Land from the Muslims proved to be a tragedy, the Pope’s convocation of the Fourth Lateran Council in 1206, was according to John O’Malley, a historian, “one of the largest and most impressive assemblies in the Middle Ages and the largest council in the history of the Church up to that Point,” (Murphy, 2014). It is seen that like the Second Vatican Council, the Fourth Lateran Council of 1215 was a council concerned with reformation (Murphy, 2014). It is reported that it was in this council that created

ever after has called the “Easter duty”: to remain in good standing, all Catholics must receive Holy Communion and, if necessary, go to confession at least once per year (Murphy, 2014).

Apart from the “Easter duty”, Innocent III’s greatest lasting influence upon the Church was his encouragement of the creation of new religious orders by St Dominic and St Francis (Murphy, 2014). Thus, a new body of ministers sprang into being alongside the regular clergy and outside of the conventional parish-based structure (Murphy, 2014). The Dominicans and Franciscans were fundamentally orders of preachers who spoke the Gospel to the people in their own language (Murphy, 2014). Their influence has been felt even today as they grew quickly in this era of renewal, and an amazing seventeen thousand friars of Francis’s new order gathered from all over Europe for the first chapter order in 1260 (Murphy, 2014).

One of the most important and lasting legacy of St Francis is his relationship to “nature” or the environment (Murphy, 2014). For example, the American ecologist Lynn White has written, “the greatest spiritual revolutionary in Western history, St Francis proposed an alternative view of nature and man’s (humans’) relation to it,” (Murphy, 2014). This important characteristic of the saint is confirmed by the Church, when Saint John Paul II in 1980 made him patron saint of ecology (Murphy, 2014). In similar manner the religious historian Marina Warner, speaking for many says, “The Franciscan spirit continues to be considered by agnostics and atheists, as well as believers, as the most genuine expression of Christ’s teaching ever approved by the Vatican,” (Murphy, 2014).

2. St Francis of Assisi and the Gospel

After his encounter with the Lord, St Francis was led by the Gospel way of life was intensely connected to a life of personal prayer, penance, and the witness of charity in the life of the one, who resumed preaching the Gospel (Murphy, 2014). It is said that sometimes Francis saw the duty of prayer as so paramount that he

wondered whether he should take time from prayer to preach at all. It is pointed out that it was only at the urging of Clare and the brothers that he continued to preach to the people the saving message of God (Murphy, 2014). His preaching had such power, and was so challenging to the demons of his time, because he prioritized prayer and embodied witness over preaching (Murphy, 2014). In one occasion St Francis was asked by the bishop to preach to St Clare and the sisters at her convent (Murphy, 2014). St Francis raised his eyes to heaven, where his heart always was, and began to pray to Christ. He then asked to bring ashes to him, and made a circle with them around himself on the pavement, and sprinkled the rest of them on his head (Murphy, 2014). When they waited for him to begin and the blessed father remained standing in silence, no small astonishment arose in their hearts (Murphy, 2014). The saint arose suddenly and to the amazement of the nuns, recited the *Miserere mei Deus* (Psalm 50), in place of a sermon (Murphy, 2014). As soon as he finished he quickly left and the servants of God were so filled with contrition because of the power of this symbolic sermon that their tears flowed in abundance and they could scarcely restrain their hands from inflicting punishment on themselves (Murphy, 2014).

There are many examples of the saint's account of preaching. For example, St Bonaventure speaks of the saint's account of preaching;

It happened that he came to Arezzo at a time when the whole city was shaken by civil war and was on the brink of destruction. Given hospitality in the outskirts, he saw over the city devils rejoicing and inflaming the troubled citizens in mutual slaughter. In order to put to flight those seditious spiritual powers, he sent Brother Sylvester, a man of dove-like simplicity, before him like a herald, saying,

“Go before the gate of the city and on the part of Almighty God command the devils to leave immediately!” This truly obedient man hastened to carry out his father’s orders and, singing psalms of praise before the face of the Lord (Ps 94:2), he began to shout out forcefully before the gate of the city: “On the part of Almighty God and at the command of his servant Francis, depart far from here, all you devils.” At once the city returned to peace and all the citizens reformed their civil statutes very peacefully. Once the raging pride of the devils, which had surrounded the city like a siege, had been driven out, the wisdom of a poor man, namely the humility of Francis, entered in, brought back peace and saved the city. By his lofty virtue of humble obedience, he had gained such powerful control over those rebellious and obstinate spirits that he could repress their ferocious brashness and drive back their savage violence (Murphy, 2014).

Another example is which occurred in 1222, on the Feast of the Assumption, when the saint gathered a crowd in the piazza of the university city of Bologna. Here is an eyewitness account of what had happened;

When I was a student in Bologna, I saw St Francis preach in the main square outside the Palazzo Communale; almost the whole city had gathered to hear him. His theme was “Angels, men and Devils.”

Although no scholar, he spoke so well and developed the subject of these three classes of rational and spiritual beings so clearly that he won the unbounded admiration of even the academics in the crowd. Yet it was more of a general address than a sermon.

He wore a tattered habit, his appearance was insignificant and his face wasn’t handsome, but

God gave his words such power that they actually restored peace to many noble families long torn apart by hatred, cruelty and murder. At the same time ordinary men and women flocked to him out of devotion and respect, afterwards trying to tear a shred from his habit or at least to touch him (Murphy, 2014).

These above passages tell us how relevant is the saint for our world of today, which is marked by so much violence, hatred and cruelty, suffering, hunger and pain, though there is so much progress and understanding among nations and humanity as a whole. Taking the influence of St Francis of Assisi on the Church and the society of his time that Pope Francis brings out his encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* for a better world.

3. Pope Francis and St Francis of Assisi

Cardinal Jorge Mario Bergoglio of Buenos Aires, on March 13, 2013, was elected Pope (Murphy M., 2014). The Pope is the first to come, as he said, “from the edge of the world,” as well as the first Jesuit and the first to take the name Francis (Murphy, 2014). When a Pope is elected to the Pontificate, he selects his name to announce a vision for his pontificate (Murphy M., 2014). It is in this vision that the Pope has taken his name as Francis, after the name of St Francis of Assisi.

In choosing the name when one is elected to the Papacy, every Pope had one’s own choice and preference of one’s mission. Pope John Paul I and Saint John Paul II carried forward the programme of renewal of reform initiated by St John XXIII, who summoned the Second Vatican Council, which was completed by Saint Pope Paul VI (Murphy, 2014). His predecessor Pope Benedict XVI, on the other hand, surveying the increasing secularization of Europe symbolized by the omission of any reference to God in the

European Union's proposed constitution, selected the name of the great founder of monasticism in the West, Benedict of Nursia, a saint who shaped Western civilization for more than a millennium (Murphy, 2014). In a typical fashion, this is how Pope Francis explains about the selection of his name to a group of six thousand journalists, who had covered the conclave that elected him;

Some people wanted to know why the Bishop of Rome wished to be called Francis. Some thought of Francis Xavier, Francis De Sales, and also Francis of Assisi. I will tell you the story. During the election, I was seated next to the Archbishop Emeritus of Sao Paulo and Prefect Emeritus of the Congregation for the Clergy, Cardinal Claudio Hummes; a good friend, a good friend! When things were looking dangerous, he encouraged me. And when the votes reached two thirds, there was the usual applause, because the Pope had been elected. And he gave me a hug and a kiss, and said: "Don't forget the poor!" and those words came to me: the poor, the poor. Then, right way, thinking of the poor, I thought of Francis of Assisi. Then I thought of all the wars, as the votes were still being counted, till the end. Francis is also the man of peace. This is how the name came into my heart: Francis of Assisi. For me, he is the man of poverty, the man of peace, the man who loves and protects creation; these days we do not have a very good relationship with creation, do we? He is the man who gives us this spirit of peace, the poor man... How I would like a Church which is poor and for the poor!"(Murphy, 2014).

The Holy Father, Pope Francis during his first Sunday recitation of the Angelus in St Peter's Square, the Pope added another reason, saying he chose the name of the patron saint of Italy to reinforce "my spiritual link with this land where, as you know, my family has its origins," (Murphy, 2014). The Pope's Italian

roots, also emphasized by the selection of this name, reinforce his conception of the Papacy as being fundamentally, the bishop of Rome, who presides in charity over the universal Church. The Holy Father says; “how I would like a Church, which is poor and for the poor!” (Murphy, 2014). What more concise description of Pontificate do we need? Thus the new evangelization, a pastoral priority of the Church in our time, can now be guided-front and centre-by the example of St Francis of Assisi (Murphy, 2014).

Another aspect of the Pope Francis (Jorge Bergoglio) is his humility in being a humble person. He chose his Episcopal motto from the English Church Father Bede, which reads, “*Miserando atque eligendo*” (having pity on him, he chose him). St Bede, who lived in the eighth century, coined this phrase in his exegesis of the call of Matthew to become an apostle (Mt 9:9-13) (Murphy, 2014). St Bede explains that Jesus saw Matthew not just in his appearance and profession but with merciful understanding (Murphy, 2014). The conversion of one sinner gives other sinners an example of repentance and pardon (Murphy, 2014). Bede draws a conclusion; “No sooner was he converted than Matthew drew after him a whole crowd of sinners along the road to salvation (Murphy, 2014). After his election to the Papacy, Pope Francis in the next day in the Sistine Chapel, during the Mass the Holy Father concelebrated with the cardinals who elected him, put aside the prepared Latin homily and speaking spontaneously and standing behind the lectern, he summarized the lectionary’s readings for the day with three verbs: walking, building, and professing (Murphy, 2014).”The thing, however, is not so easy, because in walking, in building and in professing there are sometimes shake-ups,” he said. He continued;

The same Peter, who confessed Jesus Christ says, “You are the Christ, the Son of the living God. I will follow you, but let us not speak of the cross. This has nothing to do with,” he says. “I will follow you in other ways that do not include the cross.” When we walk without the cross, when we build without the cross, and when we profess Christ without the cross, we are not disciples of the Lord. We are worldly; we are bishops, priests, cardinals, popes, but not disciples of the Lord.

I would like that all of us, after these days of grace, might have the courage-the courage-to walk in the presence of the Lord with the cross of the Lord, to build the Church on the blood of the Lord which was shed upon the cross, and to profess the one glory, Christ crucified. In this way the church will go forward (Murphy, 2014).

4. St Francis of Assisi Brings Hope to History

In St Francis, hope was made real, hope entered history, especially via the saint’s contagious care for the poor. It was St Bonaventure, who, along with Thomas of Celano, was one of Francis’s first biographers, summarized *il poverello’s* life and influence this way:

He was poor and lowly, but the Most High God looked upon him with such condescension and kindness that he not only lifted him up in his need from the dust of a worldly life, but made him a practitioner, a leader and a herald of gospel perfection and set him up as a light for believers so that by bearing witness to the light he might prepare for the Lord a way of light and peace into the hearts of the faithful (Murphy, 2014).

Thus, in the person of Pope Francis, St Francis of Assisi exemplifies, in a pre-eminent manner the beauty of the Christian

faith and the joy that comes from believing in it. As Charles M. Murphy points out that its promise is nothing less than the hope of the world at all time. He brings out a poem by Sophecles and translated by Seamus Heaney, where the poet speaks of “a further shore... reachable from here” and a time when “hope and history rhyme,” (Murphy, 2014). It is said that in St Francis of Assisi hope and history actually did come together and memorably ever after, did achieve rhyme (Murphy, 2014).

5. *Fratelli Tutti* of Pope Francis on Fraternity and Social Friendship

In his Encyclical letter *Fratelli Tutti*, Pope Francis reminds us his faithful that saint Francis of Assisi addressed his brothers and sisters and proposed to them a way of life marked by the flavor of the Gospel (Francis, 2021). He says that of the counsels the saint offers the Holy Father selects the one in which he calls for a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance, and declares blessed all those who love their brother “as much when he is far away from him as when he is with him (Murphy, 2014). The Holy Father tells us that saint Francis in his simple and direct way expresses the ‘essence of a fraternal openness’ that allows us to acknowledge, appreciate and love each person, regardless of physical proximity, regardless of where one was born or lives (Francis, 2021).

Pope Francis tells us that St Francis of Assisi who is the saint of fraternal love, simplicity and joy, inspired him to write the Encyclical *Laudato Si'*, prompts him once more to devote this new Encyclical to fraternity and social friendship (Francis, 2021). The Pope says that saint Francis of Assisi felt himself a brother to the sun, the sea and the wind, yet he knew that he was even closer to those of his flesh. He reminds us that saint Francis wherever, he went, sowed seeds of peace

and walked alongside the poor, the abandoned, the infirm and outcast, the least of his brothers and sisters (Francis, 2021).

6. A Saint without Borders

The Pope tells us that there is an episode in the life of saint Francis of Assisi, which reveals the openness of the saint's heart, which knew no bounds and transcends difference of origin, nationality, colour or religion (Francis, 2021). The Holy Father reminds us that the journey undertaken at the time of the Crusades, further demonstrated the breadth and grandeur of St Francis' love, which sought to embrace everyone. He tells us that St Francis' fidelity to his Lord and Master Jesus was commensurate with his love for his brothers and sisters (Francis, 2021). He brings to our awareness that St Francis was unconcerned with the hardships and dangers involved. To show the love of St Francis for everyone the Holy Father tells us that for example, St Francis went to meet the Sultan with same attitude that he instilled in his disciples. St Francis taught his brothers that if they found themselves among the Saracens and other nonbelievers, without renouncing their own identity they were not engage in arguments or disputes, but to be subjected to every human creature for God's sake (Francis, 2021).

a. St Francis of Assisi, a Saint for Our Times

Seeing today's world scenario Pope Francis tells us that in this context of the times, this approach and understanding of a human culture was an extraordinary recommendation. He tells us that we are impressed that some eight hundred years ago Saint Francis urged that all forms of hostility or conflict be avoided and that a humble and fraternal "subjection" be shown to those who did not share his faith (Francis, 2021).

b. St Francis of Assisi was a Person of Empathy

The Holy Father tells us that St Francis was a man of empathy. He did not wage war of words at imposing doctrines. On the other hand, he simply spread the love of God. The Pope reminds us that

he understood that “God is love and those who abide in love abide in God.” (1 Jn 4:16) (Francis, 2021). He exhorts us that in this way, St Francis became a father to all and inspired the vision of a fraternal society, which is very much needed for us humanity today (Francis, 2021). Thus Pope Francis tells us that in the world of that time, bristling with watchtowers and defensive walls, cities were a theatre of brutal wars between powerful families, even as poverty was spreading through the countryside (Francis, 2021). In this scenario of the time of St Francis, the saint was able to welcome true peace into his heart and free himself of the desire to wield power over others. Thus, he became one of the poor and sought to live in harmony with all. The Holy Father tells us that it is St Francis who has inspired these pages.

7. Pope Francis and *Fratelli Tutti*

Drawing inspiration from St Francis of Assisi, Pope Francis writes that issues of human fraternity and social friendship have always been his concern. The Holy Father tells us that in recent years, he has spoken of them repeatedly and in different settings. He says that in this Encyclical, he has sought to bring together many of those statements and to situate them in broader context of reflection and action. For example, the Holy Father reminds us that in the preparation of *Laudato Si'*, he had a source of inspiration in his brother Bartholomew, the Orthodox Patriarch, who has spoken forcefully of our need to care for creation (Francis, 2021). While for this Encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, the Holy Father says that he has felt particularly encouraged by the Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb, with whom he met in Abu Dhabi, where they have declared that “God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters, “ (Francis, 2021). He tells us that this was no mere diplomatic gesture, but a reflection born of dialogue and common commitment. Thus this Encyclical

takes up and develops some of the great themes raised in the Document that they both signed (Francis, 2021). The Holy Father tells us that in this Encyclical, he has also incorporated, along with his own thoughts, a number of letters, documents and considerations that he has received from many individuals and groups throughout the world (Francis, 2021).

a. Fratelli Tutti as an Invitation to Dialogue

By this Encyclical, Pope Francis does not claim to offer a complete teaching on fraternal love, but rather to consider its universal scope, its openness to every man and woman (Francis, 2021). He offers us in this social Encyclical a modest contribution to continued reflection, in the hope that in the face of present-day attempts to eliminate or ignore others, we may prove capable of responding with a new vision of fraternity and social friendship that will not remain at the level of words (Francis, 2021). He tells us that although he has written it from the Christian convictions that inspire and sustain him; he has sought to make this reflection as an invitation to dialogue among all people of good will (Francis, 2021).

b. The Covid-19 Pandemic and *Fratelli Tutti*

The Holy Father tells us that as he was writing this letter, the Covid-19 pandemic unexpectedly erupted, exposing our false securities (Francis, 2021). He writes that aside from the different ways that various countries responded to the crisis, their inability to work together became quite evident (Francis, 2021). He reminds us that for all our hyper-connectivity, we witnessed a fragmentation that made it more difficult to resolve problems that affect us all (Francis, 2021). He tells us that anyone who thinks that the only lesson to be learned was the need to improve what we were already doing, or to refine existing systems and regulations, is denying reality.

c. Purpose of the Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*

The Holy Father tells us that it is his desire that in this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universe aspiration to fraternity, fraternity between all men and women. In this Encyclical we have a splendid secret that shows us how to dream and to turn our life into a wonderful adventure. He reminds us that no one can face life in isolation. We need a community to support and help us, in which we can help one another to keep looking ahead (Francis, 2021). In this Encyclical the Holy Father teaches us the importance of to dream together. While by ourselves, we risk seeing mirages, things that are not there. On the other hand, dreams are built together (Francis, 2021). Thus, the Holy Father exhorts us;

Let us dream, then, as a single human family, as fellow travellers sharing the same flesh, as children of the same earth, which is our common home, each of us bringing the richness of his or her beliefs and convictions, each of us with his or her on voice brothers and sisters all (Francis, 2021).

Conclusion

Thus, seeing the present situation of the world Pope Francis by this Encyclical with the themes, fraternity and social friendship addresses us to build a better, more just and peaceful world, with an emphatic confirmation of a ‘no’ to war and to globalized indifference. He calls it as a social Encyclical, which borrows the title of the “Admonitions,” of St Francis of Assisi, who used these words to address his brothers and sisters. Thus this Encyclical aims to promote a universal aspiration toward fraternity and social friendship to build a better society as one human family and the enhancement and protection of the environment. To have a

fellowship with humanity in similar manner we read in Mark's Gospel:

They came to Capernaum, and when he got into the house he asked them, 'What were you arguing about on the road?' *They said nothing, because on the road they were arguing which of them was the greatest. *So he sat down, called the Twelve to him and said, 'if anyone wants to be first, he must make himself last of all and servant of all.' *He then took a little child who he set among them and embraced, and he said to them, *'Anyone who welcomes a little child such as this in my name, welcomes me; and anyone who welcomes me, welcomes not me but the one who sent me.' (Mk 9:33-37NJB).

References

- Collins, Michael. (2013). *Francis, Bishop of Rome. A Short Biography*. Bangalore: Claretian,
- Francis, Pope with Antonio Spadaro. (2014). *My Door is Always Open*. New Delhi: Bloomsbury.
- Francis, Pope. (2013). *Open Mind, Faithful Heart, Reflections of Following Jesus*. Bangalore: Claretian.
- Francis, Pope. (2016). *Post-Synodal Apostolic Exhortation, Amoris Laetitia. The Joy of Love*. Trivandrum: Carmel International, 2016.
- Francis, Pope. (2020). "The Holy See, Encyclical Letter *Fratelli Tutti* of the Holy Father Francis on Fraternity and Social Friendship." Retrieved 7 September 2021, https://mail.google.com/mail/u/0/#inbox/FMfc_gzGljlg_WwcMrc_dcmT_McrLnwrsWQV?Projector=1&mes_sagePa_rtId=0.2.
- Gandhi, M.K. (2005). *Pathway to God*. Ahmedabad: Navajivan Publishing House.
- John Paul II, Pope. (2005). *Apostolic Constitutions*. Trivndrum: Carmel International.

John Paul II, Pope. (2009). *Go in Peace: A Gift of Enduring Love*. Mumbai: St Pauls.

Joseph M.D. (2016). *Thrown into the World: An Existentialist's Approach to Life*. Guwahati, India: Ebh.

Joseph M.D. (2021). *Adolescence and Personality Growth: A Philosophical & Psychological Probe*. Guwahati, India: Ebh.

Murphy, M. Charles. (2014). *Reclaiming Francis How the Saint and the Pope are Renewing the Church*. Mumbai: St Pauls.

Piro Isabella. (2020). "Fratelli Tutti:" a short summary of Pope Francis's Encyclical," Retrieved 7 September 2021, from <https://www.vaticannews.va/en/pope/news/2020-10/fratelli-tutti-pope-fraternal-social-friendship-short-summary.html>.

Sheen J, Fulton. (2015). *Guide to Contentment*. Mumbai: St Pauls'.

Vattathara, Thomas. (2020). *Creative Fidelity in Mission: Reflections for a Personal Retreat*. Guwahati: Bhabani Offset & Imaging Systems Pvt.Ltd.

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The God of Small Things: A Literary Critique of la fratellanza in ‘God’s Own Country’

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Abstract: Deliberating on the concept of neighbour, in his 2020 encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, Pope Francis talks about the importance of becoming a neighbour to others by being “present to those in need of help, regardless of whether or not they belong to our social group.” Becoming a neighbour – it is easier said than done even by a society that is known for its exemplary human and social development, a Christian community that grew up on the parable of the *Good Samaritan* for close to two millennia, and a political system that not only promises but arguably fights for an egalitarian society. Detailing the sequence of events leading to the tragedy of Velutha, an ‘untouchable Christian’ and the

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ensuing fall of a ‘touchable Syrian Christian’ family, in her novel, *The God of Small Things*, Arundhati Roy depicts the failure of a society, a religion and a political system to become a neighbour to a person in need of help. In the light of *Fratelli Tutti*, this article analyses Roy’s depiction and critique of that triple failure in ‘God’s own country,’ Kerala.

Keywords: Syrian Christians, Caste System, Untouchables, Communist Party, Discrimination, Reform, Tragedy.

Introduction: On Becoming a Neighbour

The tragic plot of Arundhati Roy’s Booker Prize winning 1997 novel, *The God of Small Things*, unfolds through the reminiscences, associations and anticipations of the unfortunate sequence of events that took place in the Ipe family in 1969, and the account of what happens in the same family in the narrative present in 1993. The story is set in Ayemenem, a village in ‘God’s own country,’ Kerala, infamous for its caste-based social inequality and discrimination. While the Indian caste system (the theoretical basis of all forms of discriminations in India), dating back to about three thousand years, rests comfortably and complacently on the Eastern theological foundations of *dharma* (duty) and *karma* (work or action), it enjoys sanctification by the Hindu scriptural text, the *Purusha Sukta* of the *Rigveda*. Manu’s ancient text on dharma, the *Manusmriti*, which offers a schematic commentary on the caste system, serves as the fine print to what is said about this inequitable and unjust hierarchical system in the *Rigveda*. One main reason for the tragic turn of events in the novel is that God’s own country’s version of the unjust caste system is supported and promoted silently by the opportunistic Communists while they preach about an egalitarian society and adhered to by the Christians who teach the world that one should love one’s neighbour as oneself.

Paradoxically, this social tragedy unfolds in a county that abolished caste-based inequality and discrimination in 1950, in a society that is predominantly Hindu, in a milieu that is essentially Christian and in a political backdrop that is noticeably Communist. Discourses pertaining to society, culture, religion and politics converge at Ayemenem to ensure the death of a man who dared to defy the prevailing love laws, because, for many, such “a man’s death could be more profitable than his life had ever been” (Roy, 1997: 281). A poignant image at the heart of the novel set in this heartless world is that of the semi-conscious Velutha, one of the protagonists, brutalised by police, “abandoned by God and History; by Marx, by Man, by Woman, and—in the hours to come—by Children, lay[ing] folded on the floor” at Kottayam police station waiting to breathe his last (Roy, 1997: 310).

His skull was fractured in three places. His nose and both his cheekbones were smashed, leaving his face pulpy, undefined. The blow to his mouth had split open his upper lip and broken six teeth, three of which were embedded in his lower lip, hideously inverting his beautiful smile. Four of his ribs were splintered, one had pierced his left lung, which was what made him bleed from his mouth. The blood on his breath bright red. Fresh. Frothy. His lower intestine was ruptured and haemorrhaged, the blood collected in his abdominal cavity. His spine was damaged in two places, the concussion had paralyzed his right arm and resulted in a loss of control over his bladder and rectum. Both his kneecaps were shattered (Roy, 1997: 310).

This brutalised image of Velutha reminds us of the traveller who was attacked, robbed and abandoned by the robbers, as well as ignored by both the Priest and the Levite in the biblical *Parable of the Good Samaritan*. Deliberating on the Parable, in passing,

Pope Francis mentions in his 2020 encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti* (Brothers and Sisters All) a famous anecdote from the life of Hillel, the Jewish Rabbi of 1 BCE. As per the anecdote, once a heathen told the Rabbi that he would gladly accept Jewish faith if the Rabbi could teach him the entire Torah standing on one foot. Hillel stood on one foot and said quoting Tobit 4:15, “Never do to others what you don’t want them to do to you. This is the entire Torah. Everything else is commentary. Go and live it” (Outcalt, 2015: 62). According to Francis, when Jesus says, “do to others whatever you would that others do to you: there you have the Law and the Prophets” (Mt 7:12), he is endorsing Hillel’s teaching. This command of Jesus is “universal in scope ... [because, it embraces] everyone on the basis of our shared humanity” (Francis, 2020: 50).

The Priest and the Levite in the Parable are people dedicated to the worship of God. Their striking indifference to the suffering of the man who fell into the hands of robbers is the affirmation “that belief in God and the worship of God are not enough to ensure that we are actually living in a way pleasing to God” (Francis, 2020: 58). Jesus came up with the parable in answer to the question as to who should be considered as one’s neighbour. Probably, Jesus would have come up with the same parable if he were asked who should be considered as one’s brother or sister. The term, ‘neighbour,’ at the time of Jesus in Jewish society was used to refer to those close to us. Redefining the meaning of the term, ‘neighbour,’ Jesus “asks us to not decide who is close enough to be our neighbour, but rather that we ourselves become neighbours to all” (Francis, 2020: 63). In fact, “Jesus asks us to be present to those in need of help, regardless of whether or not they belong to our social group” (Francis, 2020: 63). Similarly, extending the meaning of the term, ‘neighbour,’ to the terms, ‘brother’ and ‘sister,’ Jesus would be asking us to be brothers and sisters to everyone

regardless of whether or not they belong to our immediate family. To be a neighbour to someone and thereby be a brother or sister, one must learn to see all as *Fratelli Tutti* – as brothers and sisters all.

Roy's multivalent novel, *The God of Small Things*, may be read as a critique on the failure of a society, a religion and a political system to function as a brother, a sister and a neighbour to those in need of help, epitomised in the novel's tragic protagonists, Velutha and Ammu. The Indian and the Keralite society that boast of their belief in the philosophy of 'vasudhaiva kutumbakam (the world is one family) and teaches their children to regard all Indians as their brothers and sisters, the Ipe family in the novel functioning as the microcosm of Kerala's Syrian Christian community that has grown up on the *Parable of the Good Samaritan* for two millennia, as well as the Communist Party that vows by the ideology of comradeship — all fail equally and deliberately. In the spirit of the universal brotherhood and sisterhood expounded in Francis's *Fratelli Tutti*, this article will analyse Roy's depiction and critique in *The God of Small Things* of this indefensible failure of a society (Keralite society), a religion (Christianity) and a political system (Kerala's Communist political system) to become a brother, a sister, and a neighbour to all, especially to the underprivileged and the vulnerable members of the human family.

1. On a Society's Failure to Become a Neighbour

The caste system, also called the varna system, which assigned the members of Hindu society to an impermeable hierarchical structure, is not only one of the most ancient and unjust social structures in the world, but also the most perilous fiction that has ever been said about humanity. The *Rigveda* traces the origin of the caste system to the mythical act and time of creation when the Brahmins were born from the mouth of Purusha (the Primeval Man or the Cosmic Being who sacrificed himself), the Kshatriyas from his arms, the Vaishyas from his thighs, and the Sudras from his feet. On account of their imagined origin from the mouth of

Purusha, the Brahmins are regarded as superior to the rest. The Kshatriyas are superior to the Vaishyas and Sudras, though inferior to the Brahmins; and the Vaishyas are superior to the Sudras though inferior to the Brahmins and Kshatriyas. Sudras, owing to their origin from the feet of Purusha, ended up as inferior to all the other three groups. During the later Vedic period, those born of inter-caste unions were assigned the status of the Outcasts or the Untouchables (known today as the Scheduled Castes). They were not part of the four-fold caste system; and they ranked below the Sudras in social status. To added insult to injury, the discourse of the retributive *karma* asserted that one's berth into a lower caste is the just punishment for the sins that one committed in one's previous life.

People were to perform duties to society in accordance with their birth. Therefore, while the Brahmins performed the duties of the priests, the Kshatriyas performed those of the military and political personnel, the Vaishyas of the cultivators, herders and merchants, and the Sudras of the servants in society. The Outcasts or the Untouchables were assigned the supposedly polluting duties such as tanning hides, scavenging, disposal of dead animals, preparing dead bodies for cremation and so on that people belonging to the caste system did not want to perform. Over the centuries, different vulnerable sections of society who performed such duties for their livelihood, solely for lack of other alternatives, also came to be regarded as Untouchables.

The name *candala* was originally the name of one such indigenous tribe. Its first appearance in the source material occurred during the Later Vedic Era but was not equated with untouchability. As their untouchability developed over time, all people associated with their way of life came to be referred to as *candalas*. Some members of Aryan agrarian

society were also added to their ranks by virtue of occupation, crime or vagabondage (Yamazaki, 1997: 12).

Even though the caste system in Kerala is rather different from that of the rest of India, until the middle of the twentieth century, Kerala had been a hotbed of caste-based social inequality and discrimination. While the conventional Kshatriyas and the Vaisyas are conspicuously absent in Kerala, the Nayars (whom the Brahmins in Kerala considered as Sudras) took the place of Kshatriyas. The Ezhavas ranked below the Nayars; and the slave castes ranked below the Ezhavas (Kurien, 2002: 45). Some historians are of the view that as elite merchants and traders, the Syrian Christians ranked somewhere between the Kshatriyas and the Vaisyas (Frykenberg, 2000: 155). Similarly, as traders, the Jews and some Muslims also seemed to have occupied the social position of the Vaisya caste. Despite being considered the Sudra caste, ranking just below the Brahmin caste, the Nayars were looked upon as an upper caste. Even though the Ezhavas performed the duties of the Sudras, they were regarded as untouchables (Kurien, 2002: 32). The predicament of the Untouchables until the early decades of the twentieth century had been rather dreadful. Recalling the wretched plight of the Untouchable Paravans during the years of her girlhood, in *The God of Small Things*, Mammachi tells her grandchildren, Estha and Rahel:

Paravans were expected to crawl backwards with a broom, sweeping away their footprints so that Brahmins or Syrian Christians would not defile themselves by accidentally stepping into a Paravan's footprint. In Mammachi's time, Paravans, like other Untouchables, were not allowed to walk on public roads, not allowed to cover their upper bodies, not allowed to carry umbrellas. They had to put their hands over their mouths when they spoke, to divert their polluted

breath away from those whom they addressed
(Roy, 2014: 73-74).

Shocked by the prevailing caste-based social inequality and discrimination that he witnessed in Kerala during his visit to the place in 1892, Swami Vivekananda writes, “Was there ever a sillier thing before in the world than what I saw in Malabar country? ... these Malabaris are all lunatics, their homes so many lunatic asylums ... Shame upon them that such wicked and diabolical customs are allowed” (Vivekananda, 1955-1960: 294). In the nineteenth and the early twentieth century, Christians with an untouchable lineage were not allowed to enter even the churches of the Syrian Christians. At the time of Vivekananda’s visit, the revival movements in the realms of religion, culture, politics, economics, literature and social consciousness in Kerala, known as *Kerala navodhanam* (Kerala Renaissance), initiated by the lower caste people, was gaining momentum. The unprecedented changes that followed the revival movement would place Kerala ahead of the rest of India in social cohesion as well as in development indicators such as life expectancy, literacy, healthcare, education, public health and so on. Nevertheless, the remnants of the evils of the caste system would continue to linger on in Kerala. The narrative of *The God of Small Things* is set at Ayemenem, a village in the ‘reformed Kerala’ of 1969 where caste-based discrimination was still prevalent. Born in 1961, and raised in Kerala, Arundhati Roy recalls her experience of growing up in Ayemenem plagued by the caste-based discrimination.

I grew up with my mother in a Syrian Christian family in Ayemenem, a small village in communist-ruled Kerala. And yet all around me were the fissures and cracks of caste. Ayemenem had its own separate ‘Paraiyan’ church where ‘Paraiyan’ priests preached to an ‘Untouchable’

congregation. Caste was implied in people's names, in the way people referred to each other, in the work they did, in the clothes they wore, in the marriages that were arranged, in the language they spoke (Roy, 2014: 13).

Even though the days of the Untouchables having to crawl backward with brooms were over by 1969, subjugation, deprivation and discrimination based on birth and caste were a reality even then. Velutha and his family in the novel are Paravans (members of a fishing community that ended up as part of the untouchable sections of south India). The Syrian Christian Ipe family's patriarch, "Pappachi would not allow Paravans into the house. Nobody would. They were not allowed to touch anything that Touchables touched. Caste Hindus and Caste Christians" (Roy, 1997: 73). If born an Untouchable, unfortunately, one could not improve one's social and financial status in the caste-ridden society in India. Hence, Pappachi's wife, "Mammachi (with impenetrable Touchable logic) often said that if only ... [Velutha] hadn't been a Paravan, he might have become an engineer. He mended radios, clocks, water pumps. He looked after the plumbing and all the electrical gadgets in the house" (Roy, 1997: 75). In the 'reformed Kerala,' engineering is certainly not meant for Velutha because, he is a Paravan! Despite Velutha being an Indian, his society denies him the fundamental rights that the constitution of India guarantees to every Indian citizen. As Francis affirms, "it is unacceptable that the mere place of one's birth or residence [or caste] should result in his or her possessing fewer opportunities for a developed and dignified life" (88).

The narrator of the novel comments on the predicament of the disadvantaged people like Velutha saying that Velutha's "lack of hesitation," his "unwarranted assurance," "the way he walked," "the way he held his head," the way he offered unsolicited suggestions, "the quiet way in which he disregarded suggestions without appearing to rebel" were laudable qualities in a person belonging to an upper caste. However, "in a Paravan they could

(and would, and indeed, should) be construed as insolence” (Roy, 1997: 76). As Francis says, when it comes to the vulnerable sections of society, “the law is no longer seen as reflecting a fundamental notion of justice but as mirroring notions currently in vogue ... everything is ‘leveled down’ by a superficial bartered consensus. In the end, the law of the strongest prevails” (152). In the case of Velutha, the law did not behave differently.

Velutha’s supposed ‘crime’ in the novel is that being an ‘Untouchable Christian,’ he dares to love Ammu, a Syrian Christian woman, an upper caste Christian woman, ‘a touchable woman’ against the love laws of the land. Their love is physical in nature. Though Velutha and Ammu are consenting adults as well as Christians, their love is seen as a crime in which Velutha stands to lose everything. As per the rule in *Manusmriti*, “A man who corrupts an unwilling virgin should instantly suffer corporal or capital punishment; but a man who corrupts a willing (virgin) when he is her equal should not undergo corporal or capital punishment ... If a man of the rear castes makes love with a virgin of the highest caste, he should be given corporal or capital punishment” (Manu, 1991: 159). Therefore, Vellya a Paapen, Velutha’s father, who though a Christian, has internalised the specifics of the appalling laws of Manu, waits “for hours at the door of their hut ... the edge of his axe glittering in the lamplight, waiting for Velutha to return” so that he himself could put his lawbreaking son to death (Roy, 1997: 283). As Francis asks, “What is law without the conviction, born of age-old reflection and great wisdom, that each human being is sacred and inviolable” (150-51). The Kottayam police almost completes the task that Vellya a Paapen undertakes but is unable to do. “Murder is not wrong simply because it is socially unacceptable and punished by law, but because of a deeper conviction” (Francis, 2020: 150-51) that “Human life, as a gift of God, is sacred and inviolable” (Paul II, 1995: 67).

As the clandestine relationship between Velutha and Ammu comes to light, in order to protect their supposed ‘family honour,’ the Ipe family files a trumped-up FIR at Kottayam police station stating that Velutha tried to rape Ammu; and after the former was dismissed from his job in their factory for misconduct, he came to their house drunk one late evening and threatened the women in family; and later, he abducted three of their children and murdered one of them, namely, Sophie Mol. Inspector Thomas Mathew who handles the investigation regarding the case knows well that the charges are false and Velutha is innocent. However, the unprincipled pragmatic in him persuades him to close his eyes against the obvious, realising that “He had a Touchable wife, two Touchable daughters – whole Touchable generations waiting in their Touchable wombs...” (Roy, 1997: 259). Therefore, Thomas Mathew sets his police force on Velutha “to square the books and collect the dues from those who broke its laws” (Roy, 1997: 308). After breaking his teeth, ribs and skull, the police handcuff Velutha and take him into their custody where he will succumb to his injuries. The narrator of the novel comments on the police brutality saying, “Man’s subliminal urge to destroy what he could neither subdue nor deify ... It was human history, masquerading as God’s Purpose, revealing herself to an under-age audience” (Roy, 1997: 308-8). The narrator goes on to say that by doing what the police did, “They were merely inoculating a community against an outbreak” (Roy, 1997: 309). Velutha’s crime – being a free citizen of a free country, he loves a consenting woman of age socially superior to him. For loving the woman, he is accused of breaking the supposedly sacrosanct love laws. His crime is interpreted as an ‘outbreak’ even by the police! “Ask any village policeman in India what his job is and he’ll probably tell you it is to ‘keep the peace.’ That is done, most of the time, by upholding the caste system. Dalit aspirations are a breach of peace” (Roy, 2014: 14). Commenting on the failure of the police personnel to function as agents of justice, as brothers, sisters and neighbours to Velutha, the narrator says:

If they [the policemen] hurt Velutha more than they intended to, it was only because any kinship, any connection between themselves and him, any implication that if nothing else, at least biologically he was a fellow creature—had been severed long ago. They were not arresting a man, they were exorcising fear. They had no instrument to calibrate how much punishment he could take. No means of gauging how much or how permanently they had damaged him. (Roy, 1997: 309).

The fear that the agents of law and order try to exorcise by fatally torturing Velutha is nothing more than what Francis terms as “a kind of ‘local’ narcissism unrelated to a healthy love of one’s own people and culture. It is born of a certain insecurity and fear of the other that leads to rejection and the desire to erect walls for self-defence” (107). The tragedy of Velutha and Ammu is a testimony to the failure of society towards its vulnerable members who need its protection, care and compassion. It is a reminder to all that “as our minds and hearts narrow, the less capable we become of understanding the world around us” (Francis, 2020:108) and the less conscious we become of the needs of our brothers, sisters and neighbours and our responsibility towards them.

2. On a Religion’s Failure to Become a Neighbour

The common profile of Christians as spelt out by St. Paul in Galatians 3: 26-28 tells us that in Christ Jesus all are children of God through faith; all who were baptized into Christ have clothed themselves with Christ. Therefore, among Christians, there is no room for any form of segregation or discrimination based on nationality, language, culture, caste, class, gender or any other parameter. All are one in Christ Jesus.

However, the Syrian Christians in Kerala would not easily look upon their brothers and sisters from the lowest strata of Hindu society baptised into Christ like themselves as their equals. The Christian faith they received from the disciple of Christ himself and the Christian tradition they pride themselves in fail to make them recognise their disadvantaged fellow humans as their brothers, sisters and neighbours. Unfortunately, as Francis argues, “A believer may be untrue to everything that his faith demands of him, and yet think he is close to God and better than others” (58-59). What makes a true Christian is not such convenient and self-righteous attitude, but rather, as Francis affirms, “an authentic openness to God ... [which] is a way of practising the faith that helps open our hearts to our brothers and sisters” (59). In adherence to the vile upper caste Hindu practice of caste-based social discrimination and untouchability, the Syrian Christians also look upon certain vulnerable and disadvantaged sections of society not only as inferior to them, but also as Untouchables, as if the latter were children of a lesser god. Does this not amount to masking, misrepresenting, manipulating and distorting the fundamental truths of Christian identity and faith? History can certainly prove how right Francis is in saying that unless we “learn to unmask the various ways that the truth is manipulated, distorted and concealed in public and private discourse ... those fundamental human rights which we now consider unassailable will be denied by those in power, once they have gained the ‘consensus’ of an apathetic or intimidated population” (151).

The privileged Syrian Christian community in the novel are depicted as active agents in denying Valutha, a less-privileged ‘Untouchable Christian,’ even his fundamental rights, let alone being a brother, sister, or a neighbour to him. These privileged Christians are certainly well informed about the fine prints of the fundamental rights; they have been conscious of what Francis reminds us: “The Book of Job sees our origin in the one Creator as the basis of certain common rights” (49); and they have been catechised about St. Paul’s teaching on the common profile of

Christians. However, their moral blindness does not permit them to consider Velutha as a brother, a neighbour and fellow Christian who is also an integral part of the mystical body Christ of which they themselves are parts, not more, not less. The gravity of the failure of the Syrian Christian community towards Velutha gets intensified by the fact that it is a community that proudly claims its Christian roots to St. Thomas, the apostle of Christ, and hence, as old as Christianity itself. The narrative of *The God of Small Things* tells us how even after two millennia of its birth in Kerala, Christianity, in many ways, has failed to inculcate the spirit of the *Parable of the Good Samaritan* into its members.

The Ipe family, the immediate agent of social discrimination against Velutha, are members of the Mar Thoma Church, a group of Syrian Christians in Kerala. In order to understand the underlying dynamics of the hierarchical social relationship between the Ipe Family and Velutha's family, one must delve into the two-thousand-year-old history of Christianity in Kerala. Though there is little evidence to ascertain the historical accuracy of the arrival of St. Thomas in India, as per the traditional beliefs of the Syrian Christians and the accounts in *The Acts of St. Thomas*, the fourth-century Edessa-based Syriac apocryphal book of unknown origin, he came to Kerala, India, in AD 52. The Indo-Parthian King, Gundaphorus was responsible for his arrival in India (The Apocryphal Acts of Thomas, 2001: 53-54). The Syrian Christians in Kerala known as St. Thomas Christians, refer to *The Acts of St. Thomas* "as evidence for the antiquity of Christian traditions in south India and for missions that the apostle Thomas conducted there in the decades after the death of Jesus of Nazareth" (Andrade, 2018: 2). The historical proof for the existence of the trade routes between India and the eastern Mediterranean at the time of Christ is often cited for establishing the possibility of St. Thomas arrival in India (Tickell, 2007: 19). Many scholars are of the

opinion that the proven existence of the “trade routes that stretched from Roman territory deep into Asia and the Indian Ocean to strengthen this premise” (Andrade, 2018: 16).

During his stay and ministry in Kerala, St. Thomas is believed to have converted some Brahmin families to Christianity and established an Indian Christian community in the Southern peninsula of India. Deliberating on the arrival of Christianity in India, the narrator of the novel says that “Christianity arrived in a boat and seeped into Kerala like tea from a teabag” (33). After having seeped into Kerala, Christianity grew into a complex blend of tradition, culture and religion. Since the initial converts into Christianity were all Brahmins, they not only continued to maintain their supposed superior status and privileges in society, but also adhered to the caste equations of Hindu society even after they embraced Christianity. Therefore, contrary to Christian tenets, the community remained rather reluctant to accept new converts, especially those from the lower castes to their fold (Tickell, 2007: 20). Talking about the underlying complexity of the Syrian Christian community in Kerala, in his article, “Hindu in Culture, Christian in Religion, Oriental in Worship,” Placid Podipara, describes them as Indians in every aspect of their culture, Christian in their faith and Oriental Syriac in their worship (529). No wonder they too have been practitioners of the Indian caste system.

The fledgling Indian Church had little or no direct contact with the Church of Rome. However, right from its infancy, it maintained its communion with the Church of Rome through the Eastern Church (which would later be known as the East Syrian or Chaldean or Babylonian Church) centred on Seleucia-Ctesiphon, the capital of the Persian Empire. The relation between the early Indian Church based in Kerala and the Persian Church goes back to the fourth century. Commissioned by the Catholicos of Babylon, a group of Christian trading families from the Middle East, in all probability from Persia (the present-day Iran and Iraq) arrived in Kerala in 345 AD under the leadership

of Thomas of Jerusalem, known also as Thomas of Cana. The local Hindu king, Chroman Perumal, granted them settlement rights in the land (Frykenberg, 2000: 155). Under the influence of the of these Persian Christian families, the Indian Christian community would grow in their Christian faith further. Soon, the church in India, began to be guided and governed by the bishops of the Persian Church. From the early fourth century, the Patriarch of the Persian Church provided India with clergy, holy texts, and ecclesiastical infrastructure. Hence, under the Persian influence, the liturgy of the Church in Kerala developed along the line of Persian liturgy in Syriac language, a dialect of Aramaic language. Following the decline of the Church in Persia in the fourteenth century, the Church in India was effectively cut off from the former.

The arrival of Vasco da Gama, the Portuguese explorer and trader, in Kerala, in 1498, and the arrival of Portuguese missionaries, thereafter, opened a new chapter in the history of the Church in India. In Goa, the Portuguese set up a colonial government and a Latin Church hierarchy under the Archbishop of Goa. Empowered by the *Padroado Real* (a series of treaties and decrees in which the Pope conferred upon the king of Portugal certain authority in ecclesiastical matters in the foreign territories they conquered), the Portuguese began their missionary activities in India. They began converting Indians into Christianity. Jesuits, Franciscans and Carmelites were the missionaries in the forefront of this mission. In Kerala, the missionary activities of Francis Xavier, a great sixteenth-century Jesuit missionary among the fisher castes “led to the creation of the second major grouping, the Latin Christians” who followed the Latin rite liturgy in their worship (Fuller, 1976: 4).

The Portuguese-dominated Romanised Catholic Church in India looked upon the Eastern Church (the Persian Church),

so also the Church in Kerala, as adherents to the controversial Nestorian doctrine. In 1560, the Portuguese “tried to eradicate the Nestorian heresy and switch the allegiance of the Syrian church [in Kerala] from Antioch to Rome” (Fuller, 1976: 59) which resulted in the famous revolt of the Syrian Christians in Kerala epitomised in *Koonan Kurishu Satyam*, Great Oath of Bent Cross. A group of those who took part in the revolt went back to profess their allegiance to Rome “then the minority but now the majority, are known as Syrian Catholics” (Fuller, 1976: 59). The rest of the group entered into a new communion with the Syriac Orthodox Church of Antioch, to form an Oriental Orthodox Church (Malankara Orthodox Syrian Church). They pledged to be under the leadership of the Patriarch of Antioch. The bishop of this group of Christians took the name Mar Thoma. Influenced by the Anglican missionaries, under the leadership of Palakunnathu Abraham Malpan, some Christians from the Oriental Orthodox Church began a reform movement combining aspects of the Protestant reformation and aspects of the Eastern church. This movement grew into another church that came to be known as Mar Thoma Church. The Ipe family in *The God of Small Things* are members of Mar Thoma Church. As we are told in the first chapter of the novel, Reverend E. John Ipe (Punnyan Kunju), Ammu’s grandfather was a priest of the Mar Thoma Church.

Unable to endure the discrimination and exploitation by the upper caste Hindus, many lower caste Hindus have embraced other religions over the centuries. However, unfortunately, their predicament has not changed because, “caste prejudice in the subcontinent trumps religious belief. Though their scriptures do not sanction it, elite Indian Muslims, Sikhs and Christians all practise caste discrimination” (Roy, 2014: 27). As the British established their political supremacy in the southern peninsula of India in the early nineteenth century, they began converting the lower caste Hindus into the Anglican Church offering them money and food as incentives (Tickell, 2007: 21). During this third phase of missionary activities, to escape social discrimination and indignities, many belonging to the lowest

caste groups in Kerala embraced Christianity in the nineteenth and the early twentieth centuries. The narrator of the novel says that it was at this time that Velutha's grandfather, Kelan, along with "a number of Paravans, Pelayas and Pulayas" (74) joined the Anglican Church and became Christians. Those who became Christians at this point in history are essentially looked down upon by society, even by the Syrian Christian community, as a pariah church (Fuller, 1976: 4). These Christians are often referred to as 'New Christians' with a derogatory connotation. If it was their desire to escape the prevailing caste-based discrimination in Hindu society that attracted them to Christianity, the material benefits that the Anglican Church promised them came as an added incentive which earned them the derogatory epithet, 'Rice Christians.' Since the constitution of India excluded the Scheduled Caste converts to Christianity from getting the benefits of the programme of 'reservation,' as the narrator informs us, they had a double disadvantage.

It didn't take them long to realize that they had jumped from the frying pan into the fire. They were made to have separate churches, with separate services, and separate priests. As a special favour they were even given their own separate Pariah Bishop. After Independence they found they were not entitled to any government benefits like job reservations or bank loans at low interest rates, because officially, on paper, they were Christians, and therefore casteless. It was a little like having to sweep away your footprints without a broom. Or worse, not being allowed to leave footprints at all (Roy, 1997: 74).

The Syrian Christians who continued to look upon the 'New Christians' not only as irreconcilably different from them,

but also as Untouchables were certainly not aliens to the spirit of the timeless message of Francis that “Those who look down on their own people tend to create within society categories of first and second class, people of greater or lesser dignity, people enjoying greater or fewer rights. In this way, they deny that there is room for everybody” (74). Regrettably, St. Paul’s affirmation that “there is nothing unclean in itself, it is only unclean for those who consider it unclean” (Rom 14:14) seems to have no impact on them. In irrational loyalty to the prevailing Hindu observance of purity and pollution, they are unwilling to allow these ‘New Christians’ “to touch anything that Touchables touched. Caste Hindus and Caste Christians” (Roy, 1997: 73). Though they have often heard the biblical assertion, “Not less than I, they too were formed in the womb by the same God who formed us all within our mothers” (Job 31:15), they refuse to pay heed to its message. Hence, they not only refuse to be a brother, sister or neighbour to Velutha, but also let him be murdered. In fact, they become active agents of his foul murder. Velutha’s unwarranted death is nothing short of the failure of Christianity itself.

3. On a Political System’s Failure to Become a Neighbour

Under the influence of Kerala Renaissance, the people of Kerala saw Communism as an antidote to the widespread social inequality in the state. To a great extent, “the widespread inequality in Kerala contributed to the Communist Party of India’s (CPI) success in Kerala” (Mahmood, 2017). Politically speaking, the election of the CPI to power in Kerala in 1957, may be regarded as the high point of Kerala Renaissance. As an earthly alternative to the Christian notion of the Kingdom of heaven, the followers of Karl Marx envisioned for the people a heaven on earth, a stateless and classless society of equals with equal opportunities. “Marxism was a simple substitute for Christianity. Replace God with Marx, Satan with the bourgeoisie, Heaven with a classless society, the Church with the Party, and the form and purpose of the journey remained similar. An obstacle race, with a

prize at the end” (Roy, 1997: 66). For many uneducated, poor landless agricultural labourers, the land and educational reforms that the CPIM government introduced came as a saving grace. No wonder, Marxism found acceptance among all classes and sections of people in Kerala. The leadership of the party as well as of the state passing through the hands of people ranging from EMS Namboodiripad to Pinarayi Vijayan is a testimony to the popular acceptance of the communist ideology by the people of Kerala.

In the novel, while Velutha, an ‘Untouchable Christian’ employee of Paradise Pickles & Preserves factory, is a card holding member of the Communist party, Chacko, its co-owner is a communist sympathiser who wants to organise the workers in his factory into a Union. At the same time, it must also be noted that many with vested interests, including the Syrian Christians, were averse to the communists and their administrative reforms, especially the Land Reform Act. As the narrator of the novel says, in “Kerala the Syrian Christians were, by and large, the wealthy, estate-owning ... feudal lords, for whom communism represented a fate worse than death. They had always voted for the Congress Party” (66). They were land-owners, traders and some of them even landlords and soldiers like the Nayars (Brown, 1956: 15) Quite complacent in their insulated world of comfort and security, in general, they were not proponents of change and reform in society.

Despite all the good that communism brought about in Kerala, it could not usher in a classless society. Often, the communists themselves are seen as perpetrators of discrimination based on caste. For instance, during a meeting between K.N.M. Pillai, the local communist leader, and Chacko, the former tells the latter that even the former’s wife, Kalyani, “will never allow Paravans and all that into her house. Never. Even I cannot persuade her. My own wife. Of

course inside the house she is Boss.” After making this statement, “He turned to her with an affectionate, naughty smile” (Roy, 1997: 278), with a sense of satisfaction and in appreciation of her conduct. Instead of rising above the caste-based inequitable social structure to bring about its promised heaven on earth, the Communist Party tried to maintain and manipulate this divisive structure for its own survival. The narrator of the novel makes a very pertinent observation in this regard:

As a reformist movement that never overtly questioned the traditional values of a caste-ridden, extremely traditional community. The Marxists worked from within the communal divides, never challenging them, never appearing not to. They offered a cocktail revolution. A heady mix of Eastern Marxism and orthodox Hinduism, spiked with a shot of democracy (66-7).

That is the reason why even though Velutha is an official card-holding member of the Communist Party and one of its committed workers, when he is implicated in crimes that he never committed, the party’s local leader, Pillai, refuses to help him despite being aware of Velutha’s innocence. Comrade Pillai, whom the narrator refers to as “Ayemenem’s own Crusader for Justice and Spokesman of the Oppressed” (303), tells Velutha who comes to seek his help in proving his innocence which alone can save his life, “Comrade, you should know that Party was not constituted to support workers’ indiscipline in their private life ... *It is not in the party’s interest to take up such matters. Individual’s interest is subordinate to the organisation’s interest*” (Roy, 1997: 287). Conveniently, the opportunistic Pillai refuses to let the Communist Party stand by Velutha, an innocent and helpless victim as well as a comrade. The local communist political system wilfully turned a deaf ear to Velutha’s desperate appeal; it let him be murdered. By omission of its responsibility, it becomes a willing participant in the murder of Velutha. Failure of a political system to be of assistance and to be a brother, sister

or neighbour to someone most in need of both! The narrator commends on this inexcusable failure saying, “And there it was again. Another religion turned against itself. Another edifice constructed by human mind, decimated by human nature” (287).

Conclusion

After Cane murdered Abel, when God asked Cane about his brother, in order to walk away from his guilt and his responsibility towards his brother, Cane asked God the proverbial rhetorical question, “Am I my brother’s keeper?” (Gen 4:9). Based on the story of Cane and Abel, we have the English phrase, ‘my brother’s keeper,’ which connotes to one’s responsibility towards, one’s siblings, one’s ‘neighbours,’ and fellow human beings in general because of our common origin and destiny as spelt out in the meditation on the ‘Principle and Foundation’ in the Spiritual Exercises of St. Ignatius of Loyola. We are all brothers and sisters — *Fratelli Tutti* — who together make the human family. Therefore, as members of the human family, everyone has a responsibility to transcend our world which has been “broken up into fragments by narrow domestic walls” (Tagore, 2002: 40) and reach out to others as brothers, sisters and neighbours. A failure to care for any one member of the human family is a failure towards the human family itself. Hence, the failure, be it of a society, a religion, and a political system to care for any person and become a brother, sister or neighbour is a failure to embody the spirit of *fratellanza* (brotherhood and sisterhood). Therefore, *The God of Small Things* may be read as a critique on the failure of ‘God’s Own Country’ in embodying the spirit of *Fratelli Tutti* in daily life, faith and practice.

References

- Andrade, N. J. (2018). *The Journey of Christianity to India in Late Antiquity: Networks and the Movement of Culture*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Brown, L. (1956). *The Indian Christians of St. Thomas*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Francis. (2020). *Fratelli Tutti*. Mumbai: St. Pauls.
- Frykenberg, R. (2000). India. In A. Hastings (Ed.), *A World History of Christianity* (pp. 147-191). Michigan & Cambridge: Eerdmans Publishing.
- Fuller, C. J. (1976, March). *Kerala Christians and the Caste System*. New Series, 11(1), 53-70.
- John Paul II, Pope. (1995). *Evangelium Vitae: The Gospel of Life*. Boston: Pauline Books & Media.
- Kurien, P. (2002). *Kaleidoscopic Ethnicity: International Migration and the Reconstruction of Community Identities in India*. New Brunswick: Rutgers University Press.
- Mahmood, N. (2017, May 28). Kerala in 1957. Retrieved October 28, 2021, from *TNS: The News on Sunday*: [https:// www. thenews.com.pk/tns/detail/563370-kerala-1957](https://www.thenews.com.pk/tns/detail/563370-kerala-1957)
- Manu. (1991). *The Laws of Manu*. (W. Doniger, & B. K. Smith, Trans.) London: Penguin.
- Outcalt, T. (2015). *Common Ground: Lessons and Legends from the World's Great Faiths*. New York: Skyhorse.
- Podipara, P. (2007). Hindu in culture, Christian in Religion, Oriental in Worship. In T. Kalayil (Ed.), *Collected Works of Rev. Dr. Placid J. Podipara C.M.I* (Vol. 2, pp. 527-450). Mannanam: Sanjos.
- Roy, A. (1997). *The God of Small Things*. Gurgaon: Penguin.
- Roy, A. (2014). The Doctor and the Saint. In B. R. Ambedkar, & S. Anand (Ed.), *Annihilation of Caste* (pp. 12-85). London & New York: Verso.

- Tagore, R. (2002). *Gitanjali*. New Delhi: Rupa.
- The Apocryphal Acts of Thomas*. (2001). In J. N. Bremmer (Ed.). Leuven: Peeters.
- Tickell, A. (2007). *Arundhati Roy's The God of Small Things*. New York: Routledge.
- Vivekananda, S. (1955-1960). *The Complete Works of Swami Vivekananda* (Vol. 3). Kolkata: Advaita Ashrama.
- Yamazaki, G. (1997). Introduction: Social Discrimination in Ancient India and its Transition to the Medieval Period. In H. Kotani (Ed.), *Caste System, Untouchability and the Depressed* (pp. 3-19). Delhi: Manohar.

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Abbracciando Tutti: Embracing All

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Abstract: The title of Pope Francis's 2020 encyclical, *Fratelli Tutti*, is very exclusive in its language though inclusive in its content. Many women in India as well as across the globe objected to the words *fratelli* and fraternity as they signal an insensitivity to the concerns of women and the signs of the time, which call for use of inclusive language and respect for the dignity of women and all persons. However, the text in itself is all-embracing and encouraging, as it exhorts practicing love, kindness, dialogue and sensitivity to transcend the borders of geography and distance and create bridges of friendship, equality, subsidiarity and solidarity. Embedded in the text is the clarion call

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to embrace all, '*abbracciare tutti*,' which requires respecting the

dignity and rights of women and others and giving them greater opportunities and protection. The article thus explores these themes in upholding peace, harmony, equality and the common good of all.

Keywords: Gender Equality, Solidarity, Friendship, Bridges, Universal Communion, Dialogue.

Introduction

While the title of Pope Francis' encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* (FT) is misleading in that it refers only to 'All Brothers', the content is all inclusive, integral as well as incumbent.

Hence, this article is titled '*Abbracciando Tutti*' from '*abbracciare tutti*,' which the pope himself uses twice in the Italian text of the encyclical (3, 60). Interestingly, the corresponding word 'embrace' occurs eight times in the English text. Using the gerund forms, *abbracciando* and embracing, implies an inherent urgent call to embrace all as brothers and sisters, beyond the constructed boundaries of class, caste, culture, gender, religion, language, space, distance and so forth. 'Embracing All' does not mean seeing and treating everyone the same but acknowledging and respecting each one's uniqueness and diversity. It is thus a more comprehensive and conducive mandate, challenging everyone to have a mind and heart that is open to all, that welcomes all, that can love and serve all, so as to enjoy universal communion and companionship. This was what was proclaimed by Pope Francis and the Grand Imam Ahmad Al-Tayyeb when they met in Abu Dhabi: "God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters" (FT 5). If men and women are created equally in the image and likeness of God, why is it then that many women and those of other sexual orientations are looked at and treated so differently from men? Why are most women vulnerable

to abuse, oppression, exploitation, and domestication? What is needed to restore the dignity, equality, and freedom of all persons? It is possible needed to restore the dignity, equality, and freedom of all persons if we uphold the vision of embracing all, which requires a move toward gender equality, building bridges, creating friendships and establishing solidarity. We find these themes developed by Francis in *Fratelli Tutti*.

1. From Gender Biases to Gender Equality

Sex and gender are often used interchangeably and even though attempts have been made to define and describe the terms, there is still confusion with the terminology and usage of the words. From the 1990s, sex began to be seen as a continuum based on biological and genetic differences while gender was considered as a combination of the personal recognition of one's sexual orientation and how one desires to be recognized by others. Thus, while sex refers to the biological characteristics that distinguish humans as female, male or other, gender is an acquired identity that is learned, changes over time, and varies widely within and across cultures. One's gender identity is determined by social and cultural norms and expectations and is influenced by psychological, economic, political, religious, and environmental factors. Sexism refers to gender stereotyping of men and women as hierarchically ordered (men over women). It enforces certain characteristics and roles for men and women on the basis of their biological differences, thereby excluding women from certain positions, places and privileges. Sexism is expressed in conventional images of women and men, exclusive language, sexist symbols, images and even advertising strategies. Sexism leads to unequal roles and relations among men and women; unequal values assigned to tasks and work; unequal access to resources, power and decision making. Sexism leads to all forms of violence and crimes against women including rape, kidnapping and abduction, dowry deaths, cruelty by husbands and relatives, molestation, sexual harassment, trafficking, physical, mental and

emotional abuse. Violence is a way to assert power and is often used to silence women and others on the margins if they attempt to change the prescribed order of things.

In 1993, India ratified the Convention on Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against women (CEDAW), and on 2nd April 2013 the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act 2013 was passed to ensure speedy trial in cases of sexual assault. The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013 came into effect on 9th December 2013 to ensure safety and protection of women at work and this was later followed by the “CBCI Guidelines to deal with Sexual harassment at workplace” on 14th September 2017, a thirty-page document issued by the Catholic Bishops Conference of India. Despite these Acts and the enforcement of laws, policies, and reservations in favour of women in the church and society, the position of women in the home, workplace, socio-cultural and religious institutions, has not changed much in the Indian context. Although there is an improvement in literacy, employment opportunities and health care for women, gender disparities, exploitation and abuse continue to affect women at all levels. They are most susceptible to being exploited economically, politically, socially, culturally and sexually. The Gender Policy of the Catholic Church in India affirms that “in most socio-cultural communities in India, women’s human rights are limited by religious, cultural and traditional practices that are based on patriarchal norms” (Gender Policy, 2010, 2).

There is thus a strong need for gender equality by which all persons can have the freedom and right to make their own choices and develop their potential to the fullest. The International Labour Organization in 2000 defined Gender Equality as:

the concept that all human beings, both men and women, are free to develop their personal abilities and make choices without the limitations set by stereotypes, rigid gender roles

and prejudices. Gender equality means that the different behaviours, aspirations and needs of women and men are considered, valued and favoured equally. It does not mean that women and men have to become the same, but that their rights, responsibilities and opportunities will not depend on whether they are born male or female.

The hallmark of gender equality is found in Paul's letter to the Galatians (3:28), where there is to be no discrimination on the basis of religious ethnicity, socio-political conditions and biological differences (Schüssler Fiorenza, 2001, 115). In recognizing that women have fewer rights mainly on the basis of their sex, Francis holds that women must not be excluded or denied a dignified life (FT 121).

While women and men are categorized differently according to socio-cultural constructions of gender, it is known that gender is not the only factor responsible for discrimination and oppression. There are diverse interwoven processes, layers and intersections of sex, gender, caste, class, race, religion, ethnicity, language and age that are responsible for the differing discriminations among people and even among women as a category. The term intersectionality was introduced to reveal the "reciprocally constructing phenomena" such as class, caste, gender, and race, that govern power relations and social inequalities (Collins, 2015, 2).

Intersectionality is a powerful framework to understand and analyse the complexity and multiple intersecting structures of power and discrimination that constitute and affect people.

Though intersectionality as a tool for analysis has become widely used in the twenty-first century in many disciplines, the idea of intersecting oppressions was already in use in India from the 19th century onwards by Savitribai Phule and her husband Jyotirao Phule who fought against caste, class, gender, economic and religious discriminations. (Collins and Bilge, 2016, 3-4). However, there is not much published on their lives and their great contribution since they belonged to

the lower caste. If gender equality is to be achieved in India, a substantial shift is needed from the intersectionality of oppressions to an inclusive interconnectedness that can embrace all persons and the entire ecosystem.

2. From Borders to Bridges

Borders or boundaries, in demarcating spaces, can either connect with others or create distances. It is not just about physical borders, but mental, emotional, psychological, and even spiritual borders that can prevent an encounter with persons, communities, cultures, and nations. Francis rightly notes that in the world today “the sense of belonging to a single human family is fading, and the dream of working together for justice and peace seems an outdated utopia. What reigns instead is a cool, comfortable and globalized indifference, born of deep disillusionment concealed behind a deceptive illusion: thinking that we are all-powerful, while failing to realize that we are all in the same boat” (FT 30). It is disconcerting at times to see the growing indifference, individualism and inhibition leading to indignity and isolation. It is only love, according to Francis, that can shatter the chains that keep people “isolated and separate” since love “builds bridges”, “exudes compassion and dignity” and “enables us to create one great family, where all of us can feel at home” (FT 62).

We are constantly invited to cross the borders that distance people and bridge the social, spatial, cultural, and religious divides. Thinking through the implications of such transitions requires a dynamic and creative theological and moral imagination – a renewed way of perceiving and imagining persons, cultures, religions, and traditions. We need new modes of knowing, new ways of being, and new processes of functioning in accordance with the mind and heart of Jesus Christ for our present context, time, and culture. The

incarnation was a border crossing event where Jesus crossed all borders to become one among us, so that he could bridge the gaps between humans and between humanity and God. As followers of Jesus, we are called to be open to engage in dialogue, create processes of mutual encounter, reach out to one another, and build bridges of love, compassion, forgiveness, and reconciliation (FT 203, 217).

While Francis considers forgiveness and reconciliation as central themes in Christianity and other religions, he clarifies that it is not about condoning an oppressor or “renouncing our own rights” (FT 237). Rather, extending love and forgiveness to an oppressor “means seeking ways to make him cease his oppression; it means stripping him of a power that he does not know how to use, and that diminishes his own humanity and that of others” (FT 241). In building bridges of compassion, “those who suffer injustice have to defend strenuously their own rights and those of their family, precisely because they must preserve the dignity they have received as a loving gift from God” (FT 241). The Church thus has an urgent mission to break down divisive and destructive borders, to build walls and to “sow seeds of reconciliation,” if it is to love and embrace everyone (FT 276). Respecting the integrity of each person, we can engage in dialogue with people of diverse religions, cultures, regions, and languages, and work together to eradicate the oppression and exploitation of women and other marginalized persons.

3. From Fragmentation to Friendship

A consumeristic culture with its focus on development and advancement leads to more production than what is required, using more than is needed, a use and throw mentality, dehumanization, and destruction of things. The rights of the poor and the marginalized, especially women and girls, must thus be safeguarded against the vested interests of the multinational corporations (MNC’s) that are controlling the market economy.

The Church in India through its creative use of media and communication can counter the advertisements and strategies employed by the MNC's that manipulate national interests and plunder the natural resources of the country. A model of mastery leads to fragmentation and alienation in contrast to the mystery model in which we are called to discover the common space in which each tradition, religion and culture finds its full identity.

Fragmentation can arise from disappointment caused by “unrealistic expectations,” exploitation from “unscrupulous traffickers,” abuses, xenophobia, separation of children from their parents who migrate (FT 39). Fragmentation is also from distancing, division and disregarding justice and human rights. The poor and marginalized continue to be oppressed and shunned, used and abused as objects of scorn, robbed of their human dignity and worth. Women are doubly poor as they have to often “endure situations of exclusion, mistreatment and violence, since they are frequently less able to defend their rights” (FT 23). During the Covid-19 pandemic women had to bear the most brunt of loss of jobs and working from home. Besides the stress from the double burden of working and managing the home, quite a few women had to put up with domestic violence, physical, verbal and emotional abuse and increase of demands from their husbands and children. The shared spaces of the home became like prison cells with no outlet for women to go out and meet other women.

There is a necessity for interpersonal encounters of kindness, dialogue, mutual listening and care for one another. For Francis, when “the dignity of the human person is respected, and his or her rights recognized and guaranteed, creativity and interdependence thrive, and the creativity of the human personality is released through actions that further the common good” (FT 18). What is needed is a sense of responsibility for all brothers and sisters, a creative openness

to the ‘other’, and protection for the rights of all persons (FT 40). With regard to migrants, Francis urges people to “welcome, protect, promote and integrate” them, thereby undertaking a journey together (FT 129). Embracing everyone on the basis of one’s shared humanity is from a universal command to love, which seeks the best for others and involves “a social friendship that excludes no one and a fraternity that is open to all” (FT 60, 94). Francis sees the importance of social friendships and a universal openness in love which goes beyond the borders of one’s family, community, and region to embrace anyone in need and thus expand one’s circle of friends (FT 96, 99). Genuine social friendships and universal fraternity enhance dignity, equality and freedom acknowledging the “worth of every human person, always and everywhere” (FT 103, 106).

Human Dignity, which is the key foundational principle in Catholic Social teaching (CST) sees humans as the *imago Dei*. The dignity and uniqueness of human beings as created in the image and likeness of God consists in their intimate relationship with God, which also implies a close relationship with other humans and with all of creation. Pope John Paul II in his Post-Synodal Apostolic Exhortation, *Ecclesia in Asia*, urged the Church in Asia to commit herself socially and pastorally to uphold the dignity of the human person and in particular to maintain the dignity, freedom and human rights of women since they are most discriminated against and treated as commodities (EA §33b, 34). He also emphasized the need for women to be given more opportunities to participate actively in the life and mission of the Church. This finds an echo in the preamble of the Constitution of India where justice (social, economic and political), liberty (of thought, expression, belief, faith and worship), equality (of status and of opportunity), and fraternity (assuring the dignity of the individual and the unity and integrity of the nation) are to be upheld and secured for all. However, social stratification marked by gender, race, class and economic status continue to affect the health and well-being of women and other persons on the margins of society.

In order to heal the fragmentation, brokenness and suffering that women and men continue to experience, we need to understand and accept the Trinitarian mystery of God which is a relationship of love, communion, equality and mutuality with no superiority, subjugation or domination. It is in community that we can learn to respect, appreciate, love and care for every person and everything and thus work together towards communion and harmony. Communion and harmony in the Indian tradition encompasses all of reality and can be experienced in the encounter of different cultures, regions and religions. The search for harmony in India is connected to “a worldview that is organic, interactive and cosmic;” one that seeks to promote life, wellbeing and happiness (Tirimanna, 2007, 111). While harmony in India is challenged by socio-political, cultural, economic, religious and ecological factors there is need for mutuality and collaboration not just to do away with conflicts, but to bring forth life and goodness. Communion and harmony do not dissolve hierarchy or positions, but it is possible to acknowledge and celebrate diversity and difference, collaborating with each other for a common vision as modelled in the Trinity.

For Elizabeth Johnson (1992), the Trinitarian symbol evokes deep communion among persons which makes for transcending binary categories such as male-female, master-slave. It indicates a genuine relationship of mutuality, radical equality and community in diversity with no domination or subordination but an encompassing of loving and liberating compassion. This communion or *perichōrēsis* signifying a revolving, cyclical movement manifests the intermingling and interweaving of persons and things (Johnson, 220). Such interconnectedness can enable humans to relate to others (within the family, workplace and society), to God and to all of creation, in a healthy and holistic manner so as to establish peace, harmony, communion and friendship despite any fragmentation.

4. From Self-Centredness to Solidarity

The Covid-19 pandemic has brought to our realization the fact that selfishness and self-centredness cannot thrive. This view is affirmed by Pope Francis who points out that we have become aware that “we are a global community, all in the same boat, where one person’s problems are the problems of all,” and since “we are brothers and sisters of one another,” it is presumed that “we can only be saved together” (FT 32). He also holds that the injustice in the world is due to a “[c]onsumerist individualism”, by which since “persons come to be viewed simply as obstacles to our own serene existence, we end up treating them as annoyances and we become increasingly aggressive” (FT 222). This type of “[r]adical individualism is a virus that is extremely difficult to eliminate” as it “makes us believe that everything consists in giving free rein to our own ambitions, as if by pursuing ever greater ambitions and creating safety nets we would somehow be serving the common good” (FT 105).

Self-centredness and individualism create rifts and boundaries through indifference and isolation. There is a narrow pre-occupation with one’s own interests and the concerns of one’s family, community, region and social group. It creates an in-group and out-group where the outsider is sometimes even viewed as a threat. Francis considers that “[c]losed groups and self-absorbed couples that define themselves in opposition to others tend to be expressions of selfishness and mere self-preservation” (FT 89). There is a tendency to hoard wealth, share less with others, and take and save more than one needs.

To counter self-centredness, Francis emphasizes the value of solidarity, which as a “moral virtue and social attitude”, expresses itself concretely in service, care for others especially the most vulnerable, “thinking and acting in terms of community,” and most of all, “combatting the structural causes of poverty, inequality, the lack of work, land and housing, the denial of social and labour rights” (FT 115-116). Solidarity is related to the foundational principles of human dignity, subsidiarity and the

common good. Thus, while working in solidarity, there can be subsidiarity at all levels to work for the common good of promoting the sustainability and flourishing of all persons. Solidarity creates shared spaces for co-responsibility, interdependence, and a sense of belongingness. A sense of solidarity can help to bring about a “universal consciousness and mutual concern,” which is so necessary in caring for persons and our common home (FT 117). This sense of solidarity must be first cultivated in the family where “the values of love and fraternity, togetherness and sharing, concern and care for others are lived out and handed on (FT 114).

Solidarity with the poor and marginalized and a commitment to respect the dignity and rights of all persons is a constant plea in the Church documents. Solidarity, for Pope John Paul II, “helps us to see the ‘other’ - whether a person, people or nation - not just as some kind of instrument, with a work capacity and physical strength to be exploited at low cost and then discarded when no longer useful, but as our ‘neighbour’, a ‘helper’ (cf. Gen 2:18-20), to be made a sharer, on par with ourselves, in the banquet of life to which all are equally invited by God” (*Sollicitudo Rei Socialis* §39). Francis goes further to look at a global ethic of solidarity “shaped by interdependence and shared responsibility in the whole human family” (FT 127, 146). This alone can lead to lasting peace, openness, welcome, concern for others and the common good Francis also thinks that the current forms of communication and proper use of digital media and the internet which offer “possibilities for encounter and solidarity” must be encouraged (FT 205). There is also an urgent need to cultivate solidarity across borders, regions, and nations so as to put an end to all forms of intersecting oppressions and discrimination created by colonialism, capitalism, patriarchy and social stratification and promote the flourishing of all persons.

Samuel Rayan (2011) sees in Micah 6:8 (“what does the LORD require of you but to do justice, and to love kindness, and to walk humbly with your God”) a program for embracing life by envisioning a renewed human community with an authentic spirituality. This spirituality consists in upholding love, justice and equity for everyone by challenging and subverting the systems and structures that have led to oppression and dehumanization of persons and destruction of the universe. It thus invites us to dream of a new world order where there is love, justice, peace, equality and solidarity.

Conclusion

The vision of *Abbracciando Tutti* or Embracing All, is one in which differences among persons, communities, movements and nations must be overcome to make room for people of different classes, races, social stratifications, religions and languages. This will allow all to live together, serve each other and work in solidarity and love to ensure dignity, equality, freedom, communion, harmony, justice and peace for all. In *Fratelli Tutti* Pope Francis rightly asserts that Covid-19 has taught us that “our lives are interwoven with and sustained by ordinary people valiantly shaping the decisive events of our shared history: doctors, nurses, pharmacists, storekeepers and supermarket workers, cleaning personnel, caretakers, transport workers, men and women working to provide essential services and public safety, volunteers, priests and religious,” and hence we need to embrace everyone as brothers and sisters and work towards “peace, justice and fraternity,” adopting a culture of dialogue as the path, mutual cooperation as the code of conduct and reciprocal understanding as the method and standard” (FT 54, 285).

How can we envisage this way forward of ‘Embracing All’ persons from different cultures, spaces and religious traditions with dignity, equality, freedom and harmony in the shared orchestra of life? Chitranina Ravikiran’s proposed concept of *melharmony*, projected to guide the use of harmony in modal music, can be used to symbolically represent this renewed vision.

Carnatic music is “one of the most colorful, complete and highly melodic systems of the world” according to Robert Morris and Chitravina N. Ravikiran (2006, 255). It focuses on “permutations of successive notes,” giving “equal importance to melody, rhythm, and lyrics,” placing “equal emphasis on composition and improvisation,” and combining “grace and force in adequate proportions.” It has “72 seven-tone scales,” with each scale as a “living entity capable of evoking or communicating emotions.” The theory of *melharmony* is “melody with harmony and chords that conform to the modal/scalar, sequential and ornamental principles of highly evolved melodic systems,” in which the leading voice at the same time is to be “derived from the melodic and combinational structure of the raga.” A raga in Indian music is a melodic scale or sequence of music notes in “a specific combination and permutation in both ascent and descent” (Morris & Ravikiran, 2006, 255). While Western music has tones in equal temperament and scales with four values (diminished, minor, major and augmented) or three values (diminished, perfect and augmented), Carnatic music postulates multiple chromatic values. Indian music thus has the potential for many combinations and styles. While “most ragas are neither equivalent nor reducible to Western common practice keys or modes,” it must be noted that “the issues of Western counterpoint and voice leading are intrinsic to melharmonic practice since Western music’s harmony grew out of the modal monophony of the Middle Ages and the progression of chords and their hierarchies are still based on melodic principles” (Morris & Ravikiran, 2006, 274). Thus, “melharmony is not about imposing harmony on modal music, but about preserving and enhancing a mode’s melodic identity in its harmonization” (Morris & Ravikiran, 2006, 274).

Is it possible to move forward from an envisioned world of harmony to a conceptual universe of *melharmony* with its echo reverberating locally as well as globally? While sacred

scriptures, traditions and structures are significant and need to be preserved, we need to see how can they be reinterpreted, reconstructed and reclaimed for the present context to enhance the human dignity of all persons for a melharmonious universe without borders, biases and selfish egoism. As Virgilio Elizondo (2008, 28) notes:

Borders will not disappear, differences will not fade away but they need not divide and keep peoples apart. Rather than being the fences of separation they can well serve as the reference points....

Rather than seeing them as the ultimate dividing line between you and me, between us and them, we can see borders as the privileged meeting places where different persons and peoples will come together to form a new and more inclusive humanity. Rather than viewing them as the ultimate chaos of mixture, impurity and disorder, we can begin to see them for what they truly are: the cradles of the new humanity.

Borders separate but they can also connect. They thus have the potential to build bridges and renew humanity although in reality it can be quite difficult and demanding. Borders even though they can never be fully dissolved, can serve as spaces for encounter, dialogue, communion and transformation. As Elizondo rightly attests, it is in the encounter with the other that we can be a source of revelation to each other, enabling new identities to emerge through the painful process of birthing and dying. This dying to a rigid exclusive position that one tends to have over religion, culture, beliefs, values, doctrines and so on is challenging and risky, but also much needed to build bridges of equality, friendship, communion and solidarity. It is only through genuine openness, engagement, reflection and dialogue that we can recognize the uniqueness and beauty of our own identity as well

as that of others and relate to each other with dignity, equality and freedom.

For true conversion to take place, we must be ready to allow God to touch us and heal us and make us whole. It is only then that we will put on the mind and heart of Jesus and see the world as sacrament and sacred. We will be able to experience God in everything and everything in God, thus being true *contemplatives in action*. Raimundo Panikkar's (Panikkar and Eastham, 1993, 55) *cosmotheandric vision* which is an extension of the Trinitarian mystery sees all of reality as a meaningful whole in communion that leads to equality and mutuality with no superiority, subjugation and domination. This "envisioning of all of reality in terms of three worlds," the divine, the human and the cosmos, is "an invariant of human culture, whether this vision is expressed spatially, temporally, cosmologically or metaphysically" (Panikkar and Eastham, 55). The three dimensions of reality coexist with each other in such a way that "they are neither three modes of a monolithic undifferentiated reality, nor three elements of a pluralistic system;" rather they are "one, though intrinsically a threefold, relation which manifests the ultimate constitution of reality" (Panikkar and Eastham, x). The *cosmotheandric vision* thus surmounts dialectical and binary relations by looking at the "trinitarian structure of everything," so as to stress the "intrinsic relationship" among the three dimensions of reality. It is an attempt to recover the "positive middle way between the paranoia of monism and the schizophrenia of dualism" (Panikkar and Eastham, 59).

For Panikkar, "the need for a unified vision of reality is all the more urgent since there are already many other unifying factors at work which may bring about a partial unification, but which ignore fundamental ingredients of the human being and consequently do violence to reality" (Panikkar and Eastham, 12). Rather than a global universal perspective which privileges one story or one truth, what is needed is an

open horizon, which is not closed up “in any single perspective, vision or system.” An open horizon enables us to cross the boundaries of our imagination and perception to discover and encounter the mystery in the other. The awareness of the “ever-elusive character of any horizon and its constitutive openness” (Panikkar and Eastham, 13), enables humans to relate to others (within the family, workplace and society), to God and to all of creation, in a healthy and holistic openness so as to establish peace, harmony and communion.

Despite the manifold borders and the interweaving of spaces over time, places and cultures, the all-encompassing *cosmotheandric vision* thus offers the hope and possibility of creating friendships and sacred spaces that cut across tradition, culture, religion, caste, race, gender and language so as to retrieve and reclaim the original state of belongingness and relatedness that all humans, whether rich or poor, citizens or strangers, black or white, can share as persons created in the image and likeness of the Triune God. Only then in true freedom, wholeness and ultimate meaning can we respond appropriately to the miseries of our time, and in particular to the fragmentation and brokenness that women and others on the margins experience. In learning to respect, appreciate, love and care for the beauty and value in everyone and everything, we can to some extent restore human dignity and work together for the common good of all, across any borders.

References

- CBCI Commission for Women (2010). *Gender Policy of the Catholic Church of India*. New Delhi: Catholic Bishops' Conference of India.
- Collins, P.H. (2015). “Intersectionality’s Definitional Dilemmas.” *Annual Review of Sociology* 41, 1–20.
- Collins, P. H. & Bilge, S. (2016). *Intersectionality (Key Concepts)*. Malden, MA: Polity Press.
- Elizondo, V. (2008). Transformation of Borders - Border Separation or a New Identity? In P. Gnanapragasam, & E. Schüssler Fiorenza, *Negotiating Borders: Theological Explorations in*

the Global Era (FS Felix Wilfred) (pp.19-32). New Delhi: Indian Society for Promoting Christian Knowledge.

Johnson, E.A. (1992). *She Who Is: The Mystery of God in a Feminist Theological Perspective*. New York: Crossroad.

John Paul II (1999). Post-Synodal Apostolic Exhortation *Ecclesia in Asia on Jesus Christ the Saviour and His Mission of Love and Service in Asia*. Vatican, Rome: Libreria Editrice Vaticana.

———. (1988). Encyclical Letter *Sollicitudo Rei Socialis* for the twentieth anniversary of *Populorum Progressio*. Vatican, Rome: Libreria Editrice Vaticana.

Morris, R. & Ravikiran, C.N. (2006). Ravikiran's Concept of Melharmony: An Inquiry into Harmony in South Indian Ragas. *Music Theory Spectrum* 28, no. 2, 255-276.

Panikkar, R & Eastham, S. (1993). *The Cosmotheandric Experience: Emerging Religious Consciousness*. Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books.

Rayan, S. (2011). A Spirituality for our Times. In K. Kunnumpuram, *In Spirit and Truth: Selected Writings of Samuel Rayan*, Vol II (pp.12-21). Mumbai: St. Paul's Publications.

Schüssler Fiorenza, E. (2001). *Wisdom Ways: Introducing Feminist Biblical Interpretation*. Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books.

Tirimanna, V. (2007). Asian Christian Perspectives on Harmony. In V. Tirimanna *Sprouts of Theology from the Asian Soil* (111-166). Bangalore: Claretian Publications.

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QUOTES FROM FRATELLI TUTTI

*“Nor can we fail to mention that seeking and pursuing the good of others and of the entire human family also implies helping individuals and societies to mature in the moral values that foster integral human development...Even more, it suggests a striving for excellence and what is best for others, their growth in maturity and health, the cultivation of values and not simply material wellbeing. A similar expression exists in Latin: *benevolentia*. This is an attitude that ‘wills the good’ of others; it bespeaks a yearning for goodness, an inclination towards all that is fine and excellent, a desire to fill the lives of others with what is beautiful, sublime and edifying” (FT 112)*

“Even when affronted, goodness is never weak but rather, shows its strength by refusing to take revenge” (FT 226)

*“Nowadays, what do certain words like democracy, freedom, justice, or unity really mean? They have been bent and shaped to serve as tools for domination, as meaningless tags that can be used to justify any action”
(FT 14)*

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Understanding *Fratelli Tutti* by Understanding ‘Understanding’

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Abstract: Understanding is oft misunderstood as a species of knowledge in philosophy by equating it with propositional understanding. However, understanding – which was regarded as a greater cognitive achievement than knowledge even in ancient Greek philosophy – is desired more than knowledge in both science and philosophy. So, revisiting understanding is the need of the hour by understanding its components, characteristics, and value. This paper aims to give an overall understanding of the notion of ‘understanding.’ Furthermore, by understanding ‘understanding,’ this paper also explores the possibilities of understanding the recent encyclical of the Pope, *Fratelli Tutti*.

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Introduction

We are living in an era, where human dignity and human rights can be evaded by selfishness and self-centred activities. The powerful remain in power and are ready to do anything to retain their power. However, the downtrodden are edged out of the mainstream to the periphery. In this self-centred world, the social encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* (FT) by Pope Francis comes as a prophetic call for a better, just, and peaceful world; inviting us to be peacemakers and “men and women prepared to work boldly and creatively to initiate processes of healing and renewed encounter” (FT 225). This social encyclical is an invitation to *understand* ‘the other’ – not only our neighbours but also ‘the strangers on the road’ (FT 56) through the goggles of love and compassion. It is a call “to build bridges, to break down walls, to sow seeds of reconciliation” (FT 276), by building ‘social friendship’ (FT 233) for ‘a more fair and fraternal future’ (FT 248).

When we read this social encyclical, the first thought that may overpower us could be, “What the Pope says is absolutely right. I have been brought up in a good catholic tradition, and I *know* very well all that Pope Francis tells through his social encyclical.” Of course, I bet that everyone of us know that we are called to be peacemakers (Mt 5:9); to love our neighbours as ourselves (Lev 19:18, Mk 12:31); to love the stranger (Lk 10:25-37) and even to love our enemies (Mt 5:44). Pope Francis also *knows* that his folk *knows* about what he has written. However, what he intends is not to enrich our *spectrum of knowledge* on these teachings of the Church, but in *expanding the horizons of our understanding* on them. The paradox of our times is that we, *knowing* the facts, refuse to *understand* them, and as a result, stay idle to

respond to the need of the hour. Jesus himself said the same about two millennia ago, “you will indeed listen, but never understand, and you will indeed look, but never perceive” (Mt 13:14).

When we say that we *know* but do not *understand*, then we are encountered with a set of spontaneous epistemological questions. “Doesn’t knowledge make me understand? Can’t I understand better when I know more? Is understanding different from knowledge?” Answering these questions will lead us to the ‘the mystery questions’ (Marcel 1949) that the encyclical poses to every individual.

In this paper, I, first, try to clarify the notion of understanding by differentiating it from knowledge. By comparing understanding with knowledge, I claim that understanding is a cognitive achievement and distinctively valuable. To defend my claim, I put forth two arguments: value argument and grasping component argument, which would prove us that understanding is different from knowledge and not a species of the latter. Secondly, I discuss a few unique characteristics of understanding, such as understanding is graded; holistic; requires certain special cognitive abilities other than knowledge abilities, and cannot be transmitted unlike knowledge, rather facilitated to others. Finally, I apply the derived conclusions in understanding *Fratelli Tutti* in the present context.

1. What is Understanding?

The question, “what can we understand?” gives us a variety of answers. We understand a subject matter, a phenomenon, a system, a mathematical calculation or theory, persons, feeling, places, maps, etc. For example, understanding the encyclical “Fratelli Tutti” is different from understanding why my friend got upset with me; or understanding how a computer algorithm functions is different from understanding the causes of recent floods in central Europe, the US and India, or understanding why something is the case is different from understanding how something is the case. Thus, understanding is multifaceted unlike

knowledge, because “knowledge is concerned with propositions, whereas understanding usually isn’t” (Prichard 2010: 74). Since understanding is multifaceted, it can be classified into different categories like propositional, interrogative, factual, objectual, explanatory and symbolic, not to exhaust the list. However, the type of understanding that I am concerned with in this paper is a subject matter, a topic (Elgin 2007, Jäger 2016), or a theoretical framework (Zagzebski 2009).¹

2. Understanding and Knowledge

Since knowledge and understanding are two main cognitive achievements, there is a tendency of titling understanding under knowledge as its species. One of the main reasons could be that one seems to require knowledge of certain body of information regarding a subject matter to understand it (Kvanvig 2003: 191). There is also a tendency to label it as an extension of knowledge, i.e., the more a person knows regarding a subject matter, the better she seems to understand it. Lipton (2004) is one of the proponents of this camp. He writes that “understanding is not some sort of super-knowledge, but simply more knowledge: knowledge of causes” (Lipton 2004: 30). Along with Lipton (2004), certain philosophers of science (like Achinstein 1983, Kitcher 2002, Salmon 1989, and Woodward 2003) also hold that whether it is knowledge-that; knowledge-why, or knowledge-how, when a person gains more of it, then she would understand better. They claim that “understanding why X is the case is equivalent to knowing why X is the case, where this is in turn equivalent to knowing that X is the case because of Y” (Prichard 2010: 74). The philosophers of science seem to zero down any type of understanding to propositional

¹ Understanding a theoretical subject matter, or domain of things is called ‘objectual understanding’ (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 5).

understanding and conclude that understanding is a species of knowledge.

Certain similarities between understanding and knowledge seem to give us the impression that understanding could be a species of knowledge. One of the main similarities is that “both knowledge and understanding involve true belief” (Khalifa 2011: 95). When additional explanations can make a person understand it well, then it seems that assenting to more true beliefs can make a person understand a subject matter. Assenting to true beliefs is nothing but coming to know them. For example, when a person reads a book on climate change by a well-known climate scientist, then she acquires knowledge regarding climate change. The process of knowledge acquisition takes place when she assents to the true beliefs of the climate scientist. So, the more she reads, the better she understands. Thus, assenting to the true beliefs seems to make a person not only know those true beliefs but also understand them.

Another similarity is in terms of conditions of knowledge. Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun (2017) claim that we could get certain conditions of understanding that could parallel the JTB conditions of knowledge. Understanding may require the belief condition, parallel to knowledge, when the understander “has to possess a representation of what is understood. It is further plausible that the representation must in some way be accepted by the agent, and so we get a condition that parallels the belief condition for knowledge” (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 6). Understanding may require the truth condition, parallel to knowledge. “Since understanding is a cognitive success, the representation needs to reflect the relevant facts adequately” (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 6). Thirdly, “it seems that understanding would not be a cognitive success of the agent if the agent could not provide good reasons for the representation that underlies her understanding or if her understanding did not result from a reliable process. This motivates a condition that parallels the justification condition for knowledge” (Baumberger,

Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 6). Thus, understanding seems to require the knowledge conditions, which once again affirm that understanding is not different from knowledge.

Apart from the philosophers of science, certain epistemologists also claim that understanding is a species of knowledge. Both Grimm (2006), who argues from the perspective of the psychological aspect of understanding, and Khalifa (2011), who takes up the antirealist perspective, argue that understanding is a species of knowledge.

However, other epistemologists (Elgin 2007; 2009, Kvanvig 2003, Pritchard 2010, Riggs 2009, and Zagzebski 2001) disagree with these philosophers. One of the main arguments that they employ to distinguish understanding from knowledge is value argument. These epistemologists strongly argue that understanding is distinctively valuable. All cognitive achievements are finally valuable. Understanding is a fundamental epistemic good and a cognitive achievement. Therefore, understanding is finally valuable (Pritchard 2010: 83, 84). When understanding is distinctively valuable, then it cannot be a species of something like knowledge. So, understanding is not a species of knowledge. When Pritchard (2010) and Zagzebski (2001) claim that both knowledge and understanding are distinctively valuable, Kvanvig (2003) makes it only for understanding. For him, only understanding that is distinctively valuable and not knowledge, because for him understanding is distinct from knowing (188).

Setting aside the debate between these two camps of philosophers, when we analyse understanding ourselves, we can observe that understanding seems to require something *more* than knowledge. For mere knowledge of something does not seem to guarantee corresponding understanding. The gained knowledge regarding a subject matter remains only as a chunk of true beliefs, until an extra cognitive work

is done with them. A person needs to do some extra cognitive work other than knowing something in order to understand it. Now the question is, what is this ‘extra element’ that makes a person understand a subject matter, when she knows it already. In order to answer this question, we shall begin with the components of understanding.

3. Components of Understanding

What are the components of understanding? Both epistemologists and philosophers of science would agree that *informational component*² is one of the building blocks of understanding (Boyd 2017: 109). Understanding requires two types of information: (i) *background information*, relevant to the subject matter and (ii) *new information* regarding the subject matter. Relevant background information is a prerequisite for the process of understanding a new body of information. Pritchard (2010) cites a case where certain background familiarity or information becomes a prerequisite to understanding a new proposition. He writes,

Suppose that I understand why my house burned down, know why it burned down, and also know that it burned down because of faulty wiring. Imagine further that my young son asks me why his house burned down, and I tell him. He has no conception of how faulty wiring might cause a fire, so we could hardly imagine that merely knowing this much suffices to afford him understanding of why his house burned down (Pritchard 2010: 81).

Relevant background information regarding faulty wiring helped Pritchard to understand why the house burned down. On the other hand, his son lacks such understanding because he does not know

² The term ‘informational component,’ means a body of *relevant* information regarding a subject matter, which is true and justified. Understanding requires *a body of information*, unlike knowledge, which can be acquired even with a single proposition.

how faulty wiring might cause a fire. Even though he knows that the house burned down due to faulty wiring, he may fail to understand it when he does not have relevant background information.

However, Boyd (2017) claims that *easy understanding* does not require any specialized background information (105). According to him, not all types of understanding need certain specialized background information, except *difficult understanding*. He argues that “most people [in general] possess the relevant background familiarity, knowledge, and cognitive skills..., for which they did not have to conscientiously develop” (Boyd 2017: 120). He claims that most of our understanding falls under *easy understanding*. However, *difficult understanding*, which can be gained only by the experts and epistemic authorities, requires certain specialized background familiarity relevant to the subject matter.

Though Boyd’s claim seems to be very lucrative, it does not rule out the basic and necessary relevant background information that a person requires to understand a new body of information. It is important here to note that *easy understanding* rules out only the sophisticated and esoteric background information, but not the necessary and relevant background information that a person requires even for simple (easy) understanding.

Secondly, an understander needs *new information or a body of new information*, which she aims to understand. In general, new information can be gained through perception, inference, or testimony, whereas memory plays the role of an information reservoir, from which an understander could collect her background information. Normally background information plays a supportive role in understanding new information. However, there are also cases, where new information could play the supportive role in order to

understand already stored information in memory. Say, a person simply assents to a body of new information (X_1) of a speaker at a point of time, t_1 but without understanding it. For unknown reasons she does not pay attention to X_1 at t_1 . While trying to understand another new body of information X_2 at a later point of time, t_2 , she happens to recall the non-understood information X_1 . Now also say, she comes to understand X_1 , with the help of her knowledge regarding X_2 . In this case, the new body of information X_2 at t_2 plays the role of background (supportive) information to understand X_1 , which was stored in memory at t_1 . So, supportive information need not always be background information rather new information as well.

Along with background information, background reasons also support understanding a new body of information. Unlike knowledge, which can be gained even with unrelated body of information, understanding requires both the body of information and reasons to hang together. For example, to understand recent phenomena on climate change, a person requires knowledge regarding gradual hike in the temperature;³ natural catastrophes like floods, forest fire, ice melting in polar glaciers, and the experts' prediction on the future global environmental crisis on the earth etc. She also requires the reasons behind these phenomena, such as CO₂ emission and Greenhouse effect, which caused by the anthropogenic activities etc. Thus, that the cognitive ability connects the links among the pieces of new information and reasons with their relevant background information and reasons, helps a person *grasp* a subject matter (Boyd 2017), which leads us to the second component of understanding.

³ The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Special Report on the Impacts of Global Warming of 1.5°C (2018) warns, "Human-induced warming reached approximately 1°C (likely between 0.8°C and 1.2°C) above pre-industrial levels in 2017, increasing at 0.2°C (likely between 0.1°C and 0.3°C) per decade" (IPCC 2018: 31)

The second main component of understanding is *grasping*. Unlike the informational component, which is common to both knowledge and understanding, the grasping component is unique to only understanding, because understanding has to do with the way in which a person combines pieces of information into a unified body (Kvanvig 2003: 197), and see how the body of information hang together in an order (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 12; Riggs 2003a: 218).

What is grasping? Grasping can be understood as (a) *fitting or placing the information in its relevant place in the web of information* (Boyd 2017, Elgin 2007; 2017, Grimm 2006, Jäger 2016, Kelp 2015, Lipton 2004, Malfatti 2019a&b, Zagzebski 2009) and (b) *fitting or placing reasons in their relevant places in the web of reasons* (Jäger 2016).

(a) As seen earlier, understanding required both background and new body of information, which need to hang together. However, placing them in the web of information requires understanding their dependency relations. Primarily, an understander requires to gain the grasping relations of parts to other parts and those of parts to a whole (Zagzebski 2009: 144), then “the grasping of explanatory and other coherence-making relationships in a large and comprehensive body of information” (Kvanvig 2003: 192), because “understanding is fundamentally the grasp of dependency relations” (Grimm 2005, Jäger 2016, Zagzebski 2009).

(b) Fitting or placing the reasons along with the information in their relevant places in the web of reasons is to be done parallelly while understanding a subject matter. Jäger (2016) claims that understanding needs the relevant background reasons along with background information. In his ‘Weight-of-Reasons Principle of Understanding,’ he writes that “the degree to which S understands a subject matter is proportional to S’s awareness of the relative epistemic

weight of the total available reasons relevant to propositions belonging to that subject matter” (Jäger 2016: 180). So, the more dependency reasons an understander has regarding a subject matter, the better she understands it.

The grasping component, which is unique to only understanding disproves the claim that understanding is a species of knowledge or an extension of knowledge.

4. Special Characteristics of Understanding

Apart from the value argument and grasping component argument, there are other special characteristics of understanding which would clearly distinguish understanding from knowledge. Philosophers like Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun (2017), Boyd (2017), Elgin (2017), Grimm (2011), Hills (2009; 2016), Jäger (2016), Kvanvig (2003), Malfatti (2019a&b), Pritchard (2010), Wilkenfeld (2013), Zagzebski (2009) list out several special characteristics of understanding. I discuss only four of them not to exhaust the list.

- (i) Understanding is graded
- (ii) Understanding requires certain special cognitive abilities
- (iii) Understanding can be facilitated via testimony
- (iv) Understanding is holistic

5. Understanding is Graded

Unlike knowledge, understanding comes in degrees. Since knowledge is propositional, it is always binary, i.e., either you know it or do not know it. However, understanding is graded (Grimm 2014, Jäger 2016, Moravcsik 1979) and progressive. An epistemic authority’s understanding will be more sophisticated than that of a novice or a layperson in the same domain. When a climate scientist explains the notion of climate change to her students, she would have a more sophisticated sort of understanding regarding climate change than that of her students, even though the latter know what climate change is. In this case,

both the scientist and the students have understanding but in different degrees. The example of Grimm may help us understand that understanding is graded.

When I start chopping onions and my eyes begin to water, I think I understand why my eyes are beginning to water, namely, because I am chopping the onions. I don't think it is because of the time of day, or the colour of the shirt I am wearing, or anything like that; it's because of the onions. But obviously someone with a greater understanding of onion (and eyeball) chemistry would be able not just to identify the onions as the cause but would be able to say what it was about the onions that was bringing this about - in this case, the particular sulphur compounds that were being broken down and released into the air when I did the chopping. What such a person would therefore grasp, which I would not, is that if I were to chop some other vegetable with these same compounds, my eyes would likewise begin to water (*ceteris paribus*); or perhaps, that if I were to chop an onion specially designed to lack these compounds, my eyes would not water; and so on (Grimm 2014: 337).

Grimm writes further, "what these facts seem to illustrate is not that the person who appeals to the compounds understands while I fail to understand, but that understanding comes in degrees; I have less of it, and he has more" (Grimm 2014: 337), the more a person grasps a body of information, the better she understands it.

That understanding comes in degrees implies that understanding is not binary rather progressive. The degree of a person's understanding depends upon not only the available body of information and reasons, but also her cognitive abilities, and the way she uses her cognitive abilities to grasp

the body of information and reasons. I would compare the process of gaining understanding to a spiral. When a person broadens her minimal understanding to higher degrees, she does it with the help of already existing (minimal) understanding. Of course, spiral understanding does not rule out any kind of new understanding at all, rather implies that existing understanding helps a person maximize her understanding to higher degrees.

6. Understanding Requires Certain Special Cognitive Abilities

Understanding requires certain cognitive abilities, without which an understander does not seem to grasp a body of new information (Boyd 2017, Malfatti 2019b, Zagzebski 2009). Though there can be a long list of such cognitive abilities, I list out the main one which are helpful to my current discussion.

The first and basic one is the ability to acquire knowledge of new information. Such cognitive abilities require reasoning and analytical abilities to justify the true beliefs. However, these abilities are common to both knowledge and understanding. The second one is the ability to find out the dependency relations between the different clusters of information and reasons. The third cognitive ability is to place information and reasons in an order and coherently according to their dependency relations in the web of information and reasons. The fourth ability is to gain the whole picture of the already placed information and reasons. The last three cognitive abilities are unique to understanding. There are also other cognitive abilities of understanding such as, gathering relevant body of information and reasons together; comparing and contrasting the gathered information and reasons with one another; finding the missing links among them; fixing them in the web of information and reasons in an order, and finding out a person's doxastic incoherencies and inconsistencies.

Along with these four abilities, there are two more characteristics of an understander. They are: answering new questions regarding the subject matter; the ability to apply explanations to

counterfactual cases and helping a person to understand by explaining a subject matter. These characteristics would function as a litmus test for an understander and help others to know the degree of understanding that an understander possesses regarding a subject matter. For example, when a climate scientist is able to describe a problem regarding the recent floods in different parts of the world clearly; explains it well and answers to the questions posed in a conference of other climate scientists, then it shows that she has a superior and sophisticated understanding regarding climate change, i.e., she owns certain abilities, which help her convert even the esoteric information and reasons into exoteric ones, and thus, make even a novice or a layperson in the domain understand them.⁴

7. Understanding can be Facilitated via Testimony

Testimony plays a vital role in acquiring knowledge and understanding. when knowledge can be transmitted via testimony, the recent debate in epistemology is, whether understanding can also be transmitted via testimony. The pertaining question is whether acquiring understanding

⁴ There are other cognitive abilities for understanding as well. For Wilkenfeld (2013), the cognitive abilities are those which would “manipulate some mental correlate of the understood object such that, in the absence of interfering factors, one would then be able to manipulate the target itself” (1003). For de Regt and Dieks (2005), they are the abilities that would “recognize qualitatively characteristic consequences of [theory] T without performing exact calculations” (151). For Newman (2014) they are problem-solving abilities. He writes “If someone has problem-solving abilities as well, she is properly said to understand a theory, which she can use to comprehend a whole range of phenomena” (59–62). I do not discuss these cognitive abilities because they may not fit in my discussion in this paper.

through ‘understanding-providing testimonial explanations’⁵ (Malfatti 2019a: 478) by a speaker can be called as transmission of understanding. In most cases, explanations seem to provide understanding, the latter being the goal of the former (Baumberger, Beisbart, and Brun 2017: 3).

The philosophers of science narrow down the propositions of understanding-why and understanding-how to understanding-what (propositional understanding) and thus, claim that all type of understanding can be called understanding-providing testimonial explanations. The understanding-providing explanations in a testimony seem to help a hearer connect the missing links and grasp the subject matter. For them, that a hearer’s understanding becomes broader with additional explanations in a testimony, proves that understanding can be transmitted.

However, I would say a straightforward ‘No’ to their claim, because the understanding-providing explanations of a speaker can only facilitate understanding in a hearer and cannot transmit understanding of the speaker. Primarily, understanding is the job of the hearer (Zagzebski 2009), and not of the speaker. Understanding depends on the cognitive work of the hearer. The understanding-providing explanations of a speaker merely transmits only the informational component and thus, triggers certain abilities in the hearer to do certain cognitive work to understand the subject matter. So, what a speaker can transmit via testimony is only the informational component of understanding and not the grasping component. However, the speaker can

⁵ Explanations can be of many kinds such as explanation-what, explanation-why and explanation-how. All types of explanations need not always be propositional. They can be tacit, visual; gestural, or symbolic. So, understanding can be gained through non-verbal communication as well, see Lipton (2009) and Khalifa (2013a). However, to make my discussion fit to my current debate, I take all three kinds of explanations as verbal (propositional) explanations.

trigger certain abilities to grasp the new body of information via testimony.

A Speaker can *facilitate* understanding in a hearer by helping him develop his cognitive abilities. An epistemic authority with her methodological superiority can help a novice or a layperson to understand the subject matter through her explanations, or by breaking down the esoteric propositions into exoteric ones. Thus, she helps him develop the necessary cognitive abilities to understand the new body of information. She may also use different methods to help the novice understand the subject matter, such as explanation, cross-examination, or asking ‘why and how’ questions, etc.

When a hearer tries to develop his cognitive abilities on his own, then it takes time for him to do so. However, an epistemic authority, with her methodological superiority and expertise in her domain, can quicken the process of developing cognitive abilities in a hearer by making him realize the inconsistencies in his doxastic attitudes, and reasoning; by showing him how to place his doxastic attitudes and reasons in their relevant places; and by helping him showing the missing link among them. Thus, a hearer can acquire understanding of even esoteric subject matter through the help of an epistemic authority with methodological superiority.

However, Boyd (2017) seems to claim that *easy understanding* can be acquired through testimony, because it “does not require much cognitive effort, nor does it require the possession of any unique or well-developed cognitive skills or abilities or any specialized background beliefs or knowledge” (116). Since the cognitive abilities of *easy understanding* are *not* highly sophisticated as those of *difficult understanding*, he claims that a person will be able to grasp even connections between relevant bits of knowledge in *easy understanding* (Boyd 2017: 115). And so,

he claims that *easy understanding* via testimony could be transmitted because “the grasping that is required for understanding can occur automatically at the level of processing the testified information” (Boyd 2017: 119).

Boyd (2017) seems to parallel the cognitive abilities of *easy understanding* with those of knowledge, by naïvely claiming that *easy understanding* does not seem to require any sophisticated cognitive abilities. He writes that

easy understanding involves understanding for which most people possess the relevant background familiarity, knowledge, and cognitive skills, but for which they did not have to conscientiously develop, and... once these background conditions are in place, one can potentially gain *easy understanding* through testimony since the grasping that is required for understanding can occur automatically at the level of processing the testified information (Boyd 2017: 120).

His claim that the job of the hearer in every knowledge transmission via testimony is “to *make sense of the content* of speaker’s testimony, and to *conceive* of the testifier or the content of her testimony in the *right way*” (Boyd 2017: 117 paraphrased and italicized by author) seems naïve, because he seems to take the grasping component of understanding for granted, by equating it with mere knowledge acquisition. When “people possess the relevant background familiarity, knowledge, and cognitive skills,” (Boyd 2017: 120) of course, grasping can be done without any other *extra* cognitive work. However, this does not mean that understanding can be transmitted by testimony. The already possessed “relevant background familiarity, knowledge, and cognitive skills” still remain as cognitive success of the hearer and not the speaker. Thus, understanding can be gained only as the result of the individual understander’s cognitive work (Zagzebski 2009). And so, it is non-transmittable via testimony.

8. Understanding is Holistic

One of the main characteristics of understanding is that it is holistic in nature (Brogaard 2015, Baumberger, Beisbart and Brun 2017, Elgin 2007; Pritchard 2010). A person can gain knowledge even through a single or a chunk of unrelated propositions. However, understanding requires a body of information, which are not only pieced together by the understander (Kvanvig 2003: 192; Malfatti 2019a&b), but also placed coherently in a relevant order. A person cannot understand a subject matter with a chunk of unrelated information, because along with a body of information, “understanding requires the grasping of explanatory and other coherence-making relationships in a large and comprehensive body of information” (Kvanvig 2003: 192). So, one cannot understand an atomistic information without understanding a larger body of information where it fits in (Brogaard 2005, Pritchard 2010). Therefore, unlike knowledge, understanding is holistic.

We have already seen that understanding requires not only new information and reasons but also background information and reasons. Moreover, understanding is possible only when we thread background information and reasons with new ones and place them in their relevant places in the web of information and reasons. When we fail to grasp any of the informational; explanatory or coherence-making relationships in the web of information, then we would end up in not understanding the subject matter. Though it may be possible for us to understand a few different clusters of information here and there regarding the subject matter, it may not be possible for me to gain an overall understanding of the subject matter, merely because understanding is holistic.

9. Is Understanding Desired Better than Knowledge?

The four special characteristics of understanding contrast understanding from knowledge, and thus, prove that understanding is neither a species of knowledge nor an extension of it. For Kvanvig (2003) understanding is desired better than knowledge. However, desiring understanding better than knowledge is not new to philosophy, “the concept of understanding was central in ancient Greek philosophy” (Moravcsik 1979: 56), because “mere knowledge of truths is of no interest to Plato” but only understanding (Moravcsik 1979: 60). In most of his Socratic Dialogues, Plato seems to aim at helping his interlocuters become aware of their doxastic inconsistencies in their arguments. Moravcsik (1979) further writes that “understanding, according to Plato, involves insight, and this insight is the grasp of, or having an adequate concept of, special abstract entities, the Forms, which make up the domain that understanding is concerned with” (59-60). So, from ancient Greek philosophy it was understanding, which was desired better than knowledge.

When understanding is desired better than mere knowledge, then understanding *Fratelli Tutti* (FT) would be better than having mere knowledge of it. By reading this social encyclical, we may come to know what the Pope wants to tell us through this encyclical. However, mere knowledge should not be our aim, rather understanding *Fratelli Tutti* by understanding what the Pope really invites us to do.

10. Understanding *Fratelli Tutti*

Walking on the footsteps of St. Francis of Assisi, Pope Francis aims, in his *Fratelli Tutti*, to promote a universal aspiration toward fraternity and social friendship (FT 5). It is a call not only to the Catholics, but also to the entire human race to conscientize oneself regarding his/her own very purpose of life on earth.

As I have said in the introduction, the first response of every reader would be to take *Fratelli Tutti* for granted, by saying “Yes, I know it already, because *Fratelli Tutti* reiterates the core Biblical teaching of loving the other.” However, the hidden danger is that when we limit ourselves with mere knowledge acquisition, then we may fall prey to certain epistemic arrogance of knowing things without understanding them. However, understanding *Fratelli Tutti* would open our minds and lead us to action.

In order to understand *Fratelli Tutti*, which is a body of new information, we may have to have a good backup of the background information regarding the major concerns that the Pope has cited in this social encyclical. Firstly, regarding the ‘dark clouds that have covered our world’ such as manipulation of freedom, democracy, and justice; selfishness and indifferent to common good; hunger for modern gadgets; the culture of waste, and disrespect to human dignity etc. Then, we must also get to know the background reasons why we ignore ‘the stranger on the road.’ Secondly, we need to grasp *Fratelli Tutti* in the right way. Grasping *Fratelli Tutti* demands us to place ourselves in the place of victims first. For we must understand that all that the Pope has said need not be a distant happening to a third person elsewhere in the world, and as if they might not affect me and my family here and now. However, grasping *Fratelli Tutti* demands the realization of the bitter truth that “I may be the next victim anytime in the future.” Pope’s concerns raise certain mystery questions, which involve every one of us. When I place myself in the context and use my cognitive abilities to grasp *Fratelli Tutti*, only then my understanding will be holistic.

Most importantly, understanding *Fratelli Tutti* calls for action, which must begin from oneself. One must treat the strangers with respect and dignity, making this world a place for all to live without fear, and teach the future generation to

be so, not only by words but deeds. For being “men and women prepared to work boldly and creatively to initiate processes of healing and renewed encounter” (FT 225) is a collective, synergical and challenging teamwork. Only when we join our hands together, for both prayer and action, then we can fulfil the dream and desire of the Pope and would contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person (FT 8).

References

- Achinstein, P. 1983. *The Nature of Explanation*. Oxford University Press.
- Baumberger, C., Beisbart, C. & Brun, G. 2017. What Is Understanding? In S. R. Grimm, C. Baumberger, & S. Ammon (Eds.), *Explaining Understanding* (pp. 1-34). Routledge.
- Boyd, K. 2017. Testifying Understanding. *Episteme*, 14(1), 123-127.
- Carter, A. & Emma G. 2014. Objectual Understanding and the Value Problem. *American Philosophical Quarterly*, 51, 1-14.
- de Regt, H. 2009a. The Epistemic Value of Understanding. *Philosophy of Science*, 76, 585-597.
- de Regt, H. 2009b. Understanding and Scientific Explanation. In H. de Regt, S. Leonelli & K. Eigner (Eds.), *Scientific Understanding* (pp. 21-42). University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Elgin, C. 2007. Understanding and the Facts. *Philosophical Studies*, 132(1), 33-42. doi:10.1007/s11098-006-9054-z.
- Elgin, C. 2009. Is Understanding Factive? In A. Haddock, A. Millar & D. Pritchard (Eds.), *Epistemic Value* (pp. 322-330). Oxford University Press.
- Elgin, C. 2017. *True Enough*. MIT Press.

- Francis, Pope. 2020. *Fratelli Tutti: On Fraternity and Social Friendship*. Orbis Books.
- Gardiner, G. 2012. Understanding, Integration, and Epistemic Value. *Acta Analytica*, 27, 163-181.
- Greco, J. 2010. *Achieving Knowledge. A Virtue Theoretic Account of Epistemic Normativity*. Cambridge University Press.
- Greco, J. 2014. Episteme: Knowledge and Understanding. In K. Timpe & C. A. Boyd (Eds.), *Virtues and Their Vices* (pp. 284–301). Oxford University Press.
- Greco, J. 2020. The Transmission of Knowledge and Garbage. *Synthese*, 197, 2867-2878.
- Grimm, S. 2006. Is Understanding a Species of Knowledge? *British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 57, 515-535.
- Grimm, S. 2011. Understanding. In S. Bernecker & D. Pritchard (Eds.), *The Routledge Companion to Epistemology* (pp. 84-94). Routledge.
- Grimm, S. 2014. Understanding as Knowledge of Causes. In A. Fairweather (Ed.), *Virtue Epistemology Naturalized: Bridges Between Virtue Epistemology and Philosophy of Science* (pp. 329-346). Springer.
- Hills, A. 2009. Moral Testimony and Moral Epistemology. *Ethics*, 120, 94-127. doi:10.1086/648610.
- Hills, A. 2016. Understanding Why. *Noûs*, 50(4), 661-688. doi:10.1111/nous.12092.
- IPCC. 2019. Special Report on “Global Warming of 1.5 °C.” <https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>.
- Jäger, C. 2016. Epistemic Authority, Preemptive Reasons, and Understanding. *Episteme*, 13(2), 167-185.

- Kelp, C. 2015. Understanding Phenomena. *Synthese*, 192(12), 3799–3816. doi:10.1007/s11229-014-0616-x.
- Khalifa, K. 2011. Understanding, Knowledge, and Scientific Antirealism. *Grazer Philosophische Studien*, 83, 93-112.
- Khalifa, K. 2012. Inaugurating Understanding or Repackaging Explanation? *Philosophy of Science*, 79, 15-37. doi:10.1086/663235.
- Khalifa, K. 2013a. The Role of Explanation in Understanding. *The British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 64(1), 161-187. JSTOR: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23356461>.
- Khalifa, K. 2013b. Understanding, Grasping and Luck. *Episteme*, 10, 1-17 doi:10.1017/eipi.2013.6
- Kitcher, P. 2002. Scientific Knowledge. *Moser*, 385-407.
- Kvanvig, J. 2003. *The Value of Knowledge and the Pursuit of Understanding*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kvanvig, J. 2009a. The Value of Understanding. In A. Haddock, A. Millar and D. Pritchard (Eds.), *Epistemic Value* (pp. 95-111). Oxford University Press.
- Kvanvig, J. 2009b. Response to Critics. In A. Haddock, A. Millar and D. Pritchard (Eds.), *Epistemic Value* (pp. 339-351). Oxford University Press.
- Lipton, P. 2004. *Inference to the Best Explanation* (2nd ed.). Routledge.
- Lipton, P. 2009. Understanding without Explanation. In H. de Regt, S. Leonelli and K. Eigner (Eds.), *Scientific Understanding* (pp. 43-63). University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Longworth, G. 2008. Linguistic Understanding and Knowledge. *Noûs*, 42(1), 50-79.

- Malfatti, F. 2019a. On Understanding Testimony. *Erkenntnis*, 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10670-019-00157-8>.
- Malfatti, F. 2019b. Can Testimony Generate Understanding? *Social Epistemology*, 33(6), 477-490. DOI: 10.1080/02691728.2019.1628319.
- Marcel, G. 1949. *Being and Having* (K. Farrer, Trans.). Dacre Press Westminster.
- Moravcsik, J. 1979. Understanding and Knowledge in Plato's Philosophy. *Neue Hefte für Philosophie*, 15, 53-69.
- Morris, K. 2012. A Defense of Lucky Understanding. *British Journal for the Philosophy of Science*, 63, 357-371.
- Pritchard, D. 2008. Knowing the Answer, Understanding and Epistemic Value. *Grazer Philosophische Studien*, 77, 325-339.
- Pritchard, D. 2010. Knowledge and Understanding. In D. Pritchard, A. Millar & A. Haddock (Eds.), *The Nature and Value of Knowledge: Three Investigations* (pp. 3-90). Oxford University Press.
- Pritchard, D., Millar, A. & Haddock, A. 2010. *The Nature and Value of Knowledge: Three Investigations*. Oxford University Press.
- Riggs, W. 2003a. Understanding 'Virtue' and the Virtue of Understanding. In M. DePaul & L. Zagzebski (Eds.), *Intellectual Virtue* (pp. 203-226). Clarendon Press.
- Riggs, W. 2003b. Balancing Our Epistemic Goals. *Noûs*, 37, 342-52.
- Riggs, W. 2009. Understanding, Knowledge, and the Meno Requirement. In A. Haddock, A. Millar & D. Pritchard

(Eds.), *Epistemic Value* (pp. 331-38). Oxford University Press.

Rohwer, Y. 2014. Lucky Understanding without Knowledge. *Synthese*, 191, 945-959.

Salmon, W. 1989. *Four Decades of Scientific Explanation*. University of Minnesota Press.

Woodward, J. 2003. *Making Things Happen: A Theory of Causal Explanation*. Oxford University Press.

Zagzebski, L. 2009. *On Epistemology*. Wadsworth.

Zagzebski, L. 2001. Recovering Understanding. In M. Steup (Ed.), *Knowledge, Truth, and Duty* (pp. 235-251). Oxford University Press.

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Review Article Continuing the Pastoral Approach of Pope Francis

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Menampampil, Archbishop Thomas SDB. *Attempt the Impossible*. Mumbai: St. Paul's India. ISBN: 978-93-5015-388-8 pp. 442 ₹ 450.

This book, *Attempt the Impossible*, is a carefully selected collection of articles by Archbishop Menampampil on the sharing of the Christian Message in the contemporary world of uncertainty where the search for meaning and purposefulness is also growing intensely.

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In an increasingly secularized world where every tenet of the Faith is being questioned every day, it has become most challenging to explain our religious convictions, remaining always open to newly emerging perspectives on life. “Return to the ways of the Acts of the Apostles”, says Archbishop Thomas. It is an exciting mission to ‘Attempt the Impossible,’ without which human life itself becomes impossible!

1. Rooted in the Sense of the Divine

Our hearts are strongly entrenched in a desire to discover what is beyond our horizon. As a result, the collection's first article, “The Lure of the Unseen,” lures us into the world of the invisible, the world of Transcendence. A yearning for the unseen has taken root in our hearts. The visionless direction of today has uprooted man from customary security and suffocated* his or her inner essence. His frenzied search for any form of; religious experience is a restless attempt to break free from a meaningless materialism. If no one can help him, he will become lost in a sea of curiosities and thrills, as well as fleeting religious experiences.

“The Sense of the Sacred,” the next chapter, builds on the previous chapter's ideas. Then it emphasizes that our secularized society owes a lot to (tribal) societies that have kept the Sacred Sense alive. In truth, all modern thought and achievements are the culmination and continuance of the quest for meaning.

The following chapter, “Those Who Take Their Commitment Seriously Ought to Act as a Dynamic Force,” examines the current conflict scenario to ensure that religion is not used as an excuse to avoid civic responsibilities. Religious people, on the other hand, should be beneficent and active in working for the general good. Their religious beliefs have helped them to bring authenticity and radical giving to the cause. They should have an informed and well-researched attitude to social issues, as well as a balanced perspective on the situation. Religious Congregations, it should be noted, come into existence with a strong sense of mission and a high level of motivation, and promotion of a Sense

of Solidarity and Purpose in Society shows that Church personnel can offer themselves as an intellectual and spiritual renewal of religious commitment, and promotion of a Sense of Solidarity and Purpose in Society shows that Religious Congregations come into existence with a strong sense of mission and a high level of motivation. It is the responsibility of every member to re-motivate fellow-religious if this zeal wanes. They give back to society in partnership with their fellow believers and all good people.

Sharing one's essential convictions is at the centre of a missionary's ministry to society, according to "Sharing the Gospel Today." As a result, they become living symbols of God's love for His people, willing to lay down their lives if necessary. Their activities, such as education, health, and social service, gains a sign-value as a result of their status as icons. This also adds to their society's cultural and moral renewal. In a society of godless consumerism and violent extremism, they bear witness to their religious convictions. Believers will benefit from collective self-criticism in order to maintain their principles and stay faithful to their aspirations. Part of this self-criticism is learning to live with problems. Much of the persecution that missionaries endure today stems from simple misunderstandings in the community. Neighbours' sensitivities and concerns must be taken into account. Most problems can be avoided by interacting respectfully with the local community. The importance of cultural incorporation cannot be overstated.

The author believes that a human approach will always win a human response. Religious faith is very much alive in Asia, according to *Whispering the Gospel to the Soul of Asia*, and people are inspired by Jesus' words. The current issue is that religion is tied to Cultural Nationalism in many areas. There is also the widely held belief that religious propagation is an unjustified interference with people's culture. Despite this, every international religion saw conveying its basic message

as a primary responsibility. It should be given with the utmost respect for the recipient and his or her freedom, and shared in private. The film “Whispering the Gospel” attempts to capture this image. In this day of warring ideologies, extremism, and violence, the Gospel may bring a sense of fairness to the table, as well as motivation and hope.

“The Origins of Religious Life: An Invitation to a Deeper Commitment to the Gospel,” the next chapter, discusses religious groups trying to witness to the radicality of the Gospel. Religious people have always been effective communicators of the Christian faith, and as spiritual masters, they have had a moral influence on society. They must ensure 'depth' in their spiritual exercises in order to be effective. They have the ability to influence society's ideas and be a blessing to all.

The following chapter, “Taking the First Steps in a New Mission Field: Know and Respect the People You Serve,” encourages readers to recognize the necessity for a missionary to adapt to local traditions, with a focus on Northeast India's distinct character. Imported ideas that are rushed can be misleading. In terms of culture, one must constantly listen and learn, from all directions!

The focus on serving people leads to the formation of collaborative communities. The Catholic Church's community-building ministry is discussed in “Community Building: The Central Challenge Before Pastoral Leaders.” Christ's followers built a family for him. Relationships with people become an important part of a pastor's spirituality and personal identity. He welcomes everyone's assistance and listens to everyone's point of view, including marginalized groups' fears, unheard opinions, unwelcome comments, unrepresented populations, unhappy sections, and opposing viewpoints. But, above all, he must devote his full attention to his spiritual exercises. He cannot disregard himself and allow his spirit to sag.

The function of various pastoral agents in Northeast India is described in the next chapter, “Diocesan Plan of Evangelization

and Pastoral Reflections.” Because the Catechist performs such an important function, he needs to be well trained and motivated. The Touring Sisters play a unique role in the region, and their commitment to service ensures the success of their mission. Schools, boarding houses, medical services, the media, lay associations...they all play a part in the overall effort. The Parish Priest and his Assistants are the ones who inspire and encourage all of the parish's activities.

Similarly, “A Second Look at Our Work” provides a critical assessment of our work from several perspectives. For example, our short-term goals may have evolved into long-term goals, or gaps between our claims and actual achievements, promises, and performance may have grown; or people may no longer be the centre of our attention, but financial security is; or our un-planning styles, lack of cultural insertion, and poor neighbourhood relationships may have resulted in negative outcomes. Our spiritual seriousness will assist us in making changes to our habits and styles.

2. Fostering Relationship Among All

In the same vein, “Catholic Education and the Church's Concern for the Marginalized” lays out the Church's educational policy: in a nutshell, all-round human development, with a focus on the poorer kids and the marginalized. The most important thing is to teach Catholic youngsters about their faith and to instil ethical awareness in all students. Many dioceses and congregations have created programs in aid of the needy, such as remedial classes, scholarships, interest-free loans, free supply of books, teaching aids, and free tuitions, despite criticism of their objectives. The most important thing is to foster an evangelical environment in all educational settings, as well as a radical commitment to the poor.

The Church places a special emphasis on the needs of families. “When it comes to assisting families in tough

situations, it's more important to understand than to be understood.” “explores scenarios of great hardship in which many families in our time find themselves, such as intercultural, interreligious marriage and extreme poverty. Working parents are unable to devote as much time as they would like to each other and their children. Families that are suffering in such harrowing circumstances deserve sympathy, not condemnation. Members of families who have recently made positive changes in their lives can be of great help to others who are experiencing anxiety.

The living presence of Christ in our midst is central to our lives and missions. In this period of wars, suicide, abortion, communal confrontations, and so on, “The Eucharist the Source of Our Strength: A Presence that Challenges and Strengthens” asserts that Jesus, present to us in the form of Bread and as Word, is the source of life. His social message must reach everyone, including those in politics, economics, education, the media, sports, and entertainment. This pushes us to be spiritually mature individuals. Currently, our communities may be fighting autocratic governments, a discriminatory bureaucracy, and heartless members of the dominant community, among other things. But, because Jesus is beside us, we never give up.

This pushes us to be more productive in our personal and professional lives. “Growing Efficient in God's Work: Exhortation to Deacons” is a wise chapter that wants for young priests to become tireless apostles, fervent pastors, and helpers of the poor, as well as promoters of good relationships. It is critical to organize one's work, manage one's time effectively, manage one's money wisely, maintain intellectual interests even in later years, and maintain spiritual sincerity.

Finally, “Telling Jesus' Stories in Today's India” remembers how the people of Israel continued to retell and learn from their stories. Because his stories addressed universal themes such as justice and peace, love and forgiveness, and provided people a way ahead in the midst of life's harsh realities, Jesus drew a lot of attention. The stories we tell must aid in the healing of personal

and collective wounds, the reconciliation of conflicting communities, and the advancement of society's future-building efforts. In India and Asia, stories about Jesus are always received. They are intended to improve people's personal lives as well as the social lives of communities, peoples, and nations. Committed individuals have given their life for such noble causes. Nothing is Impossible warns us against becoming complacent because of our early missions' success. We may need to consider whether we are losing talents such as persuasion and motivation that we gained from the pioneers. A sense of 'call' and mission should follow us at all times. For our administration and personal conduct, we are answerable to the Church and society. Even today, business consultants take their employees to 'retreats' and self-critiquing exercises, as the author points out. It's all about the spirit. The spiritual perspective makes it possible.

In this context, “Everyone is Looking for You” (Mk 1:37) argues that everyone, including our opponents, who is looking for more serious answers in life is asking for Jesus. It's critical that we focus on Jesus, paying attention to our interlocutors' emotions and tastes, and addressing the fundamental concerns that disturb their minds. Before gently introducing Jesus, one must be attentive to the other person's point of view in our contemporary period of questioning and remembering of terrible events. Your suffering will have fruit of its own, and your words may be rejected at any time. However, what is proper is finally shown right by its internal consistency and veracity. And ('Wisdom is proven correct by her deeds.') “ (Mt 11:19). “Leaving Security on the Shore” (EG 10) asserts that all members of society, including leaders and followers, bear equal responsibility. What matters is that you have a powerful mission that produces energy. Today's missionaries travel through large swaths of indifferent forest, not so much across oceans as across psychological mountains of distrust. ... the searing heat of fundamentalists vying for attention necessitates a focus on 'other' problems and shifting

moods. To arrive at a solution, discernment is essential. Exaggerations and prejudices should be avoided in any situation. Establishing and maintaining deep human relationships, which assumes our intimate union with the divine, is the most significant value in the missionary environment.

3. Everything Is Possible for Those Who Believe

The author truly holds that “Everything is possible for the person who has faith’ (Mk 9:23). The 20 specially chosen chapters in this book, including “The lure of the invisible,” “The sense of the sacred,” and “Leaving security on the shore” addresses the innermost concerns of the Church interacting with other religions in the contemporary India. With a forward by Thomas Manjaly, this book is an a genuine invitation to reflection and retrospection (p. 12). It affirms the role and significance of tribal religions which has have contributed significantly to all world religions (p. 51). It also seeks to elicit support even from opponents (p. 75), without which today’s missionary work is impossible. It invites all readers to tell the stories from their personal and experiential lives “that change mind and heart, transform societies” (p. 148). On the whole, this is a deeply relevant book for our contemporary times beset with conflict. It pleads for enduring peace, enriching dialogue and genuine relationships. Only such an approach can guarantee the relevance of religions and survival of humanity. When religions are in conflict it endangers the very survival of human race, as Pope Francis has been warning us.

As such, this book continues the pastoral approach of Pope Francis who pleads for dialogue between religions, openness to others, opting for the poor and marginalized in our missionary ventures and being truly open to the world. In fact, we may assume that Archbishop Menampampil had been following the path of Pope Francis, before he way became inspirational.

This book may be regarded as the magnum opus of Archbishop Thomas Menampampil, SDB, who has contributed significantly to the intellectual and spiritual growth of the Indian

Church and especially of North East. It is a significant contribution both to the Indian Church and the World-Christianity.

[Adapted from Kuruvilla Pandikattu. “Review Article: Attempting the Impossible as Living the Christian Life and Mission for Today” *Vidyajyoti Journal of Theological Reflection*, November 2021 85/11, 869-874.]

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